

Curiosity's Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator's Notebook: Sols 4134–4257

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Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Technical Report 0038

Cover photo

Night-time MAHLI view of a wheel-crushed target called Convict Lake, located at Whitebark Pass. This is MAHLI focus merge product 4208MH0001530001501926R00, created onboard the instrument from a focus stack acquired on Sol 4207 with the Group 2 white LEDs on.

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7.1 Definitions and conventions

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Acknowledgements

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Note that pages are not numbered in this document because all of the *Range and Scale Information Sheets*, *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, and *MAHLI Image Comment Sheets* were inserted separately after creation using a word processing tool that differs from the one used for the text.

Abstract

Covering the time between Curiosity’s 4134th and 4257th Martian days (sols) of operations in northern Gale crater, Mars, this document is a compilation of the Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Team’s notes and information about MAHLI images and activities conducted during that period. The report includes brief sol-by-sol notes—written as the mission unfolded—regarding how the MAHLI instrument was used and significant events that occurred which impacted the MAHLI instrument or investigation. The document, further, contains information regarding range and scale (camera working distance and scale of in-focus elements of an image); the parent images, range, and scale information associated with each MAHLI focus merge product created onboard the instrument; and a description of the purpose and intent behind acquisition of each MAHLI image and creation of each onboard focus merge product. The MSL science team and rover engineers routinely used the information contained in this report during the course of the mission for tactical planning, strategic planning, and scientific analysis.

1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction and purpose

This document is a compilation of the Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Team's notes and information about MAHLI images and activities that occurred during the Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) mission between Sols 4134 and 4257.

MAHLI is a 2-megapixel color camera with a focusable macro lens mounted on the turret at the end of a robotic arm aboard NASA's MSL rover, Curiosity (Edgett *et al.* 2012). The rover landed and began operation in northern Gale crater, Mars, on 6 August 2012 (Vasavada *et al.* 2014).

Each *Curiosity's Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator's Notebook* covers a specific period corresponding to a release of MAHLI data to the NASA Planetary Data System (PDS) Imaging Node (<http://pds-imaging.jpl.nasa.gov/>). As some MAHLI data can arrive from Mars months or years after a given release period, the publication of these reports typically lags behind the PDS release schedule by a period that varies from one occasion to the next, depending largely on when data acquired during that period arrive on Earth and when we have time to complete the *Principal Investigator's Notebook* report.

This report, *Curiosity's Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator's Notebook: Sols 4134–4257*, corresponds to MAHLI data Release 37 in the NASA PDS archives. These are data acquired 23 March 2024 through 28 July 2024.

1.2 Versions and change log

The enclosed materials were compiled as the MSL mission unfolded. That being the case, we might sometimes have made errors. The reader should be aware that this report might be corrected via release of a new version in the future.

A new version would also be created if new data from this report's period (Martian sols) are received from the instrument after an earlier version has been made available. This can occur because MAHLI can store data onboard the instrument for an indefinite period of time after acquisition. As a result, images are archived with the NASA PDS on the basis of when they are received on Earth, not when they are acquired on Mars.

Covering the Sol 4134 through 4257 period, this document is Version 1.

If this were a later version, this section would document the changes made relative to the previous.

2 Instrument activities for this period

This section captures day-by-day or sol-by-sol notes written by the MAHLI Team, as the mission unfolded, regarding how the MAHLI instrument was used or significant events that occurred which impacted the MAHLI instrument or investigation.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 4134 – 4257						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
Driving along the Upper Gediz Vallis ridge near Fascination Turret	23 Mar 24	4134	9	90	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Thompson_Canyon, Cabin_Lake and Smoky_Jack.
	24 Mar 24	4135	0	0	9	Focus stack images from Sol 4134 were merged.
Driving along the Upper Gediz Vallis ridge near Fascination Turret to Hinman Col	26 Mar 24	4137	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Sunrise_Lakes and the focus stack images were merged. MAHLI images that correspond to CDPIDs 1 through 3479 (data from Sols 3803-4054) were deleted from the MAHLI DEA non-volatile memory storage.
	28 Mar 24	4139	11	46	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Rainbow_Falls and MAHLI imaged the target Rancheria_Falls, which included a full run of the MAHLI proximity mode, a new capability that uses MAHLI onboard range-finding to guide MAHLI closer to the surface. The focus stack images were also merged.
	31 Mar 24	4141	10	84	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Rose_Lake, the target Whorl_Mountain and the target Little_Slide_Canyon.
	31 Mar 24	4142	0	0	8	Focus stack images from Sol 4141 were merged.
Driving along the Upper Gediz Vallis ridge towards Pinnacle Ridge	03 Apr 24	4144	3	30	3	MAHLI imaged the target Bodie and the focus stack images were also merged.
	05 Apr 24	4146	8	41	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Ruby_Peak as well as the MAHLI and APXS calibration targets. The focus stack images were also merged.
	07 Apr 24	4148	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Ahwahnee and the focus stack images were merged.
	11 Apr 24	4152	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Burro_Pass and the focus stack images were merged.
	13 Apr 24	4154	13	50	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Hetch_Hetchy. Another test to see how the performance of the DRT compares at different distances above the surface of a target was done on the target Hetch_Hetchy. The DRT was used to brush the target Hetch_Hetchy at the height of 19 mm standoff, 17 mm standoff and the standard height of 15 mm standoff. MAHLI was used to document the surface before it
	14 Apr 24	4155	0	0	3	Focus stack images from Sol 4154 were merged.
	16 Apr 24	4157	9	74	0	MAHLI imaged the target Peppermint_Pass, the DRT-brushed target Tioga_Pass and the target Wonder_Lakes.
	17 Apr 24	4158	0	0	7	Focus stack images from Sol 4157 were merged.
18 Apr 24	4159	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Tilden_Lake and the focus stack images were merged.	

MAHLI Activities During Sols 4134 – 4257						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
Driving along the Upper Gediz Vallis ridge towards Pinnacle Ridge	19 Apr 24	4160	1	4	0	MAHLI acquired four arm-stowed landscape images with the dust cover closed (at the rover position after Sol 4159 drive) in parallel with the Sol 4160 MRO PM pass.
	20 Apr 24	4161	11	86	0	MAHLI imaged the REMS UV Sensor, the target Mist_Falls, the target Castle_Rock_Spire, and the DRT-brushed target Florence_Lake.
	21 Apr 24	4162	0	0	8	Focus stack images from Sol 4161 were merged.
Driving along the Upper Gediz Vallis ridge near Pinnacle Ridge	23 Apr 24	4164	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the target Sluggo_Pass and the focus stack images were merged.
	25 Apr 24	4166	3	30	3	MAHLI imaged the target Twin_Peaks and the focus stack images were merged.
	27 Apr 24	4168	9	82	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Bilko_Pinnacle and Pipsqueak_Spire.
	28 Apr 24	4169	0	0	8	Focus stack images from Sol 4168 were merged.
Driving along the Upper Gediz Vallis ridge near Pinnacle Ridge	03 May 24	4173	9	82	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Franklin_Lakes and the target Emerald_Peak.
	04 May 24	4174	0	0	8	Focus stack images from Sol 4173 were merged.
	05 May 24	4175	11	110	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Lookout_Peak, Wilma_Lake, and Liberty_Cap.
	05 May 24	4176	0	0	11	Focus stack images from Sol 4175 were merged.
	07 May 24/ 08 May 24	4178	4	40	4	MAHLI acquired a 4x1 mosaic on the target El_Portal and the focus stack images were merged.
	10 May 24	4180	6	52	5	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Happy_Isles and acquired a 2x1 mosaic on the target Laurel_Mountain. The focus stack images were also merged.
	12 May 24	4182	10	84	0	MAHLI imaged the target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182, the target Royal_Arches, and the DRT-brushed target Boyden_Cave.
	13 May 24	4183	0	0	8	Focus stack images from Sol 4183 were merged.
	14 May 24	4184	6	44	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Tenaya_Lake and Buck_Lake.
15 May 24	4185	0	0	4	Focus stack images from Sol 4184 were merged.	
Driving towards Echo Ridge	16 May 24	4186	11	62	0	MAHLI imaged the target Parker_Lakes and the DRT-brushed target Tuolumne_Meadows.
	17 May 24	4187	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 4186 were merged.
	21 May 24	4191	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Pine_Creek and the focus stack images were merged.
At Echo Ridge	23 May 24	4193	3	30	3	MAHLI imaged the target Lake_Catherine and the focus stack images were merged.
Driving towards Whitebark Pass	26 May 24	4196	12	120	0	MAHLI imaged the target Second_Lake and MAHLI imaged the targets Josephine_Lake and Timber_Knob, which includes a 5x1 mosaic from Josephine_Lake to Timber_Knob.
	27 May 24	4197	0	0	12	Focus stack images from Sol 4196 were merged.
	29 May 24	4199	9	66	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Garnet_Lake, Rixford_Pass and Reggae_Pole.
	30 May 24	4200	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 4199 were merged.
At Whitebark_Pass	01 Jun 24/ 02 Jun 24	4202	9	86	8	MAHLI imaged the targets Gray_Peak and Snow_Lakes. The focus stack images were also merged.
	04 Jun 24	4205	13	117	0	MAHLI acquired a 6x1 mosaic on Starr_Minaret. MAHLI also imaged the DRT-brushed target Gem_Lakes and the target Convict_Lake.
	05 Jun 24	4206	0	0	11	Focus stack images from Sol 4205 were merged.
	06 Jun 24/ 07 Jun 24	4207	5	53	0	During the day, MAHLI imaged the target Convict_Lake. At night, MAHLI re-imaged the target Convict_Lake using different combinations of the LEDs, including ultraviolet to seek fluorescence.
	08 Jun 24	4208	0	0	4	Focus stack images from Sol 4207 were merged.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 4134 – 4257						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
At Whitebark_Pass	08 Jun 24/ 09 Jun 24	4209	8	72	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Grass_Lake and the target Snow_Lakes.
	09 Jun 24	4210	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 4209 were merged.
At Mammoth_Lakes2 Drill Site at Whitebark_Pass	11 Jun 24/ 12 Jun 24	4212	6	50	4	MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Mammoth_Lakes after DRT and after a drill bit preload test. The focus stack images were also merged.
	16 Jun 24	4216	7	38	3	MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Mammoth_Lakes2 after a drill bit preload test. MAHLI also imaged the target Loch_Leven and the intended site for the Mammoth_Lakes2 sample discard pile. Focus stack images were merged as well.
At Mammoth_Lakes2 Drill Site at Whitebark_Pass	04 Jul 24	4234	3	14	0	MAHLI imaged the Mammoth_Lakes2 drill hole and cuttings.
	05 Jul 24	4235	1	2	1	Focus stack images from Sol 4234 were merged. MAHLI images that correspond to CDPIDs 3480 through 4911 (data from Sols 4056-4137) were deleted from the MAHLI DEA non-volatile memory storage. MAHLI imaged the Mammoth_Lakes2 drill cuttings.
	06 Jul 24	4236	6	62	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Glacier_Notch and Lake_Ediza. At night, MAHLI imaged the Mammoth_Lakes2 drill hole wall that was investigated by ChemCam.
	07 Jul 24	4237	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 4236 were merged.
Driving towards Wishbone_Lake	09 Jul 24	4239	11	78	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Lake_Dorothy and Palisade_Glacier.
	10 Jul 24	4240	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 4239 were merged.
	11 Jul 24	4241	3	30	3	MAHLI imaged the target Donohue_Pass and the focus stack images were also merged.
At Wishbone_Lake	13 Jul 24	4243	9	82	0	MAHLI imaged the target Cattle_Creek and the target Arrowhead_Spire, which included a 4x1 mosaic.
	14 Jul 24	4244	0	0	8	Focus stack images from Sol 4243 were merged.
Driving to Fairview_Dome	16 Jul 24	4246	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the REMS UV Sensor and the target Jack_Main_Canyon. The focus stack images were also merged
At Fairview_Dome	19 Jul 24	4248	9	64	4	MAHLI imaged the sky, with the dust cover open and closed for flat fielding. MAHLI also imaged the DRT-brushed target Amphitheater_Dome. The focus stack images were merged as well.
	21 Jul 24	4250	12	69	0	MAHLI imaged the target Saddlebag_Lake and the DRT-brushed target Eagle_Scout_Peak. At night, MAHLI imaged inside the CheMin inlet for cleanliness.
	21 Jul 24	4251	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 4250 were merged.
Driving to Kings_Canyon Drill Site	24 Jul 24	4253	3	30	6	MAHLI imaged the target Discovery_Pinnacle and the focus stack images were merged.
	26 Jul 24	4255	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Russell_Pass and the focus stack images were merged.
At Kings_Canyon Drill Site	28 Jul 24	4257	5	42	4	MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Kings_Canyon after DRT. The focus stack images were also merged.

3 Helpful tips

3.1 MAHLI instrument and investigation

Please refer to Edgett *et al.* (2012) for a description of the MAHLI instrument and investigation, Edgett *et al.* (2015) for information about the characterization and calibration of the instrument, and Yingst *et al.* (2016) for some of the lessons learned after ~1.5 Mars years of surface operations. Additional information on how the instrument and data have been used is in the paper by Minitti *et al.* (2013) and the extended abstract by Garvin *et al.* (2017).

3.2 MAHLI image IDs

MAHLI images and onboard focus merge products are identified by their image IDs. The following figure describes the information content of these IDs.

Note that raw images released within minutes of receipt on Earth to the public via the JPL-Caltech web site (<http://mars.jpl.nasa.gov/msl/multimedia/raw/>) do not necessarily have the correct, final, archival image IDs.

MAHLI Image IDs

- This is the only official, correct, archival image ID scheme.
- Raw Images released rapidly at <http://mars.jpl.nasa.gov/msl/multimedia/raw/> do not always give you the correct, archival image ID.

0132MH0001580010101221C00

sol → 0132

camera
MH = MAHLI → MH

CDPID
a.k.a. MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID → 000158001

product type
as received from Mars → C00

sequence ID → 000158001

order in sequence
usually, first = 0, second = 1, etc. → 01

CDPID counter
How many times the following CDPID has been used since landing → 101

version
version received on Earth
0 = parent image on Mars → 221

GOP counter
for video Group of Pictures (JPEG video frames) → C00

Note that, for onboard focus merge products, the sol is the sol that the merge took place. This is **not** always on the same sol that the parent images were acquired.

The MAHLI team pays most attention to the items in yellow. In a focus stack, the images are acquired in order of increasing CDPID.

Product type tells you about the image as received from Mars; not necessarily the image you are looking at, if it has been further processed, uncompressed, or recompressed on Earth.

The NASA PDS archives include documentation that describes the MAHLI image ID and file naming scheme and the nature of the archived Experiment Data Record (EDR) and Reduced Data Record (RDR) products (Malin *et al.*, 2013).

The EDR products, the raw data product, have the following file name scheme:

- 1 **[Image ID]_XXXX** – these are always 8-bit images except for the 16-bit products (type A) returned from MAHLI for calibration purposes.

The RDR products are of the following nature:

- 2 **[Image ID]_DRXX** – 16-bit depth (per band) relative radiometric calibrated color images,
- 3 **[Image ID]_DRLX** – 16-bit depth (per band) relative radiometric calibrated and geometric calibrated color images,
- 4 **[Image ID]_DRCX** – 8-bit relative radiometric calibrated images for which a color correction has been applied, and
- 5 **[Image ID]_DRCL** – 8-bit relative radiometric and geometric calibrated images for which a color correction has been applied.

The following table describes the variety of image types (raw, lossless, JPEG, focus merge, thumbnail, *etc.*). Malin *et al.* (2013) described these in greater detail.

product type	product format
A	raster 16-bit image
B	raster 8-bit image
C	lossless compressed image
D	JPEG grayscale image
E	JPEG 4:2:2 color image
F	JPEG 4:4:4 color image
G	raster thumbnail of parent image
H	JPEG gray thumbnail of parent image
I	JPEG 4:4:4 thumbnail of parent image
J	raster 8-bit video frame
K	lossless compressed video frame
L	JPEG grayscale video frame
M	JPEG 4:2:2 color video frame
N	JPEG 4:4:4 color video frame
O	raster 8-bit thumbnail of video frame
P	JPEG gray thumbnail of video frame
Q	JPEG 4:4:4 thumbnail of video frame
R	focus merge best focus image product
S	focus merge range map product
T	focus merge best focus thumbnail
U	focus merge range map thumbnail

Types R and T are JPEG 4:4:4; S and U are JPEG grayscale products.

3.3 MAHLI LED positions

The MAHLI camera head has two groups of two white light LEDs (Edgett *et al.* 2012), called Group 1 and Group 2. For reference, the figure below shows their location on the camera head and how these locations translate to positions relative to pixel 0,0 (column 0, row 0) on the MAHLI CCD. In addition, MAHLI has two 365 nm ultraviolet (UV) LEDs, also shown in the figure. Each group of two LEDs (Group 1, Group 2, and UV) can be operated together or independently with each of the other two groups. When the LEDs are used, which group was operated is reported in the RATIONALE_DESC description of the image intent and purpose (Section 6).

MAHLI image TVC_MH0809080020000032B00, left, shows the violet and white reflections of the UV and Group 1 and Group 2 white light LEDs, indicating their location in relation to the CCD's pixel at column 0, row 0. The photograph on the right shows the camera head with its dust cover open and LEDs labeled.

4 Camera range and scale information

4.1 Purpose and description

MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* (or “Distance and Scale Information Sheets”) describe **(a)** the distance between the MAHLI camera and an imaged target, and **(b)** the scale of in-focus features in the image, based on knowledge of that distance. Usually, these are determined using the camera’s stepper motor count focus position (Edgett *et al.* 2015).

These information sheets were created only for cases in which there was a need. Cases for which they are not usually created include those when the only MAHLI image(s) acquired on a given sol are **(a)** views of the landscape, focused at infinity; **(b)** intended to make a rover self-portrait mosaic; **(c)** sky flat field calibration data; or **(d)** routinely-acquired images of the rover wheels for inspection purposes.

For the Sol 4134–4257 period, *Range and Scale Information Sheets* were created for the following **Sols: 4134, 4137, 4139, 4141, 4144, 4146, 4148, 4152, 4154, 4157, 4159, 4160, 4161, 4164, 4166, 4168, 4173, 4175, 4178, 4180, 4182, 4184, 4186, 4191, 4193, 4196, 4199, 4202, 4205, 4207, 4209, 4212, 4216, 4234, 4235, 4236, 4239, 4241, 4243, 4246, 4248, 4250, 4253, 4255, 4257.**

The origin of the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* was in the need for a rapid, tactical response from the MAHLI team to the Curiosity Rover Planners—the engineers tasked with operating the rover’s mobility and robotic arm systems—for range-finding and image scale information derived from MAHLI’s autofocus and focus merge capabilities. As described by Minitti *et al.* (2013), during the rover’s first sample extraction campaign, conducted at the Rocknest eolian sand deposit in October–November 2012, the engineers elected to use MAHLI autofocus sub-frames to confirm their estimates of the range to the sand surface for subsequent scoop placement (Anderson *et al.* 2015). These *Range and Scale Information Sheets* were borne of that effort to provide the information almost as soon as the data arrived on Earth.

Presented in this section are the latest versions of the *Range and Scale Information Sheets*, for the above stated sols, as of the date of this *MAHLI Technical Report* publication. Most of these sheets were actively used during the MSL mission for tactical and strategic planning, as well as for the scientific analyses. Note that some of the sheets exhibit slightly different formatting from each other, as the formatting and content evolved over time.

The image IDs presented in these Information Sheets are the identifiers of the best, least-compressed version of the image received from Mars for a given camera position for the stated purpose (autofocus, imaging, range-finding, etc.). In cases for which only a thumbnail version of the image was received, the image ID is colored orange.

4.2 Formulae

4.2.1 Working distance

The working distance (d_w , in centimeters) presented in the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* was computed from the empirical relationship between working distance and motor count for the flight unit MAHLI when the dust cover is open (m_{open}) described by Edgett *et al.* (2015):

$$d_w = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (1)$$

in which $a = 0.576786$, $b = -11.8479$, $c = 2.80153 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.266488 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.26666 \times 10^{-12}$.

For the dust cover closed case (m_{closed}), Edgett *et al.* (2015) found that m_{closed} is related to m_{open} as follows:

$$m_{closed} = 17075 - m_{open}. \quad (2)$$

4.2.2 Standoff distance (RP distance; MAHLI toolframe +X distance)

The standoff distance (d_s , in centimeters) presented in the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* is 1.9 cm less than the MAHLI working distance (Edgett *et al.* 2015). Note that “standoff distance” is equivalent to “RP distance” and “MAHLI toolframe +X distance”; see **Section 7.1**). It is determined by subtracting 1.9 cm from the working distance (d_w) computed from motor count:

$$d_s = d_w - 1.9 \text{ cm} \quad (3)$$

4.2.3 Distance or range uncertainty estimate

Estimation approach applied to the Sol 0–945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*

For the Sol 0–945 period (except Sol 687), the uncertainty in distance (whether expressed as d_w or d_s) was estimated using an early version of our team’s understanding (Edgett *et al.* 2013) of the flight unit MAHLI depth of field (DOF; d_{old_DOF} , in centimeters) as a function of working distance (d_w).

The method for estimating the far range of the DOF, d_{old_far} , was:

$$d_{old_far} = ad_w^5 - bd_w^4 + cd_w^3 + dd_w^2 + ed_w - f \quad (4)$$

in which $a = 2.067963396 \times 10^{-10}$, $b = 5.81503025785 \times 10^{-8}$, $c = 1.55563715379086 \times 10^{-5}$, $d = 1.78558768966003 \times 10^{-3}$, $e = 7.87243271888297 \times 10^{-3}$, and $f = 3.57047935299353 \times 10^{-2}$.

The method for estimating the near range of the DOF, d_{old_near} , was:

$$d_{old_near} = -(ad_w^5 + bd_w^4 - cd_w^3 + dd_w^2 - ed_w + f) \quad (5)$$

in which $a = -9.6497783 \times 10^{-12}$, $b = 1.06050131902 \times 10^{-8}$, $c = 5.8615047292452 \times 10^{-6}$, $d = 2.42284468424977 \times 10^{-3}$, $e = 4.28714139095939 \times 10^{-3}$, and $f = 7.534391000189 \times 10^{-4}$.

The MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* added the absolute values of the near and far DOF, then divided by two, to provide an overall uncertainty, $\pm d_{old_DOF}$, in centimeters:

$$\pm d_{old_DOF} = ((-d_{old_near}) + d_{old_far})/2 \quad (6)$$

The $\pm d_{old_DOF}$ estimate was sufficient for using MAHLI as a range finder for subsequent scoop placement during the Rocknest sample extraction campaign (Minitti *et al.* 2013; Anderson *et al.* 2015).

Improved estimation method, used for Sol 687 and after Sol 945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*

Later analysis refined our DOF estimate (Edgett *et al.* 2015), but these results arrived too late to be incorporated into most of the Sol 0–945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*. That said, for small working distances (e.g., < 20 cm), the results are about the same. As a function of dust cover open focus motor count (m_{open}), the near (d_{near}) and far (d_{far}) depth of field can be expressed, in centimeters, as:

$$d_{near} \text{ or } d_{far} = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (7)$$

in which, for d_{near} , $a = 1.03565$, $b = -11.9083$, $c = 2.82403 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.29003 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.34332 \times 10^{-12}$; and, for d_{far} , $a = 1.03438$, $b = -11.4118$, $c = 2.69297 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.17752 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.02494 \times 10^{-12}$.

4.2.4 Pixel scale

The estimated pixel scale (p , in μm per pixel) is based on working distance (d_w) and applies only to the in-focus portions of a given image. We estimate the scale from the working distance (d_w) as described by Edgett *et al.* (2012):

$$p = 6.9001 + 3.5201d_w. \quad (8)$$

4.2.5 Pixel scale uncertainty estimate

No estimation applied to the Sol 0–998 range and scale information sheets

No estimate of pixel scale uncertainty was applied to the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* until Sol 999.

Estimation approach

Pixel scale uncertainty (p_{far} , p_{near} , $\pm p_{uncertainty}$, in μm per pixel) can be estimated based on the depth of field (d_{far} , d_{near} , in centimeters; **Equation 7**) and pixel scale (p , in μm per pixel, **Equation 8**) as determined from working distance (d_w , in centimeters; **Equation 1**). The uncertainty applies only to the in-focus portions of a given image. The uncertainty can be estimated as follows (please round $\pm p_{uncertainty}$ to the nearest 0.1 μm per pixel):

$$p_{far} = (6.9001 + 3.5201(d_w + d_{far})) - p, \quad (9)$$

$$p_{near} = p - (6.9001 + 3.5201(d_w + d_{near})), \text{ and} \quad (10)$$

$$\pm p_{\text{uncertainty}} = (p_{\text{far}} + p_{\text{near}})/2. \quad (11)$$

4.2.6 Image dimensions estimate

The image dimension estimates described in the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* are computed by multiplying the estimated pixel scale (p) by the number of horizontal (columns) and vertical (rows) covered by the image. This simplistic approach, of course, assumes that the target is a plane parallel to the CCD.

SOL 4134 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Thompson_Canyon															
mhl100855	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm												
	4134MH0008550010904767C00	4767	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4135MH0005360000504872R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4135MH0005360000504873S00	
mhl100299	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	4134MH0002990010904777C00	4777	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4135MH0005360000504870R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4135MH0005360000504871S00	
mhl100299	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	4134MH0002990010904787C00	4787	14003	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4135MH0005360000504868R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4135MH0005360000504869S00	

target named Cabin_Lake															
mhl100855	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm												
	4134MH0008550010904797C00	4797	13039	25.2	23.3	-1.6	1.8	95.8	6.0	1608	1198	15.4	11.5		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4135MH0005360000504866R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4135MH0005360000504867S00	
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	4134MH0002240010904807C00	4807	14291	5.3	3.4	-0.1	0.1	25.4	0.4	1608	1198	4.1	3.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4135MH0005360000504864R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4135MH0005360000504865S00	
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	4134MH0002240010904817C00	4817	14283	5.3	3.4	-0.1	0.1	25.5	0.4	1608	1198	4.1	3.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4135MH0005360000504862R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4135MH0005360000504863S00	

target named Smoky_Jack															
mhl100865	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm												
	4134MH0008650010904827C00	4827	13026	26.0	24.1	-1.7	1.9	98.4	6.4	1608	1198	15.8	11.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4135MH0005360000504860R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4135MH0005360000504861S00	
mhl100841	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 15 cm												
	4134MH0008410010804837C00	4837	13285	16.1	14.2	-0.7	0.7	63.4	2.5	1608	1198	10.2	7.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4135MH0005360000504858R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4135MH0005360000504859S00	
mhl100841	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 15 cm												
	4134MH0008410010804847C00	4847	13282	16.1	14.2	-0.7	0.7	63.7	2.5	1608	1198	10.2	7.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4135MH0005360000504856R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4135MH0005360000504857S00	

UPDATED: 27_March_2024

SOL 4137 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Sunrise_Lakes - after DRT															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm												
	4137MH0001900010504875C00	4875	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4137MH0001680010504877C00	4877	14035	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4137MH0001930000304910R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4137MH0001930000304911S00
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4137MH0001680010504887C00	4887	14030	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4137MH0001930000404908R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4137MH0001930000304909S00
mhl100302	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 2 cm												
	4137MH0003020010504897C00	4897	14751	3.6	1.7	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.2	1608	1198	3.2	2.4		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4137MH0001930000404906R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4137MH0001930000404907S00

SOL 4139 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Rainbow_Falls** – after DRT

mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4139MH000190001150002C00	2	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4139MH000168001150004C00	4	14034	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4139MH0001930001500051R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4139MH0001930001500052S00	
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4139MH000168001150004C00	14	14042	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4139MH0001930001500049R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4139MH0001930001500050S00	
mhl00864	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 mm												
	4139MH0008640011500024C00	24	14958	3.1	1.2	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	1608	1198	2.9	2.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4139MH0001930001500047R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4139MH0001930001500048S00	

target named **Rancheria_Falls** – MAHLI proximity mode

mhl00866	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4139MH0008660011500034C00	34	14138	6.0	4.1	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.4
mhl00867	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 4 cm										
	4139MH0008670011500036C00	36	14192	5.7	3.8	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.2
mhl00868	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 3 cm										
	4139MH0008680011500038C00	38	14426	4.7	2.8	-0.1	0.1	23.4	0.3	1608	1198	3.8	2.8
mhl00869	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm										
	4139MH0008690011500040C00	40	14682	3.8	1.9	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.4
mhl00870	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 mm										
	4139MH0008700011500042C00	42	14877	3.3	1.4	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	1608	1198	3.0	2.2
mhl00871	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm										
	4139MH0008710011500044C00	44	15129	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0

target named **Rancheria_Falls**

mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm										
	4139MH0001900011500046C00	46	13030	25.8	23.9	-1.7	1.9	97.6	6.3	1608	1198	15.7	11.7

SOL 4142 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Rose_Lake** – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4141MH0001900011500054C00	54	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4141MH0001680011500056C00	56	14009	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4142MH0001700001500151R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4142MH0001700001500152S00	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4141MH0001680011500066C00	66	14019	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4142MH0001700001500149R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4142MH0001700001500150S00	
mhl100743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm													
	4141MH0007430011500076C00	76	15133	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4142MH0001700001500147R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4142MH0001700001500148S00	

target named **Whorl_Mountain**

mhl100865	CONTEXT STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4141MH0008650011500096C00	86	13040	25.2	23.3	-1.6	1.8	95.6	6.0	1608	1198	15.4	11.4		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4142MH0001700001500145R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4142MH0001700001500146S00	
mhl100865	CONTEXT STEREO-2 – ROTATED OFFSET	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4141MH0008650011500096C00	96	13042	25.1	23.2	-1.6	1.8	95.2	5.9	1608	1198	15.3	11.4		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4142MH0001700001500143R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4142MH0001700001500144S00	
mhl100865	CONTEXT STEREO-3 – ROTATED OFFSET	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4141MH0008650011500106C00	106	13047	24.8	22.9	-1.6	1.7	94.2	5.8	1608	1198	15.2	11.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4142MH0001700001500141R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4142MH0001700001500142S00	

target named **Little_Slide_Canyon**

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4141MH0001900011500116C00	116	13049	24.7	22.8	-1.5	1.7	93.8	5.8	1608	1198	15.1	11.2		
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4141MH0002240011500118C00	118	14338	5.1	3.2	-0.1	0.1	24.7	0.4	1608	1198	4.0	3.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4142MH0001700001500139R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4142MH0001700001500140S00	
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4141MH0002240011500128C00	128	14341	5.0	3.1	-0.1	0.1	24.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.0	3.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4142MH0001700001500137R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4142MH0001700001500138S00	

UPDATED: 03_April_2024

SOL 4144 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3790.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Bodie															
mhl00855	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm												
	4144MH0008550011500154C00	154	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4144MH0001930001500187R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4144MH0001930001500188S00	
mhl00297	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	4144MH0002970011500164C00	164	14038	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4144MH0001930001500185R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4144MH0001930001500186S00	
mhl00297	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	4144MH0002970011500174C00	174	14035	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4144MH0001930001500183R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4144MH0001930001500184S00	

UPDATED: 08_April_2024

SOL 4146 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Ruby_Peak – after DRT															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4146MH0001900011500190C00	190	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4146MH0001680011500192C00	192	14013	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4146MH0001930001500234R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4146MH0001930001500235S00	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4146MH0001680011500202C00	202	14017	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4146MH0001930001500232R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4146MH0001930001500233S00	
mhl100302	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm												
	4146MH0003020011500212C00	212	14719	3.7	1.8	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	1608	1198	3.2	2.4		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4146MH0001930001500230R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4146MH0001930001500231S00	

MAHLI calibration target													
NOTE: ONE CAN ALSO USE FEATURES IN THESE IMAGES TO DETERMINE SCALE; THE SCALE INFORMATION PRESENTED HERE IS BASED ON MOTOR COUNT, NOT ANALYSIS OF THE IMAGES.													
mhl100371	BAR TARGET – 5 cm WORKING DISTANCE												
	4146MH0003710011500222C00	222	14380	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.1	0.3	1608	1198	3.9	2.9
mhl100372	CENT TARGET – 5 cm WORKING DISTANCE												
	4146MH0003720011500224C00	224	14377	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.1	0.3	1608	1198	3.9	2.9
mhl100374	CALIBRATION TARGET + FRONT LEFT WHEEL + SURFACE – 30 cm WORKING DISTANCE												
	AUTOFOCUS ON CALIBRATION TARGET												
	4146MH0003740011500226C00	226	12964	30.1	28.2	-2.3	2.6	113.0	8.6	1608	1198	18.2	13.5
MANUAL INFINITY FOCUS													
4146MH0003740021500227C00	227	12552	(INFINITY)	1608	1198	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)						

APXS calibration target													
NOTE: ONE CAN ALSO USE FEATURES IN THESE IMAGE(S) TO DETERMINE SCALE; THE SCALE INFORMATION PRESENTED HERE IS BASED ON MOTOR COUNT, NOT ANALYSIS OF THE IMAGE(S).													
mhl100373	6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE												
	4146MH0003730011500229C00	229	13955	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.8

UPDATED: 08_April_2024

SOL 4148 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Ahwahnee - after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm										
	4148MH0001900011500237C00	237	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9	
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	4148MH0003360011500239C00	239	14051	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4148MH0001930001500272R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4148MH0001930001500273S00
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	4148MH0003360011500249C00	249	14052	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4148MH0001930001500270R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4148MH0001930001500271S00
mhl100864	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF - 1 cm										
	4148MH0008640011500259C00	259	15267	2.5	0.6	0.0	0.1	15.8	0.2	1608	1198	2.5	1.9	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4148MH0001930001500268R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4148MH0001930001500269S00

UPDATED: 11_April_2024

SOL 4152 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Burro_Pass - after DRT															
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm												
	4152MH0001900011500275C00	275	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4152MH0003360011500277C00	277	14027	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4152MH0001930001500310R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4152MH0001930001500311S00
mhl00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4152MH0003360011500287C00	287	14034	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4152MH0001930001500308R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4152MH0001930001500309S00
mhl00848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 mm												
	4152MH0008480011500297C00	297	14950	3.1	1.2	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	1608	1198	2.9	2.2		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4152MH0001930001500306R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4152MH0001930001500307S00

SOL 4154 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Hetch_Hetchy** – brush height test – before DRT

mhl100586	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 cm										
	4154MH0005860011500313C00	313	13257	16.8	14.9	-0.7	0.8	66.0	2.7	1608	1198	10.6	7.9
mhl100122	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4154MH0001220011500315C00	315	13996	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
mhl100122	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4154MH0001220011500317C00	317	13996	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7

target named **Hetch_Hetchy** – brush height test – after DRT from a height of 19 mm standoff

mhl100586	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 cm										
	4154MH0005860011500319C00	319	13257	16.8	14.9	-0.7	0.8	66.0	2.7	1608	1198	10.6	7.9
mhl100122	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4154MH0001220011500321C00	321	13995	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
mhl100122	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4154MH0001220011500323C00	323	13994	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7

target named **Hetch_Hetchy** – brush height test – after DRT from a height of 17 mm standoff

mhl100586	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 cm										
	4154MH0005860011500325C00	325	13257	16.8	14.9	-0.7	0.8	66.0	2.7	1608	1198	10.6	7.9
mhl100122	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4154MH0001220011500327C00	327	13994	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
mhl100122	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4154MH0001220011500329C00	329	13992	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7

target named **Hetch_Hetchy** – brush height test – after DRT from the standard height of 15 mm standoff

mhl100586	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 cm												
	4154MH0005860011500331C00	331	13258	16.8	14.9	-0.7	0.8	65.9	2.7	1608	1198	10.6	7.9		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4154MH0001680011500333C00	333	14000	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4155MH0001930001500366R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4155MH0001930001500367S00	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4154MH0001680011500343C00	343	13991	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4155MH0001930001500364R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4155MH0001930001500365S00	
mhl100743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm												
	4154MH0007430011500353C00	353	15061	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	1608	1198	2.8	2.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4155MH0001930001500362R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4155MH0001930001500363S00	

SOL 4157 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Peppermint_Pass**

mhlI00841	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 cm											
	4157MH0008410011500369C00	369	13314	15.4	13.5	-0.6	0.6	60.9	2.3	1608	1198	9.8	7.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4158MH0001710001500454R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4158MH0001710001500455S00					
mhlI00841	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 cm											
	4157MH0008410011500379C00	379	13313	15.4	13.5	-0.6	0.7	61.0	2.3	1608	1198	9.8	7.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4158MH0001710001500452R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4158MH0001710001500453S00					

target named **Tioga_Pass - after DRT**

mhlI00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm											
	4157MH0001900011500389C00	389	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhlI00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	4157MH0001680011500391C00	391	14021	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4158MH0001710001500450R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4158MH0001710001500451S00					
mhlI00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	4157MH0001680011500401C00	401	14031	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4158MH0001710001500448R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4158MH0001710001500449S00					
mhlI00743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 1 cm											
	4157MH0007430011500411C00	411	15163	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.5	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	2.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4158MH0001710001500446R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4158MH0001710001500447S00					

target named **Wonder_Lakes**

mhlI00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm											
	4157MH0001900011500421C00	421	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhlI00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	4157MH0001820011500423C00	423	14034	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4158MH0001710001500444R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4158MH0001710001500445S00					
mhlI00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	4157MH0001820011500433C00	433	14037	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4158MH0001710001500442R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4158MH0001710001500443S00					

UPDATED: 19_April_2024

SOL 4159 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Tilden_Lake – after DRT															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4159MH0001900011500457C00	457	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4159MH0001680011500459C00	459	14014	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4159MH0001930001500492R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4159MH0001930001500493S00
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4159MH0001680011500469C00	469	14021	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4159MH0001930001500490R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4159MH0001930001500491S00
mhl100743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm												
	4159MH0007430011500479C00	479	15157	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.5	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4159MH0001930001500488R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4159MH0001930001500489S00

UPDATED: 10_May_2024

SOL 4160 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

MAHLI and UHF comm parallelism test – landscape image – robotic arm stowed – dust cover closed

NOTE: WHERE THE MOTOR COUNT IS GIVEN IN BLUE FONT, THE DUST COVER WAS CLOSED DURING THE IMAGING; PLEASE USE CAUTION IN INTERPRETING THE RANGE AND SCALE INFORMATION, AS THE RESULTS ARE LESS CERTAIN.

mhl100875	MANUAL FOCUS AT INFINITY AND MANUAL EXPOSURE OF 15 msec													
	4160MH0008750071500494C00	494	4488	(INFINITY)	1608	1198	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)						
	MANUAL FOCUS AT INFINITY AND MANUAL EXPOSURE OF 15 msec													
	4160MH0008750091500495C00	495	4488	(INFINITY)	1608	1198	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)						
	MANUAL FOCUS AT INFINITY AND MANUAL EXPOSURE OF 15 msec													
	4160MH0008750111500496C00	496	4488	(INFINITY)	1608	1198	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)						
MANUAL FOCUS AT INFINITY AND MANUAL EXPOSURE OF 15 msec														
4160MH0008750131500497C00	497	4488	(INFINITY)	1608	1198	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)							

SOL 4161 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13148/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

REMS UV sensor													
mhl100095	STANDARD VIEWING POSITION		INTENDED STANDOFF: ~15 cm										
	4161MH000950011500499C00	499	13261	16.7	14.8	-0.7	0.8	65.6	2.6	1608	1198	10.5	7.9

target named Mist_Falls															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm												
	4161MH0001900011500501C00	501	13034	25.5	23.6	-1.6	1.8	96.7	6.1	1608	1198	15.6	11.6		
mhl100299	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4161MH0002990011500503C00	503	14185	5.8	3.9	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4162MH0001700001500598R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4162MH0001700001500599S00	
mhl100299	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4161MH0002990011500513C00	513	14186	5.8	3.9	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4162MH0001700001500596R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4162MH0001700001500597S00	

target named Castle_Rock_Spire															
mhl100865	CONTEXT STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm												
	4161MH0008650011500523C00	523	13030	25.8	23.9	-1.7	1.9	97.6	6.3	1608	1198	15.7	11.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4162MH0001700001500594R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4162MH0001700001500595S00	
mhl100865	CONTEXT STEREO-2 - ROTATED OFFSET		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm												
	4161MH0008650011500533C00	533	13031	25.7	23.8	-1.7	1.9	97.3	6.2	1608	1198	15.7	11.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4162MH0001700001500592R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4162MH0001700001500593S00	
mhl100865	CONTEXT STEREO-3 - ROTATED OFFSET		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm												
	4161MH0008650011500543C00	543	13031	25.7	23.8	-1.7	1.9	97.3	6.2	1608	1198	15.7	11.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4162MH0001700001500590R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4162MH0001700001500591S00	

target named Florence_Lake - after DRT															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm												
	4161MH0001900011500553C00	553	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4161MH0003360011500555C00	555	14037	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4162MH0001700001500588R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4162MH0001700001500589S00	
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4161MH0003360011500565C00	565	14040	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4162MH0001700001500586R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4162MH0001700001500587S00	
mhl100848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 1 cm												
	4161MH0008480011500575C00	575	15210	2.6	0.7	0.0	0.1	16.2	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	1.9		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4162MH0001700001500584R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4162MH0001700001500585S00	

UPDATED: 24_April_2024

SOL 4164 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Sluggo_Pass															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm												
	4164MH0001900011500601C00	601	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	4164MH0001680011500603C00	603	14001	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4164MH0001930001500636R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4164MH0001930001500637S00
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	4164MH0001680011500613C00	613	14000	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4164MH0001930001500634R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4164MH0001930001500635S00
mhl100302	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 2 cm												
	4164MH0003020011500623C00	623	14699	3.8	1.9	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.4		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4164MH0001930001500632R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4164MH0001930001500633S00

UPDATED: 29_April_2024

SOL 4166 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Twin_Peaks															
mhl00359	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm												
	4166MH0003590011500639C00	639	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4166MH0001930001500672R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4166MH0001930001500673S00	
mhl00342	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 10 cm												
	4166MH0003420011500649C00	649	13503	11.8	9.9	-0.4	0.4	48.5	1.4	1608	1198	7.8	5.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4166MH0001930001500670R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4166MH0001930001500671S00	
mhl00342	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 10 cm												
	4166MH0003420011500659C00	659	13505	11.8	9.9	-0.4	0.4	48.3	1.4	1608	1198	7.8	5.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4166MH0001930001500668R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4166MH0001930001500669S00	

SOL 4168 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Bilko_Pinnacle													
mhl00359	CONTEXT STEREO-2 - ROTATED OFFSET		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm										
	4168MH0003590011500675C00	675	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4169MH0001700001500770R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4169MH0001700001500771S00					
mhl00359	CONTEXT STEREO-3 - ROTATED OFFSET		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm										
	4168MH0003590011500685C00	685	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4169MH0001700001500768R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4169MH0001700001500769S00					
mhl00359	CONTEXT STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm										
	4168MH0003590011500695C00	695	13014	26.7	24.8	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4169MH0001700001500766R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4169MH0001700001500767S00					
mhl00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	4168MH0001820011500705C00	705	13993	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4169MH0001700001500764R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4169MH0001700001500765S00					
mhl00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	4168MH0001820011500715C00	715	13991	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4169MH0001700001500762R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4169MH0001700001500763S00					
mhl00302	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 2 cm										
	4168MH0003020011500725C00	725	14670	3.9	2.0	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.5
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4169MH0001700001500760R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4169MH0001700001500761S00					

target named Pipsqueak_Spire													
mhl00172	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 20 cm										
	4168MH0001720011500735C00	735	13103	22.1	20.2	-1.3	1.4	84.6	4.6	1608	1198	13.6	10.1
mhl00224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	4168MH0002240011500737C00	737	13998	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4169MH0001700001500758R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4169MH0001700001500759S00					
mhl00224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	4168MH0002240011500747C00	747	14003	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4169MH0001700001500756R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4169MH0001700001500757S00					

SOL 4173 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Franklin_Lakes – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4173MH0001900011500773C00	773	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4173MH0003360011500775C00	775	14023	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4174MH0001700001500866R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4174MH0001700001500869S00
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4173MH0003360011500785C00	785	14019	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4174MH0001700001500866R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4174MH0001700001500867S00
mhl100864	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm												
	4173MH0008640011500795C00	795	15191	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.3	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	1.9	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4174MH0001700001500864R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4174MH0001700001500865S00

target named Emerald_Peak

mhl100876	CONTEXT STEREO-2 – ROTATED OFFSET	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4173MH0008760011500805C00	805	13005	27.3	25.4	-1.9	2.1	102.9	7.0	1608	1198	16.5	12.3		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4174MH0001700001500862R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4174MH0001700001500863S00	
mhl100876	CONTEXT STEREO-3 – ROTATED OFFSET	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4173MH0008760011500815C00	815	13010	27.0	25.1	-1.8	2.1	101.8	6.9	1608	1198	16.4	12.2		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4174MH0001700001500860R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4174MH0001700001500861S00	
mhl100876	CONTEXT STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4173MH0008760011500825C00	825	13008	27.1	25.2	-1.8	2.1	102.2	6.9	1608	1198	16.4	12.2		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4174MH0001700001500858R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4174MH0001700001500859S00	
mhl100173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4173MH0001730011500835C00	835	13945	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4174MH0001700001500856R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4174MH0001700001500857S00	
mhl100173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4173MH0001730011500845C00	845	13961	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4174MH0001700001500854R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4174MH0001700001500855S00	

SOL 4175 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Lookout_Peak															
mhl100865	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4175MH0008650011500871C00	871	13012	26.8	24.9	-1.8	2.0	101.3	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4176MH0004490001501000R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4176MH0004490001501001S00	
mhl100306	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4175MH0003060011500881C00	881	14161	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4176MH0004490001500998R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4176MH0004490001500999S00	
mhl100306	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4175MH0003060011500891C00	891	14156	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4176MH0004490001500996R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4176MH0004490001500997S00	

target named Wilma_Lake															
mhl100876	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4175MH0008760011500901C00	901	13014	26.7	24.8	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4176MH0004490001500994R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4176MH0004490001500995S00	
mhl100152	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4175MH0001520011500911C00	911	14026	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4176MH0004490001500992R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4176MH0004490001500993S00	
mhl100152	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4175MH0001520011500921C00	921	14029	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4176MH0004490001500990R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4176MH0004490001500991S00	

target named Liberty_Cap															
mhl100359	CONTEXT STEREO-2 – ROTATED OFFSET		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4175MH0003590011500931C00	931	13010	27.0	25.1	-1.8	2.1	101.8	6.9	1608	1198	16.4	12.2		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4176MH0004490001500988R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4176MH0004490001500989S00	
mhl100359	CONTEXT STEREO-3 – ROTATED OFFSET		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4175MH0003590011500941C00	941	13012	26.8	24.9	-1.8	2.0	101.3	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4176MH0004490001500986R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4176MH0004490001500987S00	
mhl100359	CONTEXT STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4175MH0003590011500951C00	951	13013	26.8	24.9	-1.8	2.0	101.1	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4176MH0004490001500984R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4176MH0004490001500985S00	
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4175MH0002240011500961C00	961	13940	7.3	5.4	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4176MH0004490001500982R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4176MH0004490001500983S00	
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4175MH0002240011500971C00	971	13933	7.3	5.4	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4176MH0004490001500980R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4176MH0004490001500981S00	

UPDATED: 08_May_2024

SOL 4178 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named El_Portal - a 4 x 1 mosaic															
mhl00865	POSITION 1 OF 4		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm												
	4178MH0008650011501003C00	1003	12968	29.8	27.9	-2.2	2.6	111.9	8.4	1608	1198	18.0	13.4		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4178MH0001530001501048R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4178MH0001530001501049S00	
mhl00865	POSITION 2 OF 4		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm												
	4178MH0008650011501013C00	1013	13012	26.8	24.9	-1.8	2.0	101.3	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4178MH0001530001501046R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4178MH0001530001501047S00	
mhl00865	POSITION 3 OF 4		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm												
	4178MH0008650011501023C00	1023	13032	25.6	23.7	-1.7	1.9	97.1	6.2	1608	1198	15.6	11.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4178MH0001530001501044R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4178MH0001530001501045S00	
mhl00865	POSITION 4 OF 4		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm												
	4178MH0008650011501033C00	1033	12923	33.6	31.7	-2.8	3.3	125.3	10.7	1608	1198	20.1	15.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4178MH0001530001501042R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4178MH0001530001501043S00	

UPDATED: 13_May_2024

SOL 4180 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Happy_Isles - after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm												
	4180MH0001900011501051C00	1051	13022	26.2	24.3	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4180MH0001680011501053C00	1053	14058	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4180MH0002270001501110R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4180MH0002270001501111S00
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4180MH0001680011501063C00	1063	14056	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4180MH0002270001501110R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4180MH0002270001501110S00
mhl100743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 mm												
	4180MH0007430011501073C00	1073	15042	3.0	1.1	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	1608	1198	2.8	2.1	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4180MH0002270001501110R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4180MH0002270001501110S00

target named Laurel_Mountain - a 2 x 1 mosaic

mhl100628	POSITION 1 OF 2	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm												
	4180MH0006280011501083C00	1083	13036	25.4	23.5	-1.6	1.8	96.3	6.1	1608	1198	15.5	11.5	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4180MH0002270001501110R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4180MH0002270001501110S00
mhl100628	POSITION 2 OF 2	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm												
	4180MH0006280011501093C00	1093	13032	25.6	23.7	-1.7	1.9	97.1	6.2	1608	1198	15.6	11.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4180MH0002270001501110R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4180MH0002270001501110S00

SOL 4182 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
target named Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182													
mhl100359	CONTEXT STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm										
	4182MH0003590011501113C00	1113	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4183MH0003750001501210R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4183MH0003750001501211S00					
mhl100359	CONTEXT STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm										
	4182MH0003590011501123C00	1123	13024	26.1	24.2	-1.7	1.9	98.8	6.4	1608	1198	15.9	11.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4183MH0003750001501208R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4183MH0003750001501209S00					
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4182MH0002240011501133C00	1133	14113	6.2	4.3	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4183MH0003750001501206R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4183MH0003750001501207S00					
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4182MH0002240011501143C00	1143	14116	6.1	4.2	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4183MH0003750001501204R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4183MH0003750001501205S00					
target named Royal_Arches													
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm										
	4182MH0001900011501153C00	1153	13030	25.8	23.9	-1.7	1.9	97.6	6.3	1608	1198	15.7	11.7
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4182MH0003360011501155C00	1155	14159	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4183MH0003750001501202R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4183MH0003750001501203S00					
target named Boyden_Cave – after DRT													
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm										
	4182MH0001900011501165C00	1165	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4182MH0003360011501167C00	1167	13992	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4183MH0003750001501200R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4183MH0003750001501201S00					
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4182MH0003360011501177C00	1177	13993	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4183MH0003750001501198R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4183MH0003750001501199S00					
mhl100864	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm										
	4182MH0008640011501187C00	1187	15052	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	1608	1198	2.8	2.1
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4183MH0003750001501196R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4183MH0003750001501197S00					

SOL 4184 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Tenaya_Lake**

mhlI00172	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 20 cm										
	4184MH0001720011501213C00	1213	13101	22.2	20.3	-1.3	1.4	85.0	4.6	1608	1198	13.7	10.2	
mhlI00306	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4184MH0003060011501215C00	1215	13926	7.4	5.5	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.3	3.9	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4185MH0001530001501262R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4185MH0001530001501263S00
mhlI00306	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4184MH0003060011501225C00	1225	13927	7.3	5.4	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.3	3.9	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4185MH0001530001501260R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4185MH0001530001501261S00

target named **Buck_Lake**

mhlI00190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm										
	4184MH0001900011501235C00	1235	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1	
mhlI00299	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4184MH0002990011501237C00	1237	14007	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4185MH0001530001501258R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4185MH0001530001501259S00
mhlI00299	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4184MH0002990011501247C00	1247	13994	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4185MH0001530001501256R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4185MH0001530001501257S00

SOL 4186 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3790.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)			
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)		
target named Parker_Lakes															
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4186MH0001900011501265C00	1265	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4186MH0001730011501267C00	1267	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4187MH0002270001501334R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4187MH0002270001501335S00	
mhl00173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4186MH0001730011501277C00	1277	14009	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4187MH0002270001501332R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4187MH0002270001501333S00	
target named Tuolumne_Meadows – before DRT															
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4186MH0001900011501287C00	1287	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00122	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4186MH0001220011501289C00	1289	14015	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
target named Tuolumne_Meadows – after DRT															
mhl00190	CONTEXT STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4186MH0001900011501291C00	1291	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhl00190	CONTEXT STEREO-2 – ROTATED OFFSET		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4186MH0001900011501293C00	1293	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00190	CONTEXT STEREO-3 – ROTATED OFFSET		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4186MH0001900011501295C00	1295	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhl00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4186MH0003360011501297C00	1297	14010	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4187MH0002270001501330R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4187MH0002270001501331S00	
mhl00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4186MH0003360011501307C00	1307	14015	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4187MH0002270001501328R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4187MH0002270001501329S00	
mhl00864	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm												
	4186MH0008640011501317C00	1317	15134	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4187MH0002270001501326R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4187MH0002270001501327S00	

UPDATED: 22_May_2024

SOL 4191 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Pine_Creek – after DRT															
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4191MH0001900011501337C00	1337	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4191MH0001680011501339C00	1339	14044	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4191MH0001930001501372R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4191MH0001930001501373S00
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4191MH0001680011501349C00	1349	14047	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4191MH0001930001501370R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4191MH0001930001501371S00
mhl00743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm												
	4191MH0007430011501359C00	1359	15243	2.6	0.7	0.0	0.1	16.0	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	1.9		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4191MH0001930001501368R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4191MH0001930001501369S00

UPDATED: 28_May_2024

SOL 4193 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3790.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Lake_Catherine													
mhl00865	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm										
	4193MH0008650011501375C00	1375	13031	25.7	23.8	-1.7	1.9	97.3	6.2	1608	1198	15.7	11.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4193MH0001930001501406R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4193MH0001930001501409S00				
mhl00877	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 15 cm										
	4193MH0008770011501385C00	1385	13305	15.6	13.7	-0.7	0.7	61.7	2.3	1608	1198	9.9	7.4
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4193MH0001930001501406R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4193MH0001930001501407S00				
mhl00877	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 15 cm										
	4193MH0008770011501395C00	1395	13309	15.5	13.6	-0.6	0.7	61.4	2.3	1608	1198	9.9	7.3
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4193MH0001930001501404R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4193MH0001930001501405S00				

SOL 4196 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Second_Lake															
mhl100359	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4196MH0003590011501411C00	1411	13030	25.8	23.9	-1.7	1.9	97.6	6.3	1608	1198	15.7	11.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4197MH0004580001501552R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4197MH0004580001501553S00	
mhl100306	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4196MH0003060011501421C00	1421	14205	5.7	3.8	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4197MH0004580001501550R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4197MH0004580001501551S00	
mhl100306	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4196MH0003060011501431C00	1431	14210	5.6	3.7	-0.1	0.1	26.8	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4197MH0004580001501548R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4197MH0004580001501549S00	

target named Josephine_Lake															
mhl100865	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4196MH0008650011501441C00	1441	13026	26.0	24.1	-1.7	1.9	98.4	6.4	1608	1198	15.8	11.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4197MH0004580001501546R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4197MH0004580001501547S00	
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4196MH0001820011501451C00	1451	14157	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4197MH0004580001501544R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4197MH0004580001501545S00	
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4196MH0001820011501461C00	1461	14165	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4197MH0004580001501542R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4197MH0004580001501543S00	

a 5 x 1 mosaic from target named Josephine_Lake to target named Timber_Knob															
mhl100859	POSITION 1 OF 5		INTENDED STANDOFF – 10 cm												
	4196MH0008590011501471C00	1471	13522	11.5	9.6	-0.4	0.4	47.5	1.3	1608	1198	7.6	5.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4197MH0004580001501540R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4197MH0004580001501541S00	
mhl100859	POSITION 2 OF 5		INTENDED STANDOFF – 10 cm												
	4196MH0008590011501481C00	1481	13554	11.1	9.2	-0.4	0.3	45.9	1.2	1608	1198	7.4	5.5		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4197MH0004580001501538R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4197MH0004580001501539S00	
mhl100859	POSITION 3 OF 5		INTENDED STANDOFF – 10 cm												
	4196MH0008590011501491C00	1491	13582	10.7	8.8	-0.3	0.3	44.6	1.2	1608	1198	7.2	5.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4197MH0004580001501536R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4197MH0004580001501537S00	
mhl100859	POSITION 4 OF 5		INTENDED STANDOFF – 10 cm												
	4196MH0008590011501501C00	1501	13600	10.5	8.6	-0.3	0.3	43.8	1.1	1608	1198	7.0	5.2		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4197MH0004580001501534R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4197MH0004580001501535S00	
mhl100859	POSITION 5 OF 5		INTENDED STANDOFF – 10 cm												
	4196MH0008590011501511C00	1511	13593	10.6	8.7	-0.3	0.3	44.1	1.1	1608	1198	7.1	5.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4197MH0004580001501532R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4197MH0004580001501533S00	

target named Timber_Knob															
mhl100359	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4196MH0003590011501521C00	1521	13025	26.0	24.1	-1.7	1.9	98.6	6.4	1608	1198	15.9	11.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4197MH0004580001501530R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4197MH0004580001501531S00	

SOL 4199 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)			
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)		
target named Garnet_Lake															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4199MH0001900011501555C00	1555	13028	25.9	24.0	-1.7	1.9	98.0	6.3	1608	1198	15.8	11.7		
mhl100878	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 10 cm												
	4199MH0008780011501557C00	1557	13559	11.0	9.1	-0.4	0.3	45.6	1.2	1608	1198	7.3	5.5		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4200MH0001630001501630R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4200MH0001630001501631S00	
mhl100878	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 10 cm												
	4199MH0008780011501567C00	1567	13561	11.0	9.1	-0.3	0.3	45.5	1.2	1608	1198	7.3	5.5		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4200MH0001630001501628R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4200MH0001630001501629S00	
target named Rixford_Pass															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4199MH0001900011501577C00	1577	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0		
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4199MH0002240011501579C00	1579	13957	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4200MH0001630001501626R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4200MH0001630001501627S00	
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4199MH0002240011501589C00	1589	13967	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4200MH0001630001501624R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4200MH0001630001501625S00	
target named Reggae_Pole															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4199MH0001900011501599C00	1599	13030	25.8	23.9	-1.7	1.9	97.6	6.3	1608	1198	15.7	11.7		
mhl100297	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4199MH0002970011501601C00	1601	14159	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4200MH0001630001501622R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4200MH0001630001501623S00	
mhl100297	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4199MH0002970011501611C00	1611	14202	5.7	3.8	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4200MH0001630001501620R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4200MH0001630001501621S00	

SOL 4202 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Gray_Peak													
mhl100359	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm										
	4202MH0003590011501633C00	1633	13014	26.7	24.8	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4202MH0001700001501732R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4202MH0001700001501733S00				
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1												
	4202MH0001820011501643C00	1643	13993	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4202MH0001700001501730R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4202MH0001700001501731S00					
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1												
	4202MH0001820011501653C00	1653	13990	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4202MH0001700001501728R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4202MH0001700001501729S00					
mhl100335	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm										
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1												
	4202MH0003350011501663C00	1663	14674	3.9	2.0	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.5
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4202MH0001700001501726R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4202MH0001700001501727S00					
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2												
	4202MH0001820011501673C00	1673	13980	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4202MH0001700001501724R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4202MH0001700001501725S00					

target named Snow_Lakes														
mhl100706	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4202MH0007060011501683C00	1683	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4202MH0001700001501722R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4202MH0001700001501723S00					
mhl100879	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4202MH0008790011501686C00		1686	14030	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4202MH0001700001501722R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4202MH0001700001501723S00					
mhl100879	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4202MH0008790011501697C00		1697	14032	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4202MH0001700001501720R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4202MH0001700001501721S00					
mhl100835	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm											
	4202MH0008350011501708C00		1708	15197	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.2	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	1.9
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4202MH0001700001501718R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4202MH0001700001501719S00					

SOL 4205 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Starr_Minaret – a 6 x 1 mosaic													
mhl00849	POSITION 1 OF 6	INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 cm											
	4205MH0008490011501735C00	1735	13075	23.4	21.5	-1.4	1.5	89.2	5.2	1608	1198	14.3	10.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4206MH0004490001501871R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4206MH0004490001501872S00					
mhl00849	POSITION 2 OF 6	INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 cm											
	4205MH0008490011501745C00	1745	13199	18.5	16.6	-0.9	0.9	72.0	3.2	1608	1198	11.6	8.6
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4206MH0004490001501869R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4206MH0004490001501870S00					
mhl00849	POSITION 3 OF 6	INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 cm											
	4205MH0008490011501755C00	1755	13213	18.1	16.2	-0.9	0.9	70.4	3.1	1608	1198	11.3	8.4
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4206MH0004490001501867R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4206MH0004490001501868S00					
mhl00849	POSITION 4 OF 6	INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 cm											
	4205MH0008490011501765C00	1765	13157	19.9	18.0	-1.0	1.1	77.0	3.8	1608	1198	12.4	9.2
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4206MH0004490001501865R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4206MH0004490001501866S00					
mhl00849	POSITION 5 OF 6	INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 cm											
	4205MH0008490011501775C00	1775	13227	17.6	15.7	-0.8	0.9	69.0	3.0	1608	1198	11.1	8.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4206MH0004490001501863R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4206MH0004490001501864S00					
mhl00849	POSITION 6 OF 6	INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 cm											
	4205MH0008490011501785C00	1785	13207	18.2	16.3	-0.9	0.9	71.1	3.2	1608	1198	11.4	8.5
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4206MH0004490001501861R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4206MH0004490001501862S00					

target named Gem_Lakes – after DRT													
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4205MH0001900011501795C00	1795	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4205MH0003360011501797C00	1797	14008	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4206MH0004490001501859R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4206MH0004490001501860S00					
mhl00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4205MH0003360011501807C00	1807	14008	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4206MH0004490001501857R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4206MH0004490001501858S00					
mhl00743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm											
	4205MH0007430011501817C00	1817	15128	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4206MH0004490001501855R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4206MH0004490001501856S00					

target named Convict_Lake													
mhl00842	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4205MH0008420011501827C00	1827	13035	25.5	23.6	-1.6	1.8	96.5	6.1	1608	1198	15.5	11.6
mhl00843	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4205MH0008430011501830C00	1830	14370	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4206MH0004490001501853R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4206MH0004490001501854S00					
mhl00843	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4205MH0008430011501841C00	1841	14369	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4206MH0004490001501851R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4206MH0004490001501852S00					

SOL 4207 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Convict_Lake**

mhl100706	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4207MH0007060011501874C00	1874	13024	26.1	24.2	-1.7	1.9	98.8	6.4	1608	1198	15.9	11.8		
mhl100721	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4207MH0007210011501877C00	1877	14154	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4208MH0001530001501932R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4208MH0001530001501933S00	
mhl100721	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4207MH0007210011501888C00	1888	14129	6.1	4.2	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.4		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4208MH0001530001501930R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4208MH0001530001501931S00	
mhl100721	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	4207MH0007210011501899C00	1899	14053	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4208MH0001530001501928R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4208MH0001530001501929S00	

target named **Convict_Lake - night imaging**

NOTE: DETERMINATION OF RANGE AND SCALE FROM MOTOR COUNT CAN SOMETIMES BE LESS ACCURATE VIA NIGHT IMAGING RELATIVE TO DAYTIME IMAGING.

mhl100880	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	AFTER A 480x480 AUTOFOCUS SUB-FRAME, THERE ARE MULTIPLE FULL-FRAME IMAGES WITH DIFFERENT LED COMBINATIONS; THE IMAGE LISTED HERE IS THE ONE WITH GROUP 2 LEDS ON														
	4207MH0008800031501911C00	1911	14010	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4208MH0001530001501926R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4208MH0001530001501927S00	

SOL 4209 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Grass_Lake – after DRT

mhl100706	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm												
	4209MH0007060011501935C00	1935	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhl100879	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	4209MH0008790011501938C00	1938	14026	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4210MH0001630001502016R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4210MH0001630001502017S00
mhl100879	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	4209MH0008790011501949C00	1949	14031	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4210MH0001630001502014R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4210MH0001630001502015S00
mhl100835	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 1 cm												
	4209MH0008350011501960C00	1960	15181	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.3	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	2.0	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4210MH0001630001502012R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4210MH0001630001502013S00

target named Snow_Lakes

mhl100706	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm													
	4209MH0007060011501971C00	1971	13028	25.9	24.0	-1.7	1.9	98.0	6.3	1608	1198	15.8	11.7		
mhl100834	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	4209MH0008340011501974C00	1974	14154	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.3		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4210MH0001630001502010R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4210MH0001630001502011S00	
mhl100834	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4209MH0008340011501985C00	1985	14145	6.0	4.1	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.3		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4210MH0001630001502008R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4210MH0001630001502009S00	
mhl100834	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 3														
	4209MH0008340011501996C00	1996	14151	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.3		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4210MH0001630001502006R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4210MH0001630001502007S00	

UPDATED: 12_June_2024

SOL 4212 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

intended drill target named Mammoth_Lakes – after DRT

mhl00706	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4212MH0007060011502019C00	2019	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00879	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4212MH0008790011502022C00	2022	13996	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4212MH0001530001502074R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4212MH0001530001502075S00	
mhl00879	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4212MH0008790011502033C00	2033	13996	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4212MH0001530001502072R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4212MH0001530001502073S00	
mhl00822	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4212MH0008220011502044C00	2044	15097	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4212MH0001530001502070R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4212MH0001530001502071S00	
mhl00879	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	4212MH0008790011502055C00	2055	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4212MH0001530001502068R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4212MH0001530001502069S00	

intended drill target named Mammoth_Lakes – after drill bit pre-load test

mhl00881	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 35 cm											
	4212MH0008810011502066C00	2066	12898	36.2	34.3	-3.2	3.9	134.2	12.4	1608	1198	21.6	16.1

SOL 4216 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

intended drill target named **Mammoth_Lakes2** – after drill bit pre-load test

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl100465	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 35 cm											
	4216MH0004650011502077C00	2077	12896	36.4	34.5	-3.2	3.9	134.9	12.6	1608	1198	21.7	16.2
mhl100882	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4216MH0008820011502079C00	2079	13988	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7

target named **Loch_Leven**

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4216MH0001900011502081C00	2081	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2												
	4216MH0001680011502083C00	2083	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4216MH0001930001502118R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4216MH0001930001502119S00					
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2												
	4216MH0001680011502093C00	2093	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4216MH0001930001502116R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4216MH0001930001502117S00					
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1												
	4216MH0001680011502103C00	2103	13995	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4216MH0001930001502114R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4216MH0001930001502115S00					

intended sample discard site for planned **Mammoth_Lakes2** drill sample

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4216MH0001900011502113C00	2113	13033	25.6	23.7	-1.7	1.9	96.9	6.2	1608	1198	15.6	11.6

UPDATED: 05_July_2024

SOL 4234 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

Mammoth_Lakes2 drill hole

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl00197	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4234MH0001970011502121C00	2121	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhl00774	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 10 cm											
	4234MH0007740011502123C00	2123	13514	11.6	9.7	-0.4	0.4	47.9	1.3	1608	1198	7.7	5.7

Mammoth_Lakes2 drill hole cuttings

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl00152	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4234MH0001520011502125C00	2125	14216	5.6	3.7	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4235MH0002580001502134R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4235MH0002580001502135S00					

UPDATED: 05_July_2024

SOL 4235 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

Mammoth_Lakes2 drill hole cuttings

SEQUENCE	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm		RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)		STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)		DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
	IMAGE ID*	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	INTENDED STANDOFF (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL			HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)		
mhli00122	4235MH0001220011502137C00	2137	14206	5.7	3.8	-0.1	0.1	26.8	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2			

UPDATED: 09_July_2024

SOL 4236 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13148/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Glacier_Notch**

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)	IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)
mhl100883	CONTEXT STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 30 cm						
	4236MH0008830011502139C00	2139	12937	32.4	30.5	-2.6	3.0	120.8	9.9	1608 1198 19.4 14.5
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4237MH0008840001502208R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4237MH0008840001502209S00		
mhl100883	CONTEXT STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 30 cm						
	4236MH0008830011502150C00	2150	12943	31.8	29.9	-2.5	2.9	119.0	9.6	1608 1198 19.1 14.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4237MH0008840001502206R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4237MH0008840001502207S00		

target named **Lake_Ediza**

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)	IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm						
	4236MH0001900011502161C00	2161	13041	25.1	23.2	-1.6	1.8	95.4	6.0	1608 1198 15.3 11.4
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm						
	4236MH0001680011502163C00	2163	14276	5.3	3.4	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	1608 1198 4.1 3.1
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4237MH0008840001502204R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4237MH0008840001502205S00		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm						
	4236MH0001680011502173C00	2173	14261	5.4	3.5	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	1608 1198 4.2 3.1
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4237MH0008840001502202R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4237MH0008840001502203S00		

Mammoth_Lakes2 drill hole – angled view of wall – night imaging

NOTE: DETERMINATION OF RANGE AND SCALE FROM MOTOR COUNT CAN SOMETIMES BE LESS ACCURATE VIA NIGHT IMAGING RELATIVE TO DAYTIME IMAGING.

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)	IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)
mhl100411	MAHLI POINTING ~SOUTH – 30° FROM NORMAL RELATIVE TO PLANE DEFINED BY TOP OF DRILL HOLE			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm						
	4236MH0004110011502183C00	2183	13507	11.7	9.8	-0.4	0.4	48.2	1.4	1608 1198 7.8 5.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4237MH0008840001502200R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4237MH0008840001502201S00		

SOL 4239 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Lake_Dorothy

mhl100706	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm									
	4239MH0007060011502211C00	2211	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0
mhl100763	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm									
	4239MH0007630011502214C00	2214	14026	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4240MH0001630001502298R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4240MH0001630001502299S00									
mhl100763	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm									
	4239MH0007630011502225C00	2225	14029	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4240MH0001630001502296R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4240MH0001630001502297S00									
mhl100794	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm									
	4239MH0007940011502236C00	2236	15183	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.3	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	2.0
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4240MH0001630001502294R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4240MH0001630001502295S00									

target named Palisade_Glacier – quantitative relief model (QRM) data

mhl100706	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm									
	4239MH0007060011502247C00	2247	13014	26.7	24.8	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1
mhl100763	MED RES – STEREO-1 & RELIEF MODEL POSITION 1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm									
	4239MH0007630011502250C00	2250	13987	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4240MH0001630001502292R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4240MH0001630001502293S00									
mhl100763	MED RES – STEREO-2 & RELIEF MODEL POSITION 2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm									
	4239MH0007630011502261C00	2261	13993	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4240MH0001630001502290R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4240MH0001630001502291S00									
mhl100705	MED RES – RELIEF MODEL POSITION 3			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm									
	4239MH0007050011502272C00	2272	13983	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.8
mhl100705	MED RES – RELIEF MODEL POSITION 4			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm									
	4239MH0007050011502274C00	2274	13981	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
mhl100705	MED RES – RELIEF MODEL POSITION 5			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm									
	4239MH0007050011502276C00	2276	13992	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
mhl100794	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm									
	4239MH0007940011502278C00	2278	15062	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	1608	1198	2.8	2.1
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4240MH0001630001502288R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4240MH0001630001502289S00									

UPDATED: 12_July_2024

SOL 4241 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Donohue_Pass															
mhl00359	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm												
	4241MH0003590011502301C00	2301	13028	25.9	24.0	-1.7	1.9	98.0	6.3	1608	1198	15.8	11.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4241MH0001930001502334R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4241MH0001930001502335S00	
mhl00297	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	4241MH0002970011502311C00	2311	14149	6.0	4.1	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4241MH0001930001502332R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4241MH0001930001502333S00	
mhl00297	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	4241MH0002970011502321C00	2321	14158	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4241MH0001930001502330R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4241MH0001930001502331S00	

UPDATED: 15_July_2024

SOL 4243 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Cattle_Creek**

mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4243MH0001900011502337C00	2337	13031	25.7	23.8	-1.7	1.9	97.3	6.2	1608	1198	15.7	11.7
mhl00224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4243MH0002240011502339C00	2339	14234	5.5	3.6	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	1608	1198	4.2	3.2
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4244MH0001700001502432R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4244MH0001700001502433S00					
mhl00224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4243MH0002240011502349C00	2349	14220	5.6	3.7	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4244MH0001700001502430R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4244MH0001700001502431S00					

target named **Arrowhead_Spire**

mhl00297	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4243MH0002970011502359C00	2359	14120	6.1	4.2	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4244MH0001700001502428R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4244MH0001700001502429S00					
mhl00297	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4243MH0002970011502369C00	2369	14129	6.1	4.2	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.4
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4244MH0001700001502426R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4244MH0001700001502427S00					

target named **Arrowhead_Spire - a 4 x 1 mosaic**

mhl00855	POSITION 1 OF 4	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4243MH0008550011502379C00	2379	13006	27.2	25.3	-1.9	2.1	102.7	7.0	1608	1198	16.5	12.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4244MH0001700001502424R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4244MH0001700001502425S00					
mhl00855	POSITION 2 OF 4	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4243MH0008550011502389C00	2389	13014	26.7	24.8	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4244MH0001700001502422R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4244MH0001700001502423S00					
mhl00855	POSITION 3 OF 4	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4243MH0008550011502399C00	2399	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4244MH0001700001502420R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4244MH0001700001502421S00					
mhl00855	POSITION 4 OF 4	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4243MH0008550011502409C00	2409	13010	27.0	25.1	-1.8	2.1	101.8	6.9	1608	1198	16.4	12.2
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4244MH0001700001502418R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4244MH0001700001502419S00					

UPDATED: 17_July_2024

SOL 4246 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

REMS UV sensor													
mhl100095	STANDARD VIEWING POSITION		INTENDED STANDOFF: ~15 cm										
	4246MH0000950011502435C00	2435	13264	16.6	14.7	-0.7	0.8	65.3	2.6	1608	1198	10.5	7.8

target named Jack_Main_Canyon															
mhl100359	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF: ~ 25 cm												
	4246MH0003590011502437C00	2437	13029	25.8	23.9	-1.7	1.9	97.8	6.3	1608	1198	15.7	11.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4246MH0001930001502470R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4246MH0001930001502471S00	
mhl100306	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF: ~ 5 cm												
	4246MH0003060011502447C00	2447	14179	5.8	3.9	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4246MH0001930001502468R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4246MH0001930001502469S00	
mhl100306	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF: ~ 5 cm												
	4246MH0003060011502457C00	2457	14200	5.7	3.8	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4246MH0001930001502466R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4246MH0001930001502467S00	

SOL 4248 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13148/R6.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

MAHLI sky flat field images - dust cover closed - first set

NOTE: WHERE THE MOTOR COUNT IS GIVEN IN BLUE FONT, THE DUST COVER WAS CLOSED DURING THE IMAGING; PLEASE USE CAUTION IN INTERPRETING THE RANGE AND SCALE INFORMATION, AS THE RESULTS ARE LESS CERTAIN.

mhl100712	CLOSE FOCUS - ~2.04 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4248MH0007120001502472C00	2472	0	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	2 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~3.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4248MH0007120011502473C00	2473	2412	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	5 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4248MH0007120021502474C00	2474	3078	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	25 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~26.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4248MH0007120031502475C00	2475	4062	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
INFINITY FOCUS - MANUAL FOCUS													
4248MH0007120041502476C00	2476	4488	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	

MAHLI sky flat field images - dust cover open - first set

mhl100453	CLOSE FOCUS - ~2.04 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4248MH0004530001502477C00	2477	15996	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	2 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~3.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4248MH0004530011502478C00	2478	14664	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	5 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4248MH0004530021502479C00	2479	13998	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	25 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~26.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4248MH0004530031502480C00	2480	13014	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
PRE-LAUNCH FLAT FIELD EQUIVALENT - ~63.3 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS													
4248MH0004530041502481C00	2481	12750	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
INFINITY FOCUS - MANUAL FOCUS													
4248MH0004530051502482C00	2482	12552	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	

MAHLI sky flat field images - dust cover open - second set (camera rotated approximately 180° relative to first set)

mhl100453	CLOSE FOCUS - ~2.04 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4248MH0004530001502483C00	2483	15996	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	2 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~3.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4248MH0004530011502484C00	2484	14664	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	5 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4248MH0004530021502485C00	2485	13998	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	25 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~26.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4248MH0004530031502486C00	2486	13014	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
PRE-LAUNCH FLAT FIELD EQUIVALENT - ~63.3 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS													
4248MH0004530041502487C00	2487	12750	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
INFINITY FOCUS - MANUAL FOCUS													
4248MH0004530051502488C00	2488	12552	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	

MAHLI sky flat field images - dust cover closed - second set (camera rotated approximately 180° relative to first set)

NOTE: WHERE THE MOTOR COUNT IS GIVEN IN BLUE FONT, THE DUST COVER WAS CLOSED DURING THE IMAGING; PLEASE USE CAUTION IN INTERPRETING THE RANGE AND SCALE INFORMATION, AS THE RESULTS ARE LESS CERTAIN.

mhl100712	CLOSE FOCUS - ~2.04 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4248MH0007120001502489C00	2489	0	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	2 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~3.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4248MH0007120011502490C00	2490	2412	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	5 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4248MH0007120021502491C00	2491	3078	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	25 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~26.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4248MH0007120031502492C00	2492	4062	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
INFINITY FOCUS - MANUAL FOCUS													
4248MH0007120041502493C00	2493	4488	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	

CONTINUED ON NEXT PAGE...

target named Amphitheater_Dome - after DRT													
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm											
	4248MH0001900011502495C00	2495	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1												
	4248MH0001680011502497C00	2497	14024	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4248MH0001530001502542R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4248MH0001530001502543S00					
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1												
	4248MH0001680011502507C00	2507	14021	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4248MH0001530001502540R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4248MH0001530001502541S00					
mhl00743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 1 cm											
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1												
	4248MH0007430011502517C00	2517	15160	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.5	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	2.0
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4248MH0001530001502538R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4248MH0001530001502539S00					
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2												
	4248MH0001680011502527C00	2527	14004	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4248MH0001530001502536R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4248MH0001530001502537S00					

SOL 4250 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Saddlebagg_Lake**

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm													
	4250MH0001900011502545C00	2545	13045	24.9	23.0	-1.6	1.8	94.6	5.9	1608	1198	15.2	11.3		
mhl100173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm													
	4250MH0001730011502547C00	2547	14330	5.1	3.2	-0.1	0.1	24.8	0.4	1608	1198	4.0	3.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4251MH0001630001502623R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4251MH0001630001502624S00	
mhl100173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm													
	4250MH0001730011502557C00	2557	14332	5.1	3.2	-0.1	0.1	24.8	0.4	1608	1198	4.0	3.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4251MH0001630001502621R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4251MH0001630001502622S00	

target named **Eagle_Scout_Peak - after DRT**

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm													
	4250MH0001900011502567C00	2567	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
mhl100336	4250MH0003360011502569C00	2569	13993	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4251MH0001630001502619R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4251MH0001630001502620S00
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
mhl100336	4250MH0003360011502579C00	2579	13995	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4251MH0001630001502617R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4251MH0001630001502618S00
mhl100864	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 1 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
mhl100864	4250MH0008640011502589C00	2589	15083	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4251MH0001630001502615R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4251MH0001630001502616S00
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
mhl100336	4250MH0003360011502599C00	2599	13987	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4251MH0001630001502613R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4251MH0001630001502614S00

CheMin sample inlet - at night with its cover open - deep imaging to check cleanliness state of mesh, funnel, funnel throat

INTENDED WORKING DISTANCE TO MESH IS 12.4 cm; TO FUNNEL THROAT IS 16.3 cm - FOR SCALE, NOTE THAT MESH DIAMETER IS 3.5 cm

mhl100312	IMAGE FOCUSED AT FUNNEL THROAT (~4 cm BELOW MESH) - POSITION 1 OF 3 TO INSPECT FUNNEL THROAT												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm											
mhl100312	4250MH0003120001502608C00	2608	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6
	IMAGE FOCUSED AT MESH												
mhl100312	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO MESH: 12.4 cm											
	4250MH0003120011502609C00	2609	13458	12.5	10.6	-0.4	0.4	51.0	1.5	1024	1024	5.2	5.2
mhl100326	IMAGE FOCUSED AT FUNNEL THROAT (~4 cm BELOW MESH) - POSITION 2 OF 3 TO INSPECT FUNNEL THROAT												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm											
mhl100326	4250MH0003260001502610C00	2610	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6
	IMAGE FOCUSED AT FUNNEL THROAT (~4 cm BELOW MESH) - POSITION 3 OF 3 TO INSPECT FUNNEL THROAT												
mhl100326	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm											
	4250MH0003260001502611C00	2611	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6

CheMin sample inlet - at night with its cover open - overview of entire inlet

INTENDED WORKING DISTANCE TO INLET IS ~19 cm - FOR SCALE, NOTE THAT MESH DIAMETER IS 3.5 cm

mhl100228	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE: ~19 cm											
	4250MH0002280001502612C00	2612	13182	19.1	17.2	-0.9	1.0	74.0	3.4	1608	1198	11.9	8.9

UPDATED: 24_July_2024

SOL 4253 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Discovery_Pinnacle															
mhl00359	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm												
	4253MH0003590011502626C00	2626	13004	27.3	25.4	-1.9	2.1	103.1	7.1	1608	1198	16.6	12.4		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4253MH0001930001502659R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								4253MH0001930001502660S00	
mhl00224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	4253MH0002240011502636C00	2636	13920	7.4	5.5	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.3	3.9		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4253MH0001930001502657R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								4253MH0001930001502658S00	
mhl00224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	4253MH0002240011502646C00	2646	13883	7.7	5.8	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	1608	1198	5.5	4.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4253MH0001930001502655R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								4253MH0001930001502656S00	

UPDATED: 26_July_2024

SOL 4255 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Russell_Pass															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4255MH0001900011502662C00	2662	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4255MH0003360011502664C00	2664	14039	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4255MH0001930001502697R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4255MH0001930001502698S00
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4255MH0003360011502674C00	2674	14038	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4255MH0001930001502695R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4255MH0001930001502696S00
mhl100848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm												
	4255MH0008480011502684C00	2684	15221	2.6	0.7	0.0	0.1	16.1	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	1.9		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4255MH0001930001502693R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4255MH0001930001502694S00

UPDATED: 29_July_2024

SOL 4257 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
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 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13148/R6.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

intended drill target named Kings_Canyon – after DRT

mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4257MH0001900011502700C00	2700	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4257MH0003360011502702C00	2702	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4257MH0001530001502747R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4257MH0001530001502748S00	
mhl00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4257MH0003360011502712C00	2712	14004	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4257MH0001530001502745R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4257MH0001530001502746S00	
mhl00864	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4257MH0008640011502722C00	2722	15104	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4257MH0001530001502743R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4257MH0001530001502744S00	
mhl00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	4257MH0003360011502732C00	2732	13990	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4257MH0001530001502741R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4257MH0001530001502742S00	

5 Focus merge product information

5.1 Purpose and description

The MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* provide information about the best focus and range map products created by focus merges performed onboard the MAHLI instrument.

The information includes:

1. thumbnail images representing the appearance of each best focus and range map product;
2. a brief title or description of the image target and purpose;
3. the Sol and date (UTC) that the merged parent images were acquired;
4. the Sol on which the focus merge took place,
5. image IDs for the focus merge products and a corresponding full-frame image;
6. the MAHLI command sequence that acquired the parent images and the command sequence that created the focus merge products;
7. the commanded stack depth; that is, the number of parent images acquired in a given focus stack;
8. the type of focus stack (relative or absolute; see definitions in **Section 7**);
9. a list of the thumbnail image IDs for the parent images acquired in the focus stack (because, in some cases, these are the only versions of the focus stack images that are received on Earth);
10. the focus position (stepper motor count) for each parent image in the focus stack;
11. the range and range uncertainty determined from the focus position (motor count) of each parent image; and
12. the grayscale DN value corresponding to each parent image motor count and range in the focus merge range map product.

Further, for each parent image, the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* state whether any of the full-size images (Individual Focus Stack Images) were received on Earth, listing:

13. the image ID of the full-size parent or child image, if received on Earth;
14. the date on which the full-size image was received (applicable only to *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* for the period between Sol 0 and 946 after that, with the exception of Sol 930, this practice was abandoned as unnecessary);

15. the compression quality of the best version of the image, if received on Earth (this practice was later abandoned as unnecessary); and
16. a statement regarding the fate of parent images not received on Earth; that is, the Sol on which the parent was deleted from the data storage inside the instrument’s digital electronics assembly (DEA).

Each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet* is identified by the Sol on which the parent images were acquired. The onboard merge, in some cases, might have been performed on a later sol.

The parent images identified in rows that are colored orange, if they have a corresponding DN value in a yellow-colored column, are those that participated in the creation of the focus merge product. In other words, those that are in white rows (for which there is a corresponding DN in the yellow column) had no in-focus elements and thus were not incorporated into the merged product, even if they had been commanded to be merged. Which images were commanded to be merged can be determined by the yellow-colored column that indicates the corresponding DN values in the range map image product; for cases in which the commanded focus stack depth is > 8 , the corresponding DN values (yellow-colored column) will indicate the 8 commanded to be merged (the instrument cannot merge > 8 but it can acquire > 8 images in a focus stack).

In cases in which the focus stack parent images were returned to Earth, the data user has the option to perform a new focus merge using software approaches available on Earth, now or in the future, which might outperform the MAHLI onboard algorithm. The user also has the opportunity, in these cases, to improve each parent image before performing the merge (e.g., remove blemishes, perform flat field correction, etc.).

When a > 8 image focus stack has been acquired, the orange-colored rows can *also* indicate recommendations for images that would contain in-focus elements and could be added to a future focus merge product, whether performed onboard MAHLI or on Earth after receipt of the full-size images. Those images that are recommended, but were not merged onboard, have no “Corresponding DN in Range Map” in the yellow, rightmost columns of the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*.

For the Sol 4134–4257 period, focus stacks that were merged onboard the instrument were acquired on **Sols 4134, 4137, 4139, 4141, 4144, 4146, 4148, 4152, 4154, 4157, 4159, 4161, 4164, 4166, 4168, 4173, 4175, 4178, 4180, 4182, 4184, 4186, 4191, 4193, 4196, 4199, 4202, 4205, 4207, 4209, 4212, 4216, 4234, 4236, 4239, 4241, 4243, 4246, 4248, 4250, 4253, 4255, 4257**. Unless otherwise stated, the onboard focus merges performed during this period were all of the “basic” type (see Edgett *et al.* 2012; Edgett *et al.* 2015).

5.2 Formulae

5.2.1 Range

When acquiring a focus stack, the MAHLI camera head is held in a fixed position. This means that the working distance (d_w) — and corresponding standoff distance (d_s) — is constant (see **Section 5.2.5**). However, each image acquired in a focus stack is done so at a different focus

position; that is, a different stepper motor count position (m_{open} or m_{closed} ; usually m_{open}). That motor count is related to the range (r_{fm}) between the front lens element of the camera and the in-focus elements of the image by the same empirical formula (**Equation 1**) as applied to determine working distance from motor count. In centimeters,

$$r_{fm} = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (12)$$

in which $a = 0.576786$, $b = -11.8479$, $c = 2.80153 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.266488 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.26666 \times 10^{-12}$.

For each parent image in a given focus stack, this range is given in the green-colored column on the right side of each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*.

5.2.2 Range uncertainty estimate

The uncertainty ($\pm r_{uncertainty}$, in centimeters) in the computed range (r_{fm}) is estimated using depth of field as related to the corresponding range (via motor count; **Equation 12**) for each merged parent image. The range uncertainty estimate is noted in the light green column on the lower right side of each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*.

Focus Merge Product Information Sheets in which the relevant column is labeled “Estimated Range Uncertainty”

For MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* created before Sol 942, our estimate of range uncertainty was based on the older (Edgett *et al.* 2013) depth of field equations described in **Section 4.2.3**, **Equations 4, 5, and 6**, in which we substituted r_{fm} for d_w .

Focus Merge Product Information Sheets in which the relevant column is labeled “Depth of Field”

For MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* created starting with Sol 942, we used the refined knowledge of MAHLI depth of field, described by Edgett *et al.* (2015) and in **Equation 7** of **Section 4.2.3** to determine d_{far} and d_{near} for each focus stack parent image motor count. The resulting range uncertainty estimate ($\pm r_{uncertainty}$, in centimeters) reported in the light green column on the lower right side of the corresponding *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet* is estimated by the average of the absolute values of d_{far} and d_{near} :

$$\pm r_{uncertainty} = ((-d_{near}) + d_{far})/2. \quad (13)$$

Alternatively, particularly after Sol 1000, the depth of field is reported in the form of both the near and far (d_{far} and d_{near}) depths of field, per **Equation 7**.

5.2.3 Corresponding DN in range map product

Focus merge range map products created onboard MAHLI are returned as grayscale JPEG compressed images. The pixel values (DN) range from 0 to 255. These are assigned by the onboard software on the basis of commanded focus stack depth. The table below, from Edgett *et al.* (2015), shows the relationship between each image commanded to be focus merged and its corresponding grayscale DN value in a MAHLI range map product. In other words, if the instrument is commanded to merge eight images, DN values are assigned according to the

second column in the table; if commanded to merge only four images, the corresponding DN values are those in the sixth column. Thus, each DN in a range map product can be related to a motor count position and a corresponding range via linear interpolation between these values.

Relation between commanded image participant in an onboard MAHLI focus merge and range map grayscale data value (DN)							
image commanded to be merged	DN for 8-image merge	DN for 7-image merge	DN for 6-image merge	DN for 5-image merge	DN for 4-image merge	DN for 3-image merge	DN for 2-image merge
1st	255	255	255	255	255	255	255
2nd	223	218	212	204	191	170	127
3rd	191	182	170	153	127	84	—
4th	159	145	127	102	63	—	—
5th	127	109	84	51	—	—	—
6th	95	72	42	—	—	—	—
7th	63	36	—	—	—	—	—
8th	31	—	—	—	—	—	—

5.2.4 Determination of which parent images participated in a given focus merge product (orange rows)

Focus merge parent images in the orange-colored rows on each of the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* are an indicator of the images that were actually merged. A merge of up to 8 images might be commanded, but perhaps only 3, 4, or 5 of them actually exhibit in-focus elements the get incorporated into the best focus image product.

As discussed by Edgett *et al.* (2015), the parent images that were actually merged, relative to the number commanded to be merged (indicated by the number of yellow-colored rows regarding the corresponding DN in the range map products on the right side of each *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*), are determined by the range of grayscale DN, between 0 and 255, in the focus merge range map product. For example, if the DN range of this product is 71 to 138, then only four of 8 images commanded to be merged participated in that merge, per the DN values corresponding to an 8-image focus merge, per the table above.

5.2.5 Camera working distance and standoff distance

For a given focus stack, the distance between the MAHLI camera head and an imaged target can be determined from a corresponding image acquired via autofocus (assuming the autofocus effort found focus). In other words, while the range between the camera and the in-focus elements of a parent image are captured by the individual parent images in the focus stack (**Section 5.2.1**), the camera acquired the stack from a fixed working distance. On the MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, the corresponding autofocused image, and its stepper motor focus position, are stated on the left side of the sheet, beneath the thumbnail images, in rows and columns colored light blue.

For some *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, the working distance (d_w) and standoff distance (d_s) are provided in these blue rows and columns. These were computed from the

motor count position using the same formulae for d_w and d_s described in **Section 4.2 (Equations 1 and 3, respectively)**. Where these values are not given, the data user can apply **Equations 1 and 3** to the motor count, or use the corresponding full-frame image ID to identify the working distance and standoff distance using the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* for that Sol. We began to regularly provide a result for d_w and d_s starting with Sol 694; before that, the cases in which these values are not given are a reflection of the evolution of the production and content of the MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* over time.

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SOL 4134 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Thompson_Canyon - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4134MH0008550010904767C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4135MH0005360000504872R00	4872	MOTOR COUNT:		13016	RANGE (cm):	26.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4135MH0005360000504873S00	4873	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00855	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Mar-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4134	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4135	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4134MH0008550020904768C00	4768	12896	36.37	-3.2	3.9	134.9	12.6	255	1
4134MH0008550020904769C00	4769	12926	33.35	-2.8	3.3	124.3	10.6	223	2
4134MH0008550020904770C00	4770	12956	30.77	-2.4	2.7	115.2	9.0	191	3
4134MH0008550020904771C00	4771	12986	28.54	-2.0	2.3	107.4	7.7	159	4
4134MH0008550020904772C00	4772	13016	26.58	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	127	5
4134MH0008550020904773C00	4773	13046	24.86	-1.6	1.7	94.4	5.8	95	6
4134MH0008550020904774C00	4774	13076	23.33	-1.4	1.5	89.0	5.1	63	7
4134MH0008550020904775C00	4775	13106	21.96	-1.2	1.4	84.2	4.6	31	8

UPDATED: 28_March_2024

SOL 4134 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Thompson_Canyon - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4134MH0002990010904777C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4135MH0005360000504870R00	4870	MOTOR COUNT:		13999	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4135MH0005360000504871S00	4871	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Mar-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4134	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4135	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4134MH0002990020904778C00	4778	13855	7.90	-0.2	0.2	34.7	0.7	255	1
4134MH0002990020904779C00	4779	13891	7.62	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	223	2
4134MH0002990020904780C00	4780	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	191	3
4134MH0002990020904781C00	4781	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
4134MH0002990020904782C00	4782	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4134MH0002990020904783C00	4783	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	95	6
4134MH0002990020904784C00	4784	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
4134MH0002990020904785C00	4785	14107	6.19	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 28_March_2024

SOL 4134 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Thompson_Canyon - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4134MH0002990010904787C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4135MH0005360000504868R00	4868	MOTOR COUNT:		14003	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4135MH0005360000504869S00	4869	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Mar-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4134	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4135	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4134MH0002990020904788C00	4788	13859	7.87	-0.2	0.2	34.6	0.7	255	1
4134MH0002990020904789C00	4789	13895	7.59	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	223	2
4134MH0002990020904790C00	4790	13931	7.32	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	191	3
4134MH0002990020904791C00	4791	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
4134MH0002990020904792C00	4792	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4134MH0002990020904793C00	4793	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
4134MH0002990020904794C00	4794	14075	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
4134MH0002990020904795C00	4795	14111	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4134 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cabin_Lake - ~23 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4134MH0008550010904797C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4135MH0005360000504866R00	4866	MOTOR COUNT:		13039	RANGE (cm):	25.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4135MH0005360000504867S00	4867	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00855	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Mar-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4134	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4135	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4134MH0008550020904798C00	4798	12919	34.02	-2.9	3.4	126.6	11.0	255	1
4134MH0008550020904799C00	4799	12949	31.34	-2.4	2.9	117.2	9.3	223	2
4134MH0008550020904800C00	4800	12979	29.03	-2.1	2.4	109.1	8.0	191	3
4134MH0008550020904801C00	4801	13009	27.02	-1.8	2.1	102.0	6.9	159	4
4134MH0008550020904802C00	4802	13039	25.24	-1.6	1.8	95.8	6.0	127	5
4134MH0008550020904803C00	4803	13069	23.67	-1.4	1.6	90.2	5.3	95	6
4134MH0008550020904804C00	4804	13099	22.26	-1.3	1.4	85.3	4.7	63	7
4134MH0008550020904805C00	4805	13129	21.00	-1.1	1.2	80.8	4.2	31	8

UPDATED: 28_March_2024

SOL 4134 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cabin_Lake - stereo-1 - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4134MH0002240010904807C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4135MH0005360000504864R00	4864	MOTOR COUNT:		14291	RANGE (cm):	5.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4135MH0005360000504865S00	4865	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Mar-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4134	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4135		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4134MH0002240020904808C00	4808	14123	6.10	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	255	1
4134MH0002240020904809C00	4809	14165	5.87	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	223	2
4134MH0002240020904810C00	4810	14207	5.66	-0.1	0.1	26.8	0.4	191	3
4134MH0002240020904811C00	4811	14249	5.45	-0.1	0.1	26.1	0.4	159	4
4134MH0002240020904812C00	4812	14291	5.26	-0.1	0.1	25.4	0.4	127	5
4134MH0002240020904813C00	4813	14333	5.07	-0.1	0.1	24.8	0.4	95	6
4134MH0002240020904814C00	4814	14375	4.90	-0.1	0.1	24.1	0.4	63	7
4134MH0002240020904815C00	4815	14417	4.73	-0.1	0.1	23.6	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 28_March_2024

SOL 4134 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cabin_Lake - stereo-2 - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4134MH0002240010904817C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4135MH0005360000504862R00	4862	MOTOR COUNT:		14283	RANGE (cm):	5.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4135MH0005360000504863S00	4863	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Mar-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4134	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4135		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4134MH0002240020904818C00	4818	14115	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	255	1
4134MH0002240020904819C00	4819	14157	5.92	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	223	2
4134MH0002240020904820C00	4820	14199	5.70	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	191	3
4134MH0002240020904821C00	4821	14241	5.49	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	159	4
4134MH0002240020904822C00	4822	14283	5.30	-0.1	0.1	25.5	0.4	127	5
4134MH0002240020904823C00	4823	14325	5.11	-0.1	0.1	24.9	0.4	95	6
4134MH0002240020904824C00	4824	14367	4.93	-0.1	0.1	24.3	0.4	63	7
4134MH0002240020904825C00	4825	14409	4.76	-0.1	0.1	23.7	0.3	31	8

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SOL 4134 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Smoky_Jack - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4134MH0008650010904827C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4135MH0005360000504860R00	4860	MOTOR COUNT:		13026	RANGE (cm):		26.0	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4135MH0005360000504861S00	4861	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00865		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Mar-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4134	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4135	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4134MH0008650020904828C00	4828	12930	32.99	-2.7	3.2	123.0	10.3	255	1
4134MH0008650020904829C00	4829	12954	30.93	-2.4	2.8	115.8	9.1	223	2
4134MH0008650020804830C00	4830	12978	29.10	-2.1	2.4	109.4	8.0	191	3
4134MH0008650020804831C00	4831	13002	27.46	-1.9	2.2	103.6	7.1	159	4
4134MH0008650020804832C00	4832	13026	25.99	-1.7	1.9	98.4	6.4	127	5
4134MH0008650020804833C00	4833	13050	24.64	-1.5	1.7	93.7	5.7	95	6
4134MH0008650020804834C00	4834	13074	23.42	-1.4	1.5	89.4	5.2	63	7
4134MH0008650020804835C00	4835	13098	22.31	-1.3	1.4	85.4	4.7	31	8

UPDATED: 28_March_2024

SOL 4134 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Smoky_Jack - stereo-1 - ~14 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4134MH0008410010804837C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4135MH0005360000504858R00	4858	MOTOR COUNT:		13285	RANGE (cm):		16.1	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4135MH0005360000504859S00	4859	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00841		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Mar-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4134	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4135	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4134MH0008410020804838C00	4838	13213	18.05	-0.9	0.9	70.4	3.1	255	1
4134MH0008410020804839C00	4839	13231	17.51	-0.8	0.9	68.6	2.9	223	2
4134MH0008410020804840C00	4840	13249	17.00	-0.8	0.8	66.8	2.8	191	3
4134MH0008410020804841C00	4841	13267	16.52	-0.7	0.8	65.0	2.6	159	4
4134MH0008410020804842C00	4842	13285	16.05	-0.7	0.7	63.4	2.5	127	5
4134MH0008410020804843C00	4843	13303	15.61	-0.7	0.7	61.9	2.3	95	6
4134MH0008410020804844C00	4844	13321	15.19	-0.6	0.6	60.4	2.2	63	7
4134MH0008410020804845C00	4845	13339	14.79	-0.6	0.6	59.0	2.1	31	8

UPDATED: 28_March_2024

SOL 4134 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Smoky_Jack - stereo-2 - ~14 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4134MH0008410010804847C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4135MH0005360000504856R00	4856	MOTOR COUNT:		13282	RANGE (cm):		16.1	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4135MH0005360000504857S00	4857	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00841		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Mar-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4134	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4135	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4134MH0008410020804848C00	4848	13210	18.15	-0.9	0.9	70.8	3.1	255	1
4134MH0008410020804849C00	4849	13228	17.60	-0.8	0.9	68.9	2.9	223	2
4134MH0008410020704850C00	4850	13246	17.09	-0.8	0.8	67.0	2.8	191	3
4134MH0008410020704851C00	4851	13264	16.60	-0.7	0.8	65.3	2.6	159	4
4134MH0008410020704852C00	4852	13282	16.13	-0.7	0.7	63.7	2.5	127	5
4134MH0008410020704853C00	4853	13300	15.68	-0.7	0.7	62.1	2.4	95	6
4134MH0008410020704854C00	4854	13318	15.26	-0.6	0.6	60.6	2.2	63	7
4134MH0008410020504855C00	4855	13336	14.85	-0.6	0.6	59.2	2.1	31	8

UPDATED: 01_April_2024

SOL 4137 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sunrise_Lakes - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4137MH0001680010504877C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4137MH0001930000304910R00	4910	MOTOR COUNT:		14035	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4137MH0001930000304911S00	4911	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Mar-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4137	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4137	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4137MH0001680020504878C00	4878	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	255	1
4137MH0001680020504879C00	4879	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	223	2
4137MH0001680020504880C00	4880	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	191	3
4137MH0001680020504881C00	4881	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
4137MH0001680020504882C00	4882	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	127	5
4137MH0001680020504883C00	4883	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6
4137MH0001680020504884C00	4884	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
4137MH0001680020504885C00	4885	14089	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 01_April_2024

SOL 4137 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sunrise_Lakes - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4137MH0001680010504887C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4137MH0001930000404908R00	4908	MOTOR COUNT:		14030	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4137MH0001930000304909S00	4909	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Mar-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4137	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4137	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4137MH0001680020504888C00	4888	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	255	1
4137MH0001680020504889C00	4889	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	223	2
4137MH0001680020504890C00	4890	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	191	3
4137MH0001680020504891C00	4891	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	159	4
4137MH0001680020504892C00	4892	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
4137MH0001680020504893C00	4893	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	95	6
4137MH0001680020504894C00	4894	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
4137MH0001680020504895C00	4895	14084	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 01_April_2024

SOL 4137 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sunrise_Lakes - after DRT - ~15 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4137MH0003020010504897C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4137MH0001930000404906R00		4906		MOTOR COUNT:		14751		RANGE (cm):	3.6
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4137MH0001930000404907S00		4907		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00302		STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		26-Mar-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:	BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4137		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4137	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4137MH0003020020504898C00	4898	14631	3.99	-0.1	0.1	20.9	0.3	255	1		
4137MH0003020020504899C00	4899	14661	3.90	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	223	2		
4137MH0003020020404900C00	4900	14691	3.81	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	191	3		
4137MH0003020020404901C00	4901	14721	3.72	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	159	4		
4137MH0003020020404902C00	4902	14751	3.64	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.3	127	5		
4137MH0003020020404903C00	4903	14781	3.56	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	95	6		
4137MH0003020020404904C00	4904	14811	3.48	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	63	7		
4137MH0003020020404905C00	4905	14841	3.41	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	31	8		

UPDATED: 01_April_2024

SOL 4139 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Rainbow_Falls - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4139MH0001680011500004C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4139MH0001930001500051R00	51	MOTOR COUNT:		14034	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4139MH0001930001500052S00	52	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	28-Mar-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4139	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4139	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4139MH0001680021500005C00	5	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	255	1
4139MH0001680021500006C00	6	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	223	2
4139MH0001680021500007C00	7	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	191	3
4139MH0001680021500008C00	8	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
4139MH0001680021500009C00	9	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	127	5
4139MH0001680021500010C00	10	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6
4139MH0001680021500011C00	11	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
4139MH0001680021500012C00	12	14088	6.30	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 01_April_2024

SOL 4139 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Rainbow_Falls - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4139MH0001680011500014C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4139MH0001930001500049R00	49	MOTOR COUNT:		14042	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4139MH0001930001500050S00	50	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	28-Mar-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4139	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4139	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4139MH0001680021500015C00	15	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
4139MH0001680021500016C00	16	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	223	2
4139MH0001680021500017C00	17	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3
4139MH0001680021500018C00	18	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	159	4
4139MH0001680021500019C00	19	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	127	5
4139MH0001680021500020C00	20	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6
4139MH0001680021500021C00	21	14078	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
4139MH0001680021500022C00	22	14096	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 01_April_2024

SOL 4139 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Rainbow_Falls - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4139MH0008640011500024C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4139MH0001930001500047R00	47	MOTOR COUNT:		14958	RANGE (cm):	3.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4139MH0001930001500048S00	48	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00864	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	28-Mar-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4139	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4139	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4139MH0008640021500025C00	25	14838	3.41	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	255	1
4139MH0008640021500026C00	26	14868	3.34	-0.1	0.1	18.7	0.2	223	2
4139MH0008640021500027C00	27	14898	3.27	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	191	3
4139MH0008640021500028C00	28	14928	3.20	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	159	4
4139MH0008640021500029C00	29	14958	3.13	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	127	5
4139MH0008640021500030C00	30	14988	3.06	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	95	6
4139MH0008640021500031C00	31	15018	3.00	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	63	7
4139MH0008640021500032C00	32	15048	2.94	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 28_June_2024

SOL 4141 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Rose_Lake - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4141MH0001680011500056C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4142MH0001700001500151R00	151	MOTOR COUNT:		14009	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4142MH0001700001500152S00	152	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	31-Mar-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4141	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4142	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4141MH0001680021500057C00	57	13937	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	255	1
4141MH0001680021500058C00	58	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
4141MH0001680021500059C00	59	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
4141MH0001680021500060C00	60	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4141MH0001680021500061C00	61	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
4141MH0001680021500062C00	62	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
4141MH0001680021500063C00	63	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
4141MH0001680021500064C00	64	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 28_June_2024

SOL 4141 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Rose_Lake - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4141MH0001680011500066C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4142MH0001700001500149R00	149	MOTOR COUNT:		14019	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4142MH0001700001500150S00	150	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	31-Mar-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4141	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4142	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4141MH0001680021500067C00	67	13947	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
4141MH0001680021500068C00	68	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
4141MH0001680021500069C00	69	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
4141MH0001680021500070C00	70	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
4141MH0001680021500071C00	71	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
4141MH0001680021500072C00	72	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	95	6
4141MH0001680021500073C00	73	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
4141MH0001680021500074C00	74	14073	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 28_June_2024

SOL 4141 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Rose_Lake - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4141MH0007430011500076C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4142MH0001700001500147R00		147		MOTOR COUNT:		15133		RANGE (cm): 2.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4142MH0001700001500148S00		148		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		31-Mar-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4141		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4142	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4141MH0007430021500077C00	77	14989	3.06	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	255	1		
4141MH0007430021500078C00	78	15025	2.99	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	223	2		
4141MH0007430021500079C00	79	15061	2.91	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	191	3		
4141MH0007430021500080C00	80	15097	2.84	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	159	4		
4141MH0007430021500081C00	81	15133	2.77	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	127	5		
4141MH0007430021500082C00	82	15169	2.70	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	95	6		
4141MH0007430021500083C00	83	15205	2.64	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	63	7		
4141MH0007430021500084C00	84	15241	2.58	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	31	8		

UPDATED: 28_June_2024

SOL 4141 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-1 - ~23 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4141MH0008650011500086C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4142MH0001700001500145R00		145		MOTOR COUNT:		13040		RANGE (cm): 25.2	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4142MH0001700001500146S00		146		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00865		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		31-Mar-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4141		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4142	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4141MH0008650021500087C00	87	12944	31.76	-2.5	2.9	118.7	9.6	255	1		
4141MH0008650021500088C00	88	12968	29.84	-2.2	2.6	111.9	8.4	223	2		
4141MH0008650021500089C00	89	12992	28.13	-2.0	2.3	105.9	7.5	191	3		
4141MH0008650021500090C00	90	13016	26.58	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	159	4		
4141MH0008650021500091C00	91	13040	25.19	-1.6	1.8	95.6	6.0	127	5		
4141MH0008650021500092C00	92	13064	23.92	-1.5	1.6	91.1	5.4	95	6		
4141MH0008650021500093C00	93	13088	22.76	-1.3	1.5	87.0	4.9	63	7		
4141MH0008650021500094C00	94	13112	21.70	-1.2	1.3	83.3	4.4	31	8		

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SOL 4141 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-2 - ~23 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4141MH0008650011500096C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4142MH0001700001500143R00	143	MOTOR COUNT:		13042	RANGE (cm):	25.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4142MH0001700001500144S00	144	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00865	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	31-Mar-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4141	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4142	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4141MH0008650021500097C00	97	12946	31.59	-2.5	2.9	118.1	9.5	255	1
4141MH0008650021500098C00	98	12970	29.69	-2.2	2.5	111.4	8.3	223	2
4141MH0008650021500099C00	99	12994	27.99	-2.0	2.2	105.4	7.4	191	3
4141MH0008650021500100C00	100	13018	26.46	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	159	4
4141MH0008650021500101C00	101	13042	25.08	-1.6	1.8	95.2	5.9	127	5
4141MH0008650021500102C00	102	13066	23.82	-1.4	1.6	90.7	5.3	95	6
4141MH0008650021500103C00	103	13090	22.67	-1.3	1.4	86.7	4.8	63	7
4141MH0008650021500104C00	104	13114	21.61	-1.2	1.3	83.0	4.4	31	8

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SOL 4141 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-3 - ~23 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4141MH0008650011500106C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4142MH0001700001500141R00	141	MOTOR COUNT:		13047	RANGE (cm):	24.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4142MH0001700001500142S00	142	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00865	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	31-Mar-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4141	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4142	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4141MH0008650021500107C00	107	12951	31.18	-2.4	2.8	116.6	9.2	255	1
4141MH0008650021500108C00	108	12975	29.32	-2.2	2.5	110.1	8.1	223	2
4141MH0008650021500109C00	109	12999	27.66	-1.9	2.2	104.3	7.2	191	3
4141MH0008650021500110C00	110	13023	26.16	-1.7	1.9	99.0	6.5	159	4
4141MH0008650021500111C00	111	13047	24.81	-1.6	1.7	94.2	5.8	127	5
4141MH0008650021500112C00	112	13071	23.57	-1.4	1.6	89.9	5.2	95	6
4141MH0008650021500113C00	113	13095	22.44	-1.3	1.4	85.9	4.8	63	7
4141MH0008650021500114C00	114	13119	21.41	-1.2	1.3	82.2	4.3	31	8

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SOL 4141 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Little_Slide_Canyon - stereo-1 - ~3 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4141MH0002240011500118C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4142MH0001700001500139R00	139	MOTOR COUNT:		14338	RANGE (cm):	5.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4142MH0001700001500140S00	140	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	31-Mar-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4141	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4142	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4141MH0002240021500119C00	119	14170	5.85	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	255	1
4141MH0002240021500120C00	120	14212	5.63	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	223	2
4141MH0002240021500121C00	121	14254	5.43	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	191	3
4141MH0002240021500122C00	122	14296	5.24	-0.1	0.1	25.3	0.4	159	4
4141MH0002240021500123C00	123	14338	5.05	-0.1	0.1	24.7	0.4	127	5
4141MH0002240021500124C00	124	14380	4.88	-0.1	0.1	24.1	0.4	95	6
4141MH0002240021500125C00	125	14422	4.71	-0.1	0.1	23.5	0.3	63	7
4141MH0002240021500126C00	126	14464	4.55	-0.1	0.1	22.9	0.3	31	8

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SOL 4141 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Little_Slide_Canyon - stereo-2 - ~3 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4141MH0002240011500128C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4142MH0001700001500137R00	137	MOTOR COUNT:		14341	RANGE (cm):	5.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4142MH0001700001500138S00	138	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	31-Mar-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4141	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4142	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4141MH0002240021500129C00	129	14173	5.83	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	255	1
4141MH0002240021500130C00	130	14215	5.62	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	223	2
4141MH0002240021500131C00	131	14257	5.42	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	191	3
4141MH0002240021500132C00	132	14299	5.22	-0.1	0.1	25.3	0.4	159	4
4141MH0002240021500133C00	133	14341	5.04	-0.1	0.1	24.6	0.4	127	5
4141MH0002240021500134C00	134	14383	4.87	-0.1	0.1	24.0	0.4	95	6
4141MH0002240021500135C00	135	14425	4.70	-0.1	0.1	23.4	0.3	63	7
4141MH0002240021500136C00	136	14467	4.54	-0.1	0.1	22.9	0.3	31	8

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SOL 4144 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Bodie - ~24 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4144MH0008550011500154C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4144MH0001930001500187R00		187		MOTOR COUNT:		13020		RANGE (cm): 26.3	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4144MH0001930001500188S00		188		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00855		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		3-Apr-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4144		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4144	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4144MH0008550021500155C00	155	12900	35.94	-3.2	3.8	133.4	12.3	255	1		
4144MH0008550021500156C00	156	12930	32.99	-2.7	3.2	123.0	10.3	223	2		
4144MH0008550021500157C00	157	12960	30.46	-2.3	2.7	114.1	8.8	191	3		
4144MH0008550021500158C00	158	12990	28.26	-2.0	2.3	106.4	7.5	159	4		
4144MH0008550021500159C00	159	13020	26.34	-1.8	2.0	99.6	6.6	127	5		
4144MH0008550021500160C00	160	13050	24.64	-1.5	1.7	93.7	5.7	95	6		
4144MH0008550021500161C00	161	13080	23.14	-1.4	1.5	88.3	5.1	63	7		
4144MH0008550021500162C00	162	13110	21.78	-1.2	1.3	83.6	4.5	31	8		

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SOL 4144 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Bodie - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4144MH0002970011500164C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4144MH0001930001500185R00		185		MOTOR COUNT:		14038		RANGE (cm): 6.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4144MH0001930001500186S00		186		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00297		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		3-Apr-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		60		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4144		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4144	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4144MH0002970021500165C00	165	13798	8.39	-0.2	0.2	36.4	0.8	255	1		
4144MH0002970021500166C00	166	13858	7.88	-0.2	0.2	34.6	0.7	223	2		
4144MH0002970021500167C00	167	13918	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	191	3		
4144MH0002970021500168C00	168	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4		
4144MH0002970021500169C00	169	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	127	5		
4144MH0002970021500170C00	170	14098	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	95	6		
4144MH0002970021500171C00	171	14158	5.91	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	63	7		
4144MH0002970021500172C00	172	14218	5.60	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	31	8		

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SOL 4144 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Bodie - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4144MH0002970011500174C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4144MH0001930001500183R00	183	MOTOR COUNT:		14035	RANGE (cm):		6.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4144MH0001930001500184S00	184	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00297		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Apr-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		60	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4144		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4144
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4144MH0002970021500175C00	175	13795	8.41	-0.2	0.2	36.5	0.8	255	1
4144MH0002970021500176C00	176	13855	7.90	-0.2	0.2	34.7	0.7	223	2
4144MH0002970021500177C00	177	13915	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	191	3
4144MH0002970021500178C00	178	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
4144MH0002970021500179C00	179	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	127	5
4144MH0002970021500180C00	180	14095	6.26	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	95	6
4144MH0002970021500181C00	181	14155	5.93	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	63	7
4144MH0002970021500182C00	182	14215	5.62	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4146 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Ruby_Peak - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4146MH0001680011500192C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4146MH0001930001500234R00	234	MOTOR COUNT:		14013	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4146MH0001930001500235S00	235	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Apr-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4146	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4146	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4146MH0001680021500193C00	193	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
4146MH0001680021500194C00	194	13959	7.12	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
4146MH0001680021500195C00	195	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
4146MH0001680021500196C00	196	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
4146MH0001680021500197C00	197	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
4146MH0001680021500198C00	198	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
4146MH0001680021500199C00	199	14049	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
4146MH0001680021500200C00	200	14067	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4146 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Ruby_Peak - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4146MH0001680011500202C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4146MH0001930001500232R00	232	MOTOR COUNT:		14017	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4146MH0001930001500233S00	233	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Apr-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4146	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4146	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4146MH0001680021500203C00	203	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
4146MH0001680021500204C00	204	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
4146MH0001680021500205C00	205	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
4146MH0001680021500206C00	206	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
4146MH0001680021500207C00	207	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
4146MH0001680021500208C00	208	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	95	6
4146MH0001680021500209C00	209	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
4146MH0001680021500210C00	210	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4146 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Ruby_Peak - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff												
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4146MH0003020011500212C00								
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4146MH0001930001500230R00		230		MOTOR COUNT:		14719		RANGE (cm):		3.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4146MH0001930001500231S00		231		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00302		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		5-Apr-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			30		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4146		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4146			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8					
				NEAR	FAR									
4146MH0003020021500213C00	213	14599	4.09	-0.1	0.1	21.3	0.3	255	1					
4146MH0003020021500214C00	214	14629	4.00	-0.1	0.1	21.0	0.3	223	2					
4146MH0003020021500215C00	215	14659	3.90	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	191	3					
4146MH0003020021500216C00	216	14689	3.82	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	159	4					
4146MH0003020021500217C00	217	14719	3.73	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	127	5					
4146MH0003020021500218C00	218	14749	3.65	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.3	95	6					
4146MH0003020021500219C00	219	14779	3.57	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	63	7					
4146MH0003020021500220C00	220	14809	3.49	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	31	8					

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SOL 4148 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Ahwahnee - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4148MH0003360011500239C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4148MH0001930001500272R00	272	MOTOR COUNT:		14051	RANGE (cm):	6.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4148MH0001930001500273S00	273	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Apr-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4148	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4148	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4148MH0003360021500240C00	240	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	255	1
4148MH0003360021500241C00	241	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	223	2
4148MH0003360021500242C00	242	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	191	3
4148MH0003360021500243C00	243	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	159	4
4148MH0003360021500244C00	244	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	127	5
4148MH0003360021500245C00	245	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	95	6
4148MH0003360021500246C00	246	14075	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
4148MH0003360021500247C00	247	14087	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4148 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Ahwahnee - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4148MH0003360011500249C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4148MH0001930001500270R00	270	MOTOR COUNT:		14052	RANGE (cm):	6.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4148MH0001930001500271S00	271	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Apr-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4148	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4148	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4148MH0003360021500250C00	250	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	255	1
4148MH0003360021500251C00	251	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	223	2
4148MH0003360021500252C00	252	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	191	3
4148MH0003360021500253C00	253	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	159	4
4148MH0003360021500254C00	254	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	127	5
4148MH0003360021500255C00	255	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	95	6
4148MH0003360021500256C00	256	14076	6.37	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
4148MH0003360021500257C00	257	14088	6.30	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 28_June_2024

SOL 4148 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Ahwahnee – after DRT – ~5 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4148MH0008640011500259C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4148MH0001930001500268R00	268	MOTOR COUNT:		15267	RANGE (cm):		2.5	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4148MH0001930001500269S00	269	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00864		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Apr-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4148		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4148
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4148MH0008640021500260C00	260	15147	2.74	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	255	1
4148MH0008640021500261C00	261	15177	2.69	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	223	2
4148MH0008640021500262C00	262	15207	2.63	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	191	3
4148MH0008640021500263C00	263	15237	2.58	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	159	4
4148MH0008640021500264C00	264	15267	2.53	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	127	5
4148MH0008640021500265C00	265	15297	2.48	0.0	0.1	15.6	0.2	95	6
4148MH0008640021500266C00	266	15327	2.43	0.0	0.1	15.5	0.2	63	7
4148MH0008640021500267C00	267	15357	2.39	0.0	0.1	15.3	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 01_July_2024

SOL 4152 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Burro_Pass - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4152MH0003360011500277C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4152MH0001930001500310R00	310	MOTOR COUNT:		14027	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4152MH0001930001500311S00	311	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	11-Apr-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4152	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4152	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4152MH0003360021500278C00	278	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	255	1
4152MH0003360021500279C00	279	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
4152MH0003360021500280C00	280	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3
4152MH0003360021500281C00	281	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
4152MH0003360021500282C00	282	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
4152MH0003360021500283C00	283	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
4152MH0003360021500284C00	284	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
4152MH0003360021500285C00	285	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 01_July_2024

SOL 4152 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Burro_Pass - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4152MH0003360011500287C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4152MH0001930001500308R00	308	MOTOR COUNT:		14034	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4152MH0001930001500309S00	309	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	11-Apr-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4152	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4152	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4152MH0003360021500288C00	288	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	255	1
4152MH0003360021500289C00	289	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	223	2
4152MH0003360021500290C00	290	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	191	3
4152MH0003360021500291C00	291	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	159	4
4152MH0003360021500292C00	292	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	127	5
4152MH0003360021500293C00	293	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	95	6
4152MH0003360021500294C00	294	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
4152MH0003360021500295C00	295	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 01_July_2024

SOL 4152 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Burro_Pass - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4152MH0008480011500297C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4152MH0001930001500306R00	306	MOTOR COUNT:		14950	RANGE (cm):		3.1	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4152MH0001930001500307S00	307	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	11-Apr-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4152	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4152	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4152MH0008480021500298C00	298	14854	3.37	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	255	1
4152MH0008480021500299C00	299	14878	3.32	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	223	2
4152MH0008480021500300C00	300	14902	3.26	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	191	3
4152MH0008480021500301C00	301	14926	3.20	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	159	4
4152MH0008480021500302C00	302	14950	3.15	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	127	5
4152MH0008480021500303C00	303	14974	3.10	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	95	6
4152MH0008480021500304C00	304	14998	3.04	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	63	7
4152MH0008480021500305C00	305	15022	2.99	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 28_June_2024

SOL 4154 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Hetch_Hetchy - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4154MH0001680011500333C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4155MH0001930001500366R00	366	MOTOR COUNT:		14000	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4155MH0001930001500367S00	367	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-Apr-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4154	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4155		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4154MH0001680021500334C00	334	13928	7.34	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
4154MH0001680021500335C00	335	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
4154MH0001680021500336C00	336	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4154MH0001680021500337C00	337	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4154MH0001680021500338C00	338	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4154MH0001680021500339C00	339	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4154MH0001680021500340C00	340	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	63	7
4154MH0001680021500341C00	341	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 28_June_2024

SOL 4154 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Hetch_Hetchy - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4154MH0001680011500343C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4155MH0001930001500364R00	364	MOTOR COUNT:		13991	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4155MH0001930001500365S00	365	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-Apr-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4154	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4155		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4154MH0001680021500344C00	344	13919	7.41	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	255	1
4154MH0001680021500345C00	345	13937	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	223	2
4154MH0001680021500346C00	346	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
4154MH0001680021500347C00	347	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
4154MH0001680021500348C00	348	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4154MH0001680021500349C00	349	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
4154MH0001680021500350C00	350	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4154MH0001680021500351C00	351	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 28_June_2024

SOL 4154 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Hetch_Hetchy - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4155MH0001930001500362R00		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4154MH0007430011500353C00	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4155MH0001930001500363S00		362		MOTOR COUNT:		15061	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		13-Apr-24		363		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES		CDPID		MOTOR COUNT		RANGE (cm)		RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)	
								PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	
								PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	
								DN IN RANGE MAP	
								IMAGE N OF 8	
						NEAR		FAR	
4154MH0007430021500354C00		354		14917		3.22		-0.1 0.1	
4154MH0007430021500355C00		355		14953		3.14		-0.1 0.1	
4154MH0007430021500356C00		356		14989		3.06		-0.1 0.1	
4154MH0007430021500357C00		357		15025		2.99		-0.1 0.1	
4154MH0007430021500358C00		358		15061		2.91		-0.1 0.1	
4154MH0007430021500359C00		359		15097		2.84		-0.1 0.1	
4154MH0007430021500360C00		360		15133		2.77		-0.1 0.1	
4154MH0007430021500361C00		361		15169		2.70		-0.1 0.1	
								18.2 0.2	
								18.0 0.2	
								17.7 0.2	
								17.4 0.2	
								17.1 0.2	
								16.9 0.2	
								16.7 0.2	
								16.4 0.2	
								255	
								223	
								191	
								159	
								127	
								95	
								63	
								31	
								8	

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4157 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Peppermint_Pass - stereo-1 - ~14 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4157MH0008410011500369C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4158MH0001710001500454R00	454	MOTOR COUNT:		13314	RANGE (cm):	15.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4158MH0001710001500455S00	455	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00841	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Apr-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4157	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4158		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4157MH0008410021500370C00	370	13242	17.20	-0.8	0.8	67.4	2.8	255	1
4157MH0008410021500371C00	371	13260	16.70	-0.7	0.8	65.7	2.7	223	2
4157MH0008410021500372C00	372	13278	16.23	-0.7	0.7	64.0	2.5	191	3
4157MH0008410021500373C00	373	13296	15.78	-0.7	0.7	62.4	2.4	159	4
4157MH0008410021500374C00	374	13314	15.35	-0.6	0.7	60.9	2.3	127	5
4157MH0008410021500375C00	375	13332	14.94	-0.6	0.6	59.5	2.1	95	6
4157MH0008410021500376C00	376	13350	14.55	-0.6	0.6	58.1	2.0	63	7
4157MH0008410021500377C00	377	13368	14.17	-0.6	0.6	56.8	1.9	31	8

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4157 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Peppermint_Pass - stereo-2 - ~14 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4157MH0008410011500379C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4158MH0001710001500452R00	452	MOTOR COUNT:		13313	RANGE (cm):	15.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4158MH0001710001500453S00	453	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00841	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Apr-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4157	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4158		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4157MH0008410021500380C00	380	13241	17.23	-0.8	0.8	67.5	2.8	255	1
4157MH0008410021500381C00	381	13259	16.73	-0.7	0.8	65.8	2.7	223	2
4157MH0008410021500382C00	382	13277	16.26	-0.7	0.7	64.1	2.5	191	3
4157MH0008410021500383C00	383	13295	15.80	-0.7	0.7	62.5	2.4	159	4
4157MH0008410021500384C00	384	13313	15.37	-0.6	0.7	61.0	2.3	127	5
4157MH0008410021500385C00	385	13331	14.96	-0.6	0.6	59.6	2.2	95	6
4157MH0008410021500386C00	386	13349	14.57	-0.6	0.6	58.2	2.0	63	7
4157MH0008410021500387C00	387	13367	14.19	-0.6	0.6	56.9	2.0	31	8

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4157 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tioga_Pass - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
				CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4157MH0001680011500391C00		
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4158MH0001710001500450R00			450	MOTOR COUNT:		14021	RANGE (cm):	6.7
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4158MH0001710001500451S00			451	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Apr-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4157		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4158
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4157MH0001680021500392C00	392	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1
4157MH0001680021500393C00	393	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
4157MH0001680021500394C00	394	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3
4157MH0001680021500395C00	395	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
4157MH0001680021500396C00	396	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5
4157MH0001680021500397C00	397	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
4157MH0001680021500398C00	398	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
4157MH0001680021500399C00	399	14075	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4157 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tioga_Pass - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
				CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4157MH0001680011500401C00		
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4158MH0001710001500448R00			448	MOTOR COUNT:		14031	RANGE (cm):	6.6
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4158MH0001710001500449S00			449	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Apr-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4157		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4158
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4157MH0001680021500402C00	402	13959	7.12	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	255	1
4157MH0001680021500403C00	403	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	223	2
4157MH0001680021500404C00	404	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	191	3
4157MH0001680021500405C00	405	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	159	4
4157MH0001680021500406C00	406	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
4157MH0001680021500407C00	407	14049	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	95	6
4157MH0001680021500408C00	408	14067	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
4157MH0001680021500409C00	409	14085	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4157 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tioga_Pass - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff								
				CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4157MH0007430011500411C00			
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4158MH0001710001500446R00		446		MOTOR COUNT:		15163	RANGE (cm):	2.7	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4158MH0001710001500447S00		447		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Apr-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4157		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4158
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8	
				NEAR	FAR					
4157MH0007430021500412C00	412	15019	3.00	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	255	1	
4157MH0007430021500413C00	413	15055	2.92	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	223	2	
4157MH0007430021500414C00	414	15091	2.85	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	191	3	
4157MH0007430021500415C00	415	15127	2.78	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	159	4	
4157MH0007430021500416C00	416	15163	2.71	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	127	5	
4157MH0007430021500417C00	417	15199	2.65	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	95	6	
4157MH0007430021500418C00	418	15235	2.59	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	63	7	
4157MH0007430021500419C00	419	15271	2.52	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	31	8	

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4157 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Wonder_Lakes - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff								
				CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4157MH0001820011500423C00			
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4158MH0001710001500444R00		444		MOTOR COUNT:		14034	RANGE (cm):	6.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4158MH0001710001500445S00		445		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Apr-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4157		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4158
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8	
				NEAR	FAR					
4157MH0001820021500424C00	424	13938	7.27	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	255	1	
4157MH0001820021500425C00	425	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2	
4157MH0001820021500426C00	426	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3	
4157MH0001820021500427C00	427	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	159	4	
4157MH0001820021500428C00	428	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	127	5	
4157MH0001820021500429C00	429	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6	
4157MH0001820021500430C00	430	14082	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7	
4157MH0001820021500431C00	431	14106	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8	

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4157 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Wonder_Lakes - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4157MH0001820011500433C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4158MH0001710001500442R00	442	MOTOR COUNT:		14037	RANGE (cm):		6.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4158MH0001710001500443S00	443	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Apr-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4157		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4158
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4157MH0001820021500434C00	434	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
4157MH0001820021500435C00	435	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
4157MH0001820021500436C00	436	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
4157MH0001820021500437C00	437	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	159	4
4157MH0001820021500438C00	438	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	127	5
4157MH0001820021500439C00	439	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	95	6
4157MH0001820021500440C00	440	14085	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
4157MH0001820021500441C00	441	14109	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 01_July_2024

SOL 4159 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tilden_Lake - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4159MH0001680011500459C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4159MH0001930001500492R00	492	MOTOR COUNT:		14014	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4159MH0001930001500493S00	493	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	18-Apr-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4159	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4159	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4159MH0001680021500460C00	460	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
4159MH0001680021500461C00	461	13960	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
4159MH0001680021500462C00	462	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
4159MH0001680021500463C00	463	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
4159MH0001680021500464C00	464	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
4159MH0001680021500465C00	465	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
4159MH0001680021500466C00	466	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
4159MH0001680021500467C00	467	14068	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 01_July_2024

SOL 4159 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tilden_Lake - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4159MH0001680011500469C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4159MH0001930001500490R00	490	MOTOR COUNT:		14021	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4159MH0001930001500491S00	491	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	18-Apr-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4159	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4159	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4159MH0001680021500470C00	470	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1
4159MH0001680021500471C00	471	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
4159MH0001680021500472C00	472	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3
4159MH0001680021500473C00	473	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
4159MH0001680021500474C00	474	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5
4159MH0001680021500475C00	475	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
4159MH0001680021500476C00	476	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
4159MH0001680021500477C00	477	14075	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 01_July_2024

SOL 4159 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tilden_Lake – after DRT – ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4159MH0007430011500479C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4159MH0001930001500488R00	488	MOTOR COUNT:		15157	RANGE (cm):		2.7	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4159MH0001930001500489S00	489	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	18-Apr-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4159	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4159	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4159MH0007430021500480C00	480	15013	3.01	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	255	1
4159MH0007430021500481C00	481	15049	2.94	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	223	2
4159MH0007430021500482C00	482	15085	2.86	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	191	3
4159MH0007430021500483C00	483	15121	2.79	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	159	4
4159MH0007430021500484C00	484	15157	2.73	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	127	5
4159MH0007430021500485C00	485	15193	2.66	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	95	6
4159MH0007430021500486C00	486	15229	2.60	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	63	7
4159MH0007430021500487C00	487	15265	2.53	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4161 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mist_Falls - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4161MH0002990011500503C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4162MH0001700001500598R00	598	MOTOR COUNT:		14185	RANGE (cm):	5.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4162MH0001700001500599S00	599	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	20-Apr-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4161	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4162		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4161MH0002990021500504C00	504	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	255	1
4161MH0002990021500505C00	505	14077	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	223	2
4161MH0002990021500506C00	506	14113	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	191	3
4161MH0002990021500507C00	507	14149	5.96	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	159	4
4161MH0002990021500508C00	508	14185	5.77	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	127	5
4161MH0002990021500509C00	509	14221	5.59	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	95	6
4161MH0002990021500510C00	510	14257	5.42	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	63	7
4161MH0002990021500511C00	511	14293	5.25	-0.1	0.1	25.4	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4161 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mist_Falls - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4161MH0002990011500513C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4162MH0001700001500596R00	596	MOTOR COUNT:		14186	RANGE (cm):	5.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4162MH0001700001500597S00	597	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	20-Apr-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4161	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4162		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4161MH0002990021500514C00	514	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	255	1
4161MH0002990021500515C00	515	14078	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	223	2
4161MH0002990021500516C00	516	14114	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	191	3
4161MH0002990021500517C00	517	14150	5.95	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	159	4
4161MH0002990021500518C00	518	14186	5.76	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	127	5
4161MH0002990021500519C00	519	14222	5.58	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	95	6
4161MH0002990021500520C00	520	14258	5.41	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	63	7
4161MH0002990021500521C00	521	14294	5.25	-0.1	0.1	25.4	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4161 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-1 - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4161MH0008650011500523C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4162MH0001700001500594R00	594	MOTOR COUNT:		13030	RANGE (cm):	25.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4162MH0001700001500595S00	595	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00865	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	20-Apr-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4161	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4162		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4161MH0008650021500524C00	524	12934	32.63	-2.6	3.1	121.8	10.1	255	1
4161MH0008650021500525C00	525	12958	30.61	-2.3	2.7	114.7	8.9	223	2
4161MH0008650021500526C00	526	12982	28.82	-2.1	2.4	108.3	7.9	191	3
4161MH0008650021500527C00	527	13006	27.21	-1.9	2.1	102.7	7.0	159	4
4161MH0008650021500528C00	528	13030	25.75	-1.7	1.9	97.6	6.3	127	5
4161MH0008650021500529C00	529	13054	24.43	-1.5	1.7	92.9	5.6	95	6
4161MH0008650021500530C00	530	13078	23.23	-1.4	1.5	88.7	5.1	63	7
4161MH0008650021500531C00	531	13102	22.13	-1.3	1.4	84.8	4.6	31	8

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4161 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-2 - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4161MH0008650011500533C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4162MH0001700001500592R00	592	MOTOR COUNT:		13031	RANGE (cm):	25.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4162MH0001700001500593S00	593	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00865	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	20-Apr-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4161	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4162		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4161MH0008650021500534C00	534	12935	32.54	-2.6	3.1	121.4	10.0	255	1
4161MH0008650021500535C00	535	12959	30.54	-2.3	2.7	114.4	8.8	223	2
4161MH0008650021500536C00	536	12983	28.75	-2.1	2.4	108.1	7.8	191	3
4161MH0008650021500537C00	537	13007	27.14	-1.9	2.1	102.4	7.0	159	4
4161MH0008650021500538C00	538	13031	25.70	-1.7	1.9	97.3	6.2	127	5
4161MH0008650021500539C00	539	13055	24.38	-1.5	1.7	92.7	5.6	95	6
4161MH0008650021500540C00	540	13079	23.18	-1.4	1.5	88.5	5.1	63	7
4161MH0008650021500541C00	541	13103	22.09	-1.3	1.4	84.6	4.6	31	8

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4161 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-3 - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4161MH0008650011500543C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4162MH0001700001500590R00	590	MOTOR COUNT:		13031	RANGE (cm):	25.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4162MH0001700001500591S00	591	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00865	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	20-Apr-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4161	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4162		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4161MH0008650021500544C00	544	12935	32.54	-2.6	3.1	121.4	10.0	255	1
4161MH0008650021500545C00	545	12959	30.54	-2.3	2.7	114.4	8.8	223	2
4161MH0008650021500546C00	546	12983	28.75	-2.1	2.4	108.1	7.8	191	3
4161MH0008650021500547C00	547	13007	27.14	-1.9	2.1	102.4	7.0	159	4
4161MH0008650021500548C00	548	13031	25.70	-1.7	1.9	97.3	6.2	127	5
4161MH0008650021500549C00	549	13055	24.38	-1.5	1.7	92.7	5.6	95	6
4161MH0008650021500550C00	550	13079	23.18	-1.4	1.5	88.5	5.1	63	7
4161MH0008650021500551C00	551	13103	22.09	-1.3	1.4	84.6	4.6	31	8

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4161 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Florence_Lake - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4161MH0003360011500555C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4162MH0001700001500588R00	588	MOTOR COUNT:		14037	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4162MH0001700001500589S00	589	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	20-Apr-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4161	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4162		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4161MH0003360021500556C00	556	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	255	1
4161MH0003360021500557C00	557	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	223	2
4161MH0003360021500558C00	558	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	191	3
4161MH0003360021500559C00	559	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	159	4
4161MH0003360021500560C00	560	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	127	5
4161MH0003360021500561C00	561	14049	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	95	6
4161MH0003360021500562C00	562	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
4161MH0003360021500563C00	563	14073	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4161 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Florence_Lake - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4161MH0003360011500565C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4162MH0001700001500586R00	586	MOTOR COUNT:		14040	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4162MH0001700001500587S00	587	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	20-Apr-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4161	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4162	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4161MH0003360021500566C00	566	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	255	1
4161MH0003360021500567C00	567	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	223	2
4161MH0003360021500568C00	568	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	191	3
4161MH0003360021500569C00	569	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	159	4
4161MH0003360021500570C00	570	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	127	5
4161MH0003360021500571C00	571	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6
4161MH0003360021500572C00	572	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
4161MH0003360021500573C00	573	14076	6.37	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4161 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Florence_Lake - after DRT - ~5 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4161MH0008480011500575C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4162MH0001700001500584R00	584	MOTOR COUNT:		15210	RANGE (cm):	2.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4162MH0001700001500585S00	585	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	20-Apr-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4161	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4162	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4161MH0008480021500576C00	576	15114	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	255	1
4161MH0008480021500577C00	577	15138	2.76	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	223	2
4161MH0008480021500578C00	578	15162	2.72	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	191	3
4161MH0008480021500579C00	579	15186	2.67	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	159	4
4161MH0008480021500580C00	580	15210	2.63	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	127	5
4161MH0008480021500581C00	581	15234	2.59	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	95	6
4161MH0008480021500582C00	582	15258	2.55	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	63	7
4161MH0008480021500583C00	583	15282	2.51	0.0	0.1	15.7	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4164 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sluggo_Pass - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4164MH0001680011500603C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4164MH0001930001500636R00	636	MOTOR COUNT:		14001	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4164MH0001930001500637S00	637	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Apr-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4164	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4164	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4164MH0001680021500604C00	604	13929	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
4164MH0001680021500605C00	605	13947	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
4164MH0001680021500606C00	606	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4164MH0001680021500607C00	607	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4164MH0001680021500608C00	608	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4164MH0001680021500609C00	609	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4164MH0001680021500610C00	610	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	63	7
4164MH0001680021500611C00	611	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4164 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sluggo_Pass - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4164MH0001680011500613C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4164MH0001930001500634R00	634	MOTOR COUNT:		14000	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4164MH0001930001500635S00	635	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Apr-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4164	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4164	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4164MH0001680021500614C00	614	13928	7.34	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
4164MH0001680021500615C00	615	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
4164MH0001680021500616C00	616	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4164MH0001680021500617C00	617	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4164MH0001680021500618C00	618	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4164MH0001680021500619C00	619	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4164MH0001680021500620C00	620	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	63	7
4164MH0001680021500621C00	621	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4164 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sluggo_Pass - ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4164MH0003020011500623C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4164MH0001930001500632R00	632	MOTOR COUNT:		14699	RANGE (cm):		3.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4164MH0001930001500633S00	633	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00302	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Apr-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4164	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4164	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4164MH0003020021500624C00	624	14579	4.15	-0.1	0.1	21.5	0.3	255	1
4164MH0003020021500625C00	625	14609	4.06	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	223	2
4164MH0003020021500626C00	626	14639	3.96	-0.1	0.1	20.9	0.3	191	3
4164MH0003020021500627C00	627	14669	3.87	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	159	4
4164MH0003020021500628C00	628	14699	3.79	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	127	5
4164MH0003020021500629C00	629	14729	3.70	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	95	6
4164MH0003020021500630C00	630	14759	3.62	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	63	7
4164MH0003020021500631C00	631	14789	3.54	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 01_July_2024

SOL 4166 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Twin_Peaks - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4166MH0003590011500639C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4166MH0001930001500672R00	672	MOTOR COUNT:		13020	RANGE (cm):	26.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4166MH0001930001500673S00	673	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	25-Apr-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4166	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4166		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4166MH0003590021500640C00	640	12948	31.42	-2.5	2.9	117.5	9.4	255	1
4166MH0003590021500641C00	641	12966	29.99	-2.2	2.6	112.5	8.5	223	2
4166MH0003590021500642C00	642	12984	28.68	-2.1	2.4	107.8	7.8	191	3
4166MH0003590021500643C00	643	13002	27.46	-1.9	2.2	103.6	7.1	159	4
4166MH0003590021500644C00	644	13020	26.34	-1.8	2.0	99.6	6.6	127	5
4166MH0003590021500645C00	645	13038	25.30	-1.6	1.8	96.0	6.0	95	6
4166MH0003590021500646C00	646	13056	24.33	-1.5	1.7	92.5	5.6	63	7
4166MH0003590021500647C00	647	13074	23.42	-1.4	1.5	89.4	5.2	31	8

UPDATED: 01_July_2024

SOL 4166 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Twin_Peaks - stereo-1 - ~10 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4166MH0003420011500649C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4166MH0001930001500670R00	670	MOTOR COUNT:		13503	RANGE (cm):	11.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4166MH0001930001500671S00	671	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00342	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	25-Apr-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4166	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4166		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4166MH0003420021500650C00	650	13407	13.41	-0.5	0.5	54.1	1.8	255	1
4166MH0003420021500651C00	651	13431	12.98	-0.5	0.5	52.6	1.7	223	2
4166MH0003420021500652C00	652	13455	12.57	-0.4	0.4	51.1	1.6	191	3
4166MH0003420021500653C00	653	13479	12.18	-0.4	0.4	49.8	1.5	159	4
4166MH0003420021500654C00	654	13503	11.80	-0.4	0.4	48.5	1.4	127	5
4166MH0003420021500655C00	655	13527	11.45	-0.4	0.4	47.2	1.3	95	6
4166MH0003420021500656C00	656	13551	11.11	-0.4	0.4	46.0	1.3	63	7
4166MH0003420021500657C00	657	13575	10.79	-0.3	0.3	44.9	1.2	31	8

UPDATED: 01_July_2024

SOL 4166 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Twin_Peaks - stereo-2 - ~10 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4166MH0003420011500659C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4166MH0001930001500668R00	668	MOTOR COUNT:		13505	RANGE (cm):		11.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4166MH0001930001500669S00	669	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00342		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	25-Apr-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4166		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4166
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4166MH0003420021500660C00	660	13409	13.38	-0.5	0.5	54.0	1.7	255	1
4166MH0003420021500661C00	661	13433	12.94	-0.5	0.5	52.5	1.6	223	2
4166MH0003420021500662C00	662	13457	12.53	-0.4	0.4	51.0	1.6	191	3
4166MH0003420021500663C00	663	13481	12.14	-0.4	0.4	49.7	1.5	159	4
4166MH0003420021500664C00	664	13505	11.77	-0.4	0.4	48.3	1.4	127	5
4166MH0003420021500665C00	665	13529	11.42	-0.4	0.4	47.1	1.3	95	6
4166MH0003420021500666C00	666	13553	11.09	-0.4	0.4	45.9	1.3	63	7
4166MH0003420021500667C00	667	13577	10.77	-0.3	0.3	44.8	1.2	31	8

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4168 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - ~25 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4168MH0003590011500675C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4169MH0001700001500770R00		770		MOTOR COUNT:		13015		RANGE (cm): 26.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4169MH0001700001500771S00		771		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		27-Apr-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4168		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4169	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4168MH0003590021500676C00	676	12943	31.85	-2.5	2.9	119.0	9.6	255	1		
4168MH0003590021500677C00	677	12961	30.38	-2.3	2.7	113.8	8.7	223	2		
4168MH0003590021500678C00	678	12979	29.03	-2.1	2.4	109.1	8.0	191	3		
4168MH0003590021500679C00	679	12997	27.79	-1.9	2.2	104.7	7.3	159	4		
4168MH0003590021500680C00	680	13015	26.64	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	127	5		
4168MH0003590021500681C00	681	13033	25.58	-1.7	1.9	96.9	6.2	95	6		
4168MH0003590021500682C00	682	13051	24.59	-1.5	1.7	93.5	5.7	63	7		
4168MH0003590021500683C00	683	13069	23.67	-1.4	1.6	90.2	5.3	31	8		

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4168 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-3 - ~25 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4168MH0003590011500685C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4169MH0001700001500768R00		768		MOTOR COUNT:		13016		RANGE (cm): 26.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4169MH0001700001500769S00		769		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		27-Apr-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4168		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4169	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4168MH0003590021500686C00	686	12944	31.76	-2.5	2.9	118.7	9.6	255	1		
4168MH0003590021500687C00	687	12962	30.30	-2.3	2.7	113.6	8.7	223	2		
4168MH0003590021500688C00	688	12980	28.96	-2.1	2.4	108.8	7.9	191	3		
4168MH0003590021500689C00	689	12998	27.73	-1.9	2.2	104.5	7.3	159	4		
4168MH0003590021500690C00	690	13016	26.58	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	127	5		
4168MH0003590021500691C00	691	13034	25.52	-1.7	1.8	96.7	6.1	95	6		
4168MH0003590021500692C00	692	13052	24.54	-1.5	1.7	93.3	5.7	63	7		
4168MH0003590021500693C00	693	13070	23.62	-1.4	1.6	90.0	5.3	31	8		

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4168 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4168MH0003590011500695C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4169MH0001700001500766R00	766	MOTOR COUNT:		13014	RANGE (cm):	26.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4169MH0001700001500767S00	767	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Apr-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4168	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4169		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4168MH0003590021500696C00	696	12942	31.93	-2.5	3.0	119.3	9.7	255	1
4168MH0003590021500697C00	697	12960	30.46	-2.3	2.7	114.1	8.8	223	2
4168MH0003590021500698C00	698	12978	29.10	-2.1	2.4	109.4	8.0	191	3
4168MH0003590021500699C00	699	12996	27.86	-2.0	2.2	105.0	7.3	159	4
4168MH0003590021500700C00	700	13014	26.71	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	127	5
4168MH0003590021500701C00	701	13032	25.64	-1.7	1.9	97.1	6.2	95	6
4168MH0003590021500702C00	702	13050	24.64	-1.5	1.7	93.7	5.7	63	7
4168MH0003590021500703C00	703	13068	23.72	-1.4	1.6	90.4	5.3	31	8

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4168 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4168MH0001820011500705C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4169MH0001700001500764R00	764	MOTOR COUNT:		13993	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4169MH0001700001500765S00	765	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Apr-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4168	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4169		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4168MH0001820021500706C00	706	13897	7.57	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
4168MH0001820021500707C00	707	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
4168MH0001820021500708C00	708	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
4168MH0001820021500709C00	709	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
4168MH0001820021500710C00	710	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4168MH0001820021500711C00	711	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4168MH0001820021500712C00	712	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
4168MH0001820021500713C00	713	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4168 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4168MH0001820011500715C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4169MH0001700001500762R00	762	MOTOR COUNT:		13991	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4169MH0001700001500763S00	763	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Apr-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4168	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4169	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4168MH0001820021500716C00	716	13895	7.59	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
4168MH0001820021500717C00	717	13919	7.41	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	223	2
4168MH0001820021500718C00	718	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
4168MH0001820021500719C00	719	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
4168MH0001820021500720C00	720	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4168MH0001820021500721C00	721	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4168MH0001820021500722C00	722	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
4168MH0001820021500723C00	723	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4168 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Bilko_Pinnacle - ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4168MH0003020011500725C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4169MH0001700001500760R00	760	MOTOR COUNT:		14670	RANGE (cm):	3.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4169MH0001700001500761S00	761	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00302	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Apr-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4168	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4169	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4168MH0003020021500726C00	726	14550	4.25	-0.1	0.1	21.9	0.3	255	1
4168MH0003020021500727C00	727	14580	4.15	-0.1	0.1	21.5	0.3	223	2
4168MH0003020021500728C00	728	14610	4.05	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	191	3
4168MH0003020021500729C00	729	14640	3.96	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	159	4
4168MH0003020021500730C00	730	14670	3.87	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	127	5
4168MH0003020021500731C00	731	14700	3.78	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	95	6
4168MH0003020021500732C00	732	14730	3.70	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	63	7
4168MH0003020021500733C00	733	14760	3.62	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4168 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Pipsqueak_Spire - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4168MH0002240011500737C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4169MH0001700001500758R00	758	MOTOR COUNT:		13998	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4169MH0001700001500759S00	759	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Apr-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4168	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4169	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4168MH0002240021500738C00	738	13830	8.11	-0.2	0.2	35.4	0.7	255	1
4168MH0002240021500739C00	739	13872	7.77	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	223	2
4168MH0002240021500740C00	740	13914	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	191	3
4168MH0002240021500741C00	741	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	159	4
4168MH0002240021500742C00	742	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4168MH0002240021500743C00	743	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
4168MH0002240021500744C00	744	14082	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
4168MH0002240021500745C00	745	14124	6.10	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4168 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Pipsqueak_Spire - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4168MH0002240011500747C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4169MH0001700001500756R00	756	MOTOR COUNT:		14003	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4169MH0001700001500757S00	757	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Apr-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4168	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4169	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4168MH0002240021500748C00	748	13835	8.07	-0.2	0.2	35.3	0.7	255	1
4168MH0002240021500749C00	749	13877	7.73	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	223	2
4168MH0002240021500750C00	750	13919	7.41	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	191	3
4168MH0002240021500751C00	751	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
4168MH0002240021500752C00	752	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4168MH0002240021500753C00	753	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	95	6
4168MH0002240021500754C00	754	14087	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
4168MH0002240021500755C00	755	14129	6.07	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4173 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Franklin_Lakes - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4173MH0003360011500775C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4174MH0001700001500868R00	868	MOTOR COUNT:		14023	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4174MH0001700001500869S00	869	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4173	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4174		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4173MH0003360021500776C00	776	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	255	1
4173MH0003360021500777C00	777	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	223	2
4173MH0003360021500778C00	778	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	191	3
4173MH0003360021500779C00	779	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	159	4
4173MH0003360021500780C00	780	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5
4173MH0003360021500781C00	781	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	95	6
4173MH0003360021500782C00	782	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
4173MH0003360021500783C00	783	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4173 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Franklin_Lakes - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4173MH0003360011500785C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4174MH0001700001500866R00	866	MOTOR COUNT:		14019	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4174MH0001700001500867S00	867	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4173	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4174		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4173MH0003360021500786C00	786	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
4173MH0003360021500787C00	787	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	223	2
4173MH0003360021500788C00	788	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	191	3
4173MH0003360021500789C00	789	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	159	4
4173MH0003360021500790C00	790	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
4173MH0003360021500791C00	791	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
4173MH0003360021500792C00	792	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
4173MH0003360021500793C00	793	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4173 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Franklin_Lakes - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4173MH0008640011500795C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4174MH0001700001500864R00	864	MOTOR COUNT:		15191	RANGE (cm):	2.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4174MH0001700001500865S00	865	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00864	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4173	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4174	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4173MH0008640021500796C00	796	15071	2.89	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	255	1
4173MH0008640021500797C00	797	15101	2.83	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	223	2
4173MH0008640021500798C00	798	15131	2.77	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	191	3
4173MH0008640021500799C00	799	15161	2.72	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	159	4
4173MH0008640021500800C00	800	15191	2.66	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	127	5
4173MH0008640021500801C00	801	15221	2.61	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	95	6
4173MH0008640021500802C00	802	15251	2.56	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	63	7
4173MH0008640021500803C00	803	15281	2.51	0.0	0.1	15.7	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4173 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Emerald_Peak - stereo-2 - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4173MH0008760011500805C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4174MH0001700001500862R00	862	MOTOR COUNT:		13005	RANGE (cm):	27.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4174MH0001700001500863S00	863	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00876	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4173	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4174	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4173MH0008760021500806C00	806	12957	30.69	-2.3	2.7	114.9	8.9	255	1
4173MH0008760021500807C00	807	12969	29.77	-2.2	2.6	111.7	8.4	223	2
4173MH0008760021500808C00	808	12981	28.89	-2.1	2.4	108.6	7.9	191	3
4173MH0008760021500809C00	809	12993	28.06	-2.0	2.3	105.7	7.4	159	4
4173MH0008760021500810C00	810	13005	27.27	-1.9	2.1	102.9	7.0	127	5
4173MH0008760021500811C00	811	13017	26.52	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	95	6
4173MH0008760021500812C00	812	13029	25.81	-1.7	1.9	97.8	6.3	63	7
4173MH0008760021500813C00	813	13041	25.13	-1.6	1.8	95.4	6.0	31	8

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4173 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Emerald_Peak - stereo-3 - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4173MH0008760011500815C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4174MH0001700001500860R00	860	MOTOR COUNT:		13010	RANGE (cm):	27.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4174MH0001700001500861S00	861	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00876	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-May-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4173	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4174	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4173MH0008760021500816C00	816	12962	30.30	-2.3	2.7	113.6	8.7	255	1
4173MH0008760021500817C00	817	12974	29.40	-2.2	2.5	110.4	8.2	223	2
4173MH0008760021500818C00	818	12986	28.54	-2.0	2.3	107.4	7.7	191	3
4173MH0008760021500819C00	819	12998	27.73	-1.9	2.2	104.5	7.3	159	4
4173MH0008760021500820C00	820	13010	26.95	-1.8	2.1	101.8	6.9	127	5
4173MH0008760021500821C00	821	13022	26.22	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	95	6
4173MH0008760021500822C00	822	13034	25.52	-1.7	1.8	96.7	6.1	63	7
4173MH0008760021500823C00	823	13046	24.86	-1.6	1.7	94.4	5.8	31	8

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4173 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Emerald_Peak - stereo-1 - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4173MH0008760011500825C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4174MH0001700001500858R00	858	MOTOR COUNT:		13008	RANGE (cm):	27.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4174MH0001700001500859S00	859	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00876	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-May-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4173	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4174	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4173MH0008760021500826C00	826	12960	30.46	-2.3	2.7	114.1	8.8	255	1
4173MH0008760021500827C00	827	12972	29.54	-2.2	2.5	110.9	8.3	223	2
4173MH0008760021500828C00	828	12984	28.68	-2.1	2.4	107.8	7.8	191	3
4173MH0008760021500829C00	829	12996	27.86	-2.0	2.2	105.0	7.3	159	4
4173MH0008760021500830C00	830	13008	27.08	-1.8	2.1	102.2	6.9	127	5
4173MH0008760021500831C00	831	13020	26.34	-1.8	2.0	99.6	6.6	95	6
4173MH0008760021500832C00	832	13032	25.64	-1.7	1.9	97.1	6.2	63	7
4173MH0008760021500833C00	833	13044	24.97	-1.6	1.8	94.8	5.9	31	8

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4173 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Emerald_Peak - stereo-1 - ~55 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4173MH0001730011500835C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4174MH0001700001500856R00	856	MOTOR COUNT:		13945	RANGE (cm):	7.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4174MH0001700001500857S00	857	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-May-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4173	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4174	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4173MH0001730021500836C00	836	13825	8.15	-0.2	0.2	35.6	0.7	255	1
4173MH0001730021500837C00	837	13855	7.90	-0.2	0.2	34.7	0.7	223	2
4173MH0001730021500838C00	838	13885	7.66	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	191	3
4173MH0001730021500839C00	839	13915	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	159	4
4173MH0001730021500840C00	840	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	127	5
4173MH0001730021500841C00	841	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	95	6
4173MH0001730021500842C00	842	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	63	7
4173MH0001730021500843C00	843	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 03_July_2024

SOL 4173 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Emerald_Peak - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4173MH0001730011500845C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4174MH0001700001500854R00	854	MOTOR COUNT:		13961	RANGE (cm):	7.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4174MH0001700001500855S00	855	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-May-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4173	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4174	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4173MH0001730021500846C00	846	13841	8.02	-0.2	0.2	35.1	0.7	255	1
4173MH0001730021500847C00	847	13871	7.77	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	223	2
4173MH0001730021500848C00	848	13901	7.54	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	191	3
4173MH0001730021500849C00	849	13931	7.32	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	159	4
4173MH0001730021500850C00	850	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	127	5
4173MH0001730021500851C00	851	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	95	6
4173MH0001730021500852C00	852	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	63	7
4173MH0001730021500853C00	853	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 08_July_2024

SOL 4175 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lookout_Peak - ~25 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4175MH0008650011500871C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4176MH0004490001501000R00		1000		MOTOR COUNT:		13012		RANGE (cm): 26.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4176MH0004490001501001S00		1001		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00865		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		5-May-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4175		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4176	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4175MH0008650021500872C00	872	12916	34.31	-2.9	3.5	127.7	11.2	255	1		
4175MH0008650021500873C00	873	12940	32.10	-2.6	3.0	119.9	9.8	223	2		
4175MH0008650021500874C00	874	12964	30.15	-2.3	2.6	113.0	8.6	191	3		
4175MH0008650021500875C00	875	12988	28.40	-2.0	2.3	106.9	7.6	159	4		
4175MH0008650021500876C00	876	13012	26.83	-1.8	2.1	101.3	6.8	127	5		
4175MH0008650021500877C00	877	13036	25.41	-1.6	1.8	96.3	6.1	95	6		
4175MH0008650021500878C00	878	13060	24.12	-1.5	1.6	91.8	5.5	63	7		
4175MH0008650021500879C00	879	13084	22.95	-1.4	1.5	87.7	5.0	31	8		

UPDATED: 08_July_2024

SOL 4175 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lookout_Peak - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4175MH0003060011500881C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4176MH0004490001500998R00		998		MOTOR COUNT:		14161		RANGE (cm): 5.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4176MH0004490001500999S00		999		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00306		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		5-May-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4175		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4176	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4175MH0003060021500882C00	882	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1		
4175MH0003060021500883C00	883	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	223	2		
4175MH0003060021500884C00	884	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	191	3		
4175MH0003060021500885C00	885	14107	6.19	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	159	4		
4175MH0003060021500886C00	886	14161	5.89	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	127	5		
4175MH0003060021500887C00	887	14215	5.62	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	95	6		
4175MH0003060021500888C00	888	14269	5.36	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	63	7		
4175MH0003060021500889C00	889	14323	5.12	-0.1	0.1	24.9	0.4	31	8		

UPDATED: 08_July_2024

SOL 4175 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lookout_Peak - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4175MH0003060011500891C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4176MH0004490001500996R00	996	MOTOR COUNT:		14156	RANGE (cm):	5.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4176MH0004490001500997S00	997	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00306	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4175	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4176	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4175MH0003060021500892C00	892	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
4175MH0003060021500893C00	893	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	223	2
4175MH0003060021500894C00	894	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	191	3
4175MH0003060021500895C00	895	14102	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	159	4
4175MH0003060021500896C00	896	14156	5.92	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.5	127	5
4175MH0003060021500897C00	897	14210	5.64	-0.1	0.1	26.8	0.4	95	6
4175MH0003060021500898C00	898	14264	5.38	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	63	7
4175MH0003060021500899C00	899	14318	5.14	-0.1	0.1	25.0	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 08_July_2024

SOL 4175 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Wilma_Lake - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4175MH0008760011500901C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4176MH0004490001500994R00	994	MOTOR COUNT:		13014	RANGE (cm):	26.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4176MH0004490001500995S00	995	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00876	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4175	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4176	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4175MH0008760021500902C00	902	12966	29.99	-2.2	2.6	112.5	8.5	255	1
4175MH0008760021500903C00	903	12978	29.10	-2.1	2.4	109.4	8.0	223	2
4175MH0008760021500904C00	904	12990	28.26	-2.0	2.3	106.4	7.5	191	3
4175MH0008760021500905C00	905	13002	27.46	-1.9	2.2	103.6	7.1	159	4
4175MH0008760021500906C00	906	13014	26.71	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	127	5
4175MH0008760021500907C00	907	13026	25.99	-1.7	1.9	98.4	6.4	95	6
4175MH0008760021500908C00	908	13038	25.30	-1.6	1.8	96.0	6.0	63	7
4175MH0008760021500909C00	909	13050	24.64	-1.5	1.7	93.7	5.7	31	8

UPDATED: 08_July_2024

SOL 4175 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Wilma_Lake - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4175MH0001520011500911C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4176MH0004490001500992R00	992	MOTOR COUNT:		14026	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4176MH0004490001500993S00	993	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4175	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4176	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4175MH0001520021500912C00	912	13834	8.08	-0.2	0.2	35.3	0.7	255	1
4175MH0001520021500913C00	913	13882	7.69	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	223	2
4175MH0001520021500914C00	914	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	191	3
4175MH0001520021500915C00	915	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
4175MH0001520021500916C00	916	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
4175MH0001520021500917C00	917	14074	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	95	6
4175MH0001520021500918C00	918	14122	6.11	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	63	7
4175MH0001520021500919C00	919	14170	5.85	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 08_July_2024

SOL 4175 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Wilma_Lake - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4175MH0001520011500921C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4176MH0004490001500990R00	990	MOTOR COUNT:		14029	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4176MH0004490001500991S00	991	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4175	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4176	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4175MH0001520021500922C00	922	13837	8.05	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	255	1
4175MH0001520021500923C00	923	13885	7.66	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	223	2
4175MH0001520021500924C00	924	13933	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	191	3
4175MH0001520021500925C00	925	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4175MH0001520021500926C00	926	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
4175MH0001520021500927C00	927	14077	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	95	6
4175MH0001520021500928C00	928	14125	6.09	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	63	7
4175MH0001520021500929C00	929	14173	5.83	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 08_July_2024

SOL 4175 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Liberty_Cap - stereo-2 - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4175MH0003590011500931C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4176MH0004490001500988R00	988	MOTOR COUNT:		13010	RANGE (cm):	27.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4176MH0004490001500989S00	989	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-May-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4175	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4176		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4175MH0003590021500932C00	932	12938	32.28	-2.6	3.0	120.5	9.9	255	1
4175MH0003590021500933C00	933	12956	30.77	-2.4	2.7	115.2	9.0	223	2
4175MH0003590021500934C00	934	12974	29.40	-2.2	2.5	110.4	8.2	191	3
4175MH0003590021500935C00	935	12992	28.13	-2.0	2.3	105.9	7.5	159	4
4175MH0003590021500936C00	936	13010	26.95	-1.8	2.1	101.8	6.9	127	5
4175MH0003590021500937C00	937	13028	25.87	-1.7	1.9	98.0	6.3	95	6
4175MH0003590021500938C00	938	13046	24.86	-1.6	1.7	94.4	5.8	63	7
4175MH0003590021500939C00	939	13064	23.92	-1.5	1.6	91.1	5.4	31	8

UPDATED: 08_July_2024

SOL 4175 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Liberty_Cap - stereo-3 - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4175MH0003590011500941C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4176MH0004490001500986R00	986	MOTOR COUNT:		13012	RANGE (cm):	26.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4176MH0004490001500987S00	987	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-May-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4175	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4176		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4175MH0003590021500942C00	942	12940	32.10	-2.6	3.0	119.9	9.8	255	1
4175MH0003590021500943C00	943	12958	30.61	-2.3	2.7	114.7	8.9	223	2
4175MH0003590021500944C00	944	12976	29.25	-2.1	2.5	109.9	8.1	191	3
4175MH0003590021500945C00	945	12994	27.99	-2.0	2.2	105.4	7.4	159	4
4175MH0003590021500946C00	946	13012	26.83	-1.8	2.1	101.3	6.8	127	5
4175MH0003590021500947C00	947	13030	25.75	-1.7	1.9	97.6	6.3	95	6
4175MH0003590021500948C00	948	13048	24.75	-1.6	1.7	94.0	5.8	63	7
4175MH0003590021500949C00	949	13066	23.82	-1.4	1.6	90.7	5.3	31	8

UPDATED: 08_July_2024

SOL 4175 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Liberty_Cap - stereo-1 - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4175MH0003590011500951C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4176MH0004490001500984R00	984	MOTOR COUNT:		13013	RANGE (cm):	26.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4176MH0004490001500985S00	985	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4175	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4176	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4175MH0003590021500952C00	952	12941	32.02	-2.5	3.0	119.6	9.7	255	1
4175MH0003590021500953C00	953	12959	30.54	-2.3	2.7	114.4	8.8	223	2
4175MH0003590021500954C00	954	12977	29.18	-2.1	2.4	109.6	8.0	191	3
4175MH0003590021500955C00	955	12995	27.92	-2.0	2.2	105.2	7.4	159	4
4175MH0003590021500956C00	956	13013	26.77	-1.8	2.0	101.1	6.8	127	5
4175MH0003590021500957C00	957	13031	25.70	-1.7	1.9	97.3	6.2	95	6
4175MH0003590021500958C00	958	13049	24.70	-1.6	1.7	93.8	5.8	63	7
4175MH0003590021500959C00	959	13067	23.77	-1.4	1.6	90.6	5.3	31	8

UPDATED: 08_July_2024

SOL 4175 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Liberty_Cap - stereo-1 - ~55 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4175MH0002240011500961C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4176MH0004490001500982R00	982	MOTOR COUNT:		13940	RANGE (cm):	7.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4176MH0004490001500983S00	983	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4175	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4176	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4175MH0002240021500962C00	962	13772	8.62	-0.2	0.2	37.3	0.8	255	1
4175MH0002240021500963C00	963	13814	8.25	-0.2	0.2	35.9	0.8	223	2
4175MH0002240021500964C00	964	13856	7.89	-0.2	0.2	34.7	0.7	191	3
4175MH0002240021500965C00	965	13898	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	159	4
4175MH0002240021500966C00	966	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	127	5
4175MH0002240021500967C00	967	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	95	6
4175MH0002240021500968C00	968	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4175MH0002240021500969C00	969	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 08_July_2024

SOL 4175 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Liberty_Cap - stereo-2 - ~55 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4175MH0002240011500971C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4176MH0004490001500980R00	980	MOTOR COUNT:		13933	RANGE (cm):	7.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4176MH0004490001500981S00	981	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-May-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4175	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4176	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4175MH0002240021500972C00	972	13765	8.69	-0.2	0.2	37.5	0.8	255	1
4175MH0002240021500973C00	973	13807	8.31	-0.2	0.2	36.1	0.8	223	2
4175MH0002240021500974C00	974	13849	7.95	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	191	3
4175MH0002240021500975C00	975	13891	7.62	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	159	4
4175MH0002240021500976C00	976	13933	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	127	5
4175MH0002240021500977C00	977	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	95	6
4175MH0002240021500978C00	978	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	63	7
4175MH0002240021500979C00	979	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 05_July_2024

SOL 4178 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target EL_Portal - mosaic postion 1 of 4 - ~28 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4178MH0008650011501003C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4178MH0001530001501048R00	1048	MOTOR COUNT:		12968	RANGE (cm):	29.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4178MH0001530001501049S00	1049	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00865	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4178	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4178	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4178MH0008650021501004C00	1004	12872	39.17	-3.7	4.6	144.8	14.6	255	1
4178MH0008650021501005C00	1005	12896	36.37	-3.2	3.9	134.9	12.6	223	2
4178MH0008650021501006C00	1006	12920	33.92	-2.8	3.4	126.3	10.9	191	3
4178MH0008650021501007C00	1007	12944	31.76	-2.5	2.9	118.7	9.6	159	4
4178MH0008650021501008C00	1008	12968	29.84	-2.2	2.6	111.9	8.4	127	5
4178MH0008650021501009C00	1009	12992	28.13	-2.0	2.3	105.9	7.5	95	6
4178MH0008650021501010C00	1010	13016	26.58	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	63	7
4178MH0008650021501011C00	1011	13040	25.19	-1.6	1.8	95.6	6.0	31	8

UPDATED: 05_July_2024

SOL 4178 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target EL_Portal - mosaic postion 2 of 4 - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4178MH0008650011501013C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4178MH0001530001501046R00	1046	MOTOR COUNT:		13012	RANGE (cm):	26.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4178MH0001530001501047S00	1047	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00865	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4178	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4178	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4178MH0008650021501014C00	1014	12916	34.31	-2.9	3.5	127.7	11.2	255	1
4178MH0008650021501015C00	1015	12940	32.10	-2.6	3.0	119.9	9.8	223	2
4178MH0008650021501016C00	1016	12964	30.15	-2.3	2.6	113.0	8.6	191	3
4178MH0008650021501017C00	1017	12988	28.40	-2.0	2.3	106.9	7.6	159	4
4178MH0008650021501018C00	1018	13012	26.83	-1.8	2.1	101.3	6.8	127	5
4178MH0008650021501019C00	1019	13036	25.41	-1.6	1.8	96.3	6.1	95	6
4178MH0008650021501020C00	1020	13060	24.12	-1.5	1.6	91.8	5.5	63	7
4178MH0008650021501021C00	1021	13084	22.95	-1.4	1.5	87.7	5.0	31	8

UPDATED: 05_July_2024

SOL 4178 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target EL_Portal - mosaic postion 3 of 4 - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4178MH0008650011501023C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4178MH0001530001501044R00	1044	MOTOR COUNT:		13032	RANGE (cm):	25.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4178MH0001530001501045S00	1045	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00865	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4178	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4178		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4178MH0008650021501024C00	1024	12936	32.45	-2.6	3.1	121.1	10.0	255	1
4178MH0008650021501025C00	1025	12960	30.46	-2.3	2.7	114.1	8.8	223	2
4178MH0008650021501026C00	1026	12984	28.68	-2.1	2.4	107.8	7.8	191	3
4178MH0008650021501027C00	1027	13008	27.08	-1.8	2.1	102.2	6.9	159	4
4178MH0008650021501028C00	1028	13032	25.64	-1.7	1.9	97.1	6.2	127	5
4178MH0008650021501029C00	1029	13056	24.33	-1.5	1.7	92.5	5.6	95	6
4178MH0008650021501030C00	1030	13080	23.14	-1.4	1.5	88.3	5.1	63	7
4178MH0008650021501031C00	1031	13104	22.04	-1.3	1.4	84.5	4.6	31	8

UPDATED: 05_July_2024

SOL 4178 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target EL_Portal - mosaic postion 4 of 4 - ~32 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4178MH0008650011501033C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4178MH0001530001501042R00	1042	MOTOR COUNT:		12923	RANGE (cm):	33.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4178MH0001530001501043S00	1043	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00865	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4178	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4178		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4178MH0008650021501034C00	1034	12827	45.69	-5.0	6.4	167.7	20.1	255	1
4178MH0008650021501035C00	1035	12851	41.98	-4.3	5.3	154.7	16.9	223	2
4178MH0008650021501036C00	1036	12875	38.80	-3.7	4.5	143.5	14.4	191	3
4178MH0008650021501037C00	1037	12899	36.05	-3.2	3.8	133.8	12.4	159	4
4178MH0008650021501038C00	1038	12923	33.64	-2.8	3.3	125.3	10.7	127	5
4178MH0008650021501039C00	1039	12947	31.51	-2.5	2.9	117.8	9.4	95	6
4178MH0008650021501040C00	1040	12971	29.62	-2.2	2.5	111.2	8.3	63	7
4178MH0008650021501041C00	1041	12995	27.92	-2.0	2.2	105.2	7.4	31	8

UPDATED: 08_July_2024

SOL 4180 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Happy_Isles - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff								
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4180MH0001680011501053C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4180MH0002270001501110R00		1110		MOTOR COUNT:		14058	RANGE (cm):	6.5
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4180MH0002270001501111S00		1111		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		10-May-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4180		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4180
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8	
				NEAR	FAR					
4180MH0001680021501054C00	1054	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	255	1	
4180MH0001680021501055C00	1055	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	223	2	
4180MH0001680021501056C00	1056	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	191	3	
4180MH0001680021501057C00	1057	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	159	4	
4180MH0001680021501058C00	1058	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	127	5	
4180MH0001680021501059C00	1059	14076	6.37	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	95	6	
4180MH0001680021501060C00	1060	14094	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7	
4180MH0001680021501061C00	1061	14112	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	31	8	

UPDATED: 08_July_2024

SOL 4180 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Happy_Isles - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff								
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4180MH0001680011501063C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4180MH0002270001501108R00		1108		MOTOR COUNT:		14056	RANGE (cm):	6.5
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4180MH0002270001501109S00		1109		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		10-May-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4180		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4180
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8	
				NEAR	FAR					
4180MH0001680021501064C00	1064	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	255	1	
4180MH0001680021501065C00	1065	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	223	2	
4180MH0001680021501066C00	1066	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	191	3	
4180MH0001680021501067C00	1067	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	159	4	
4180MH0001680021501068C00	1068	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	127	5	
4180MH0001680021501069C00	1069	14074	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	95	6	
4180MH0001680021501070C00	1070	14092	6.28	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7	
4180MH0001680021501071C00	1071	14110	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	31	8	

UPDATED: 08_July_2024

SOL 4180 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Happy_Isles - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4180MH0007430011501073C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4180MH0002270001501106R00		1106		MOTOR COUNT:		15042		RANGE (cm): 3.0	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4180MH0002270001501107S00		1107		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		10-May-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4180		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4180	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4180MH0007430021501074C00	1074	14898	3.27	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	255	1		
4180MH0007430021501075C00	1075	14934	3.18	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	223	2		
4180MH0007430021501076C00	1076	14970	3.10	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	191	3		
4180MH0007430021501077C00	1077	15006	3.03	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	159	4		
4180MH0007430021501078C00	1078	15042	2.95	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	127	5		
4180MH0007430021501079C00	1079	15078	2.88	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	95	6		
4180MH0007430021501080C00	1080	15114	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	63	7		
4180MH0007430021501081C00	1081	15150	2.74	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	31	8		

UPDATED: 08_July_2024

SOL 4180 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Laurel_Mountain - mosaic position 1 of 2 - ~24 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4180MH0006280011501083C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4180MH0002270001501104R00		1104		MOTOR COUNT:		13036		RANGE (cm): 25.4	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4180MH0002270001501105S00		1105		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00628		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		10-May-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4180		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4180	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4180MH0006280021501084C00	1084	12868	39.68	-3.8	4.7	146.6	15.0	255	1		
4180MH0006280021501085C00	1085	12910	34.90	-3.0	3.6	129.8	11.6	223	2		
4180MH0006280021501086C00	1086	12952	31.10	-2.4	2.8	116.4	9.2	191	3		
4180MH0006280021501087C00	1087	12994	27.99	-2.0	2.2	105.4	7.4	159	4		
4180MH0006280021501088C00	1088	13036	25.41	-1.6	1.8	96.3	6.1	127	5		
4180MH0006280021501089C00	1089	13078	23.23	-1.4	1.5	88.7	5.1	95	6		
4180MH0006280021501090C00	1090	13120	21.36	-1.2	1.3	82.1	4.3	63	7		
4180MH0006280021501091C00	1091	13162	19.75	-1.0	1.1	76.4	3.7	31	8		

UPDATED: 08_July_2024

SOL 4180 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Laurel_Mountain - mosaic position 2 of 2 - ~24 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4180MH0006280011501093C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4180MH0002270001501102R00		1102		MOTOR COUNT:		13032		RANGE (cm): 25.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4180MH0002270001501103S00		1103		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00628		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		10-May-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4180		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4180	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4180MH0006280021501094C00	1094	12864	40.20	-3.9	4.9	148.4	15.5	255	1		
4180MH0006280021501095C00	1095	12906	35.31	-3.1	3.7	131.2	11.9	223	2		
4180MH0006280021501096C00	1096	12948	31.42	-2.5	2.9	117.5	9.4	191	3		
4180MH0006280021501097C00	1097	12990	28.26	-2.0	2.3	106.4	7.5	159	4		
4180MH0006280021501098C00	1098	13032	25.64	-1.7	1.9	97.1	6.2	127	5		
4180MH0006280021501099C00	1099	13074	23.42	-1.4	1.5	89.4	5.2	95	6		
4180MH0006280021501100C00	1100	13116	21.53	-1.2	1.3	82.7	4.4	63	7		
4180MH0006280021501101C00	1101	13158	19.89	-1.0	1.1	76.9	3.8	31	8		

UPDATED: 18_July_2024

SOL 4182 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-1 - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4182MH0003590011501113C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4183MH0003750001501210R00	1210	MOTOR COUNT:		13021	RANGE (cm):	26.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4183MH0003750001501211S00	1211	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00375	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4182	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4183	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4182MH0003590021501114C00	1114	12949	31.34	-2.4	2.9	117.2	9.3	255	1
4182MH0003590021501115C00	1115	12967	29.92	-2.2	2.6	112.2	8.5	223	2
4182MH0003590021501116C00	1116	12985	28.61	-2.1	2.3	107.6	7.7	191	3
4182MH0003590021501117C00	1117	13003	27.40	-1.9	2.1	103.3	7.1	159	4
4182MH0003590021501118C00	1118	13021	26.28	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	127	5
4182MH0003590021501119C00	1119	13039	25.24	-1.6	1.8	95.8	6.0	95	6
4182MH0003590021501120C00	1120	13057	24.28	-1.5	1.7	92.4	5.6	63	7
4182MH0003590021501121C00	1121	13075	23.37	-1.4	1.5	89.2	5.1	31	8

UPDATED: 18_July_2024

SOL 4182 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-2 - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4182MH0003590011501123C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4183MH0003750001501208R00	1208	MOTOR COUNT:		13024	RANGE (cm):	26.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4183MH0003750001501209S00	1209	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00375	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4182	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4183	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4182MH0003590021501124C00	1124	12952	31.10	-2.4	2.8	116.4	9.2	255	1
4182MH0003590021501125C00	1125	12970	29.69	-2.2	2.5	111.4	8.3	223	2
4182MH0003590021501126C00	1126	12988	28.40	-2.0	2.3	106.9	7.6	191	3
4182MH0003590021501127C00	1127	13006	27.21	-1.9	2.1	102.7	7.0	159	4
4182MH0003590021501128C00	1128	13024	26.10	-1.7	1.9	98.8	6.4	127	5
4182MH0003590021501129C00	1129	13042	25.08	-1.6	1.8	95.2	5.9	95	6
4182MH0003590021501130C00	1130	13060	24.12	-1.5	1.6	91.8	5.5	63	7
4182MH0003590021501131C00	1131	13078	23.23	-1.4	1.5	88.7	5.1	31	8

UPDATED: 18_July_2024

SOL 4182 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4182MH0002240011501133C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4183MH0003750001501206R00	1206	MOTOR COUNT:		14113	RANGE (cm):	6.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4183MH0003750001501207S00	1207	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00375	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4182	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4183		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4182MH0002240021501134C00	1134	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
4182MH0002240021501135C00	1135	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	223	2
4182MH0002240021501136C00	1136	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	191	3
4182MH0002240021501137C00	1137	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	159	4
4182MH0002240021501138C00	1138	14113	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	127	5
4182MH0002240021501139C00	1139	14155	5.93	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	95	6
4182MH0002240021501140C00	1140	14197	5.71	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	63	7
4182MH0002240021501141C00	1141	14239	5.50	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 18_July_2024

SOL 4182 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4182MH0002240011501143C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4183MH0003750001501204R00	1204	MOTOR COUNT:		14116	RANGE (cm):	6.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4183MH0003750001501205S00	1205	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00375	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4182	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4183		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4182MH0002240021501144C00	1144	13948	7.20	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1
4182MH0002240021501145C00	1145	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
4182MH0002240021501146C00	1146	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	191	3
4182MH0002240021501147C00	1147	14074	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	159	4
4182MH0002240021501148C00	1148	14116	6.14	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	127	5
4182MH0002240021501149C00	1149	14158	5.91	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	95	6
4182MH0002240021501150C00	1150	14200	5.69	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	63	7
4182MH0002240021501151C00	1151	14242	5.49	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4182 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Royal_Arches - ~4 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4182MH0003360011501155C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4183MH0003750001501202R00	1202	MOTOR COUNT:		14159	RANGE (cm):	5.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4183MH0003750001501203S00	1203	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00375	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4182	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4183		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4182MH0003360021501156C00	1156	14111	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	255	1
4182MH0003360021501157C00	1157	14123	6.10	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	223	2
4182MH0003360021501158C00	1158	14135	6.03	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	191	3
4182MH0003360021501159C00	1159	14147	5.97	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	159	4
4182MH0003360021501160C00	1160	14159	5.91	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	127	5
4182MH0003360021501161C00	1161	14171	5.84	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	95	6
4182MH0003360021501162C00	1162	14183	5.78	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	63	7
4182MH0003360021501163C00	1163	14195	5.72	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 18_July_2024

SOL 4182 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Boyden_Cave - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4182MH0003360011501167C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4183MH0003750001501200R00	1200	MOTOR COUNT:		13992	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4183MH0003750001501201S00	1201	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00375	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4182	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4183		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4182MH0003360021501168C00	1168	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
4182MH0003360021501169C00	1169	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
4182MH0003360021501170C00	1170	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
4182MH0003360021501171C00	1171	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
4182MH0003360021501172C00	1172	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4182MH0003360021501173C00	1173	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
4182MH0003360021501174C00	1174	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	63	7
4182MH0003360021501175C00	1175	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 18_July_2024

SOL 4182 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Boyden_Cave - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4182MH0003360011501177C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4183MH0003750001501198R00	1198	MOTOR COUNT:		13993	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4183MH0003750001501199S00	1199	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00375	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4182	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4183		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4182MH0003360021501178C00	1178	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
4182MH0003360021501179C00	1179	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
4182MH0003360021501180C00	1180	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
4182MH0003360021501181C00	1181	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4182MH0003360021501182C00	1182	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4182MH0003360021501183C00	1183	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
4182MH0003360021501184C00	1184	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	63	7
4182MH0003360021501185C00	1185	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 18_July_2024

SOL 4182 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Boyden_Cave - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4182MH0008640011501187C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4183MH0003750001501196R00	1196	MOTOR COUNT:		15052	RANGE (cm):	2.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4183MH0003750001501197S00	1197	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00864	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00375	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4182	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4183		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4182MH0008640021501188C00	1188	14932	3.19	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	255	1
4182MH0008640021501189C00	1189	14962	3.12	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	223	2
4182MH0008640021501190C00	1190	14992	3.06	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	191	3
4182MH0008640021501191C00	1191	15022	2.99	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	159	4
4182MH0008640021501192C00	1192	15052	2.93	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	127	5
4182MH0008640021501193C00	1193	15082	2.87	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	95	6
4182MH0008640021501194C00	1194	15112	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	63	7
4182MH0008640021501195C00	1195	15142	2.75	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	31	8

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SOL 4184 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tenaya_Lake - stereo-1 - ~55 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4184MH0003060011501215C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4185MH0001530001501262R00	1262	MOTOR COUNT:		13926	RANGE (cm):	7.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4185MH0001530001501263S00	1263	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00306	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	14-May-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4184	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4185		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4184MH0003060021501216C00	1216	13710	9.23	-0.3	0.3	39.4	0.9	255	1
4184MH0003060021501217C00	1217	13764	8.70	-0.2	0.2	37.5	0.8	223	2
4184MH0003060021501218C00	1218	13818	8.21	-0.2	0.2	35.8	0.8	191	3
4184MH0003060021501219C00	1219	13872	7.77	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	159	4
4184MH0003060021501220C00	1220	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	127	5
4184MH0003060021501221C00	1221	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	95	6
4184MH0003060021501222C00	1222	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
4184MH0003060021501223C00	1223	14088	6.30	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 09_July_2024

SOL 4184 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tenaya_Lake - stereo-2 - ~55 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4184MH0003060011501225C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4185MH0001530001501260R00	1260	MOTOR COUNT:		13927	RANGE (cm):	7.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4185MH0001530001501261S00	1261	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00306	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	14-May-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4184	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4185		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4184MH0003060021501226C00	1226	13711	9.22	-0.3	0.3	39.3	0.9	255	1
4184MH0003060021501227C00	1227	13765	8.69	-0.2	0.2	37.5	0.8	223	2
4184MH0003060021501228C00	1228	13819	8.20	-0.2	0.2	35.8	0.7	191	3
4184MH0003060021501229C00	1229	13873	7.76	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	159	4
4184MH0003060021501230C00	1230	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	127	5
4184MH0003060021501231C00	1231	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	95	6
4184MH0003060021501232C00	1232	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
4184MH0003060021501233C00	1233	14089	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4184 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Buck_Lake - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4184MH0002990011501237C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4185MH0001530001501258R00	1258	MOTOR COUNT:		14007	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4185MH0001530001501259S00	1259	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	14-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4184	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4185	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4184MH0002990021501238C00	1238	13863	7.84	-0.2	0.2	34.5	0.7	255	1
4184MH0002990021501239C00	1239	13899	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	223	2
4184MH0002990021501240C00	1240	13935	7.29	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	191	3
4184MH0002990021501241C00	1241	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
4184MH0002990021501242C00	1242	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
4184MH0002990021501243C00	1243	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	95	6
4184MH0002990021501244C00	1244	14079	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
4184MH0002990021501245C00	1245	14115	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4184 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Buck_Lake - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4184MH0002990011501247C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4185MH0001530001501256R00	1256	MOTOR COUNT:		13994	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4185MH0001530001501257S00	1257	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	14-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4184	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4185	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4184MH0002990021501248C00	1248	13850	7.94	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	255	1
4184MH0002990021501249C00	1249	13886	7.66	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	223	2
4184MH0002990021501250C00	1250	13922	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	191	3
4184MH0002990021501251C00	1251	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	159	4
4184MH0002990021501252C00	1252	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
4184MH0002990021501253C00	1253	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
4184MH0002990021501254C00	1254	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
4184MH0002990021501255C00	1255	14102	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 09_July_2024

SOL 4186 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Parker_Lakes - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4186MH0001730011501267C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4187MH0002270001501334R00	1334	MOTOR COUNT:		13999	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4187MH0002270001501335S00	1335	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4186	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4187	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4186MH0001730021501268C00	1268	13879	7.71	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	255	1
4186MH0001730021501269C00	1269	13909	7.48	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	223	2
4186MH0001730021501270C00	1270	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	191	3
4186MH0001730021501271C00	1271	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
4186MH0001730021501272C00	1272	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4186MH0001730021501273C00	1273	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
4186MH0001730021501274C00	1274	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
4186MH0001730021501275C00	1275	14089	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 09_July_2024

SOL 4186 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Parker_Lakes - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4186MH0001730011501277C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4187MH0002270001501332R00	1332	MOTOR COUNT:		14009	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4187MH0002270001501333S00	1333	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4186	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4187	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4186MH0001730021501278C00	1278	13889	7.63	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	255	1
4186MH0001730021501279C00	1279	13919	7.41	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	223	2
4186MH0001730021501280C00	1280	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
4186MH0001730021501281C00	1281	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
4186MH0001730021501282C00	1282	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
4186MH0001730021501283C00	1283	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
4186MH0001730021501284C00	1284	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
4186MH0001730021501285C00	1285	14099	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4186 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tuolumne_Meadows - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4186MH0003360011501297C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4187MH0002270001501330R00	1330	MOTOR COUNT:		14010	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4187MH0002270001501331S00	1331	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4186	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4187	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4186MH0003360021501298C00	1298	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	255	1
4186MH0003360021501299C00	1299	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	223	2
4186MH0003360021501300C00	1300	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3
4186MH0003360021501301C00	1301	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
4186MH0003360021501302C00	1302	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
4186MH0003360021501303C00	1303	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
4186MH0003360021501304C00	1304	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
4186MH0003360021501305C00	1305	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4186 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tuolumne_Meadows - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4186MH0003360011501307C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4187MH0002270001501328R00	1328	MOTOR COUNT:		14015	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4187MH0002270001501329S00	1329	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4186	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4187	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4186MH0003360021501308C00	1308	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	255	1
4186MH0003360021501309C00	1309	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	223	2
4186MH0003360021501310C00	1310	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
4186MH0003360021501311C00	1311	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
4186MH0003360021501312C00	1312	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
4186MH0003360021501313C00	1313	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
4186MH0003360021501314C00	1314	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
4186MH0003360021501315C00	1315	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 09_July_2024

SOL 4186 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tuolumne_Meadows – after DRT – ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4186MH0008640011501317C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4187MH0002270001501326R00	1326	MOTOR COUNT:		15134	RANGE (cm):		2.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4187MH0002270001501327S00	1327	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00864	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-May-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4186	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4187	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4186MH0008640021501318C00	1318	15014	3.01	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	255	1
4186MH0008640021501319C00	1319	15044	2.95	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	223	2
4186MH0008640021501320C00	1320	15074	2.89	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	191	3
4186MH0008640021501321C00	1321	15104	2.83	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	159	4
4186MH0008640021501322C00	1322	15134	2.77	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	127	5
4186MH0008640021501323C00	1323	15164	2.71	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	95	6
4186MH0008640021501324C00	1324	15194	2.66	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	63	7
4186MH0008640021501325C00	1325	15224	2.60	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 15_July_2024

SOL 4191 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Pine_Creek - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4191MH0001680011501339C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4191MH0001930001501372R00	1372	MOTOR COUNT:		14044	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4191MH0001930001501373S00	1373	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4191	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4191	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4191MH0001680021501340C00	1340	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
4191MH0001680021501341C00	1341	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
4191MH0001680021501342C00	1342	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	191	3
4191MH0001680021501343C00	1343	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	159	4
4191MH0001680021501344C00	1344	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	127	5
4191MH0001680021501345C00	1345	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	95	6
4191MH0001680021501346C00	1346	14080	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
4191MH0001680021501347C00	1347	14098	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 15_July_2024

SOL 4191 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Pine_Creek - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4191MH0001680011501349C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4191MH0001930001501370R00	1370	MOTOR COUNT:		14047	RANGE (cm):	6.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4191MH0001930001501371S00	1371	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4191	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4191	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4191MH0001680021501350C00	1350	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	255	1
4191MH0001680021501351C00	1351	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
4191MH0001680021501352C00	1352	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	191	3
4191MH0001680021501353C00	1353	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	159	4
4191MH0001680021501354C00	1354	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	127	5
4191MH0001680021501355C00	1355	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	95	6
4191MH0001680021501356C00	1356	14083	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
4191MH0001680021501357C00	1357	14101	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 15_July_2024

SOL 4191 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Pine_Creek – after DRT – ~5 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4191MH0007430011501359C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4191MH0001930001501368R00	1368	MOTOR COUNT:		15243	RANGE (cm):		2.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4191MH0001930001501369S00	1369	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-May-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4191	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4191	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4191MH0007430021501360C00	1360	15099	2.84	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	255	1
4191MH0007430021501361C00	1361	15135	2.77	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	223	2
4191MH0007430021501362C00	1362	15171	2.70	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	191	3
4191MH0007430021501363C00	1363	15207	2.63	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	159	4
4191MH0007430021501364C00	1364	15243	2.57	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	127	5
4191MH0007430021501365C00	1365	15279	2.51	0.0	0.1	15.7	0.2	95	6
4191MH0007430021501366C00	1366	15315	2.45	0.0	0.1	15.5	0.2	63	7
4191MH0007430021501367C00	1367	15351	2.39	0.0	0.1	15.3	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 11_July_2024

SOL 4193 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lake_Catherine - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4193MH0008650011501375C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4193MH0001930001501408R00	1408	MOTOR COUNT:		13031	RANGE (cm):		25.7	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4193MH0001930001501409S00	1409	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00865		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-May-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4193	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4193	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4193MH0008650021501376C00	1376	12935	32.54	-2.6	3.1	121.4	10.0	255	1
4193MH0008650021501377C00	1377	12959	30.54	-2.3	2.7	114.4	8.8	223	2
4193MH0008650021501378C00	1378	12983	28.75	-2.1	2.4	108.1	7.8	191	3
4193MH0008650021501379C00	1379	13007	27.14	-1.9	2.1	102.4	7.0	159	4
4193MH0008650021501380C00	1380	13031	25.70	-1.7	1.9	97.3	6.2	127	5
4193MH0008650021501381C00	1381	13055	24.38	-1.5	1.7	92.7	5.6	95	6
4193MH0008650021501382C00	1382	13079	23.18	-1.4	1.5	88.5	5.1	63	7
4193MH0008650021501383C00	1383	13103	22.09	-1.3	1.4	84.6	4.6	31	8

UPDATED: 11_July_2024

SOL 4193 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lake_Catherine - stereo-1 - ~14 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4193MH0008770011501385C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4193MH0001930001501406R00	1406	MOTOR COUNT:		13305	RANGE (cm):		15.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4193MH0001930001501407S00	1407	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00877		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-May-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4193	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4193	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4193MH0008770021501386C00	1386	13185	18.95	-0.9	1.0	73.6	3.4	255	1
4193MH0008770021501387C00	1387	13215	17.99	-0.9	0.9	70.2	3.1	223	2
4193MH0008770021501388C00	1388	13245	17.11	-0.8	0.8	67.1	2.8	191	3
4193MH0008770021501389C00	1389	13275	16.31	-0.7	0.7	64.3	2.5	159	4
4193MH0008770021501390C00	1390	13305	15.56	-0.7	0.7	61.7	2.3	127	5
4193MH0008770021501391C00	1391	13335	14.87	-0.6	0.6	59.3	2.1	95	6
4193MH0008770021501392C00	1392	13365	14.24	-0.6	0.6	57.0	2.0	63	7
4193MH0008770021501393C00	1393	13395	13.64	-0.5	0.5	54.9	1.8	31	8

UPDATED: 11_July_2024

SOL 4193 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lake_Catherine - stereo-2 - ~14 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4193MH0008770011501395C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4193MH0001930001501404R00	1404	MOTOR COUNT:		13309	RANGE (cm):		15.5	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4193MH0001930001501405S00	1405	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00877		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-May-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4193		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4193
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4193MH0008770021501396C00	1396	13189	18.82	-0.9	1.0	73.1	3.4	255	1
4193MH0008770021501397C00	1397	13219	17.87	-0.8	0.9	69.8	3.0	223	2
4193MH0008770021501398C00	1398	13249	17.00	-0.8	0.8	66.8	2.8	191	3
4193MH0008770021501399C00	1399	13279	16.20	-0.7	0.7	63.9	2.5	159	4
4193MH0008770021501400C00	1400	13309	15.47	-0.6	0.7	61.4	2.3	127	5
4193MH0008770021501401C00	1401	13339	14.79	-0.6	0.6	59.0	2.1	95	6
4193MH0008770021501402C00	1402	13369	14.15	-0.6	0.6	56.7	1.9	63	7
4193MH0008770021501403C00	1403	13399	13.56	-0.5	0.5	54.7	1.8	31	8

UPDATED: 25_July_2024

SOL 4196 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Second_Lake - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4196MH0003590011501411C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4197MH0004580001501552R00	1552	MOTOR COUNT:		13030	RANGE (cm):	25.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4197MH0004580001501553S00	1553	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00458	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4196	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4197		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4196MH0003590021501412C00	1412	12958	30.61	-2.3	2.7	114.7	8.9	255	1
4196MH0003590021501413C00	1413	12976	29.25	-2.1	2.5	109.9	8.1	223	2
4196MH0003590021501414C00	1414	12994	27.99	-2.0	2.2	105.4	7.4	191	3
4196MH0003590021501415C00	1415	13012	26.83	-1.8	2.1	101.3	6.8	159	4
4196MH0003590021501416C00	1416	13030	25.75	-1.7	1.9	97.6	6.3	127	5
4196MH0003590021501417C00	1417	13048	24.75	-1.6	1.7	94.0	5.8	95	6
4196MH0003590021501418C00	1418	13066	23.82	-1.4	1.6	90.7	5.3	63	7
4196MH0003590021501419C00	1419	13084	22.95	-1.4	1.5	87.7	5.0	31	8

UPDATED: 25_July_2024

SOL 4196 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Second_Lake - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4196MH0003060011501421C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4197MH0004580001501550R00	1550	MOTOR COUNT:		14205	RANGE (cm):	5.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4197MH0004580001501551S00	1551	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00306	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00458	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4196	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4197		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4196MH0003060021501422C00	1422	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	255	1
4196MH0003060021501423C00	1423	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	223	2
4196MH0003060021501424C00	1424	14097	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	191	3
4196MH0003060021501425C00	1425	14151	5.95	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	159	4
4196MH0003060021501426C00	1426	14205	5.67	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	127	5
4196MH0003060021501427C00	1427	14259	5.41	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	95	6
4196MH0003060021501428C00	1428	14313	5.16	-0.1	0.1	25.1	0.4	63	7
4196MH0003060021501429C00	1429	14367	4.93	-0.1	0.1	24.3	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 25_July_2024

SOL 4196 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Second_Lake - stereo-2 - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4196MH0003060011501431C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4197MH0004580001501548R00	1548	MOTOR COUNT:		14210	RANGE (cm):		5.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4197MH0004580001501549S00	1549	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00306		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-May-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00458		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4196	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4197	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4196MH0003060021501432C00	1432	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	255	1
4196MH0003060021501433C00	1433	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	223	2
4196MH0003060021501434C00	1434	14102	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	191	3
4196MH0003060021501435C00	1435	14156	5.92	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.5	159	4
4196MH0003060021501436C00	1436	14210	5.64	-0.1	0.1	26.8	0.4	127	5
4196MH0003060021501437C00	1437	14264	5.38	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	95	6
4196MH0003060021501438C00	1438	14318	5.14	-0.1	0.1	25.0	0.4	63	7
4196MH0003060021501439C00	1439	14372	4.91	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 25_July_2024

SOL 4196 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Josephine_Lake - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4196MH0008650011501441C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4197MH0004580001501546R00	1546	MOTOR COUNT:		13026	RANGE (cm):		26.0	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4197MH0004580001501547S00	1547	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00865		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-May-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00458		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4196	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4197	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4196MH0008650021501442C00	1442	12930	32.99	-2.7	3.2	123.0	10.3	255	1
4196MH0008650021501443C00	1443	12954	30.93	-2.4	2.8	115.8	9.1	223	2
4196MH0008650021501444C00	1444	12978	29.10	-2.1	2.4	109.4	8.0	191	3
4196MH0008650021501445C00	1445	13002	27.46	-1.9	2.2	103.6	7.1	159	4
4196MH0008650021501446C00	1446	13026	25.99	-1.7	1.9	98.4	6.4	127	5
4196MH0008650021501447C00	1447	13050	24.64	-1.5	1.7	93.7	5.7	95	6
4196MH0008650021501448C00	1448	13074	23.42	-1.4	1.5	89.4	5.2	63	7
4196MH0008650021501449C00	1449	13098	22.31	-1.3	1.4	85.4	4.7	31	8

UPDATED: 25_July_2024

SOL 4196 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Josephine_Lake - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4196MH0001820011501451C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4197MH0004580001501544R00	1544	MOTOR COUNT:		14157	RANGE (cm):	5.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4197MH0004580001501545S00	1545	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00458	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4196	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4197	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4196MH0001820021501452C00	1452	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	255	1
4196MH0001820021501453C00	1453	14085	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	223	2
4196MH0001820021501454C00	1454	14109	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	191	3
4196MH0001820021501455C00	1455	14133	6.05	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	159	4
4196MH0001820021501456C00	1456	14157	5.92	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	127	5
4196MH0001820021501457C00	1457	14181	5.79	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	95	6
4196MH0001820021501458C00	1458	14205	5.67	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	63	7
4196MH0001820021501459C00	1459	14229	5.55	-0.1	0.1	26.4	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 25_July_2024

SOL 4196 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Josephine_Lake - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4196MH0001820011501461C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4197MH0004580001501542R00	1542	MOTOR COUNT:		14165	RANGE (cm):	5.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4197MH0004580001501543S00	1543	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00458	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4196	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4197	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4196MH0001820021501462C00	1462	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	255	1
4196MH0001820021501463C00	1463	14093	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	223	2
4196MH0001820021501464C00	1464	14117	6.13	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	191	3
4196MH0001820021501465C00	1465	14141	6.00	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	159	4
4196MH0001820021501466C00	1466	14165	5.87	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	127	5
4196MH0001820021501467C00	1467	14189	5.75	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	95	6
4196MH0001820021501468C00	1468	14213	5.63	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	63	7
4196MH0001820021501469C00	1469	14237	5.51	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4196 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	mosaic from Josephine_Lake to Timber_Knob - mosaic position 1 of 5 - ~95 mm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4196MH0008590011501471C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4197MH0004580001501540R00	1540	MOTOR COUNT:		13522	RANGE (cm):	11.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4197MH0004580001501541S00	1541	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00859	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00458	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4196	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4197	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4196MH0008590021501472C00	1472	13330	14.99	-0.6	0.6	59.7	2.2	255	1
4196MH0008590021501473C00	1473	13378	13.97	-0.5	0.5	56.1	1.9	223	2
4196MH0008590021501474C00	1474	13426	13.07	-0.5	0.5	52.9	1.7	191	3
4196MH0008590021501475C00	1475	13474	12.26	-0.4	0.4	50.0	1.5	159	4
4196MH0008590021501476C00	1476	13522	11.52	-0.4	0.4	47.5	1.3	127	5
4196MH0008590021501477C00	1477	13570	10.86	-0.3	0.3	45.1	1.2	95	6
4196MH0008590021501478C00	1478	13618	10.25	-0.3	0.3	43.0	1.1	63	7
4196MH0008590021501479C00	1479	13666	9.70	-0.3	0.3	41.0	1.0	31	8

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SOL 4196 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	mosaic from Josephine_Lake to Timber_Knob - mosaic position 2 of 5 - ~9 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4196MH0008590011501481C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4197MH0004580001501538R00	1538	MOTOR COUNT:		13554	RANGE (cm):	11.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4197MH0004580001501539S00	1539	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00859	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00458	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4196	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4197	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4196MH0008590021501482C00	1482	13362	14.30	-0.6	0.6	57.2	2.0	255	1
4196MH0008590021501483C00	1483	13410	13.36	-0.5	0.5	53.9	1.7	223	2
4196MH0008590021501484C00	1484	13458	12.52	-0.4	0.4	51.0	1.6	191	3
4196MH0008590021501485C00	1485	13506	11.76	-0.4	0.4	48.3	1.4	159	4
4196MH0008590021501486C00	1486	13554	11.07	-0.4	0.4	45.9	1.2	127	5
4196MH0008590021501487C00	1487	13602	10.45	-0.3	0.3	43.7	1.1	95	6
4196MH0008590021501488C00	1488	13650	9.88	-0.3	0.3	41.7	1.0	63	7
4196MH0008590021501489C00	1489	13698	9.35	-0.3	0.3	39.8	0.9	31	8

UPDATED: 25_July_2024

SOL 4196 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	mosaic from Josephine_Lake to Timber_Knob - mosaic position 3 of 5 - ~9 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4196MH0008590011501491C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4197MH0004580001501536R00	1536	MOTOR COUNT:		13582	RANGE (cm):	10.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4197MH0004580001501537S00	1537	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00859	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00458	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4196	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4197	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4196MH0008590021501492C00	1492	13390	13.74	-0.5	0.5	55.3	1.8	255	1
4196MH0008590021501493C00	1493	13438	12.86	-0.5	0.5	52.2	1.6	223	2
4196MH0008590021501494C00	1494	13486	12.07	-0.4	0.4	49.4	1.4	191	3
4196MH0008590021501495C00	1495	13534	11.35	-0.4	0.4	46.9	1.3	159	4
4196MH0008590021501496C00	1496	13582	10.70	-0.3	0.3	44.6	1.1	127	5
4196MH0008590021501497C00	1497	13630	10.11	-0.3	0.3	42.5	1.0	95	6
4196MH0008590021501498C00	1498	13678	9.56	-0.3	0.3	40.6	1.0	63	7
4196MH0008590021501499C00	1499	13726	9.06	-0.3	0.2	38.8	0.9	31	8

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SOL 4196 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	mosaic from Josephine_Lake to Timber_Knob - mosaic position 4 of 5 - ~85 mm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4196MH0008590011501501C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4197MH0004580001501534R00	1534	MOTOR COUNT:		13600	RANGE (cm):	10.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4197MH0004580001501535S00	1535	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00859	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00458	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4196	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4197	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4196MH0008590021501502C00	1502	13408	13.40	-0.5	0.5	54.1	1.8	255	1
4196MH0008590021501503C00	1503	13456	12.55	-0.4	0.4	51.1	1.6	223	2
4196MH0008590021501504C00	1504	13504	11.79	-0.4	0.4	48.4	1.4	191	3
4196MH0008590021501505C00	1505	13552	11.10	-0.4	0.4	46.0	1.3	159	4
4196MH0008590021501506C00	1506	13600	10.47	-0.3	0.3	43.8	1.1	127	5
4196MH0008590021501507C00	1507	13648	9.90	-0.3	0.3	41.7	1.0	95	6
4196MH0008590021501508C00	1508	13696	9.37	-0.3	0.3	39.9	0.9	63	7
4196MH0008590021501509C00	1509	13744	8.89	-0.3	0.2	38.2	0.8	31	8

UPDATED: 25_July_2024

SOL 4196 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		mosaic from Josephine_Lake to Timber_Knob – mosaic position 5 of 5 – ~85 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4196MH0008590011501511C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4197MH0004580001501532R00	1532	MOTOR COUNT:		13593	RANGE (cm):	10.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4197MH0004580001501533S00	1533	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00859	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00458	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4196	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4197	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4196MH0008590021501512C00	1512	13401	13.53	-0.5	0.5	54.5	1.8	255	1
4196MH0008590021501513C00	1513	13449	12.67	-0.5	0.5	51.5	1.6	223	2
4196MH0008590021501514C00	1514	13497	11.90	-0.4	0.4	48.8	1.4	191	3
4196MH0008590021501515C00	1515	13545	11.20	-0.4	0.4	46.3	1.3	159	4
4196MH0008590021501516C00	1516	13593	10.56	-0.3	0.3	44.1	1.1	127	5
4196MH0008590021501517C00	1517	13641	9.98	-0.3	0.3	42.0	1.0	95	6
4196MH0008590021501518C00	1518	13689	9.45	-0.3	0.3	40.1	0.9	63	7
4196MH0008590021501519C00	1519	13737	8.96	-0.3	0.2	38.4	0.9	31	8

UPDATED: 25_July_2024

SOL 4196 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Timber_Knob – ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4196MH0003590011501521C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4197MH0004580001501530R00	1530	MOTOR COUNT:		13025	RANGE (cm):	26.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4197MH0004580001501531S00	1531	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00458	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4196	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4197	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4196MH0003590021501522C00	1522	12953	31.01	-2.4	2.8	116.1	9.1	255	1
4196MH0003590021501523C00	1523	12971	29.62	-2.2	2.5	111.2	8.3	223	2
4196MH0003590021501524C00	1524	12989	28.33	-2.0	2.3	106.6	7.6	191	3
4196MH0003590021501525C00	1525	13007	27.14	-1.9	2.1	102.4	7.0	159	4
4196MH0003590021501526C00	1526	13025	26.04	-1.7	1.9	98.6	6.4	127	5
4196MH0003590021501527C00	1527	13043	25.02	-1.6	1.8	95.0	5.9	95	6
4196MH0003590021501528C00	1528	13061	24.07	-1.5	1.6	91.6	5.5	63	7
4196MH0003590021501529C00	1529	13079	23.18	-1.4	1.5	88.5	5.1	31	8

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SOL 4199 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Garnet_Lake - stereo-1 - ~9 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4199MH0008780011501557C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4200MH0001630001501630R00	1630	MOTOR COUNT:		13559	RANGE (cm):	11.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4200MH0001630001501631S00	1631	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00878	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-May-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4199	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4200		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4199MH0008780021501558C00	1558	13487	12.05	-0.4	0.4	49.3	1.4	255	1
4199MH0008780021501559C00	1559	13505	11.77	-0.4	0.4	48.3	1.4	223	2
4199MH0008780021501560C00	1560	13523	11.51	-0.4	0.4	47.4	1.3	191	3
4199MH0008780021501561C00	1561	13541	11.25	-0.4	0.4	46.5	1.3	159	4
4199MH0008780021501562C00	1562	13559	11.00	-0.4	0.3	45.6	1.2	127	5
4199MH0008780021501563C00	1563	13577	10.77	-0.3	0.3	44.8	1.2	95	6
4199MH0008780021501564C00	1564	13595	10.53	-0.3	0.3	44.0	1.1	63	7
4199MH0008780021501565C00	1565	13613	10.31	-0.3	0.3	43.2	1.1	31	8

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SOL 4199 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Garnet_Lake - stereo-2 - ~9 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4199MH0008780011501567C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4200MH0001630001501628R00	1628	MOTOR COUNT:		13561	RANGE (cm):	11.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4200MH0001630001501629S00	1629	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00878	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-May-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4199	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4200		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4199MH0008780021501568C00	1568	13489	12.02	-0.4	0.4	49.2	1.4	255	1
4199MH0008780021501569C00	1569	13507	11.74	-0.4	0.4	48.2	1.4	223	2
4199MH0008780021501570C00	1570	13525	11.48	-0.4	0.4	47.3	1.3	191	3
4199MH0008780021501571C00	1571	13543	11.22	-0.4	0.4	46.4	1.3	159	4
4199MH0008780021501572C00	1572	13561	10.98	-0.4	0.3	45.5	1.2	127	5
4199MH0008780021501573C00	1573	13579	10.74	-0.3	0.3	44.7	1.2	95	6
4199MH0008780021501574C00	1574	13597	10.51	-0.3	0.3	43.9	1.1	63	7
4199MH0008780021501575C00	1575	13615	10.29	-0.3	0.3	43.1	1.1	31	8

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SOL 4199 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Rixford_Pass - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4199MH0002240011501579C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4200MH0001630001501626R00	1626	MOTOR COUNT:		13957	RANGE (cm):	7.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4200MH0001630001501627S00	1627	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4199	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4200		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4199MH0002240021501580C00	1580	13789	8.47	-0.2	0.2	36.7	0.8	255	1
4199MH0002240021501581C00	1581	13831	8.10	-0.2	0.2	35.4	0.7	223	2
4199MH0002240021501582C00	1582	13873	7.76	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	191	3
4199MH0002240021501583C00	1583	13915	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	159	4
4199MH0002240021501584C00	1584	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	127	5
4199MH0002240021501585C00	1585	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	95	6
4199MH0002240021501586C00	1586	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
4199MH0002240021501587C00	1587	14083	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4199 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Rixford_Pass - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4199MH0002240011501589C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4200MH0001630001501624R00	1624	MOTOR COUNT:		13967	RANGE (cm):	7.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4200MH0001630001501625S00	1625	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4199	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4200		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4199MH0002240021501590C00	1590	13799	8.38	-0.2	0.2	36.4	0.8	255	1
4199MH0002240021501591C00	1591	13841	8.02	-0.2	0.2	35.1	0.7	223	2
4199MH0002240021501592C00	1592	13883	7.68	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	191	3
4199MH0002240021501593C00	1593	13925	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	159	4
4199MH0002240021501594C00	1594	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	127	5
4199MH0002240021501595C00	1595	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
4199MH0002240021501596C00	1596	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
4199MH0002240021501597C00	1597	14093	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4199 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Reggae_Pole - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4199MH0002970011501601C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4200MH0001630001501622R00	1622	MOTOR COUNT:		14159	RANGE (cm):	5.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4200MH0001630001501623S00	1623	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00297	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		60	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4199	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4200	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4199MH0002970021501602C00	1602	13919	7.41	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	255	1
4199MH0002970021501603C00	1603	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	223	2
4199MH0002970021501604C00	1604	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	191	3
4199MH0002970021501605C00	1605	14099	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	159	4
4199MH0002970021501606C00	1606	14159	5.91	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	127	5
4199MH0002970021501607C00	1607	14219	5.60	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	95	6
4199MH0002970021501608C00	1608	14279	5.31	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	63	7
4199MH0002970021501609C00	1609	14339	5.05	-0.1	0.1	24.7	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4199 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Reggae_Pole - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4199MH0002970011501611C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4200MH0001630001501620R00	1620	MOTOR COUNT:		14202	RANGE (cm):	5.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4200MH0001630001501621S00	1621	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00297	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-May-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		60	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4199	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4200	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4199MH0002970021501612C00	1612	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	255	1
4199MH0002970021501613C00	1613	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	223	2
4199MH0002970021501614C00	1614	14082	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	191	3
4199MH0002970021501615C00	1615	14142	6.00	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	159	4
4199MH0002970021501616C00	1616	14202	5.68	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	127	5
4199MH0002970021501617C00	1617	14262	5.39	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	95	6
4199MH0002970021501618C00	1618	14322	5.12	-0.1	0.1	24.9	0.4	63	7
4199MH0002970021501619C00	1619	14382	4.87	-0.1	0.1	24.0	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4202 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Grey_Peak - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4202MH0003590011501633C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4202MH0001700001501732R00	1732	MOTOR COUNT:		13014	RANGE (cm):	26.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4202MH0001700001501733S00	1733	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Jun-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4202	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4202		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4202MH0003590021501634C00	1634	12942	31.93	-2.5	3.0	119.3	9.7	255	1
4202MH0003590021501635C00	1635	12960	30.46	-2.3	2.7	114.1	8.8	223	2
4202MH0003590021501636C00	1636	12978	29.10	-2.1	2.4	109.4	8.0	191	3
4202MH0003590021501637C00	1637	12996	27.86	-2.0	2.2	105.0	7.3	159	4
4202MH0003590021501638C00	1638	13014	26.71	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	127	5
4202MH0003590021501639C00	1639	13032	25.64	-1.7	1.9	97.1	6.2	95	6
4202MH0003590021501640C00	1640	13050	24.64	-1.5	1.7	93.7	5.7	63	7
4202MH0003590021501641C00	1641	13068	23.72	-1.4	1.6	90.4	5.3	31	8

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SOL 4202 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Grey_Peak - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4202MH0001820011501643C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4202MH0001700001501730R00	1730	MOTOR COUNT:		13993	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4202MH0001700001501731S00	1731	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Jun-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4202	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4202		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4202MH0001820021501644C00	1644	13897	7.57	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
4202MH0001820021501645C00	1645	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
4202MH0001820021501646C00	1646	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
4202MH0001820021501647C00	1647	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
4202MH0001820021501648C00	1648	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4202MH0001820021501649C00	1649	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4202MH0001820021501650C00	1650	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
4202MH0001820021501651C00	1651	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4202 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Grey_Peak - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4202MH0001820011501653C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4202MH0001700001501728R00	1728	MOTOR COUNT:		13990	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4202MH0001700001501729S00	1729	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Jun-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4202	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4202	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4202MH0001820021501654C00	1654	13894	7.60	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
4202MH0001820021501655C00	1655	13918	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	223	2
4202MH0001820021501656C00	1656	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
4202MH0001820021501657C00	1657	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
4202MH0001820021501658C00	1658	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4202MH0001820021501659C00	1659	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4202MH0001820021501660C00	1660	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
4202MH0001820021501661C00	1661	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4202 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Grey_Peak - APXS spot 1 - ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4202MH0003350011501663C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4202MH0001700001501726R00	1726	MOTOR COUNT:		14674	RANGE (cm):	3.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4202MH0001700001501727S00	1727	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00335	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Jun-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4202	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4202	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4202MH0003350021501664C00	1664	14458	4.58	-0.1	0.1	23.0	0.3	255	1
4202MH0003350021501665C00	1665	14512	4.38	-0.1	0.1	22.3	0.3	223	2
4202MH0003350021501666C00	1666	14566	4.20	-0.1	0.1	21.7	0.3	191	3
4202MH0003350021501667C00	1667	14620	4.02	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	159	4
4202MH0003350021501668C00	1668	14674	3.86	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	127	5
4202MH0003350021501669C00	1669	14728	3.70	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	95	6
4202MH0003350021501670C00	1670	14782	3.56	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	63	7
4202MH0003350021501671C00	1671	14836	3.42	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	31	8

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SOL 4202 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Grey_Peak - APXS spot 2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4202MH0001820011501673C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4202MH0001700001501724R00	1724	MOTOR COUNT:		13980	RANGE (cm):	7.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4202MH0001700001501725S00	1725	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Jun-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4202	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4202		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4202MH0001820021501674C00	1674	13884	7.67	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	255	1
4202MH0001820021501675C00	1675	13908	7.49	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	223	2
4202MH0001820021501676C00	1676	13932	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	191	3
4202MH0001820021501677C00	1677	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	159	4
4202MH0001820021501678C00	1678	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	127	5
4202MH0001820021501679C00	1679	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
4202MH0001820021501680C00	1680	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4202MH0001820021501681C00	1681	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4202 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Snow_Lakes - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4202MH00008790011501686C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4202MH0001700001501722R00	1722	MOTOR COUNT:		14030	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4202MH0001700001501723S00	1723	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00879	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Jun-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4202	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4202		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4202MH00008790031501688C00	1688	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	255	1
4202MH00008790031501689C00	1689	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	223	2
4202MH00008790031501690C00	1690	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3
4202MH00008790031501691C00	1691	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
4202MH00008790031501692C00	1692	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
4202MH00008790031501693C00	1693	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	95	6
4202MH00008790031501694C00	1694	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
4202MH00008790031501695C00	1695	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4202 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Snow_Lakes - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4202MH0008790011501697C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4202MH0001700001501720R00	1720	MOTOR COUNT:		14032	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4202MH0001700001501721S00	1721	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00879	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Jun-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4202	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4202	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4202MH0008790031501699C00	1699	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	255	1
4202MH0008790031501700C00	1700	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	223	2
4202MH0008790031501701C00	1701	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	191	3
4202MH0008790031501702C00	1702	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	159	4
4202MH0008790031501703C00	1703	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
4202MH0008790031501704C00	1704	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	95	6
4202MH0008790031501705C00	1705	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
4202MH0008790031501706C00	1706	14068	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4202 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Snow_Lakes - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4202MH0008350011501708C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4202MH0001700001501718R00	1718	MOTOR COUNT:		15197	RANGE (cm):	2.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4202MH0001700001501719S00	1719	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00835	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Jun-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4202	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4202	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4202MH0008350031501710C00	1710	15077	2.88	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	255	1
4202MH0008350031501711C00	1711	15107	2.82	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	223	2
4202MH0008350031501712C00	1712	15137	2.76	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	191	3
4202MH0008350031501713C00	1713	15167	2.71	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	159	4
4202MH0008350031501714C00	1714	15197	2.65	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	127	5
4202MH0008350031501715C00	1715	15227	2.60	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	95	6
4202MH0008350031501716C00	1716	15257	2.55	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	63	7
4202MH0008350031501717C00	1717	15287	2.50	0.0	0.1	15.7	0.2	31	8

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SOL 4205 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Starr_Minaret – mosaic position 1 of 6 – ~22 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4205MH0008490011501735C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4206MH0004490001501871R00		1871		MOTOR COUNT:		13075		RANGE (cm): 23.4	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4206MH0004490001501872S00		1872		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00849		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		4-Jun-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4205		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4206	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4205MH0008490021501736C00	1736	12931	32.90	-2.7	3.2	122.7	10.3	255	1		
4205MH0008490021501737C00	1737	12967	29.92	-2.2	2.6	112.2	8.5	223	2		
4205MH0008490021501738C00	1738	13003	27.40	-1.9	2.1	103.3	7.1	191	3		
4205MH0008490021501739C00	1739	13039	25.24	-1.6	1.8	95.8	6.0	159	4		
4205MH0008490021501740C00	1740	13075	23.37	-1.4	1.5	89.2	5.1	127	5		
4205MH0008490021501741C00	1741	13111	21.74	-1.2	1.3	83.4	4.5	95	6		
4205MH0008490021501742C00	1742	13147	20.30	-1.1	1.1	78.4	3.9	63	7		
4205MH0008490021501743C00	1743	13183	19.02	-0.9	1.0	73.8	3.4	31	8		

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SOL 4205 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Starr_Minaret – mosaic position 2 of 6 – ~17 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4205MH0008490011501745C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4206MH0004490001501869R00		1869		MOTOR COUNT:		13199		RANGE (cm): 18.5	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4206MH0004490001501870S00		1870		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00849		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		4-Jun-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4205		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4206	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4205MH0008490021501746C00	1746	13055	24.38	-1.5	1.7	92.7	5.6	255	1		
4205MH0008490021501747C00	1747	13091	22.62	-1.3	1.4	86.5	4.8	223	2		
4205MH0008490021501748C00	1748	13127	21.08	-1.2	1.2	81.1	4.2	191	3		
4205MH0008490021501749C00	1749	13163	19.71	-1.0	1.1	76.3	3.7	159	4		
4205MH0008490021501750C00	1750	13199	18.49	-0.9	0.9	72.0	3.2	127	5		
4205MH0008490021501751C00	1751	13235	17.40	-0.8	0.8	68.1	2.9	95	6		
4205MH0008490021501752C00	1752	13271	16.41	-0.7	0.7	64.7	2.6	63	7		
4205MH0008490021501753C00	1753	13307	15.52	-0.7	0.7	61.5	2.3	31	8		

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SOL 4205 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Starr_Minaret - mosaic position 3 of 6 - ~16 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4205MH0008490011501755C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4206MH0004490001501867R00		1867		MOTOR COUNT:		13213		RANGE (cm): 18.1	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4206MH0004490001501868S00		1868		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00849		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		4-Jun-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4205		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4206	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4205MH0008490021501756C00	1756	13069	23.67	-1.4	1.6	90.2	5.3	255	1		
4205MH0008490021501757C00	1757	13105	22.00	-1.2	1.4	84.3	4.6	223	2		
4205MH0008490021501758C00	1758	13141	20.53	-1.1	1.2	79.2	4.0	191	3		
4205MH0008490021501759C00	1759	13177	19.22	-1.0	1.0	74.6	3.5	159	4		
4205MH0008490021501760C00	1760	13213	18.05	-0.9	0.9	70.4	3.1	127	5		
4205MH0008490021501761C00	1761	13249	17.00	-0.8	0.8	66.8	2.8	95	6		
4205MH0008490021501762C00	1762	13285	16.05	-0.7	0.7	63.4	2.5	63	7		
4205MH0008490021501763C00	1763	13321	15.19	-0.6	0.6	60.4	2.2	31	8		

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SOL 4205 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Starr_Minaret - mosaic position 4 of 6 - ~18 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4205MH0008490011501765C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4206MH0004490001501865R00		1865		MOTOR COUNT:		13157		RANGE (cm): 19.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4206MH0004490001501866S00		1866		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00849		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		4-Jun-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4205		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4206	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4205MH0008490021501766C00	1766	13013	26.77	-1.8	2.0	101.1	6.8	255	1		
4205MH0008490021501767C00	1767	13049	24.70	-1.6	1.7	93.8	5.8	223	2		
4205MH0008490021501768C00	1768	13085	22.90	-1.3	1.5	87.5	5.0	191	3		
4205MH0008490021501769C00	1769	13121	21.32	-1.2	1.3	82.0	4.3	159	4		
4205MH0008490021501770C00	1770	13157	19.93	-1.0	1.1	77.0	3.8	127	5		
4205MH0008490021501771C00	1771	13193	18.69	-0.9	1.0	72.7	3.3	95	6		
4205MH0008490021501772C00	1772	13229	17.57	-0.8	0.9	68.8	2.9	63	7		
4205MH0008490021501773C00	1773	13265	16.57	-0.7	0.8	65.2	2.6	31	8		

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SOL 4205 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Starr_Minaret - mosaic position 5 of 6 - ~16 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4205MH0008490011501775C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4206MH0004490001501863R00		1863		MOTOR COUNT:		13227		RANGE (cm): 17.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4206MH0004490001501864S00		1864		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00849		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		4-Jun-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4205		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4206	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4205MH0008490021501776C00	1776	13083	22.99	-1.4	1.5	87.8	5.0	255	1		
4205MH0008490021501777C00	1777	13119	21.41	-1.2	1.3	82.2	4.3	223	2		
4205MH0008490021501778C00	1778	13155	20.00	-1.0	1.1	77.3	3.8	191	3		
4205MH0008490021501779C00	1779	13191	18.75	-0.9	1.0	72.9	3.3	159	4		
4205MH0008490021501780C00	1780	13227	17.63	-0.8	0.9	69.0	3.0	127	5		
4205MH0008490021501781C00	1781	13263	16.62	-0.7	0.8	65.4	2.6	95	6		
4205MH0008490021501782C00	1782	13299	15.71	-0.7	0.7	62.2	2.4	63	7		
4205MH0008490021501783C00	1783	13335	14.87	-0.6	0.6	59.3	2.1	31	8		

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SOL 4205 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Starr_Minaret - mosaic position 6 of 6 - ~16 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4205MH0008490011501785C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4206MH0004490001501861R00		1861		MOTOR COUNT:		13207		RANGE (cm): 18.2	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4206MH0004490001501862S00		1862		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00849		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		4-Jun-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4205		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4206	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4205MH0008490021501786C00	1786	13063	23.97	-1.5	1.6	91.3	5.4	255	1		
4205MH0008490021501787C00	1787	13099	22.26	-1.3	1.4	85.3	4.7	223	2		
4205MH0008490021501788C00	1788	13135	20.76	-1.1	1.2	80.0	4.1	191	3		
4205MH0008490021501789C00	1789	13171	19.43	-1.0	1.0	75.3	3.6	159	4		
4205MH0008490021501790C00	1790	13207	18.24	-0.9	0.9	71.1	3.2	127	5		
4205MH0008490021501791C00	1791	13243	17.17	-0.8	0.8	67.3	2.8	95	6		
4205MH0008490021501792C00	1792	13279	16.20	-0.7	0.7	63.9	2.5	63	7		
4205MH0008490021501793C00	1793	13315	15.33	-0.6	0.7	60.9	2.3	31	8		

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SOL 4205 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Gem_Lakes - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4205MH0003360011501797C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4206MH0004490001501859R00	1859	MOTOR COUNT:		14008	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4206MH0004490001501860S00	1860	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	4-Jun-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4205	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4206	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4205MH0003360021501798C00	1798	13960	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	255	1
4205MH0003360021501799C00	1799	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	223	2
4205MH0003360021501800C00	1800	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
4205MH0003360021501801C00	1801	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
4205MH0003360021501802C00	1802	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
4205MH0003360021501803C00	1803	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
4205MH0003360021501804C00	1804	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
4205MH0003360021501805C00	1805	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4205 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Gem_Lakes - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4205MH0003360011501807C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4206MH0004490001501857R00	1857	MOTOR COUNT:		14008	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4206MH0004490001501858S00	1858	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	4-Jun-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4205	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4206	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4205MH0003360021501808C00	1808	13960	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	255	1
4205MH0003360021501809C00	1809	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	223	2
4205MH0003360021501810C00	1810	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
4205MH0003360021501811C00	1811	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
4205MH0003360021501812C00	1812	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
4205MH0003360021501813C00	1813	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
4205MH0003360021501814C00	1814	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
4205MH0003360021501815C00	1815	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4205 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Gem_Lakes - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4205MH0007430011501817C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4206MH0004490001501855R00	1855	MOTOR COUNT:		15128	RANGE (cm):	2.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4206MH0004490001501856S00	1856	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	4-Jun-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4205	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4206	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4205MH0007430021501818C00	1818	14984	3.07	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	255	1
4205MH0007430021501819C00	1819	15020	3.00	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	223	2
4205MH0007430021501820C00	1820	15056	2.92	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	191	3
4205MH0007430021501821C00	1821	15092	2.85	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	159	4
4205MH0007430021501822C00	1822	15128	2.78	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	127	5
4205MH0007430021501823C00	1823	15164	2.71	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	95	6
4205MH0007430021501824C00	1824	15200	2.65	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	63	7
4205MH0007430021501825C00	1825	15236	2.58	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	31	8

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SOL 4205 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Convict_Lake - stereo-1 - ~3 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4205MH0008430011501830C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4206MH0004490001501853R00	1853	MOTOR COUNT:		14370	RANGE (cm):	4.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4206MH0004490001501854S00	1854	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00843	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	4-Jun-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4205	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4206	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4205MH0008430031501832C00	1832	14202	5.68	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	255	1
4205MH0008430031501833C00	1833	14244	5.48	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	223	2
4205MH0008430031501834C00	1834	14286	5.28	-0.1	0.1	25.5	0.4	191	3
4205MH0008430031501835C00	1835	14328	5.10	-0.1	0.1	24.8	0.4	159	4
4205MH0008430031501836C00	1836	14370	4.92	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	127	5
4205MH0008430031501837C00	1837	14412	4.75	-0.1	0.1	23.6	0.3	95	6
4205MH0008430031501838C00	1838	14454	4.59	-0.1	0.1	23.1	0.3	63	7
4205MH0008430031501839C00	1839	14496	4.44	-0.1	0.1	22.5	0.3	31	8

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SOL 4205 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Convict_Lake - stereo-2 - ~3 cm standoff							
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4206MH0004490001501851R00		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4205MH0008430011501841C00		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4206MH0004490001501852S00		1851	MOTOR COUNT:		14369	RANGE (cm):	4.9
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		4-Jun-24		1852	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00843	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4205		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4206			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4205MH0008430031501843C00	1843	14201	5.69	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	255	1
4205MH0008430031501844C00	1844	14243	5.48	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	223	2
4205MH0008430031501845C00	1845	14285	5.29	-0.1	0.1	25.5	0.4	191	3
4205MH0008430031501846C00	1846	14327	5.10	-0.1	0.1	24.9	0.4	159	4
4205MH0008430031501847C00	1847	14369	4.92	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	127	5
4205MH0008430031501848C00	1848	14411	4.75	-0.1	0.1	23.6	0.3	95	6
4205MH0008430031501849C00	1849	14453	4.59	-0.1	0.1	23.1	0.3	63	7
4205MH0008430031501850C00	1850	14495	4.44	-0.1	0.1	22.5	0.3	31	8

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SOL 4207 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4207MH0007210011501877C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4208MH0001530001501932R00	1932	MOTOR COUNT:		14154	RANGE (cm):		5.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4208MH0001530001501933S00	1933	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00721	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	6-Jun-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4207	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4208	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4207MH0007210031501879C00	1879	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	255	1
4207MH0007210031501880C00	1880	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	223	2
4207MH0007210031501881C00	1881	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	191	3
4207MH0007210031501882C00	1882	14112	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	159	4
4207MH0007210031501883C00	1883	14154	5.93	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	127	5
4207MH0007210031501884C00	1884	14196	5.71	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	95	6
4207MH0007210031501885C00	1885	14238	5.51	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	63	7
4207MH0007210031501886C00	1886	14280	5.31	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4207 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4207MH0007210011501888C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4208MH0001530001501930R00	1930	MOTOR COUNT:		14129	RANGE (cm):		6.1	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4208MH0001530001501931S00	1931	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00721	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	6-Jun-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4207	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4208	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4207MH0007210031501890C00	1890	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	255	1
4207MH0007210031501891C00	1891	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	223	2
4207MH0007210031501892C00	1892	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	191	3
4207MH0007210031501893C00	1893	14087	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	159	4
4207MH0007210031501894C00	1894	14129	6.07	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	127	5
4207MH0007210031501895C00	1895	14171	5.84	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	95	6
4207MH0007210031501896C00	1896	14213	5.63	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	63	7
4207MH0007210031501897C00	1897	14255	5.42	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 25_July_2024

SOL 4207 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 1 - ~45 mm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4207MH0007210011501899C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4208MH0001530001501928R00	1928	MOTOR COUNT:		14053	RANGE (cm):	6.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4208MH0001530001501929S00	1929	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00721	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	6-Jun-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4207	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4208	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4207MH0007210031501901C00	1901	13885	7.66	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	255	1
4207MH0007210031501902C00	1902	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
4207MH0007210031501903C00	1903	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
4207MH0007210031501904C00	1904	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	159	4
4207MH0007210031501905C00	1905	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	127	5
4207MH0007210031501906C00	1906	14095	6.26	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	95	6
4207MH0007210031501907C00	1907	14137	6.02	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	63	7
4207MH0007210031501908C00	1908	14179	5.80	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4207 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - night imaging - group 2 LEDs on - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4207MH0008800031501911C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4208MH0001530001501926R00	1926	MOTOR COUNT:		14010	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4208MH0001530001501927S00	1927	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00880	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Jun-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4207	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4208	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4207MH0008800101501918C00	1918	13842	8.01	-0.2	0.2	35.1	0.7	255	1
4207MH0008800101501919C00	1919	13884	7.67	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	223	2
4207MH0008800101501920C00	1920	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	191	3
4207MH0008800101501921C00	1921	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
4207MH0008800101501922C00	1922	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
4207MH0008800101501923C00	1923	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6
4207MH0008800101501924C00	1924	14094	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7
4207MH0008800101501925C00	1925	14136	6.03	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4209 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Grass_Lake - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4209MH0008790011501938C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4210MH0001630001502016R00		2016		MOTOR COUNT:		14026		RANGE (cm): 6.7	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4210MH0001630001502017S00		2017		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00879		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		8-Jun-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4209		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4210	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4209MH0008790031501940C00	1940	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	255	1		
4209MH0008790031501941C00	1941	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2		
4209MH0008790031501942C00	1942	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3		
4209MH0008790031501943C00	1943	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	159	4		
4209MH0008790031501944C00	1944	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5		
4209MH0008790031501945C00	1945	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6		
4209MH0008790031501946C00	1946	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7		
4209MH0008790031501947C00	1947	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8		

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SOL 4209 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Grass_Lake - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4209MH0008790011501949C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4210MH0001630001502014R00		2014		MOTOR COUNT:		14031		RANGE (cm): 6.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4210MH0001630001502015S00		2015		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00879		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		8-Jun-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4209		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4210	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4209MH0008790031501951C00	1951	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	255	1		
4209MH0008790031501952C00	1952	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	223	2		
4209MH0008790031501953C00	1953	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	191	3		
4209MH0008790031501954C00	1954	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4		
4209MH0008790031501955C00	1955	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5		
4209MH0008790031501956C00	1956	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	95	6		
4209MH0008790031501957C00	1957	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7		
4209MH0008790031501958C00	1958	14067	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8		

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SOL 4209 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Grass_Lake – after DRT – ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4209MH0008350011501960C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4210MH0001630001502012R00	2012	MOTOR COUNT:		15181	RANGE (cm):	2.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4210MH0001630001502013S00	2013	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00835	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	8-Jun-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4209	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4210	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4209MH0008350031501962C00	1962	15061	2.91	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	255	1
4209MH0008350031501963C00	1963	15091	2.85	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	223	2
4209MH0008350031501964C00	1964	15121	2.79	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	191	3
4209MH0008350031501965C00	1965	15151	2.74	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	159	4
4209MH0008350031501966C00	1966	15181	2.68	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	127	5
4209MH0008350031501967C00	1967	15211	2.63	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	95	6
4209MH0008350031501968C00	1968	15241	2.58	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	63	7
4209MH0008350031501969C00	1969	15271	2.52	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	31	8

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SOL 4209 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Snow_Lakes – APXS spot 1 – ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4209MH0008340011501974C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4210MH0001630001502010R00	2010	MOTOR COUNT:		14154	RANGE (cm):	5.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4210MH0001630001502011S00	2011	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00834	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	8-Jun-24/9-Jun-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4209	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4210	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4209MH0008340031501976C00	1976	14082	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	255	1
4209MH0008340031501977C00	1977	14100	6.23	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	223	2
4209MH0008340031501978C00	1978	14118	6.13	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	191	3
4209MH0008340031501979C00	1979	14136	6.03	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	159	4
4209MH0008340031501980C00	1980	14154	5.93	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	127	5
4209MH0008340031501981C00	1981	14172	5.84	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	95	6
4209MH0008340031501982C00	1982	14190	5.74	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	63	7
4209MH0008340031501983C00	1983	14208	5.65	-0.1	0.1	26.8	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4209 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Snow_Lakes – APXS spot 2 – ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4209MH0008340011501985C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4210MH0001630001502008R00	2008	MOTOR COUNT:		14145	RANGE (cm):	6.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4210MH0001630001502009S00	2009	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00834	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	9-Jun-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4209	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4210		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4209MH0008340031501987C00	1987	14073	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	255	1
4209MH0008340031501988C00	1988	14091	6.28	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	223	2
4209MH0008340031501989C00	1989	14109	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	191	3
4209MH0008340031501990C00	1990	14127	6.08	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	159	4
4209MH0008340031501991C00	1991	14145	5.98	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	127	5
4209MH0008340031501992C00	1992	14163	5.88	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	95	6
4209MH0008340031501993C00	1993	14181	5.79	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	63	7
4209MH0008340031501994C00	1994	14199	5.70	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4209 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Snow_Lakes – APXS spot 3 – ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4209MH0008340011501996C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4210MH0001630001502006R00	2006	MOTOR COUNT:		14151	RANGE (cm):	5.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4210MH0001630001502007S00	2007	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00834	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	9-Jun-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4209	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4210		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4209MH0008340031501998C00	1998	14079	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	255	1
4209MH0008340031501999C00	1999	14097	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	223	2
4209MH0008340031502000C00	2000	14115	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	191	3
4209MH0008340031502001C00	2001	14133	6.05	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	159	4
4209MH0008340031502002C00	2002	14151	5.95	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	127	5
4209MH0008340031502003C00	2003	14169	5.85	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	95	6
4209MH0008340031502004C00	2004	14187	5.76	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	63	7
4209MH0008340031502005C00	2005	14205	5.67	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4212 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mammoth_Lakes - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4212MH0008790011502022C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4212MH0001530001502074R00	2074	MOTOR COUNT:		13996	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4212MH0001530001502075S00	2075	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00879	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	11-Jun-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4212	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4212	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4212MH0008790031502024C00	2024	13948	7.20	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1
4212MH0008790031502025C00	2025	13960	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
4212MH0008790031502026C00	2026	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
4212MH0008790031502027C00	2027	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4212MH0008790031502028C00	2028	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
4212MH0008790031502029C00	2029	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
4212MH0008790031502030C00	2030	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	63	7
4212MH0008790031502031C00	2031	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	31	8

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SOL 4212 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mammoth_Lakes - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4212MH0008790011502033C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4212MH0001530001502072R00	2072	MOTOR COUNT:		13996	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4212MH0001530001502073S00	2073	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00879	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	11-Jun-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4212	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4212	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4212MH0008790031502035C00	2035	13948	7.20	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1
4212MH0008790031502036C00	2036	13960	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
4212MH0008790031502037C00	2037	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
4212MH0008790031502038C00	2038	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4212MH0008790031502039C00	2039	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
4212MH0008790031502040C00	2040	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
4212MH0008790031502041C00	2041	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	63	7
4212MH0008790031502042C00	2042	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	31	8

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SOL 4212 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mammoth_Lakes - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4212MH0008220011502044C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4212MH0001530001502070R00	2070	MOTOR COUNT:		15097	RANGE (cm):	2.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4212MH0001530001502071S00	2071	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00822	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	11-Jun-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4212	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4212	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4212MH0008220031502046C00	2046	15001	3.04	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	255	1
4212MH0008220031502047C00	2047	15025	2.99	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	223	2
4212MH0008220031502048C00	2048	15049	2.94	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	191	3
4212MH0008220031502049C00	2049	15073	2.89	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	159	4
4212MH0008220031502050C00	2050	15097	2.84	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	127	5
4212MH0008220031502051C00	2051	15121	2.79	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	95	6
4212MH0008220031502052C00	2052	15145	2.75	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	63	7
4212MH0008220031502053C00	2053	15169	2.70	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	31	8

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SOL 4212 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mammoth_Lakes - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4212MH0008790011502055C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4212MH0001530001502068R00	2068	MOTOR COUNT:		13999	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4212MH0001530001502069S00	2069	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00879	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	11-Jun-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4212	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4212	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4212MH0008790031502057C00	2057	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1
4212MH0008790031502058C00	2058	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
4212MH0008790031502059C00	2059	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
4212MH0008790031502060C00	2060	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
4212MH0008790031502061C00	2061	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4212MH0008790031502062C00	2062	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4212MH0008790031502063C00	2063	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	63	7
4212MH0008790031502064C00	2064	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	31	8

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SOL 4216 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4216MH0001680011502083C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4216MH0001930001502118R00	2118	MOTOR COUNT:		13999	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4216MH0001930001502119S00	2119	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Jun-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4216	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4216	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4216MH0001680021502084C00	2084	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
4216MH0001680021502085C00	2085	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
4216MH0001680021502086C00	2086	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
4216MH0001680021502087C00	2087	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4216MH0001680021502088C00	2088	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4216MH0001680021502089C00	2089	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4216MH0001680021502090C00	2090	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
4216MH0001680021502091C00	2091	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4216 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4216MH0001680011502093C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4216MH0001930001502116R00	2116	MOTOR COUNT:		13999	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4216MH0001930001502117S00	2117	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Jun-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4216	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4216	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4216MH0001680021502094C00	2094	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
4216MH0001680021502095C00	2095	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
4216MH0001680021502096C00	2096	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
4216MH0001680021502097C00	2097	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4216MH0001680021502098C00	2098	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4216MH0001680021502099C00	2099	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4216MH0001680021502100C00	2100	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
4216MH0001680021502101C00	2101	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4216 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Loch_Leven – APXS spot 1 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4216MH0001680011502103C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4216MH0001930001502114R00	2114	MOTOR COUNT:		13995	RANGE (cm):		6.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4216MH0001930001502115S00	2115	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Jun-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4216		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4216
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4216MH0001680021502104C00	2104	13923	7.38	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1
4216MH0001680021502105C00	2105	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
4216MH0001680021502106C00	2106	13959	7.12	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
4216MH0001680021502107C00	2107	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
4216MH0001680021502108C00	2108	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
4216MH0001680021502109C00	2109	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4216MH0001680021502110C00	2110	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
4216MH0001680021502111C00	2111	14049	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4234 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		Mammoth_Lakes2 drill cuttings - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4234MH0001520011502125C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4235MH0002580001502134R00	2134	MOTOR COUNT:		14216	RANGE (cm):		5.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4235MH0002580001502135S00	2135	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	4-Jul-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00258		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4234		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4235
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4234MH0001520021502126C00	2126	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	255	1
4234MH0001520021502127C00	2127	14072	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	223	2
4234MH0001520021502128C00	2128	14120	6.12	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	191	3
4234MH0001520021502129C00	2129	14168	5.86	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	159	4
4234MH0001520021502130C00	2130	14216	5.61	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	127	5
4234MH0001520021502131C00	2131	14264	5.38	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	95	6
4234MH0001520021502132C00	2132	14312	5.17	-0.1	0.1	25.1	0.4	63	7
4234MH0001520021502133C00	2133	14360	4.96	-0.1	0.1	24.4	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4236 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Glacier_Notch - stereo-1 - ~31 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4236MH0008830011502139C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4237MH0008840001502208R00	2208	MOTOR COUNT:		12937	RANGE (cm):	32.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4237MH0008840001502209S00	2209	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00883	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	6-Jul-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00884	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4236	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4237	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4236MH0008830031502141C00	2141	12865	40.07	-3.9	4.8	147.9	15.4	255	1
4236MH0008830031502142C00	2142	12883	37.84	-3.5	4.3	140.1	13.6	223	2
4236MH0008830031502143C00	2143	12901	35.83	-3.2	3.8	133.0	12.2	191	3
4236MH0008830031502144C00	2144	12919	34.02	-2.9	3.4	126.6	11.0	159	4
4236MH0008830031502145C00	2145	12937	32.36	-2.6	3.1	120.8	9.9	127	5
4236MH0008830031502146C00	2146	12955	30.85	-2.4	2.8	115.5	9.0	95	6
4236MH0008830031502147C00	2147	12973	29.47	-2.2	2.5	110.6	8.2	63	7
4236MH0008830031502148C00	2148	12991	28.19	-2.0	2.3	106.1	7.5	31	8

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SOL 4236 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Glacier_Notch - stereo-2 - ~30 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4236MH0008830011502150C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4237MH0008840001502206R00	2206	MOTOR COUNT:		12943	RANGE (cm):	31.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4237MH0008840001502207S00	2207	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00883	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	6-Jul-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00884	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4236	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4237	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4236MH0008830031502152C00	2152	12871	39.30	-3.8	4.6	145.2	14.7	255	1
4236MH0008830031502153C00	2153	12889	37.15	-3.4	4.1	137.7	13.2	223	2
4236MH0008830031502154C00	2154	12907	35.21	-3.0	3.7	130.8	11.8	191	3
4236MH0008830031502155C00	2155	12925	33.45	-2.8	3.3	124.6	10.6	159	4
4236MH0008830031502156C00	2156	12943	31.85	-2.5	2.9	119.0	9.6	127	5
4236MH0008830031502157C00	2157	12961	30.38	-2.3	2.7	113.8	8.7	95	6
4236MH0008830031502158C00	2158	12979	29.03	-2.1	2.4	109.1	8.0	63	7
4236MH0008830031502159C00	2159	12997	27.79	-1.9	2.2	104.7	7.3	31	8

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SOL 4236 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lake_Ediza - stereo-1 - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4236MH0001680011502163C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4237MH0008840001502204R00	2204	MOTOR COUNT:		14276	RANGE (cm):	5.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4237MH0008840001502205S00	2205	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	6-Jul-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00884	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4236	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4237	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4236MH0001680021502164C00	2164	14204	5.67	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	255	1
4236MH0001680021502165C00	2165	14222	5.58	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	223	2
4236MH0001680021502166C00	2166	14240	5.50	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	191	3
4236MH0001680021502167C00	2167	14258	5.41	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	159	4
4236MH0001680021502168C00	2168	14276	5.33	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	127	5
4236MH0001680021502169C00	2169	14294	5.25	-0.1	0.1	25.4	0.4	95	6
4236MH0001680021502170C00	2170	14312	5.17	-0.1	0.1	25.1	0.4	63	7
4236MH0001680021502171C00	2171	14330	5.09	-0.1	0.1	24.8	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4236 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lake_Ediza - stereo-2 - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4236MH0001680011502173C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4237MH0008840001502202R00	2202	MOTOR COUNT:		14261	RANGE (cm):	5.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4237MH0008840001502203S00	2203	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	6-Jul-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00884	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4236	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4237	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4236MH0001680021502174C00	2174	14189	5.75	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	255	1
4236MH0001680021502175C00	2175	14207	5.66	-0.1	0.1	26.8	0.4	223	2
4236MH0001680021502176C00	2176	14225	5.57	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	191	3
4236MH0001680021502177C00	2177	14243	5.48	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	159	4
4236MH0001680021502178C00	2178	14261	5.40	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	127	5
4236MH0001680021502179C00	2179	14279	5.31	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	95	6
4236MH0001680021502180C00	2180	14297	5.23	-0.1	0.1	25.3	0.4	63	7
4236MH0001680021502181C00	2181	14315	5.15	-0.1	0.1	25.0	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4236 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		Mammoth_Lakes2 drill hole - looking south - 30° from normal - night imaging - all white LEDs on - ~9 cm standoff - merge of images 4-11 of 16								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4236MH0004110011502183C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4237MH0008840001502200R00	2200	MOTOR COUNT:		13507	RANGE (cm):		11.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4237MH0008840001502201S00	2201	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00411		STACK TYPE:		ABSOLUTE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	6-Jul-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00884		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4236	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4237		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 16	
				NEAR	FAR					
4236MH0004110021502184C00	2184	13296	15.78	-0.7	0.7	62.4	2.4	n/a	1	
4236MH0004110021502185C00	2185	13332	14.94	-0.6	0.6	59.5	2.1	n/a	2	
4236MH0004110021502186C00	2186	13368	14.17	-0.6	0.6	56.8	1.9	n/a	3	
4236MH0004110021502187C00	2187	13404	13.47	-0.5	0.5	54.3	1.8	255	4	
4236MH0004110021502188C00	2188	13440	12.82	-0.5	0.5	52.0	1.6	223	5	
4236MH0004110021502189C00	2189	13476	12.22	-0.4	0.4	49.9	1.5	191	6	
4236MH0004110021502190C00	2190	13512	11.67	-0.4	0.4	48.0	1.4	159	7	
4236MH0004110021502191C00	2191	13548	11.15	-0.4	0.4	46.2	1.3	127	8	
4236MH0004110021502192C00	2192	13584	10.67	-0.3	0.3	44.5	1.1	95	9	
4236MH0004110021502193C00	2193	13620	10.23	-0.3	0.3	42.9	1.1	63	10	
4236MH0004110021502194C00	2194	13656	9.81	-0.3	0.3	41.4	1.0	31	11	
4236MH0004110021502195C00	2195	13692	9.41	-0.3	0.3	40.0	0.9	n/a	12	
4236MH0004110021502196C00	2196	13728	9.04	-0.3	0.2	38.7	0.9	n/a	13	
4236MH0004110021502197C00	2197	13764	8.70	-0.2	0.2	37.5	0.8	n/a	14	
4236MH0004110021502198C00	2198	13800	8.37	-0.2	0.2	36.4	0.8	n/a	15	
4236MH0004110021502199C00	2199	13836	8.06	-0.2	0.2	35.3	0.7	n/a	16	

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SOL 4239 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lake_Dorothy - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4239MH0007630011502214C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4240MH0001630001502298R00	2298	MOTOR COUNT:		14026	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4240MH0001630001502299S00	2299	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00763	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	9-Jul-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4239	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4240		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4239MH0007630031502216C00	2216	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
4239MH0007630031502217C00	2217	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
4239MH0007630031502218C00	2218	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
4239MH0007630031502219C00	2219	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
4239MH0007630031502220C00	2220	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
4239MH0007630031502221C00	2221	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	95	6
4239MH0007630031502222C00	2222	14074	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
4239MH0007630031502223C00	2223	14098	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4239 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lake_Dorothy - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4239MH0007630011502225C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4240MH0001630001502296R00	2296	MOTOR COUNT:		14029	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4240MH0001630001502297S00	2297	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00763	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	9-Jul-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4239	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4240		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4239MH0007630031502227C00	2227	13933	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
4239MH0007630031502228C00	2228	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
4239MH0007630031502229C00	2229	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
4239MH0007630031502230C00	2230	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
4239MH0007630031502231C00	2231	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
4239MH0007630031502232C00	2232	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6
4239MH0007630031502233C00	2233	14077	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
4239MH0007630031502234C00	2234	14101	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4239 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Lake_Dorothy - ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4239MH0007940011502236C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4240MH0001630001502294R00	2294	MOTOR COUNT:		15183	RANGE (cm):	2.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4240MH0001630001502295S00	2295	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00794	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	9-Jul-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4239	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4240		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4239MH0007940031502238C00	2238	14991	3.06	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	255	1
4239MH0007940031502239C00	2239	15039	2.96	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	223	2
4239MH0007940031502240C00	2240	15087	2.86	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	191	3
4239MH0007940031502241C00	2241	15135	2.77	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	159	4
4239MH0007940031502242C00	2242	15183	2.68	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	127	5
4239MH0007940031502243C00	2243	15231	2.59	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	95	6
4239MH0007940031502244C00	2244	15279	2.51	0.0	0.1	15.7	0.2	63	7
4239MH0007940031502245C00	2245	15327	2.43	0.0	0.1	15.5	0.2	31	8

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SOL 4239 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Palisade_Glacier - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4239MH0007630011502250C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4240MH0001630001502292R00	2292	MOTOR COUNT:		13987	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4240MH0001630001502293S00	2293	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00763	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	9-Jul-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4239	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4240		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4239MH0007630031502252C00	2252	13891	7.62	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1
4239MH0007630031502253C00	2253	13915	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	223	2
4239MH0007630031502254C00	2254	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	191	3
4239MH0007630031502255C00	2255	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
4239MH0007630031502256C00	2256	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
4239MH0007630031502257C00	2257	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4239MH0007630031502258C00	2258	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
4239MH0007630031502259C00	2259	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4239 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Palisade_Glacier - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4239MH0007630011502261C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4240MH0001630001502290R00	2290	MOTOR COUNT:		13993	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4240MH0001630001502291S00	2291	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00763	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	9-Jul-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4239	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4240		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4239MH0007630031502263C00	2263	13897	7.57	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
4239MH0007630031502264C00	2264	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
4239MH0007630031502265C00	2265	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
4239MH0007630031502266C00	2266	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
4239MH0007630031502267C00	2267	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4239MH0007630031502268C00	2268	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4239MH0007630031502269C00	2269	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
4239MH0007630031502270C00	2270	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4239 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Palisade_Glacier - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4239MH0007940011502278C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4240MH0001630001502288R00	2288	MOTOR COUNT:		15062	RANGE (cm):	2.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4240MH0001630001502289S00	2289	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00794	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	9-Jul-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4239	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4240		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4239MH0007940031502280C00	2280	14870	3.34	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	255	1
4239MH0007940031502281C00	2281	14918	3.22	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	223	2
4239MH0007940031502282C00	2282	14966	3.11	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	191	3
4239MH0007940031502283C00	2283	15014	3.01	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	159	4
4239MH0007940031502284C00	2284	15062	2.91	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	127	5
4239MH0007940031502285C00	2285	15110	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	95	6
4239MH0007940031502286C00	2286	15158	2.72	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	63	7
4239MH0007940031502287C00	2287	15206	2.64	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	31	8

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SOL 4241 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Donohue_Pass – ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4241MH0003590011502301C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4241MH0001930001502334R00	2334	MOTOR COUNT:		13028	RANGE (cm):	25.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4241MH0001930001502335S00	2335	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	11-Jul-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4241	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4241		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4241MH0003590021502302C00	2302	12956	30.77	-2.4	2.7	115.2	9.0	255	1
4241MH0003590021502303C00	2303	12974	29.40	-2.2	2.5	110.4	8.2	223	2
4241MH0003590021502304C00	2304	12992	28.13	-2.0	2.3	105.9	7.5	191	3
4241MH0003590021502305C00	2305	13010	26.95	-1.8	2.1	101.8	6.9	159	4
4241MH0003590021502306C00	2306	13028	25.87	-1.7	1.9	98.0	6.3	127	5
4241MH0003590021502307C00	2307	13046	24.86	-1.6	1.7	94.4	5.8	95	6
4241MH0003590021502308C00	2308	13064	23.92	-1.5	1.6	91.1	5.4	63	7
4241MH0003590021502309C00	2309	13082	23.04	-1.4	1.5	88.0	5.0	31	8

UPDATED: 17_December_2024

SOL 4241 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Donohue_Pass – stereo-1 – ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4241MH0002970011502311C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4241MH0001930001502332R00	2332	MOTOR COUNT:		14149	RANGE (cm):	6.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4241MH0001930001502333S00	2333	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00297	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	11-Jul-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		60	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4241	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4241		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4241MH0002970021502312C00	2312	13909	7.48	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	255	1
4241MH0002970021502313C00	2313	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	223	2
4241MH0002970021502314C00	2314	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	191	3
4241MH0002970021502315C00	2315	14089	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	159	4
4241MH0002970021502316C00	2316	14149	5.96	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	127	5
4241MH0002970021502317C00	2317	14209	5.65	-0.1	0.1	26.8	0.4	95	6
4241MH0002970021502318C00	2318	14269	5.36	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	63	7
4241MH0002970021502319C00	2319	14329	5.09	-0.1	0.1	24.8	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 17_December_2024

SOL 4241 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Donohue_Pass - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4241MH0002970011502321C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4241MH0001930001502330R00	2330	MOTOR COUNT:		14158	RANGE (cm):		5.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4241MH0001930001502331S00	2331	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00297		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	11-Jul-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		60	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4241		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4241
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4241MH0002970021502322C00	2322	13918	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	255	1
4241MH0002970021502323C00	2323	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	223	2
4241MH0002970021502324C00	2324	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	191	3
4241MH0002970021502325C00	2325	14098	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	159	4
4241MH0002970021502326C00	2326	14158	5.91	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	127	5
4241MH0002970021502327C00	2327	14218	5.60	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	95	6
4241MH0002970021502328C00	2328	14278	5.32	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	63	7
4241MH0002970021502329C00	2329	14338	5.05	-0.1	0.1	24.7	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4243 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cattle_Creek - stereo-1 - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4243MH0002240011502339C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4244MH0001700001502432R00	2432	MOTOR COUNT:		14234	RANGE (cm):	5.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4244MH0001700001502433S00	2433	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-Jul-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4243	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4244	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4243MH0002240021502340C00	2340	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	255	1
4243MH0002240021502341C00	2341	14108	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	223	2
4243MH0002240021502342C00	2342	14150	5.95	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	191	3
4243MH0002240021502343C00	2343	14192	5.73	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	159	4
4243MH0002240021502344C00	2344	14234	5.53	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	127	5
4243MH0002240021502345C00	2345	14276	5.33	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	95	6
4243MH0002240021502346C00	2346	14318	5.14	-0.1	0.1	25.0	0.4	63	7
4243MH0002240021502347C00	2347	14360	4.96	-0.1	0.1	24.4	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 29_July_2024

SOL 4243 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cattle_Creek - stereo-2 - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4243MH0002240011502349C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4244MH0001700001502430R00	2430	MOTOR COUNT:		14220	RANGE (cm):	5.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4244MH0001700001502431S00	2431	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-Jul-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4243	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4244	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4243MH0002240021502350C00	2350	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	255	1
4243MH0002240021502351C00	2351	14094	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	223	2
4243MH0002240021502352C00	2352	14136	6.03	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	191	3
4243MH0002240021502353C00	2353	14178	5.81	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	159	4
4243MH0002240021502354C00	2354	14220	5.59	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	127	5
4243MH0002240021502355C00	2355	14262	5.39	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	95	6
4243MH0002240021502356C00	2356	14304	5.20	-0.1	0.1	25.2	0.4	63	7
4243MH0002240021502357C00	2357	14346	5.02	-0.1	0.1	24.6	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4243 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Arrowhead_Spire - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4243MH0002970011502359C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4244MH0001700001502428R00	2428	MOTOR COUNT:	14120	RANGE (cm):	6.1			
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4244MH0001700001502429S00	2429	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:	mhli00297	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE			
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-Jul-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		60	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4243	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4244		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4243MH0002970021502360C00	2360	13880	7.70	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	255	1
4243MH0002970021502361C00	2361	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
4243MH0002970021502362C00	2362	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	191	3
4243MH0002970021502363C00	2363	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	159	4
4243MH0002970021502364C00	2364	14120	6.12	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	127	5
4243MH0002970021502365C00	2365	14180	5.80	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	95	6
4243MH0002970021502366C00	2366	14240	5.50	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	63	7
4243MH0002970021502367C00	2367	14300	5.22	-0.1	0.1	25.3	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 29_July_2024

SOL 4243 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Arrowhead_Spire - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4243MH0002970011502369C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4244MH0001700001502426R00	2426	MOTOR COUNT:	14129	RANGE (cm):	6.1			
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4244MH0001700001502427S00	2427	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:	mhli00297	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE			
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-Jul-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		60	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4243	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4244		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4243MH0002970021502370C00	2370	13889	7.63	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	255	1
4243MH0002970021502371C00	2371	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
4243MH0002970021502372C00	2372	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	191	3
4243MH0002970021502373C00	2373	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	159	4
4243MH0002970021502374C00	2374	14129	6.07	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	127	5
4243MH0002970021502375C00	2375	14189	5.75	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	95	6
4243MH0002970021502376C00	2376	14249	5.45	-0.1	0.1	26.1	0.4	63	7
4243MH0002970021502377C00	2377	14309	5.18	-0.1	0.1	25.1	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 29_July_2024

SOL 4243 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Arrowhead_Spire – mosaic position 1 of 4 – ~25 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4243MH0008550011502379C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4244MH0001700001502424R00	2424	MOTOR COUNT:		13006	RANGE (cm):	27.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4244MH0001700001502425S00	2425	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00855	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-Jul-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4243	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4244	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4243MH0008550021502380C00	2380	12886	37.49	-3.4	4.2	138.9	13.4	255	1
4243MH0008550021502381C00	2381	12916	34.31	-2.9	3.5	127.7	11.2	223	2
4243MH0008550021502382C00	2382	12946	31.59	-2.5	2.9	118.1	9.5	191	3
4243MH0008550021502383C00	2383	12976	29.25	-2.1	2.5	109.9	8.1	159	4
4243MH0008550021502384C00	2384	13006	27.21	-1.9	2.1	102.7	7.0	127	5
4243MH0008550021502385C00	2385	13036	25.41	-1.6	1.8	96.3	6.1	95	6
4243MH0008550021502386C00	2386	13066	23.82	-1.4	1.6	90.7	5.3	63	7
4243MH0008550021502387C00	2387	13096	22.40	-1.3	1.4	85.7	4.7	31	8

UPDATED: 29_July_2024

SOL 4243 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Arrowhead_Spire – mosaic position 2 of 4 – ~25 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4243MH0008550011502389C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4244MH0001700001502422R00	2422	MOTOR COUNT:		13014	RANGE (cm):	26.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4244MH0001700001502423S00	2423	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00855	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-Jul-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4243	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4244	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4243MH0008550021502390C00	2390	12894	36.59	-3.3	4.0	135.7	12.7	255	1
4243MH0008550021502391C00	2391	12924	33.54	-2.8	3.3	125.0	10.7	223	2
4243MH0008550021502392C00	2392	12954	30.93	-2.4	2.8	115.8	9.1	191	3
4243MH0008550021502393C00	2393	12984	28.68	-2.1	2.4	107.8	7.8	159	4
4243MH0008550021502394C00	2394	13014	26.71	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	127	5
4243MH0008550021502395C00	2395	13044	24.97	-1.6	1.8	94.8	5.9	95	6
4243MH0008550021502396C00	2396	13074	23.42	-1.4	1.5	89.4	5.2	63	7
4243MH0008550021502397C00	2397	13104	22.04	-1.3	1.4	84.5	4.6	31	8

UPDATED: 29_July_2024

SOL 4243 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Arrowhead_Spire – mosaic position 3 of 4 – ~24 cm standoff							
				CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4243MH0008550011502399C00		
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4244MH0001700001502420R00			2420	MOTOR COUNT:		13020	RANGE (cm):	26.3
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4244MH0001700001502421S00			2421	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00855	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-Jul-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30		ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4243		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4244
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4243MH0008550021502400C00	2400	12900	35.94	-3.2	3.8	133.4	12.3	255	1
4243MH0008550021502401C00	2401	12930	32.99	-2.7	3.2	123.0	10.3	223	2
4243MH0008550021502402C00	2402	12960	30.46	-2.3	2.7	114.1	8.8	191	3
4243MH0008550021502403C00	2403	12990	28.26	-2.0	2.3	106.4	7.5	159	4
4243MH0008550021502404C00	2404	13020	26.34	-1.8	2.0	99.6	6.6	127	5
4243MH0008550021502405C00	2405	13050	24.64	-1.5	1.7	93.7	5.7	95	6
4243MH0008550021502406C00	2406	13080	23.14	-1.4	1.5	88.3	5.1	63	7
4243MH0008550021502407C00	2407	13110	21.78	-1.2	1.3	83.6	4.5	31	8

UPDATED: 29_July_2024

SOL 4243 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Arrowhead_Spire – mosaic position 4 of 4 – ~25 cm standoff							
				CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4243MH0008550011502409C00		
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4244MH0001700001502418R00			2418	MOTOR COUNT:		13010	RANGE (cm):	27.0
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4244MH0001700001502419S00			2419	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00855	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-Jul-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30		ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4243		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4244
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4243MH0008550021502410C00	2410	12890	37.03	-3.4	4.1	137.3	13.1	255	1
4243MH0008550021502411C00	2411	12920	33.92	-2.8	3.4	126.3	10.9	223	2
4243MH0008550021502412C00	2412	12950	31.26	-2.4	2.8	116.9	9.3	191	3
4243MH0008550021502413C00	2413	12980	28.96	-2.1	2.4	108.8	7.9	159	4
4243MH0008550021502414C00	2414	13010	26.95	-1.8	2.1	101.8	6.9	127	5
4243MH0008550021502415C00	2415	13040	25.19	-1.6	1.8	95.6	6.0	95	6
4243MH0008550021502416C00	2416	13070	23.62	-1.4	1.6	90.0	5.3	63	7
4243MH0008550021502417C00	2417	13100	22.22	-1.3	1.4	85.1	4.7	31	8

UPDATED: 29_July_2024

SOL 4246 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Jack_Main_Canyon - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4246MH0003590011502437C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4246MH0001930001502470R00	2470	MOTOR COUNT:		13029	RANGE (cm):	25.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4246MH0001930001502471S00	2471	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Jul-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4246	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4246		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4246MH0003590021502438C00	2438	12957	30.69	-2.3	2.7	114.9	8.9	255	1
4246MH0003590021502439C00	2439	12975	29.32	-2.2	2.5	110.1	8.1	223	2
4246MH0003590021502440C00	2440	12993	28.06	-2.0	2.3	105.7	7.4	191	3
4246MH0003590021502441C00	2441	13011	26.89	-1.8	2.1	101.6	6.8	159	4
4246MH0003590021502442C00	2442	13029	25.81	-1.7	1.9	97.8	6.3	127	5
4246MH0003590021502443C00	2443	13047	24.81	-1.6	1.7	94.2	5.8	95	6
4246MH0003590021502444C00	2444	13065	23.87	-1.5	1.6	90.9	5.4	63	7
4246MH0003590021502445C00	2445	13083	22.99	-1.4	1.5	87.8	5.0	31	8

UPDATED: 29_July_2024

SOL 4246 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Jack_Main_Canyon - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4246MH0003060011502447C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4246MH0001930001502468R00	2468	MOTOR COUNT:		14179	RANGE (cm):	5.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4246MH0001930001502469S00	2469	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00306	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Jul-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4246	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4246		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4246MH0003060021502448C00	2448	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	255	1
4246MH0003060021502449C00	2449	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	223	2
4246MH0003060021502450C00	2450	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	191	3
4246MH0003060021502451C00	2451	14125	6.09	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	159	4
4246MH0003060021502452C00	2452	14179	5.80	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	127	5
4246MH0003060021502453C00	2453	14233	5.53	-0.1	0.1	26.4	0.4	95	6
4246MH0003060021502454C00	2454	14287	5.28	-0.1	0.1	25.5	0.4	63	7
4246MH0003060021502455C00	2455	14341	5.04	-0.1	0.1	24.6	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 29_July_2024

SOL 4246 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Jack_Main_Canyon - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4246MH0003060011502457C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4246MH0001930001502466R00	2466	MOTOR COUNT:		14200	RANGE (cm):		5.7	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4246MH0001930001502467S00	2467	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00306	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Jul-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4246	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4246	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4246MH0003060021502458C00	2458	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	255	1
4246MH0003060021502459C00	2459	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	223	2
4246MH0003060021502460C00	2460	14092	6.28	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	191	3
4246MH0003060021502461C00	2461	14146	5.97	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	159	4
4246MH0003060021502462C00	2462	14200	5.69	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	127	5
4246MH0003060021502463C00	2463	14254	5.43	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	95	6
4246MH0003060021502464C00	2464	14308	5.18	-0.1	0.1	25.1	0.4	63	7
4246MH0003060021502465C00	2465	14362	4.95	-0.1	0.1	24.3	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 01_August_2024

SOL 4248 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Amphitheater_Dome - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4248MH0001680011502497C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4248MH0001530001502542R00	2542	MOTOR COUNT:		14024	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4248MH0001530001502543S00	2543	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Jul-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4248	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4248	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4248MH0001680021502498C00	2498	13952	7.17	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	255	1
4248MH0001680021502499C00	2499	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	223	2
4248MH0001680021502500C00	2500	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3
4248MH0001680021502501C00	2501	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
4248MH0001680021502502C00	2502	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
4248MH0001680021502503C00	2503	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	95	6
4248MH0001680021502504C00	2504	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
4248MH0001680021502505C00	2505	14078	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 01_August_2024

SOL 4248 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Amphitheater_Dome - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4248MH0001680011502507C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4248MH0001530001502540R00	2540	MOTOR COUNT:		14021	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4248MH0001530001502541S00	2541	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Jul-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4248	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4248	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4248MH0001680021502508C00	2508	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1
4248MH0001680021502509C00	2509	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
4248MH0001680021502510C00	2510	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3
4248MH0001680021502511C00	2511	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
4248MH0001680021502512C00	2512	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5
4248MH0001680021502513C00	2513	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
4248MH0001680021502514C00	2514	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
4248MH0001680021502515C00	2515	14075	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 01_August_2024

SOL 4248 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Amphiheater_Dome - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4248MH0007430011502517C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4248MH0001530001502538R00	2538	MOTOR COUNT:		15160	RANGE (cm):	2.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4248MH0001530001502539S00	2539	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Jul-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4248	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4248	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4248MH0007430021502518C00	2518	15016	3.00	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	255	1
4248MH0007430021502519C00	2519	15052	2.93	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	223	2
4248MH0007430021502520C00	2520	15088	2.86	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	191	3
4248MH0007430021502521C00	2521	15124	2.79	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	159	4
4248MH0007430021502522C00	2522	15160	2.72	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	127	5
4248MH0007430021502523C00	2523	15196	2.65	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	95	6
4248MH0007430021502524C00	2524	15232	2.59	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	63	7
4248MH0007430021502525C00	2525	15268	2.53	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 01_August_2024

SOL 4248 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Amphiheater_Dome - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4248MH0001680011502527C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4248MH0001530001502536R00	2536	MOTOR COUNT:		14004	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4248MH0001530001502537S00	2537	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Jul-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4248	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4248	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4248MH0001680021502528C00	2528	13932	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
4248MH0001680021502529C00	2529	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
4248MH0001680021502530C00	2530	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
4248MH0001680021502531C00	2531	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
4248MH0001680021502532C00	2532	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4248MH0001680021502533C00	2533	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
4248MH0001680021502534C00	2534	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
4248MH0001680021502535C00	2535	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 01_August_2024

SOL 4250 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Saddlebag_Lake - stereo-1 - ~3 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4250MH0001730011502547C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4251MH0001630001502623R00	2623	MOTOR COUNT:		14330	RANGE (cm):	5.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4251MH0001630001502624S00	2624	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Jul-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4250	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4251		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4250MH0001730021502548C00	2548	14210	5.64	-0.1	0.1	26.8	0.4	255	1
4250MH0001730021502549C00	2549	14240	5.50	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	223	2
4250MH0001730021502550C00	2550	14270	5.35	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	191	3
4250MH0001730021502551C00	2551	14300	5.22	-0.1	0.1	25.3	0.4	159	4
4250MH0001730021502552C00	2552	14330	5.09	-0.1	0.1	24.8	0.4	127	5
4250MH0001730021502553C00	2553	14360	4.96	-0.1	0.1	24.4	0.4	95	6
4250MH0001730021502554C00	2554	14390	4.84	-0.1	0.1	23.9	0.4	63	7
4250MH0001730021502555C00	2555	14420	4.72	-0.1	0.1	23.5	0.3	31	8

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SOL 4250 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Saddlebag_Lake - stereo-2 - ~3 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4250MH0001730011502557C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4251MH0001630001502621R00	2621	MOTOR COUNT:		14332	RANGE (cm):	5.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4251MH0001630001502622S00	2622	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Jul-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4250	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4251		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4250MH0001730021502558C00	2558	14212	5.63	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	255	1
4250MH0001730021502559C00	2559	14242	5.49	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	223	2
4250MH0001730021502560C00	2560	14272	5.35	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	191	3
4250MH0001730021502561C00	2561	14302	5.21	-0.1	0.1	25.2	0.4	159	4
4250MH0001730021502562C00	2562	14332	5.08	-0.1	0.1	24.8	0.4	127	5
4250MH0001730021502563C00	2563	14362	4.95	-0.1	0.1	24.3	0.4	95	6
4250MH0001730021502564C00	2564	14392	4.83	-0.1	0.1	23.9	0.4	63	7
4250MH0001730021502565C00	2565	14422	4.71	-0.1	0.1	23.5	0.3	31	8

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SOL 4250 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4250MH0003360011502569C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4251MH0001630001502619R00	2619	MOTOR COUNT:		13993	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4251MH0001630001502620S00	2620	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Jul-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4250	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4251		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4250MH0003360021502570C00	2570	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
4250MH0003360021502571C00	2571	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
4250MH0003360021502572C00	2572	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
4250MH0003360021502573C00	2573	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4250MH0003360021502574C00	2574	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4250MH0003360021502575C00	2575	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
4250MH0003360021502576C00	2576	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	63	7
4250MH0003360021502577C00	2577	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	31	8

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SOL 4250 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4250MH0003360011502579C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4251MH0001630001502617R00	2617	MOTOR COUNT:		13995	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4251MH0001630001502618S00	2618	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Jul-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4250	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4251		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4250MH0003360021502580C00	2580	13947	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
4250MH0003360021502581C00	2581	13959	7.12	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
4250MH0003360021502582C00	2582	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
4250MH0003360021502583C00	2583	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4250MH0003360021502584C00	2584	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
4250MH0003360021502585C00	2585	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
4250MH0003360021502586C00	2586	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	63	7
4250MH0003360021502587C00	2587	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	31	8

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SOL 4250 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4250MH0008640011502589C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4251MH0001630001502615R00	2615	MOTOR COUNT:		15083	RANGE (cm):	2.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4251MH0001630001502616S00	2616	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00864	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Jul-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4250	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4251		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4250MH0008640021502590C00	2590	14963	3.12	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	255	1
4250MH0008640021502591C00	2591	14993	3.05	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	223	2
4250MH0008640021502592C00	2592	15023	2.99	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	191	3
4250MH0008640021502593C00	2593	15053	2.93	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	159	4
4250MH0008640021502594C00	2594	15083	2.87	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	127	5
4250MH0008640021502595C00	2595	15113	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	95	6
4250MH0008640021502596C00	2596	15143	2.75	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	63	7
4250MH0008640021502597C00	2597	15173	2.70	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	31	8

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SOL 4250 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4250MH0003360011502599C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4251MH0001630001502613R00	2613	MOTOR COUNT:		13987	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4251MH0001630001502614S00	2614	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Jul-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4250	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4251		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4250MH0003360021502600C00	2600	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	255	1
4250MH0003360021502601C00	2601	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
4250MH0003360021502602C00	2602	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
4250MH0003360021502603C00	2603	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
4250MH0003360021502604C00	2604	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
4250MH0003360021502605C00	2605	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	95	6
4250MH0003360021502606C00	2606	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	63	7
4250MH0003360021502607C00	2607	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	31	8

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SOL 4253 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Discovery_Pinnacle - ~25 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4253MH0003590011502626C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4253MH0001930001502659R00	2659	MOTOR COUNT:		13004	RANGE (cm):	27.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4253MH0001930001502660S00	2660	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	24-Jul-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4253	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4253	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4253MH0003590021502627C00	2627	12932	32.81	-2.7	3.1	122.4	10.2	255	1
4253MH0003590021502628C00	2628	12950	31.26	-2.4	2.8	116.9	9.3	223	2
4253MH0003590021502629C00	2629	12968	29.84	-2.2	2.6	111.9	8.4	191	3
4253MH0003590021502630C00	2630	12986	28.54	-2.0	2.3	107.4	7.7	159	4
4253MH0003590021502631C00	2631	13004	27.34	-1.9	2.1	103.1	7.1	127	5
4253MH0003590021502632C00	2632	13022	26.22	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	95	6
4253MH0003590021502633C00	2633	13040	25.19	-1.6	1.8	95.6	6.0	63	7
4253MH0003590021502634C00	2634	13058	24.22	-1.5	1.7	92.2	5.5	31	8

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SOL 4253 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Discovery_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - ~55 mm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4253MH0002240011502636C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4253MH0001930001502657R00	2657	MOTOR COUNT:		13920	RANGE (cm):	7.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4253MH0001930001502658S00	2658	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	24-Jul-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4253	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4253	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4253MH0002240021502637C00	2637	13752	8.81	-0.2	0.2	37.9	0.8	255	1
4253MH0002240021502638C00	2638	13794	8.42	-0.2	0.2	36.5	0.8	223	2
4253MH0002240021502639C00	2639	13836	8.06	-0.2	0.2	35.3	0.7	191	3
4253MH0002240021502640C00	2640	13878	7.72	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	159	4
4253MH0002240021502641C00	2641	13920	7.40	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	127	5
4253MH0002240021502642C00	2642	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	95	6
4253MH0002240021502643C00	2643	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	63	7
4253MH0002240021502644C00	2644	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4253 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Discovery_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - ~6 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4253MH0002240011502646C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4253MH0001930001502655R00	2655	MOTOR COUNT:		13883	RANGE (cm):	7.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4253MH0001930001502656S00	2656	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	24-Jul-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4253	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4253	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4253MH0002240021502647C00	2647	13715	9.18	-0.3	0.3	39.2	0.9	255	1
4253MH0002240021502648C00	2648	13757	8.76	-0.2	0.2	37.7	0.8	223	2
4253MH0002240021502649C00	2649	13799	8.38	-0.2	0.2	36.4	0.8	191	3
4253MH0002240021502650C00	2650	13841	8.02	-0.2	0.2	35.1	0.7	159	4
4253MH0002240021502651C00	2651	13883	7.68	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	127	5
4253MH0002240021502652C00	2652	13925	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	95	6
4253MH0002240021502653C00	2653	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	63	7
4253MH0002240021502654C00	2654	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	31	8

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SOL 4255 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Russell_Pass - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4255MH0003360011502664C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4255MH0001930001502697R00	2697	MOTOR COUNT:		14039	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4255MH0001930001502698S00	2698	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Jul-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4255	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4255	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4255MH0003360021502665C00	2665	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	255	1
4255MH0003360021502666C00	2666	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	223	2
4255MH0003360021502667C00	2667	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	191	3
4255MH0003360021502668C00	2668	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	159	4
4255MH0003360021502669C00	2669	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	127	5
4255MH0003360021502670C00	2670	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	95	6
4255MH0003360021502671C00	2671	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
4255MH0003360021502672C00	2672	14075	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4255 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Russell_Pass - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4255MH0003360011502674C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4255MH0001930001502695R00	2695	MOTOR COUNT:		14038	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4255MH0001930001502696S00	2696	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Jul-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4255	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4255	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4255MH0003360021502675C00	2675	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	255	1
4255MH0003360021502676C00	2676	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	223	2
4255MH0003360021502677C00	2677	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	191	3
4255MH0003360021502678C00	2678	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	159	4
4255MH0003360021502679C00	2679	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	127	5
4255MH0003360021502680C00	2680	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	95	6
4255MH0003360021502681C00	2681	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
4255MH0003360021502682C00	2682	14074	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4255 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Russell_Pass - after DRT - ~5 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4255MH0008480011502684C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4255MH0001930001502693R00	2693	MOTOR COUNT:		15221	RANGE (cm):		2.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4255MH0001930001502694S00	2694	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Jul-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4255		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4255
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4255MH0008480021502685C00	2685	15125	2.79	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	255	1
4255MH0008480021502686C00	2686	15149	2.74	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	223	2
4255MH0008480021502687C00	2687	15173	2.70	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	191	3
4255MH0008480021502688C00	2688	15197	2.65	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	159	4
4255MH0008480021502689C00	2689	15221	2.61	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	127	5
4255MH0008480021502690C00	2690	15245	2.57	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	95	6
4255MH0008480021502691C00	2691	15269	2.53	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	63	7
4255MH0008480021502692C00	2692	15293	2.49	0.0	0.1	15.7	0.2	31	8

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SOL 4257 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Kings_Canyon - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4257MH0003360011502702C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4257MH0001530001502747R00	2747	MOTOR COUNT:		13999	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4257MH0001530001502748S00	2748	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	28-Jul-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4257	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4257	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4257MH0003360021502703C00	2703	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1
4257MH0003360021502704C00	2704	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
4257MH0003360021502705C00	2705	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
4257MH0003360021502706C00	2706	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
4257MH0003360021502707C00	2707	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4257MH0003360021502708C00	2708	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4257MH0003360021502709C00	2709	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	63	7
4257MH0003360021502710C00	2710	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 01_August_2024

SOL 4257 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Kings_Canyon - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4257MH0003360011502712C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4257MH0001530001502745R00	2745	MOTOR COUNT:		14004	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4257MH0001530001502746S00	2746	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	28-Jul-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4257	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4257	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4257MH0003360021502713C00	2713	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	255	1
4257MH0003360021502714C00	2714	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	223	2
4257MH0003360021502715C00	2715	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
4257MH0003360021502716C00	2716	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4257MH0003360021502717C00	2717	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4257MH0003360021502718C00	2718	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4257MH0003360021502719C00	2719	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4257MH0003360021502720C00	2720	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 01_August_2024

SOL 4257 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Kings_Canyon - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4257MH0008640011502722C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4257MH0001530001502743R00	2743	MOTOR COUNT:		15104	RANGE (cm):	2.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4257MH0001530001502744S00	2744	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00864	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	28-Jul-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4257	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4257	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4257MH0008640021502723C00	2723	14984	3.07	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	255	1
4257MH0008640021502724C00	2724	15014	3.01	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	223	2
4257MH0008640021502725C00	2725	15044	2.95	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	191	3
4257MH0008640021502726C00	2726	15074	2.89	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	159	4
4257MH0008640021502727C00	2727	15104	2.83	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	127	5
4257MH0008640021502728C00	2728	15134	2.77	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	95	6
4257MH0008640021502729C00	2729	15164	2.71	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	63	7
4257MH0008640021502730C00	2730	15194	2.66	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 01_August_2024

SOL 4257 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Kings_Canyon - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4257MH0003360011502732C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4257MH0001530001502741R00	2741	MOTOR COUNT:		13990	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4257MH0001530001502742S00	2742	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	28-Jul-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4257	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4257	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4257MH0003360021502733C00	2733	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
4257MH0003360021502734C00	2734	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
4257MH0003360021502735C00	2735	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4257MH0003360021502736C00	2736	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
4257MH0003360021502737C00	2737	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4257MH0003360021502738C00	2738	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
4257MH0003360021502739C00	2739	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	63	7
4257MH0003360021502740C00	2740	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	31	8

6 Image comment, purpose, RATIONALE_DESC

A RATIONALE_DESC accompanies each MAHLI image and each focus merge product archived with the NASA PDS. It is found in in each archived image label file (.LBL).

The RATIONALE_DESC is a text description of the purpose (rationale) behind the acquisition of each MAHLI parent image.

For onboard focus merge products, the RATIONALE_DESC includes information regarding when the merge was performed and which parent images were merged. This information is not automatically tracked by the instrument or ground data system and thus requires human intervention; this is the only pathway by which this information is conveyed to the data user through the NASA PDS archival products.

The MAHLI Team drafts each RATIONALE_DESC as the data are acquired and returned to Earth. Final editing of each RATIONALE_DESC is performed a few months before the data are archived with the NASA PDS. In some cases, an error might be detected in a RATIONALE_DESC some time after the data are first archived; in such a case, the corrections are made in a later release of MAHLI data to the PDS (as long as the mission continues and funding is available to do so).

The pages that follow capture the RATIONALE_DESC for each MAHLI image acquired and lists the ID for the best available image or focus merge product returned to Earth. Note that the RATIONALE_DESC also applies to any other child images spawned by a given parent image and thus there might be additional images, not listed here, that correspond to a given RATIONALE_DESC. In some cases, it was only necessary to return a thumbnail image; the IDs for these are given in orange text. As noted earlier, purple text indicates Image IDs for which the last two characters might differ from those in the NASA PDS archives.

Note that the text on the pages that follow is tiny. We highly recommend that the reader view this document electronically (*i.e.*, PDF file on a computer screen) and magnify the view $\geq 400\%$.

The *MAHLI Image Comment Sheets* that follow include data acquired Sol 4134–4257. During this period, the instrument obtained images and/or performed focus merges on **Sols 4134, 4135, 4137, 4139, 4141, 4142, 4144, 4146, 4148, 4152, 4154, 4155, 4157, 4158, 4159, 4160, 4161, 4162, 4164, 4166, 4168, 4169, 4173, 4174, 4175, 4176, 4178, 4180, 4182, 4183, 4184, 4185, 4186, 4187, 4191, 4193, 4196, 4197, 4199, 4200, 4202, 4205, 4206, 4207, 4208, 4209, 4210, 4212, 4216, 4234, 4235, 4236, 4237, 4239, 4240, 4241, 4243, 4244, 4246, 4248, 4250, 4251, 4253, 4255, 4257.**

updated: 28_March_2024

Sol 4134 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	23-Mar-24
camera position	95
total parent images	95
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	95

MAHLI imaged the targets Thompson_Canyon, Cabin_Lake and Smoky_Jack.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN00855	Thompson_Canyon ~25 cm standoff	4134MH000855002904766C00	4766	autofocus sub-frame for target Thompson_Canyon - standoff near 25 cm		
		4134MH0008550010904767C00	4767	target Thompson_Canyon - standoff near 25 cm		
		4134MH000855002904768C00	4768	target Thompson_Canyon - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4134MH000855002904769C00	4769	target Thompson_Canyon - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4134MH000855002904770C00	4770	target Thompson_Canyon - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4134MH000855002904771C00	4771	target Thompson_Canyon - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4134MH000855002904772C00	4772	target Thompson_Canyon - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4134MH000855002904773C00	4773	target Thompson_Canyon - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4134MH000855002904774C00	4774	target Thompson_Canyon - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4134MH000855002904775C00	4775	target Thompson_Canyon - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00299	Thompson_Canyon Stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4134MH000299002904776C00	4776	autofocus sub-frame for target Thompson_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
				4134MH0002990010904777C00	4777	target Thompson_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
				4134MH000299002904778C00	4778	target Thompson_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4134MH000299002904779C00	4779	target Thompson_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
4134MH000299002904780C00	4780			target Thompson_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4134MH000299002904781C00	4781			target Thompson_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4134MH000299002904782C00	4782			target Thompson_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4134MH000299002904783C00	4783			target Thompson_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4134MH000299002904784C00	4784			target Thompson_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4134MH000299002904785C00	4785			target Thompson_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00299	Thompson_Canyon Stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff			4134MH000299002904786C00	4786	autofocus sub-frame for target Thompson_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				4134MH0002990010904787C00	4787	target Thompson_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				4134MH000299002904788C00	4788	target Thompson_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4134MH000299002904789C00	4789	target Thompson_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4134MH000299002904790C00	4790	target Thompson_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4134MH000299002904791C00	4791	target Thompson_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4134MH000299002904792C00	4792	target Thompson_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4134MH000299002904793C00	4793	target Thompson_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4134MH000299002904794C00	4794	target Thompson_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4134MH000299002904795C00	4795	target Thompson_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00855	Cabin_Lake ~23 cm standoff	4134MH000855002904796C00	4796	autofocus sub-frame for target Cabin_Lake - standoff near 23 cm
				4134MH0008550010904797C00	4797	target Cabin_Lake - standoff near 23 cm
				4134MH000855002904798C00	4798	target Cabin_Lake - standoff near 23 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4134MH000855002904799C00	4799	target Cabin_Lake - standoff near 23 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
4134MH000855002904800C00	4800			target Cabin_Lake - standoff near 23 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4134MH000855002904801C00	4801			target Cabin_Lake - standoff near 23 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4134MH000855002904802C00	4802			target Cabin_Lake - standoff near 23 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4134MH000855002904803C00	4803			target Cabin_Lake - standoff near 23 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4134MH000855002904804C00	4804			target Cabin_Lake - standoff near 23 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4134MH000855002904805C00	4805			target Cabin_Lake - standoff near 23 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00224	Cabin_Lake Stereo-1 ~35 mm standoff			4134MH000224002904806C00	4806	autofocus sub-frame for target Cabin_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
				4134MH0002240010904807C00	4807	target Cabin_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
				4134MH000224002904808C00	4808	target Cabin_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4134MH000224002904809C00	4809	target Cabin_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4134MH000224002904810C00	4810	target Cabin_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4134MH000224002904811C00	4811	target Cabin_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4134MH000224002904812C00	4812	target Cabin_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4134MH000224002904813C00	4813	target Cabin_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4134MH000224002904814C00	4814	target Cabin_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4134MH000224002904815C00	4815	target Cabin_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00224	Cabin_Lake Stereo-2 ~35 mm standoff	4134MH000224002904816C00	4816	autofocus sub-frame for target Cabin_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
				4134MH0002240010904817C00	4817	target Cabin_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
				4134MH000224002904818C00	4818	target Cabin_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4134MH000224002904819C00	4819	target Cabin_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
4134MH000224002904820C00	4820			target Cabin_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4134MH000224002904821C00	4821			target Cabin_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4134MH000224002904822C00	4822			target Cabin_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4134MH000224002904823C00	4823			target Cabin_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4134MH000224002904824C00	4824			target Cabin_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4134MH000224002904825C00	4825			target Cabin_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

Continued on Next Page...

mH00865	Smoky_Jack ~24 cm standoff	413MH00865000904826C00	4236	autofocus sub-frame for target Smoky_Jack - standoff near 24 cm
		413MH008650010904827C00	4237	target Smoky_Jack - standoff near 24 cm
		413MH00865000904828C00	4238	target Smoky_Jack - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		413MH008650020904829C00	4239	target Smoky_Jack - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		413MH00865000904830C00	4230	target Smoky_Jack - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		413MH008650020904831C00	4231	target Smoky_Jack - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		413MH00865000904832C00	4232	target Smoky_Jack - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		413MH008650020904833C00	4233	target Smoky_Jack - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		413MH00865000904834C00	4234	target Smoky_Jack - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
413MH008650020904835C00	4235	target Smoky_Jack - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mH00841	Smoky_Jack stereo-1 ~14 cm standoff	413MH008410003084836C00	4236	autofocus sub-frame for target Smoky_Jack - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm
		413MH00841001084837C00	4237	target Smoky_Jack - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm
		413MH008410003084838C00	4238	target Smoky_Jack - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		413MH00841002084839C00	4239	target Smoky_Jack - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		413MH008410003084840C00	4240	target Smoky_Jack - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		413MH00841002084841C00	4241	target Smoky_Jack - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		413MH008410003084842C00	4242	target Smoky_Jack - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		413MH00841002084843C00	4243	target Smoky_Jack - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		413MH008410003084844C00	4244	target Smoky_Jack - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
413MH00841002084845C00	4245	target Smoky_Jack - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mH00841	Smoky_Jack stereo-2 ~14 cm standoff	413MH008410003084846C00	4246	autofocus sub-frame for target Smoky_Jack - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm
		413MH00841001084847C00	4247	target Smoky_Jack - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm
		413MH008410003084848C00	4248	target Smoky_Jack - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		413MH00841002084849C00	4249	target Smoky_Jack - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		413MH008410003084850C00	4250	target Smoky_Jack - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		413MH008410020704851C00	4251	target Smoky_Jack - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		413MH008410003084852C00	4252	target Smoky_Jack - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		413MH008410020704853C00	4253	target Smoky_Jack - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		413MH008410003084854C00	4254	target Smoky_Jack - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
413MH008410020904855C00	4255	target Smoky_Jack - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 25_March_2024

Sol 4135 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	24-Mar-24
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	9
total focus merge products	18
total parent images + focus merge products	18

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4134 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00536	Focus Merges	4135MH00536000504856R00	4856	target Smoky_Jack - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4134 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4848-4855 - best focus image product
		4135MH00536000504857S00	4857	target Smoky_Jack - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4134 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4848-4855 - range map product
		4135MH00536000504858R00	4858	target Smoky_Jack - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4134 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4838-4845 - best focus image product
		4135MH00536000504859S00	4859	target Smoky_Jack - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4134 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4838-4845 - range map product
		4135MH00536000504860R00	4860	target Smoky_Jack - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4134 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4828-4835 - best focus image product
		4135MH00536000504861S00	4861	target Smoky_Jack - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4134 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4828-4835 - range map product
		4135MH00536000504862R00	4862	target Cabin_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4134 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4818-4825 - best focus image product
		4135MH00536000504863S00	4863	target Cabin_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4134 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4818-4825 - range map product
		4135MH00536000504864R00	4864	target Cabin_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4134 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4808-4815 - best focus image product
		4135MH00536000504865S00	4865	target Cabin_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4134 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4808-4815 - range map product
		4135MH00536000504866R00	4866	target Cabin_Lake - standoff near 23 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4134 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4798-4805 - best focus image product
		4135MH00536000504867S00	4867	target Cabin_Lake - standoff near 23 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4134 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4798-4805 - range map product
		4135MH00536000504868R00	4868	target Thompson_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4134 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4788-4795 - best focus image product
		4135MH00536000504869S00	4869	target Thompson_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4134 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4788-4795 - range map product
		4135MH00536000504870R00	4870	target Thompson_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4134 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4778-4785 - best focus image product
		4135MH00536000504871S00	4871	target Thompson_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4134 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4778-4785 - range map product
		4135MH00536000504872R00	4872	target Thompson_Canyon - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4134 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4768-4775 - best focus image product
		4135MH00536000504873S00	4873	target Thompson_Canyon - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4134 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4768-4775 - range map product

updated: 01_April_2024

Sol 4137 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	26-Mar-24	
		camera position:	4	Image ID:
		total parent images:	33	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed:	3	CPDPID:
		total focus merge products:	6	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products:	39	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Sunrise_Lakes and the focus stack images were merged. MAHLI Images that correspond to CPDPID: 1 through 3479 (data from Sols 3803-4005) were deleted from the MAHLI DEA non-volatile memory storage.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL: DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Sunrise_Lakes after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4137MH00190002050487420D	4874	autoFocus sub-frame for target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		4137MH00190001050487520D	4875	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mN00168	Sunrise_Lakes after DRT stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4137MH00168002050487620D	4876	autoFocus sub-frame for target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4137MH00168001050487720D	4877	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4137MH00168002050487820D	4878	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4137MH00168001050487920D	4879	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4137MH00168002050488020D	4880	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4137MH00168001050488120D	4881	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4137MH00168002050488220D	4882	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4137MH00168001050488320D	4883	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4137MH00168002050488420D	4884	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4137MH00168001050488520D	4885	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Sunrise_Lakes after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4137MH00168002050488620D	4886	autoFocus sub-frame for target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4137MH00168001050488720D	4887	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4137MH00168002050488820D	4888	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4137MH00168001050488920D	4889	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4137MH00168002050489020D	4890	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4137MH00168001050489120D	4891	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4137MH00168002050489220D	4892	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4137MH00168001050489320D	4893	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4137MH00168002050489420D	4894	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4137MH00168001050489520D	4895	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00302	Sunrise_Lakes after DRT ~15 mm standoff	4137MH00302002050489620D	4896	autoFocus sub-frame for target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		4137MH00302001050489720D	4897	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		4137MH00302002050489820D	4898	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4137MH00302001050489920D	4899	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4137MH00302002050490020D	4900	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4137MH00302001050490120D	4901	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4137MH00302002050490220D	4902	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4137MH00302001050490320D	4903	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4137MH00302002050490420D	4904	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4137MH00302001050490520D	4905	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00193	Focus Merges	4137MH001930020409060D	4906	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4137 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4898-4901 - best focus image product
		4137MH0019300040490750D	4907	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4137 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4898-4905 - range map product
		4137MH001930020409080D	4908	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4137 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4898-4895 - best focus image product
		4137MH0019300030490900D	4909	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4137 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4898-4895 - range map product
		4137MH0019300030491000D	4910	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4137 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4878-4883 - best focus image product
		4137MH0019300030491150D	4911	target Sunrise_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4137 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4878-4885 - range map product

updated: 29_March_2024

Sol 4139 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	28-Mar-24
camera position	13
total parent images	45
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	53

MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Rainbow_Falls and MAHLI imaged the target Rancheria_Falls, which included a full run of the MAHLI proximity mode, a new capability that uses MAHLI onboard range-finding to guide MAHLI closer to the surface. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Rainbow_Falls after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4139MH00190001160001C00	1	autofocus sub-frame for target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		4139MH00190001150002C00	2	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mN00168	Rainbow_Falls after DRT stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4139MH00168001150003C00	3	autofocus sub-frame for target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4139MH00168001150004C00	4	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4139MH00168001150005C00	5	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4139MH00168001150006C00	6	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4139MH00168001150007C00	7	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4139MH00168001150008C00	8	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4139MH00168001150009C00	9	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4139MH00168001150010C00	10	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4139MH00168001150011C00	11	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4139MH00168001150012C00	12	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Rainbow_Falls after DRT stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4139MH00168001150013C00	13	autofocus sub-frame for target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4139MH00168001150014C00	14	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4139MH00168001150015C00	15	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4139MH00168001150016C00	16	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4139MH00168001150017C00	17	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4139MH00168001150018C00	18	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4139MH00168001150019C00	19	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4139MH00168001150020C00	20	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4139MH00168001150021C00	21	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4139MH00168001150022C00	22	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00864	Rainbow_Falls after DRT ~1 cm standoff	4139MH000864001150023C00	23	autofocus sub-frame for target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4139MH000864001150024C00	24	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4139MH000864001150025C00	25	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4139MH000864001150026C00	26	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4139MH000864001150027C00	27	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4139MH000864001150028C00	28	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4139MH000864001150029C00	29	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4139MH000864001150030C00	30	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4139MH000864001150031C00	31	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4139MH000864001150032C00	32	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00866	Rancheria_Falls MAHLI prox mode ~4 cm standoff	4139MH000866001150033C00	33	autofocus sub-frame for target Rancheria_Falls - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 4 cm
		4139MH000866001150034C00	34	target Rancheria_Falls - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 4 cm
mN00867	Rancheria_Falls MAHLI prox mode ~4 cm standoff	4139MH000867001150035C00	35	autofocus sub-frame for target Rancheria_Falls - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 4 cm
		4139MH000867001150036C00	36	target Rancheria_Falls - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 4 cm
mN00868	Rancheria_Falls MAHLI prox mode ~3 cm standoff	4139MH000868001150037C00	37	autofocus sub-frame for target Rancheria_Falls - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 3 cm
		4139MH000868001150038C00	38	target Rancheria_Falls - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 3 cm
mN00869	Rancheria_Falls MAHLI prox mode ~2 cm standoff	4139MH000869001150039C00	39	autofocus sub-frame for target Rancheria_Falls - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 2 cm
		4139MH000869001150040C00	40	target Rancheria_Falls - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 2 cm
mN00870	Rancheria_Falls MAHLI prox mode ~15 mm standoff	4139MH000870001150041C00	41	autofocus sub-frame for target Rancheria_Falls - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 15 mm
		4139MH000870001150042C00	42	target Rancheria_Falls - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 15 mm
mN00871	Rancheria_Falls MAHLI prox mode ~1 cm standoff	4139MH000871001150043C00	43	autofocus sub-frame for target Rancheria_Falls - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 1 cm
		4139MH000871001150044C00	44	target Rancheria_Falls - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 1 cm
mN00190	Rainbow_Falls ~24 cm standoff	4139MH00190001150045C00	45	autofocus sub-frame for target Rainbow_Falls - standoff near 24 cm
		4139MH00190001150046C00	46	target Rainbow_Falls - standoff near 24 cm
mN00193	Focus Merges	4139MH00193001150047R00	47	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4139 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 21-30 - best focus image product
		4139MH00193001150048S00	48	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4139 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 25-32 - range map product
		4139MH00193001150049W00	49	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4139 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 15-22 - best focus image product
		4139MH00193001150050S00	50	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4139 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 15-22 - range map product
		4139MH00193001150051W00	51	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4139 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3-12 - best focus image product
		4139MH00193001150052S00	52	target Rainbow_Falls - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4139 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 5-12 - range map product

updated: 28_June_2024

Sol 4141 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	31-Mar-24
camera position	85
total parent images	85
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	85

MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Rose_Lake, the target Whorl_Mountain and the target Little_Slide_Canyon.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00290	Rose_Lake after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4141MH00190000115009530D	53	autofocus sub-frame for target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4141MH0019000115009540D	54	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00268	Rose_Lake after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4141MH00168000115009550D	55	autofocus sub-frame for target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4141MH0016800115009560D	56	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4141MH00168002115009570D	57	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH00168003115009580D	58	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH00168004115009590D	59	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH00168005115009600D	60	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH00168006115009610D	61	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH00168007115009620D	62	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH00168008115009630D	63	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH00168009115009640D	64	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00268	Rose_Lake after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4141MH00168000115009650D	65	autofocus sub-frame for target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4141MH0016800115009660D	66	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4141MH00168002115009670D	67	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH00168003115009680D	68	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH00168004115009690D	69	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH00168005115009700D	70	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH00168006115009710D	71	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH00168007115009720D	72	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH00168008115009730D	73	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH00168009115009740D	74	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00274	Rose_Lake after DRT ~1 cm standoff	4141MH000743000115009750D	75	autofocus sub-frame for target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4141MH00074300115009760D	76	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4141MH000743002115009770D	77	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000743003115009780D	78	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000743004115009790D	79	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000743005115009800D	80	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000743006115009810D	81	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000743007115009820D	82	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000743008115009830D	83	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000743009115009840D	84	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00865	Whorl_Mountain stereo-1 ~23 cm standoff	4141MH00086500115009850D	85	autofocus sub-frame for target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 23 cm
		4141MH000865002115009860D	86	target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 23 cm
		4141MH000865003115009870D	87	target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 23 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000865004115009880D	88	target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 23 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000865005115009890D	89	target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 23 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000865006115009900D	90	target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 23 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000865007115009910D	91	target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 23 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000865008115009920D	92	target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 23 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000865009115009930D	93	target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 23 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000865010115009940D	94	target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 23 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00865	Whorl_Mountain stereo-2 ~23 cm standoff	4141MH00086500115009950D	95	autofocus sub-frame for target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 23 cm
		4141MH000865002115009960D	96	target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 23 cm
		4141MH000865003115009970D	97	target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 23 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000865004115009980D	98	target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 23 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000865005115009990D	99	target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 23 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000865010115001000D	100	target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 23 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH00086501115001010D	101	target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 23 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000865012115001020D	102	target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 23 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000865013115001030D	103	target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 23 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000865014115001040D	104	target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 23 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00865	Whorl_Mountain stereo-3 ~23 cm standoff	4141MH00086500115001050D	105	autofocus sub-frame for target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-3 - standoff near 23 cm
		4141MH000865002115001060D	106	target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-3 - standoff near 23 cm
		4141MH000865003115001070D	107	target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-3 - standoff near 23 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000865004115001080D	108	target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-3 - standoff near 23 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000865005115001090D	109	target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-3 - standoff near 23 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000865006115001100D	110	target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-3 - standoff near 23 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000865007115001110D	111	target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-3 - standoff near 23 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000865008115001120D	112	target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-3 - standoff near 23 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000865009115001130D	113	target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-3 - standoff near 23 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000865010115001140D	114	target Whorl_Mountain - stereo-3 - standoff near 23 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

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mH00190	Little_Slide_Canyon ~23 cm standoff	4141MH000190001500115C00	115	autofocus sub-frame for target Little_Slide_Canyon - standoff near 23 cm
		4141MH000190001500116C00	116	target Little_Slide_Canyon - standoff near 23 cm
mH00224	Little_Slide_Canyon stereo-1 ~3 cm standoff	4141MH000240001500117C00	117	autofocus sub-frame for target Little_Slide_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm
		4141MH000240001500118C00	118	target Little_Slide_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm
		4141MH000240001500119C00	119	target Little_Slide_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000240001500120C00	120	target Little_Slide_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000240001500121C00	121	target Little_Slide_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000240001500122C00	122	target Little_Slide_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000240001500123C00	123	target Little_Slide_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000240001500124C00	124	target Little_Slide_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000240001500125C00	125	target Little_Slide_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000240001500126C00	126	target Little_Slide_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mH00224	Little_Slide_Canyon stereo-2 ~3 cm standoff	4141MH000240001500127C00	127	autofocus sub-frame for target Little_Slide_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm
		4141MH000240001500128C00	128	target Little_Slide_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm
		4141MH000240001500129C00	129	target Little_Slide_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000240001500130C00	130	target Little_Slide_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000240001500131C00	131	target Little_Slide_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000240001500132C00	132	target Little_Slide_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000240001500133C00	133	target Little_Slide_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000240001500134C00	134	target Little_Slide_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000240001500135C00	135	target Little_Slide_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4141MH000240001500136C00	136	target Little_Slide_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 08_August_2024

Sol 4142 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	31-Mar-24
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	8
total focus merge products	16
total parent images + focus merge products	16

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4141 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00170	Focus Merges	4142MH001700001500137900	137	target Little_Slide_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4141 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 129-136 - best focus image product
		4142MH001700001500138500	138	target Little_Slide_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4141 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 129-136 - range map product
		4142MH001700001500139900	139	target Little_Slide_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4141 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 119-126 - best focus image product
		4142MH001700001500140500	140	target Little_Slide_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4141 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 119-126 - range map product
		4142MH001700001500141900	141	target Whori_Mountain - stereo-3 - standoff near 23 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4141 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 107-114 - best focus image product
		4142MH001700001500142500	142	target Whori_Mountain - stereo-3 - standoff near 23 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4141 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 107-114 - range map product
		4142MH001700001500143900	143	target Whori_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 23 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4141 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 97-104 - best focus image product
		4142MH001700001500144500	144	target Whori_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 23 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4141 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 97-104 - range map product
		4142MH001700001500145900	145	target Whori_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 23 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4141 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 87-94 - best focus image product
		4142MH001700001500146500	146	target Whori_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 23 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4141 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 87-94 - range map product
		4142MH001700001500147900	147	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4141 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 77-84 - best focus image product
		4142MH001700001500148500	148	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4141 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 77-84 - range map product
		4142MH001700001500149900	149	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4141 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 67-74 - best focus image product
		4142MH001700001500150500	150	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4141 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 67-74 - range map product
		4142MH001700001500151900	151	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4141 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 57-64 - best focus image product
		4142MH001700001500152500	152	target Rose_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4141 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 57-64 - range map product

updated: 28_June_2024

Sol 4144 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	8 Apr 24
camera position	2
total parent images	35
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the target Bodie and the focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN00855	Bodie ~24 cm standoff	4144MH00085500115001330D	153	autoFocus sub-frame for target Bodie - standoff near 24 cm		
		4144MH00085500115001540D	154	target Bodie - standoff near 24 cm		
		4144MH00085500115001550D	155	target Bodie - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4144MH00085500115001560D	156	target Bodie - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4144MH00085500115001570D	157	target Bodie - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4144MH00085500115001580D	158	target Bodie - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4144MH00085500115001590D	159	target Bodie - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4144MH00085500115001600D	160	target Bodie - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4144MH00085500115001610D	161	target Bodie - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4144MH00085500115001620D	162	target Bodie - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00297	Bodie stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4144MH00029700115001630D	163	autoFocus sub-frame for target Bodie - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
				4144MH00029700115001640D	164	target Bodie - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
				4144MH00029700115001650D	165	target Bodie - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4144MH00029700115001660D	166	target Bodie - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
4144MH00029700115001670D	167			target Bodie - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4144MH00029700115001680D	168			target Bodie - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4144MH00029700115001690D	169			target Bodie - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4144MH00029700115001700D	170			target Bodie - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4144MH00029700115001710D	171			target Bodie - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4144MH00029700115001720D	172			target Bodie - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00297	Bodie stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff			4144MH00029700115001730D	173	autoFocus sub-frame for target Bodie - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
				4144MH00029700115001740D	174	target Bodie - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
				4144MH00029700115001750D	175	target Bodie - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4144MH00029700115001760D	176	target Bodie - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4144MH00029700115001770D	177	target Bodie - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4144MH00029700115001780D	178	target Bodie - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4144MH00029700115001790D	179	target Bodie - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4144MH00029700115001800D	180	target Bodie - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4144MH00029700115001810D	181	target Bodie - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4144MH00029700115001820D	182	target Bodie - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00189	Focus Merges	4144MH00019300115001830D	183	target Bodie - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4144 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 175-182 - best focus image product
				4144MH000193001150018450D	184	target Bodie - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4144 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 175-182 - range map product
				4144MH000193001150018590D	185	target Bodie - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4144 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 165-172 - best focus image product
				4144MH000193001150018650D	186	target Bodie - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4144 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 165-172 - range map product
4144MH000193001150018790D	187			target Bodie - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4144 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 155-162 - best focus image product		
4144MH000193001150018850D	188			target Bodie - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4144 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 155-162 - range map product		

Sol 4146 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	5 Apr 24
camera position	6
total parent images	41
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	47

MAHLI imaged the DRT brushed target Ruby_Peak as well as the MAHLI and APXS calibration targets. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_E_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Ruby_Peak after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4146MH0019000015001890C0	189	autofocus sub-frame for target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4146MH0019000115001900C0	190	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Ruby_Peak after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4146MH0016800015001910C0	191	autofocus sub-frame for target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4146MH0016800115001920C0	192	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4146MH0016800215001930C0	193	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4146MH0016800315001940C0	194	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4146MH0016800415001950C0	195	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4146MH0016800515001960C0	196	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4146MH0016800615001970C0	197	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4146MH0016800715001980C0	198	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4146MH0016800815001990C0	199	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4146MH0016800915002000C0	200	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Ruby_Peak after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4146MH0016800015002010C0	201	autofocus sub-frame for target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4146MH0016800115002020C0	202	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4146MH0016800215002030C0	203	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4146MH0016800315002040C0	204	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4146MH0016800415002050C0	205	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4146MH0016800515002060C0	206	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4146MH0016800615002070C0	207	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4146MH0016800715002080C0	208	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4146MH0016800815002090C0	209	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4146MH0016800915002100C0	210	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00302	Ruby_Peak after DRT ~2 cm standoff	4146MH0030200015002110C0	211	autofocus sub-frame for target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		4146MH0030200115002120C0	212	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		4146MH0030200215002130C0	213	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4146MH0030200315002140C0	214	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4146MH0030200415002150C0	215	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4146MH0030200515002160C0	216	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4146MH0030200615002170C0	217	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4146MH0030200715002180C0	218	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4146MH0030200815002190C0	219	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4146MH0030200915002200C0	220	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00371	MAHLI cal target - centered on bar target ~5 cm working distance	4146MH0037100015002210C0	221	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target - bar target - near 5 cm working distance
		4146MH0037100115002220C0	222	MAHLI calibration target - bar target - near 5 cm working distance
mN00372	MAHLI cal target - centered on cent target ~5 cm working distance	4146MH0037200015002230C0	223	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target - cent target - near 5 cm working distance
		4146MH0037200115002240C0	224	MAHLI calibration target - cent target - near 5 cm working distance
mN00374	MAHLI cal target = wheel + surface 30 cm working distance from target	4146MH0037400015002250C0	225	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - focus on calibration target
		4146MH0037400115002260C0	226	MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - focus on calibration target
		4146MH0037400215002270C0	227	MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - manual focus at infinity
mN00373	APXS cal target ~5 cm standoff	4146MH0037300015002280C0	228	autofocus sub-frame for APXS calibration target - standoff near 5 cm
		4146MH0037300115002290C0	229	APXS calibration target - standoff near 5 cm
mN00193	Focus Merges	4146MH0019300015002300C0	230	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4146 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 213-220 - best focus image product
		4146MH0019300115002310C0	231	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4146 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 213-220 - range map product
		4146MH0019300215002320C0	232	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4146 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 203-210 - best focus image product
		4146MH0019300315002330C0	233	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4146 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 203-210 - range map product
		4146MH0019300415002340C0	234	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4146 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 193-200 - best focus image product
4146MH0019300515002350C0	235	target Ruby_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4146 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 193-200 - range map product		

Sol 4148 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	7 Apr 24
camera position	6
total parent images	33
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the DRT brushed target Alwahnee and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL, DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002190	Alwahnee after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4148MH001900011500236C0D	236	autoFocus sub-frame for target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		4148MH001900011500237C0D	237	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mN002196	Alwahnee after DRT stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4148MH003360011500238C0D	238	autoFocus sub-frame for target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4148MH003360011500239C0D	239	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4148MH0033600211500240C0D	240	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4148MH0033600211500241C0D	241	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4148MH0033600211500242C0D	242	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4148MH0033600211500243C0D	243	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4148MH0033600211500244C0D	244	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4148MH0033600211500245C0D	245	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4148MH0033600211500246C0D	246	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4148MH0033600211500247C0D	247	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002196	Alwahnee after DRT stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4148MH003360011500248C0D	248	autoFocus sub-frame for target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4148MH003360011500249C0D	249	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4148MH0033600211500250C0D	250	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4148MH0033600211500251C0D	251	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4148MH0033600211500252C0D	252	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4148MH0033600211500253C0D	253	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4148MH0033600211500254C0D	254	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4148MH0033600211500255C0D	255	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4148MH0033600211500256C0D	256	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4148MH0033600211500257C0D	257	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002196	Alwahnee after DRT ~5 mm standoff	4148MH0008640011500258C0D	258	autoFocus sub-frame for target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		4148MH0008640011500259C0D	259	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		4148MH00086400211500260C0D	260	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4148MH00086400211500261C0D	261	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4148MH00086400211500262C0D	262	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4148MH00086400211500263C0D	263	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4148MH00086400211500264C0D	264	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4148MH00086400211500265C0D	265	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4148MH00086400211500266C0D	266	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4148MH00086400211500267C0D	267	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002199	Focus Merges	4148MH001930011500268R0D	268	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4148 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 260-267 - best focus image product
		4148MH001930011500269R0D	269	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4148 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 260-267 - range map product
		4148MH001930011500270R0D	270	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4148 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 250-257 - best focus image product
		4148MH001930011500271S0D	271	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4148 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 250-257 - range map product
		4148MH001930011500272R0D	272	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4148 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 240-247 - best focus image product
		4148MH001930011500273S0D	273	target Alwahnee - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4148 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 240-247 - range map product

updated: 01_July_2024

Sol 4152 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)		11-Apr-24		
camera positions		4		
total parent images		33		
focus merges performed		3		
total focus merge products		6		
total parent images + focus merge products		39		
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT brushed target Burro_Pass and the focus stack images were merged.				
Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received				
CPDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002190	Burro_Pass after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4152MH001900001500274200	274	autoFocus sub-frame for target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4152MH0019000150027500	275	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN002196	Burro_Pass after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4152MH003360001500276000	276	autoFocus sub-frame for target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4152MH00336001500277000	277	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4152MH003360021500278000	278	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4152MH003360021500279000	279	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4152MH003360021500280000	280	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4152MH003360021500281000	281	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4152MH003360021500282000	282	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4152MH003360021500283000	283	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4152MH003360021500284000	284	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4152MH003360021500285000	285	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002196	Burro_Pass after DRT stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4152MH003360001500286000	286	autoFocus sub-frame for target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4152MH00336001500287000	287	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4152MH003360021500288000	288	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4152MH003360021500289000	289	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4152MH003360021500290000	290	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4152MH003360021500291000	291	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4152MH003360021500292000	292	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4152MH003360021500293000	293	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4152MH003360021500294000	294	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4152MH003360021500295000	295	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002848	Burro_Pass after DRT ~1 cm standoff	4152MH008480001500296000	296	autoFocus sub-frame for target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4152MH00848001500297000	297	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4152MH008480021500298000	298	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4152MH008480021500299000	299	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4152MH008480021500300000	300	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4152MH008480021500301000	301	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4152MH008480021500302000	302	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4152MH008480021500303000	303	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4152MH008480021500304000	304	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4152MH008480021500305000	305	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002193	Focus Merges	4152MH001930001500306000	306	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4152 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 298-305 - best focus image product
		4152MH001930001500307000	307	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4152 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 298-305 - range map product
		4152MH001930001500308000	308	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4152 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 288-295 - best focus image product
		4152MH001930001500309000	309	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4152 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 288-295 - range map product
		4152MH001930001500310000	310	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4152 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 278-285 - best focus image product
		4152MH001930001500311000	311	target Burro_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4152 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 278-285 - range map product

updated: 28_June_2024

Sol 4154 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	19-Apr-24	
		camera position	55	Image ID:
		total parent images	0	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	0	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in POS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	55	
summary of MAHLI activities				
MAHLI images of the DRT brushed target Hetch_Hetchy. Another test to see how the performance of the DRT compares at different distances above the surface of a target was done on the target Hetch_Hetchy. The DRT was used to brush the target Hetch_Hetchy at the height of 19 mm standoff, 17 mm standoff and the standard height of 15 mm standoff. MAHLI was used to document the surface before it was brushed and after the three brush events.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00586	Hetch_Hetchy before DRT ~15 cm standoff	4154MH000586000150031200	312	autofocus sub-frame for target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 cm
		4154MH000586001500313000	313	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 cm
mN00122	Hetch_Hetchy before DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4154MH000122001500314000	314	autofocus sub-frame for target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4154MH000122001500315000	315	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00122	Hetch_Hetchy before DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4154MH000122001500316000	316	autofocus sub-frame for target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4154MH000122001500317000	317	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00586	after DRT from height of 19 mm standoff ~15 cm standoff	4154MH000586000150031800	318	autofocus sub-frame for target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from a height of 19 mm standoff - standoff near 15 cm
		4154MH000586001500319000	319	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from a height of 19 mm standoff - standoff near 15 cm
mN00122	after DRT from height of 19 mm standoff - stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4154MH000122001500320000	320	autofocus sub-frame for target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from a height of 19 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4154MH000122001500321000	321	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from a height of 19 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00122	after DRT from height of 19 mm standoff - stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4154MH000122001500322000	322	autofocus sub-frame for target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from a height of 19 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4154MH000122001500323000	323	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from a height of 19 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00586	after DRT from height of 17 mm standoff ~15 cm standoff	4154MH000586000150032400	324	autofocus sub-frame for target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from a height of 17 mm standoff - standoff near 15 cm
		4154MH000586001500325000	325	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from a height of 17 mm standoff - standoff near 15 cm
mN00122	after DRT from height of 17 mm standoff - stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4154MH000122001500326000	326	autofocus sub-frame for target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from a height of 17 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4154MH000122001500327000	327	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from a height of 17 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00122	after DRT from height of 17 mm standoff - stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4154MH000122001500328000	328	autofocus sub-frame for target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from a height of 17 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4154MH000122001500329000	329	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from a height of 17 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00586	Hetch_Hetchy after DRT ~15 cm standoff	4154MH000586000150033000	330	autofocus sub-frame for target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - standoff near 15 cm
		4154MH000586001500331000	331	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - standoff near 15 cm
mN00168	Hetch_Hetchy after DRT from height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4154MH000168000150033200	332	autofocus sub-frame for target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4154MH000168001500333000	333	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4154MH000168002150033400	334	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4154MH000168003150033500	335	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4154MH000168004150033600	336	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4154MH000168005150033700	337	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4154MH000168006150033800	338	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4154MH000168007150033900	339	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4154MH000168008150034000	340	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4154MH000168009150034100	341	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Hetch_Hetchy after DRT from height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4154MH000168000150034200	342	autofocus sub-frame for target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4154MH000168001150034300	343	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4154MH000168002150034400	344	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4154MH000168003150034500	345	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4154MH000168004150034600	346	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4154MH000168005150034700	347	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4154MH000168006150034800	348	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4154MH000168007150034900	349	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4154MH000168008150035000	350	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4154MH000168009150035100	351	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00743	Hetch_Hetchy after DRT from height of 15 mm standoff ~1 cm standoff	4154MH00074300150035200	352	autofocus sub-frame for target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - standoff near 1 cm
		4154MH000743001500353000	353	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - standoff near 1 cm
		4154MH000743002150035400	354	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4154MH000743003150035500	355	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4154MH000743004150035600	356	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4154MH000743005150035700	357	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4154MH000743006150035800	358	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4154MH000743007150035900	359	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4154MH000743008150036000	360	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4154MH000743009150036100	361	target Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 15_April_2024

Sol 4155 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	16_Apr_24
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	3
total parent images + focus merge products	3

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities		Focus stack images from Sol 4154 were merged.		Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	
mN00289	Focus Merges	4155MH001930001500362900	362	target: Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4154 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 354-361 - best focus image product
		4155MH001930001500363500	363	target: Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4154 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 354-361 - range map product
		4155MH001930001500364900	364	target: Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4154 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 344-351 - best focus image product
		4155MH001930001500365500	365	target: Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4154 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 344-351 - range map product
		4155MH001930001500366900	366	target: Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4154 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 334-341 - best focus image product
		4155MH001930001500367500	367	target: Hetch_Hetchy - brush height test - after dust removal tool (DRT) from the standard height of 15 mm standoff - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4154 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 334-341 - range map product

updated: 03_July_2024

Sol 4157 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	16-Apr-24			
		camera position	75	Image ID:		
		total parent images	0	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received		
		focus merges performed	0	CDPID:		
		total focus merge products	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		
		total parent images + focus merge products	74			
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the target Peppermint_Pass, the DRT-brushed target Tioga_Pass and the target Wonder_Lakes.						
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALISE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN00841	Peppermint_Pass stereo-1 ~14 cm standoff	4157MH0008410011500368C00	368	autofocus sub-frame for target Peppermint_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm		
		4157MH0008410011500369C00	369	target Peppermint_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm		
		4157MH0008410011500370C00	370	target Peppermint_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4157MH0008410011500371C00	371	target Peppermint_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4157MH0008410011500372C00	372	target Peppermint_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4157MH0008410011500373C00	373	target Peppermint_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4157MH0008410011500374C00	374	target Peppermint_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4157MH0008410011500375C00	375	target Peppermint_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4157MH0008410011500376C00	376	target Peppermint_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4157MH0008410011500377C00	377	target Peppermint_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4157MH0008410011500378C00	378	autofocus sub-frame for target Peppermint_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm		
		4157MH0008410011500379C00	379	target Peppermint_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm		
		4157MH0008410011500380C00	380	target Peppermint_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4157MH0008410011500381C00	381	target Peppermint_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00842	Peppermint_Pass stereo-2 ~14 cm standoff	4157MH0008410011500382C00	382	target Peppermint_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4157MH0008410011500383C00	383	target Peppermint_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4157MH0008410011500384C00	384	target Peppermint_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4157MH0008410011500385C00	385	target Peppermint_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4157MH0008410011500386C00	386	target Peppermint_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4157MH0008410011500387C00	387	target Peppermint_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00190	Tioga_Pass after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4157MH0001900011500388C00	388	autofocus sub-frame for target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
				4157MH0001900011500389C00	389	target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		mN00168	Tioga_Pass after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4157MH0001680011500390C00	390	autofocus sub-frame for target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
				4157MH0001680011500391C00	391	target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
				4157MH0001680011500392C00	392	target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4157MH0001680011500393C00	393	target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4157MH0001680011500394C00	394	target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4157MH0001680011500395C00	395	target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
4157MH0001680011500396C00	396			target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4157MH0001680011500397C00	397			target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4157MH0001680011500398C00	398			target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4157MH0001680011500399C00	399			target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00168	Tioga_Pass after DRT stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff			4157MH0001680011500400C00	400	autofocus sub-frame for target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
				4157MH0001680011500401C00	401	target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
				4157MH0001680011500402C00	402	target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4157MH0001680011500403C00	403	target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4157MH0001680011500404C00	404	target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4157MH0001680011500405C00	405	target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4157MH0001680011500406C00	406	target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4157MH0001680011500407C00	407	target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4157MH0001680011500408C00	408	target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4157MH0001680011500409C00	409	target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00743	Tioga_Pass after DRT ~1 cm standoff	4157MH0007430011500410C00	410	autofocus sub-frame for target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
				4157MH0007430011500411C00	411	target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
				4157MH0007430011500412C00	412	target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4157MH0007430011500413C00	413	target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
4157MH0007430011500414C00	414			target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4157MH0007430011500415C00	415			target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4157MH0007430011500416C00	416			target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4157MH0007430011500417C00	417			target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4157MH0007430011500418C00	418			target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4157MH0007430011500419C00	419			target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00190	Wonder_Lakes ~25 cm standoff			4157MH0001900011500420C00	420	autofocus sub-frame for target Wonder_Lakes - standoff near 25 cm
				4157MH0001900011500421C00	421	target Wonder_Lakes - standoff near 25 cm
mN00182	Wonder_Lakes stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff			4157MH0001820011500422C00	422	autofocus sub-frame for target Wonder_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
				4157MH0001820011500423C00	423	target Wonder_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4157MH0001820011500424C00	424	target Wonder_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4157MH0001820011500425C00	425	target Wonder_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4157MH0001820011500426C00	426	target Wonder_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4157MH0001820011500427C00	427	target Wonder_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4157MH0001820011500428C00	428	target Wonder_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4157MH0001820011500429C00	429	target Wonder_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4157MH0001820011500430C00	430	target Wonder_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4157MH0001820011500431C00	431	target Wonder_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

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mH00182	Wonder Lakes stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4157MH0001820001500432C00	432	autofocus sub-frame for target Wonder Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4157MH0001820011500433C00	433	target Wonder_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4157MH0001820021500434C00	434	target Wonder_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4157MH0001820021500435C00	435	target Wonder_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4157MH0001820021500436C00	436	target Wonder_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4157MH0001820021500437C00	437	target Wonder_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4157MH0001820021500438C00	438	target Wonder_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4157MH0001820021500439C00	439	target Wonder_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4157MH0001820021500440C00	440	target Wonder_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4157MH0001820021500441C00	441	target Wonder_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 18_April_2024

Sol 4158 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	17_Apr_24
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	7
total focus merge products	14
total parent images + focus merge products	14

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4157 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002171	Focus Merges	4158MH00017J000150042900	442	target Wonder_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4157 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 434-441 - best focus image product
		4158MH00017J000150043500	443	target Wonder_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4157 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 434-441 - range map product
		4158MH00017J000150044800	444	target Wonder_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4157 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 424-431 - best focus image product
		4158MH00017J000150045500	445	target Wonder_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4157 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 424-431 - range map product
		4158MH00017J000150046800	446	target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4157 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 412-419 - best focus image product
		4158MH00017J000150047500	447	target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4157 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 412-419 - range map product
		4158MH00017J000150048800	448	target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4157 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 402-409 - best focus image product
		4158MH00017J000150049500	449	target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4157 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 402-409 - range map product
		4158MH00017J000150049800	450	target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4157 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 392-399 - best focus image product
		4158MH00017J0001500451500	451	target Tioga_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4157 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 392-399 - range map product
		4158MH00017J000150046200	452	target Peppermint_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4157 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 380-387 - best focus image product
		4158MH00017J0001500453500	453	target Peppermint_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4157 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 380-387 - range map product
		4158MH00017J0001500454000	454	target Peppermint_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4157 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 370-377 - best focus image product
		4158MH00017J0001500455500	455	target Peppermint_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4157 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 370-377 - range map product

updated: 01_July_2024

Sol 4159 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	18-Apr-24
camera position	4
total parent images	33
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Tilden_Lake and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002190	Tilden_Lake after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4159MH0001900011500456C00	456	autoFocus sub-frame for target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		4159MH0001900011500457C00	457	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mN002168	Tilden_Lake after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4159MH0001680011500458C00	458	autoFocus sub-frame for target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4159MH0001680011500459C00	459	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4159MH0001680011500460C00	460	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4159MH0001680011500461C00	461	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4159MH0001680011500462C00	462	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4159MH0001680011500463C00	463	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4159MH0001680011500464C00	464	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4159MH0001680011500465C00	465	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4159MH0001680011500466C00	466	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4159MH0001680011500467C00	467	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002168	Tilden_Lake after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4159MH0001680011500468C00	468	autoFocus sub-frame for target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4159MH0001680011500469C00	469	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4159MH0001680011500470C00	470	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4159MH0001680011500471C00	471	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4159MH0001680011500472C00	472	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4159MH0001680011500473C00	473	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4159MH0001680011500474C00	474	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4159MH0001680011500475C00	475	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4159MH0001680011500476C00	476	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4159MH0001680011500477C00	477	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002743	Tilden_Lake after DRT ~1 cm standoff	4159MH0007430011500478C00	478	autoFocus sub-frame for target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4159MH0007430011500479C00	479	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4159MH0007430011500480C00	480	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4159MH0007430011500481C00	481	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4159MH0007430011500482C00	482	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4159MH0007430011500483C00	483	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4159MH0007430011500484C00	484	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4159MH0007430011500485C00	485	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4159MH0007430011500486C00	486	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4159MH0007430011500487C00	487	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002193	Focus Merges	4159MH001930011500488R00	488	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4159 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 480-487 - best focus image product
		4159MH001930011500489S00	489	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4159 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 480-487 - range map product
		4159MH001930011500490R00	490	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4159 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 470-477 - best focus image product
		4159MH001930011500491S00	491	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4159 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 470-477 - range map product
		4159MH001930011500492R00	492	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4159 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 460-467 - best focus image product
		4159MH001930011500493S00	493	target Tilden_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4159 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 460-467 - range map product

updated: 10_May_2024

Sol 4160 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)		19-Apr-24		
camera position		4		
total parent images		4		
focus merges performed		0		
total focus merge products		0		
total parent images + focus merge products		4		
summary of MAHLI activities		MAHLI acquired four arm-stowed landscape images with the dust cover closed (at the rover position after Sol 4159 drive) in parallel with the Sol 4160 MRO PM pass.		
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m100875	arm stowed view of landscape dust cover closed	4160MH0008750071500494C00	494	first time activity to test parallelism of MAHLI imaging commands and ultra-high frequency (UHF) communication passes where a successful test would allow more flexibility in MAHLI activity placement in future plans - stowed robotic arm landscape image at rover location at end of sol 4159 drive - dust cover closed - manual exposure duration of 15 milliseconds - image 1 of 4
		4160MH0008750091500495C00	495	first time activity to test parallelism of MAHLI imaging commands and ultra-high frequency (UHF) communication passes where a successful test would allow more flexibility in MAHLI activity placement in future plans - stowed robotic arm landscape image at rover location at end of sol 4159 drive - dust cover closed - manual exposure duration of 15 milliseconds - image 2 of 4
		4160MH0008750111500496C00	496	first time activity to test parallelism of MAHLI imaging commands and ultra-high frequency (UHF) communication passes where a successful test would allow more flexibility in MAHLI activity placement in future plans - stowed robotic arm landscape image at rover location at end of sol 4159 drive - dust cover closed - manual exposure duration of 15 milliseconds - image 3 of 4
		4160MH0008750131500497C00	497	first time activity to test parallelism of MAHLI imaging commands and ultra-high frequency (UHF) communication passes where a successful test would allow more flexibility in MAHLI activity placement in future plans - stowed robotic arm landscape image at rover location at end of sol 4159 drive - dust cover closed - manual exposure duration of 15 milliseconds - image 4 of 4

Sol 4161 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	20-Apr-24
camera position	41
total parent images	85
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	85

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CPDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

MAHLI imaged the REMS UV sensor, the target Mist_Falls, the target Castle_Rock_Spire, and the DRT-brushed target Florence_Lake.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALISE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00095	REMS UV sensor ~15 cm standoff	4161MH000295001150049800	498	autofocus sub-frame for REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation
		4161MH000295001150049900	499	REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation
mN00190	Mist_Falls ~24 cm standoff	4161MH001190001150050000	500	autofocus sub-frame for target Mist_Falls - standoff near 24 cm
		4161MH001190001150050100	501	target Mist_Falls - standoff near 24 cm
mN00299	Mist_Falls stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	4161MH002299001150050200	502	autofocus sub-frame for target Mist_Falls - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4161MH002299001150050300	503	target Mist_Falls - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4161MH002299001150050400	504	target Mist_Falls - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH002299001150050500	505	target Mist_Falls - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH002299001150050600	506	target Mist_Falls - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH002299001150050700	507	target Mist_Falls - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH002299001150050800	508	target Mist_Falls - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH002299001150050900	509	target Mist_Falls - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH002299001150051000	510	target Mist_Falls - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH002299001150051100	511	target Mist_Falls - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00299	Mist_Falls stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	4161MH002299001150051200	512	autofocus sub-frame for target Mist_Falls - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4161MH002299001150051300	513	target Mist_Falls - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4161MH002299001150051400	514	target Mist_Falls - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH002299001150051500	515	target Mist_Falls - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH002299001150051600	516	target Mist_Falls - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH002299001150051700	517	target Mist_Falls - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH002299001150051800	518	target Mist_Falls - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH002299001150051900	519	target Mist_Falls - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH002299001150052000	520	target Mist_Falls - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH002299001150052100	521	target Mist_Falls - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00865	Castle_Rock_Spire stereo-1 ~24 cm standoff	4161MH00865001150052200	522	autofocus sub-frame for target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm
		4161MH00865001150052300	523	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm
		4161MH00865001150052400	524	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH00865001150052500	525	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH00865001150052600	526	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH00865001150052700	527	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH00865001150052800	528	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH00865001150052900	529	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH00865001150053000	530	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH00865001150053100	531	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00865	Castle_Rock_Spire stereo-2 ~24 cm standoff	4161MH00865001150053200	532	autofocus sub-frame for target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm
		4161MH00865001150053300	533	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm
		4161MH00865001150053400	534	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH00865001150053500	535	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH00865001150053600	536	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH00865001150053700	537	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH00865001150053800	538	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH00865001150053900	539	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH00865001150054000	540	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH00865001150054100	541	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00865	Castle_Rock_Spire stereo-3 ~24 cm standoff	4161MH00865001150054200	542	autofocus sub-frame for target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm
		4161MH00865001150054300	543	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm
		4161MH00865001150054400	544	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH00865001150054500	545	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH00865001150054600	546	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH00865001150054700	547	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH00865001150054800	548	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH00865001150054900	549	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH00865001150055000	550	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH00865001150055100	551	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Florence_Lake after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4161MH001190001150055200	552	autofocus sub-frame for target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		4161MH001190001150055300	553	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mN00336	Florence_Lake after DRT stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4161MH00336001150055400	554	autofocus sub-frame for target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4161MH00336001150055500	555	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4161MH00336001150055600	556	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH00336001150055700	557	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH00336001150055800	558	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH00336001150055900	559	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH00336001150056000	560	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH00336001150056100	561	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH00336001150056200	562	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH00336001150056300	563	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

Continued on Next Page...

mH00336	Florence_Lake after DRT stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4161MH003360011500564C00	564	autofocus sub-frame for target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4161MH003360011500565C00	565	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4161MH003360011500566C00	566	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH003360011500567C00	567	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH003360011500568C00	568	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH003360011500569C00	569	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH003360011500570C00	570	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH003360011500571C00	571	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH003360011500572C00	572	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH003360011500573C00	573	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mH00848	Florence_Lake after DRT ~5 mm standoff	4161MH008480011500574C00	574	autofocus sub-frame for target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		4161MH008480011500575C00	575	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		4161MH008480011500576C00	576	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH008480011500577C00	577	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH008480011500578C00	578	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH008480011500579C00	579	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH008480011500580C00	580	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH008480011500581C00	581	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH008480011500582C00	582	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4161MH008480011500583C00	583	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 08_August_2024

Sol 4162 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	21_Apr-24
camera position	0
total parent images	0 <small>black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received</small>
focus merges performed	8
total focus merge products	16
total parent images + focus merge products	16
Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels	

summary of MAHLI activities	Focus stack images from Sol 4162 were merged.
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Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1000170	Focus Merges	4162MH0017000150094400	584	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4161 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 576-583 - best focus image product
		4162MH00170001500958500	585	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4161 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 576-583 - range map product
		4162MH0017000150096800	586	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4161 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 566-573 - best focus image product
		4162MH00170001500987500	587	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4161 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 566-573 - range map product
		4162MH0017000150098800	588	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4161 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 556-563 - best focus image product
		4162MH00170001500989500	589	target Florence_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4161 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 556-563 - range map product
		4162MH0017000150099000	590	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4161 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 544-551 - best focus image product
		4162MH00170001500991500	591	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4161 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 544-551 - range map product
		4162MH0017000150099200	592	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4161 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 534-541 - best focus image product
		4162MH00170001500993500	593	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4161 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 534-541 - range map product
		4162MH0017000150099400	594	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4161 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 524-531 - best focus image product
		4162MH00170001500995500	595	target Castle_Rock_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4161 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 524-531 - range map product
		4162MH0017000150099600	596	target Mist_Falls - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4161 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 514-521 - best focus image product
		4162MH00170001500997500	597	target Mist_Falls - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4161 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 514-521 - range map product
		4162MH0017000150099800	598	target Mist_Falls - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4161 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 504-511 - best focus image product
		4162MH00170001500999500	599	target Mist_Falls - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4161 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 504-511 - range map product

updated: 03_July_2024

Sol 4164 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	23-Apr-24
camera position	4
total parent images	33
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the target Sluggo_Pass and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Sluggo_Pass ~25 cm standoff	4164MH001900011500600C00	600	autofocus sub-frame for target Sluggo_Pass - standoff near 25 cm
		4164MH001900011500601C00	601	target Sluggo_Pass - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Sluggo_Pass stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4164MH001680011500602C00	602	autofocus sub-frame for target Sluggo_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4164MH001680011500603C00	603	target Sluggo_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4164MH001680011500604C00	604	target Sluggo_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4164MH001680011500605C00	605	target Sluggo_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4164MH001680011500606C00	606	target Sluggo_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4164MH001680011500607C00	607	target Sluggo_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4164MH001680011500608C00	608	target Sluggo_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4164MH001680011500609C00	609	target Sluggo_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4164MH001680011500610C00	610	target Sluggo_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4164MH001680011500611C00	611	target Sluggo_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Sluggo_Pass stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4164MH001680011500612C00	612	autofocus sub-frame for target Sluggo_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4164MH001680011500613C00	613	target Sluggo_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4164MH001680011500614C00	614	target Sluggo_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4164MH001680011500615C00	615	target Sluggo_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4164MH001680011500616C00	616	target Sluggo_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4164MH001680011500617C00	617	target Sluggo_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4164MH001680011500618C00	618	target Sluggo_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4164MH001680011500619C00	619	target Sluggo_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4164MH001680011500620C00	620	target Sluggo_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4164MH001680011500621C00	621	target Sluggo_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00302	Sluggo_Pass ~2 cm standoff	4164MH003020011500622C00	622	autofocus sub-frame for target Sluggo_Pass - standoff near 2 cm
		4164MH003020011500623C00	623	target Sluggo_Pass - standoff near 2 cm
		4164MH003020011500624C00	624	target Sluggo_Pass - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4164MH003020011500625C00	625	target Sluggo_Pass - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4164MH003020011500626C00	626	target Sluggo_Pass - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4164MH003020011500627C00	627	target Sluggo_Pass - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4164MH003020011500628C00	628	target Sluggo_Pass - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4164MH003020011500629C00	629	target Sluggo_Pass - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4164MH003020011500630C00	630	target Sluggo_Pass - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4164MH003020011500631C00	631	target Sluggo_Pass - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00193	Focus Merges	4164MH001930011500632R00	632	target Sluggo_Pass - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4164 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 624-631 - best focus image product
		4164MH001930011500633S00	633	target Sluggo_Pass - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4164 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 624-631 - range map product
		4164MH001930011500634R00	634	target Sluggo_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4164 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 614-621 - best focus image product
		4164MH001930011500635S00	635	target Sluggo_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4164 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 614-621 - range map product
		4164MH001930011500636R00	636	target Sluggo_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4164 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 604-611 - best focus image product
		4164MH001930011500637S00	637	target Sluggo_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4164 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 604-611 - range map product

updated: 01_July_2024

Sol 4166 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	25-Apr-24
camera position	3
total parent images	35
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the target Twin_Peaks and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN00359	Twin_Peaks ~24 cm standoff	4166MH00390021500638C00	638	autofocus sub-frame for target Twin_Peaks - standoff near 24 cm		
		4166MH00390011500639C00	639	target Twin_Peaks - standoff near 24 cm		
		4166MH00390021500640C00	640	target Twin_Peaks - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4166MH00390011500641C00	641	target Twin_Peaks - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4166MH00390021500642C00	642	target Twin_Peaks - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4166MH00390011500643C00	643	target Twin_Peaks - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4166MH00390021500644C00	644	target Twin_Peaks - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4166MH00390011500645C00	645	target Twin_Peaks - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4166MH00390021500646C00	646	target Twin_Peaks - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4166MH00390011500647C00	647	target Twin_Peaks - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00342	Twin_Peaks stereo 1 ~10 cm standoff	4166MH00342001500648C00	648	autofocus sub-frame for target Twin_Peaks - stereo-1 - standoff near 10 cm
				4166MH00342001500649C00	649	target Twin_Peaks - stereo-1 - standoff near 10 cm
				4166MH00342001500650C00	650	target Twin_Peaks - stereo-1 - standoff near 10 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4166MH00342001500651C00	651	target Twin_Peaks - stereo-1 - standoff near 10 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
4166MH00342001500652C00	652			target Twin_Peaks - stereo-1 - standoff near 10 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4166MH00342001500653C00	653			target Twin_Peaks - stereo-1 - standoff near 10 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4166MH00342001500654C00	654			target Twin_Peaks - stereo-1 - standoff near 10 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4166MH00342001500655C00	655			target Twin_Peaks - stereo-1 - standoff near 10 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4166MH00342001500656C00	656			target Twin_Peaks - stereo-1 - standoff near 10 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4166MH00342001500657C00	657			target Twin_Peaks - stereo-1 - standoff near 10 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00342	Twin_Peaks stereo 2 ~10 cm standoff			4166MH00342001500658C00	658	autofocus sub-frame for target Twin_Peaks - stereo-2 - standoff near 10 cm
				4166MH00342001500659C00	659	target Twin_Peaks - stereo-2 - standoff near 10 cm
				4166MH00342001500660C00	660	target Twin_Peaks - stereo-2 - standoff near 10 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4166MH00342001500661C00	661	target Twin_Peaks - stereo-2 - standoff near 10 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4166MH00342001500662C00	662	target Twin_Peaks - stereo-2 - standoff near 10 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4166MH00342001500663C00	663	target Twin_Peaks - stereo-2 - standoff near 10 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4166MH00342001500664C00	664	target Twin_Peaks - stereo-2 - standoff near 10 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4166MH00342001500665C00	665	target Twin_Peaks - stereo-2 - standoff near 10 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4166MH00342001500666C00	666	target Twin_Peaks - stereo-2 - standoff near 10 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4166MH00342001500667C00	667	target Twin_Peaks - stereo-2 - standoff near 10 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00189	Focus Merges	4166MH00193001500668R00	668	target Twin_Peaks - stereo-2 - standoff near 10 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4166 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 660-667 - best focus image product
				4166MH00193001500669S00	669	target Twin_Peaks - stereo-2 - standoff near 10 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4166 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 660-667 - range map product
				4166MH00193001500670R00	670	target Twin_Peaks - stereo-1 - standoff near 10 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4166 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 650-657 - best focus image product
				4166MH00193001500671S00	671	target Twin_Peaks - stereo-1 - standoff near 10 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4166 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 650-657 - range map product
4166MH00193001500672R00	672			target Twin_Peaks - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4166 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 640-647 - best focus image product		
4166MH00193001500673S00	673			target Twin_Peaks - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4166 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 640-647 - range map product		

updated: 03_July_2024

Sol 4168 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	27-Apr-24
camera position	83
total parent images	83
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	83

MAHLI image of the targets Bilko_Pinnacle and Pipsqueak_Spire.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00359	Bilko_Pinnacle Stereo-2 ~25 cm standoff	4168MH0039002150067400	674	autofocus sub-frame for target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm
		4168MH0039002150067500	675	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm
		4168MH0039002150067600	676	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH0039002150067700	677	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH0039002150067800	678	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH0039002150067900	679	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH0039002150068000	680	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH0039002150068100	681	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH0039002150068200	682	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH0039002150068300	683	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH0039002150068400	684	autofocus sub-frame for target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-3 - standoff near 25 cm
		4168MH0039002150068500	685	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-3 - standoff near 25 cm
		4168MH0039002150068600	686	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-3 - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH0039002150068700	687	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-3 - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00359	Bilko_Pinnacle Stereo-3 ~25 cm standoff	4168MH0039002150068800	688	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-3 - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH0039002150068900	689	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-3 - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH0039002150069000	690	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-3 - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH0039002150069100	691	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-3 - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH0039002150069200	692	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-3 - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH0039002150069300	693	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-3 - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH0039002150069400	694	autofocus sub-frame for target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm
		4168MH0039002150069500	695	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm
		4168MH0039002150069600	696	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH0039002150069700	697	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH0039002150069800	698	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH0039002150069900	699	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH0039002150070000	700	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH0039002150070100	701	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
4168MH0039002150070200	702	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4168MH0039002150070300	703	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00182	Bilko_Pinnacle Stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4168MH00182002150070400	704	autofocus sub-frame for target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4168MH00182002150070500	705	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4168MH00182002150070600	706	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH00182002150070700	707	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH00182002150070800	708	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH00182002150070900	709	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH00182002150071000	710	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH00182002150071100	711	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH00182002150071200	712	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH00182002150071300	713	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH00182002150071400	714	autofocus sub-frame for target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4168MH00182002150071500	715	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4168MH00182002150071600	716	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH00182002150071700	717	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Bilko_Pinnacle Stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4168MH00182002150071800	718	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH00182002150071900	719	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH00182002150072000	720	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH00182002150072100	721	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH00182002150072200	722	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH00182002150072300	723	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH00302002150072400	724	autofocus sub-frame for target Bilko_Pinnacle - standoff near 2 cm
		4168MH00302002150072500	725	target Bilko_Pinnacle - standoff near 2 cm
		4168MH00302002150072600	726	target Bilko_Pinnacle - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH00302002150072700	727	target Bilko_Pinnacle - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH00302002150072800	728	target Bilko_Pinnacle - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH00302002150072900	729	target Bilko_Pinnacle - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH00302002150073000	730	target Bilko_Pinnacle - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4168MH00302002150073100	731	target Bilko_Pinnacle - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
4168MH00302002150073200	732	target Bilko_Pinnacle - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4168MH00302002150073300	733	target Bilko_Pinnacle - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00172	Pipsqueak_Spire ~20 cm standoff	4168MH00172002150073400	734	autofocus sub-frame for target Pipsqueak_Spire - standoff near 20 cm
		4168MH00172002150073500	735	target Pipsqueak_Spire - standoff near 20 cm

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mH00224	Pipsqueak_Spire stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	416BMH000240011500736C00	736	autofocus sub-frame for target Pipsqueak_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		416BMH000240011500737C00	737	target Pipsqueak_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		416BMH000240011500738C00	738	target Pipsqueak_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in B-image relative focus stack
		416BMH000240011500739C00	739	target Pipsqueak_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in B-image relative focus stack
		416BMH000240011500740C00	740	target Pipsqueak_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in B-image relative focus stack
		416BMH000240011500741C00	741	target Pipsqueak_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in B-image relative focus stack
		416BMH000240011500742C00	742	target Pipsqueak_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in B-image relative focus stack
		416BMH000240011500743C00	743	target Pipsqueak_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in B-image relative focus stack
		416BMH000240011500744C00	744	target Pipsqueak_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in B-image relative focus stack
416BMH000240011500745C00	745	target Pipsqueak_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in B-image relative focus stack		
mH00224	Pipsqueak_Spire stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	416BMH000240011500746C00	746	autofocus sub-frame for target Pipsqueak_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		416BMH000240011500747C00	747	target Pipsqueak_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		416BMH000240011500748C00	748	target Pipsqueak_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in B-image relative focus stack
		416BMH000240011500749C00	749	target Pipsqueak_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in B-image relative focus stack
		416BMH000240011500750C00	750	target Pipsqueak_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in B-image relative focus stack
		416BMH000240011500751C00	751	target Pipsqueak_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in B-image relative focus stack
		416BMH000240011500752C00	752	target Pipsqueak_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in B-image relative focus stack
		416BMH000240011500753C00	753	target Pipsqueak_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in B-image relative focus stack
		416BMH000240011500754C00	754	target Pipsqueak_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in B-image relative focus stack
416BMH000240011500755C00	755	target Pipsqueak_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in B-image relative focus stack		

updated: 08_August_2024

Sol 4169 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	28-Apr-24
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	8
total focus merge products	16
total parent images + focus merge products	16

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4168 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1000170	Focus Merges	4169MH00170001500756900	756	target Pipsqueak_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4168 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 748-750 - best focus image product
		4169MH00170001500757500	757	target Pipsqueak_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4168 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 748-755 - range map product
		4169MH00170001500758900	758	target Pipsqueak_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4168 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 738-745 - best focus image product
		4169MH00170001500759500	759	target Pipsqueak_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4168 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 738-745 - range map product
		4169MH00170001500760900	760	target Bilko_Pinnacle - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4168 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 726-733 - best focus image product
		4169MH00170001500761500	761	target Bilko_Pinnacle - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4168 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 726-733 - range map product
		4169MH00170001500762900	762	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4168 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 716-723 - best focus image product
		4169MH00170001500763500	763	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4168 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 716-723 - range map product
		4169MH00170001500764900	764	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4168 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 706-713 - best focus image product
		4169MH00170001500765500	765	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4168 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 706-713 - range map product
		4169MH00170001500766900	766	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4168 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 696-703 - best focus image product
		4169MH00170001500767500	767	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4168 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 696-703 - range map product
		4169MH00170001500768900	768	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-3 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4168 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 686-693 - best focus image product
		4169MH00170001500769500	769	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-3 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4168 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 686-693 - range map product
		4169MH00170001500770900	770	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4168 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 676-683 - best focus image product
		4169MH00170001500771500	771	target Bilko_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4168 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 676-683 - range map product

mH00173	Emerald_Peak stereo-1 ~55 mm standoff	4173MH000173001500834C00	834	autofocus sub-frame for target Emerald_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
		4173MH000173001500835C00	835	target Emerald_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
		4173MH000173001500836C00	836	target Emerald_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4173MH000173001500837C00	837	target Emerald_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4173MH000173001500838C00	838	target Emerald_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4173MH000173001500839C00	839	target Emerald_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4173MH000173001500840C00	840	target Emerald_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4173MH000173001500841C00	841	target Emerald_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4173MH000173001500842C00	842	target Emerald_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4173MH000173001500843C00	843	target Emerald_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mH00173	Emerald_Peak stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4173MH000173001500844C00	844	autofocus sub-frame for target Emerald_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4173MH000173001500845C00	845	target Emerald_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4173MH000173001500846C00	846	target Emerald_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4173MH000173001500847C00	847	target Emerald_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4173MH000173001500848C00	848	target Emerald_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4173MH000173001500849C00	849	target Emerald_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4173MH000173001500850C00	850	target Emerald_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4173MH000173001500851C00	851	target Emerald_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4173MH000173001500852C00	852	target Emerald_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4173MH000173001500853C00	853	target Emerald_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 08_August_2024

Sol 4174 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	4-May-24
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	8
total focus merge products	16
total parent images + focus merge products	16

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4173 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1000170	Focus Merges	4174MH0017000150085400	854	target Emerald_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4173 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 846-853 - best focus image product
		4174MH0017000150085500	855	target Emerald_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4173 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 846-853 - range map product
		4174MH0017000150085600	856	target Emerald_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4173 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 836-843 - best focus image product
		4174MH0017000150085700	857	target Emerald_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4173 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 836-843 - range map product
		4174MH0017000150085800	858	target Emerald_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4173 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 826-833 - best focus image product
		4174MH0017000150085900	859	target Emerald_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4173 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 826-833 - range map product
		4174MH0017000150086000	860	target Emerald_Peak - stereo-3 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4173 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 816-823 - best focus image product
		4174MH0017000150086100	861	target Emerald_Peak - stereo-3 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4173 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 816-823 - range map product
		4174MH0017000150086200	862	target Emerald_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4173 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 806-813 - best focus image product
		4174MH0017000150086300	863	target Emerald_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4173 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 806-813 - range map product
		4174MH0017000150086400	864	target Franklin_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4173 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 796-803 - best focus image product
		4174MH0017000150086500	865	target Franklin_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4173 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 796-803 - range map product
		4174MH0017000150086600	866	target Franklin_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4173 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 786-793 - best focus image product
		4174MH0017000150086700	867	target Franklin_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4173 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 786-793 - range map product
		4174MH0017000150086800	868	target Franklin_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4173 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 776-783 - best focus image product
		4174MH0017000150086900	869	target Franklin_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4173 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 776-783 - range map product

updated: 08_July_2024

Sol 4175 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	5-May-24
camera position	11
total parent images	110
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	110

MAHLI images of the targets Lookout_Peak, Wilma_Lake, and Liberty_Cap.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00865	Lookout_Peak ~25 cm standoff	4175MH0008650011500870C00	870	autofocus sub-frame for target Lookout_Peak - standoff near 25 cm
		4175MH0008650011500871C00	871	target Lookout_Peak - standoff near 25 cm
		4175MH0008650011500872C00	872	target Lookout_Peak - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH0008650011500873C00	873	target Lookout_Peak - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH0008650011500874C00	874	target Lookout_Peak - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH0008650011500875C00	875	target Lookout_Peak - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH0008650011500876C00	876	target Lookout_Peak - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH0008650011500877C00	877	target Lookout_Peak - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH0008650011500878C00	878	target Lookout_Peak - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH0008650011500879C00	879	target Lookout_Peak - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00326	Lookout_Peak stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	4175MH00032600011500880C00	880	autofocus sub-frame for target Lookout_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4175MH00032600011500881C00	881	target Lookout_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4175MH00032600011500882C00	882	target Lookout_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH00032600011500883C00	883	target Lookout_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH00032600011500884C00	884	target Lookout_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH00032600011500885C00	885	target Lookout_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH00032600011500886C00	886	target Lookout_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH00032600011500887C00	887	target Lookout_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH00032600011500888C00	888	target Lookout_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH00032600011500889C00	889	target Lookout_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00326	Lookout_Peak stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	4175MH00032600011500890C00	890	autofocus sub-frame for target Lookout_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4175MH00032600011500891C00	891	target Lookout_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4175MH00032600011500892C00	892	target Lookout_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH00032600011500893C00	893	target Lookout_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH00032600011500894C00	894	target Lookout_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH00032600011500895C00	895	target Lookout_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH00032600011500896C00	896	target Lookout_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH00032600011500897C00	897	target Lookout_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH00032600011500898C00	898	target Lookout_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH00032600011500899C00	899	target Lookout_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00876	Wilma_Lake ~25 cm standoff	4175MH0008760011500900C00	900	autofocus sub-frame for target Wilma_Lake - standoff near 25 cm
		4175MH0008760011500901C00	901	target Wilma_Lake - standoff near 25 cm
		4175MH0008760011500902C00	902	target Wilma_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH0008760011500903C00	903	target Wilma_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH0008760011500904C00	904	target Wilma_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH0008760011500905C00	905	target Wilma_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH0008760011500906C00	906	target Wilma_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH0008760011500907C00	907	target Wilma_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH0008760011500908C00	908	target Wilma_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH0008760011500909C00	909	target Wilma_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00152	Wilma_Lake stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4175MH0001520011500910C00	910	autofocus sub-frame for target Wilma_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4175MH0001520011500911C00	911	target Wilma_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4175MH0001520011500912C00	912	target Wilma_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH0001520011500913C00	913	target Wilma_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH0001520011500914C00	914	target Wilma_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH0001520011500915C00	915	target Wilma_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH0001520011500916C00	916	target Wilma_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH0001520011500917C00	917	target Wilma_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH0001520011500918C00	918	target Wilma_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH0001520011500919C00	919	target Wilma_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00152	Wilma_Lake stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4175MH0001520011500920C00	920	autofocus sub-frame for target Wilma_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4175MH0001520011500921C00	921	target Wilma_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4175MH0001520011500922C00	922	target Wilma_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH0001520011500923C00	923	target Wilma_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH0001520011500924C00	924	target Wilma_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH0001520011500925C00	925	target Wilma_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH0001520011500926C00	926	target Wilma_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH0001520011500927C00	927	target Wilma_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH0001520011500928C00	928	target Wilma_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4175MH0001520011500929C00	929	target Wilma_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

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updated: 06_May_2024

Sol 4176 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	5-May-24
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	11
total focus merge products:	22
total parent images + focus merge products:	22

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4175 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00449	Focus Merges	4176MH00049000150098000	980	target Liberty_Cap - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4175 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 972-979 - best focus image product
		4176MH00049000150098150	981	target Liberty_Cap - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4175 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 972-979 - range map product
		4176MH00049000150098200	982	target Liberty_Cap - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4175 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 962-969 - best focus image product
		4176MH00049000150098350	983	target Liberty_Cap - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4175 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 962-969 - range map product
		4176MH00049000150098400	984	target Liberty_Cap - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4175 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 952-959 - best focus image product
		4176MH00049000150098550	985	target Liberty_Cap - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4175 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 952-959 - range map product
		4176MH00049000150098600	986	target Liberty_Cap - stereo-3 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4175 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 942-949 - best focus image product
		4176MH00049000150098750	987	target Liberty_Cap - stereo-3 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4175 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 942-949 - range map product
		4176MH00049000150098800	988	target Liberty_Cap - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4175 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 932-939 - best focus image product
		4176MH00049000150098950	989	target Liberty_Cap - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4175 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 932-939 - range map product
		4176MH00049000150099000	990	target Wilna_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4175 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 922-929 - best focus image product
		4176MH00049000150099150	991	target Wilna_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4175 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 922-929 - range map product
		4176MH00049000150099200	992	target Wilna_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4175 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 912-919 - best focus image product
		4176MH00049000150099350	993	target Wilna_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4175 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 912-919 - range map product
		4176MH00049000150099400	994	target Wilna_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4175 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 902-909 - best focus image product
		4176MH00049000150099550	995	target Wilna_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4175 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 902-909 - range map product
		4176MH00049000150099600	996	target Lookout_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4175 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 892-899 - best focus image product
		4176MH00049000150099750	997	target Lookout_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4175 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 892-899 - range map product
		4176MH00049000150099800	998	target Lookout_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4175 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 882-889 - best focus image product
		4176MH00049000150099950	999	target Lookout_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4175 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 882-889 - range map product
		4176MH00049000150100000	1000	target Lookout_Peak - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4175 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 872-879 - best focus image product
		4176MH00049000150100150	1001	target Lookout_Peak - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4175 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 872-879 - range map product

updated: 05_July_2024

Sol 4178 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	2024/07/05
camera position	4
total parent images	40
focus merges performed	4
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	48

MAHLI acquired 4x1 mosaic on the target El_Portal and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00865	El_Portal mosaic position 1 of 4 ~28 cm standoff	4178MH000865001501002C00	1002	autofocus sub-frame for target El_Portal - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 28 cm
		4178MH000865001501003C00	1003	target El_Portal - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 28 cm
		4178MH000865001501004C00	1004	target El_Portal - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 28 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4178MH000865001501005C00	1005	target El_Portal - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 28 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4178MH000865001501006C00	1006	target El_Portal - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 28 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4178MH000865001501007C00	1007	target El_Portal - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 28 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4178MH000865001501008C00	1008	target El_Portal - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 28 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4178MH000865001501009C00	1009	target El_Portal - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 28 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4178MH000865001501010C00	1010	target El_Portal - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 28 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4178MH000865001501011C00	1011	target El_Portal - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 28 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mN00865	El_Portal mosaic position 2 of 4 ~25 cm standoff	4178MH000865001501012C00
4178MH000865001501013C00	1013			target El_Portal - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm
4178MH000865001501014C00	1014			target El_Portal - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
4178MH000865001501015C00	1015			target El_Portal - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
4178MH000865001501016C00	1016			target El_Portal - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
4178MH000865001501017C00	1017			target El_Portal - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
4178MH000865001501018C00	1018			target El_Portal - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
4178MH000865001501019C00	1019			target El_Portal - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
4178MH000865001501020C00	1020			target El_Portal - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4178MH000865001501021C00	1021			target El_Portal - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00865	El_Portal mosaic position 3 of 4 ~24 cm standoff			4178MH000865001501022C00
		4178MH000865001501023C00	1023	target El_Portal - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 24 cm
		4178MH000865001501024C00	1024	target El_Portal - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4178MH000865001501025C00	1025	target El_Portal - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4178MH000865001501026C00	1026	target El_Portal - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4178MH000865001501027C00	1027	target El_Portal - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4178MH000865001501028C00	1028	target El_Portal - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4178MH000865001501029C00	1029	target El_Portal - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4178MH000865001501030C00	1030	target El_Portal - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4178MH000865001501031C00	1031	target El_Portal - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mN00865	El_Portal mosaic position 4 of 4 ~32 cm standoff	4178MH000865001501032C00
4178MH000865001501033C00	1033			target El_Portal - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 32 cm
4178MH000865001501034C00	1034			target El_Portal - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 32 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
4178MH000865001501035C00	1035			target El_Portal - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 32 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
4178MH000865001501036C00	1036			target El_Portal - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 32 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
4178MH000865001501037C00	1037			target El_Portal - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 32 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
4178MH000865001501038C00	1038			target El_Portal - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 32 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
4178MH000865001501039C00	1039			target El_Portal - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 32 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
4178MH000865001501040C00	1040			target El_Portal - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 32 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4178MH000865001501041C00	1041			target El_Portal - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 32 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00133	Focus Merges			4178MH000133001501042R00
		4178MH000133001501043R00	1043	target El_Portal - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 32 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4178 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1034-1041 - range map product
		4178MH000133001501044R00	1044	target El_Portal - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4178 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1024-1031 - best focus image product
		4178MH000133001501045R00	1045	target El_Portal - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4178 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1024-1031 - range map product
		4178MH000133001501046R00	1046	target El_Portal - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4178 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1014-1021 - best focus image product
		4178MH000133001501047R00	1047	target El_Portal - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4178 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1014-1021 - range map product
		4178MH000133001501048R00	1048	target El_Portal - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 28 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4178 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1004-1011 - best focus image product
		4178MH000133001501049R00	1049	target El_Portal - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 28 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4178 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1004-1011 - range map product

updated: 07_January_2025

Sol 4180 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	10-May-24
camera position	6
total parent images	53
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	63

MAHLI imaged the DRT brushed target Happy_Isles and acquired a 2x1 mosaic on the target Laurel_Mountain. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00290	Happy_Isles after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4180MH0019000015010500C0	1050	autofocus sub-frame for target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		4180MH0019000150105100C0	1051	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mN00268	Happy_Isles after DRT stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4180MH0016800015010502C0	1052	autofocus sub-frame for target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4180MH0016800150105300C0	1053	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4180MH0016800215010540C0	1054	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0016800215010550C0	1055	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0016800215010560C0	1056	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0016800215010570C0	1057	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0016800215010580C0	1058	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0016800215010590C0	1059	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0016800215010600C0	1060	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0016800215010610C0	1061	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00268	Happy_Isles after DRT stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4180MH0016800015010620C0	1062	autofocus sub-frame for target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4180MH001680015010630C0	1063	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4180MH0016800215010640C0	1064	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0016800215010650C0	1065	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0016800215010660C0	1066	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0016800215010670C0	1067	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0016800215010680C0	1068	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0016800215010690C0	1069	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0016800215010700C0	1070	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0016800215010710C0	1071	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00274	Happy_Isles after DRT ~1 cm standoff	4180MH0074300015010720C0	1072	autofocus sub-frame for target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4180MH0074300150107300C0	1073	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4180MH0074300215010740C0	1074	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0074300215010750C0	1075	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0074300215010760C0	1076	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0074300215010770C0	1077	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0074300215010780C0	1078	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0074300215010790C0	1079	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0074300215010800C0	1080	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0074300215010810C0	1081	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00628	Laurel_Mountain mosaic position 1 of 2 ~24 cm standoff	4180MH0062800015010820C0	1082	autofocus sub-frame for target Laurel_Mountain - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm
		4180MH006280015010830C0	1083	target Laurel_Mountain - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm
		4180MH0062800215010840C0	1084	target Laurel_Mountain - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0062800215010850C0	1085	target Laurel_Mountain - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0062800215010860C0	1086	target Laurel_Mountain - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0062800215010870C0	1087	target Laurel_Mountain - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0062800215010880C0	1088	target Laurel_Mountain - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0062800215010890C0	1089	target Laurel_Mountain - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0062800215010900C0	1090	target Laurel_Mountain - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0062800215010910C0	1091	target Laurel_Mountain - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00628	Laurel_Mountain mosaic position 2 of 2 ~24 cm standoff	4180MH0062800015010920C0	1092	autofocus sub-frame for target Laurel_Mountain - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm
		4180MH006280015010930C0	1093	target Laurel_Mountain - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm
		4180MH0062800215010940C0	1094	target Laurel_Mountain - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0062800215010950C0	1095	target Laurel_Mountain - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0062800215010960C0	1096	target Laurel_Mountain - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0062800215010970C0	1097	target Laurel_Mountain - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0062800215010980C0	1098	target Laurel_Mountain - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0062800215010990C0	1099	target Laurel_Mountain - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0062800215011000C0	1100	target Laurel_Mountain - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4180MH0062800215011010C0	1101	target Laurel_Mountain - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00227	Focus Merges	4180MH002270001501102000	1102	target Laurel_Mountain - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4180 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1094-1101 - best focus image product
		4180MH002270001501103000	1103	target Laurel_Mountain - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4180 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1094-1101 - range map product
		4180MH002270001501104000	1104	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4180 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1074-1081 - best focus image product
		4180MH002270001501105000	1105	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4180 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1074-1081 - range map product
		4180MH002270001501106000	1106	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4180 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1074-1081 - best focus image product
		4180MH002270001501107000	1107	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4180 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1074-1081 - range map product
		4180MH002270001501108000	1108	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4180 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1064-1071 - best focus image product
		4180MH002270001501109000	1109	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4180 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1064-1071 - range map product
		4180MH002270001501110000	1110	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4180 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1054-1061 - best focus image product
		4180MH002270001501111000	1111	target Happy_Isles - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4180 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1054-1061 - range map product

updated: 18 July 2024

Sol 4182 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	12 May 24
camera position	84
total parent images	84
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	84

MAHLI images of the target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182, the target Royal_Arches, and the DRT-brushed target Boyden_Cave.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN00059	Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 stereo-1 ~24 cm standoff	4182MH0003900015011200D	1112	autofocus sub-frame for target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm		
		4182MH0003900015011300D	1113	target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm		
		4182MH0003900015011400D	1114	target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4182MH0003900015011500D	1115	target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4182MH0003900015011600D	1116	target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4182MH0003900015011700D	1117	target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4182MH0003900015011800D	1118	target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4182MH0003900015011900D	1119	target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4182MH0003900015012000D	1120	target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4182MH0003900015012100D	1121	target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00059	Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 stereo-2 ~24 cm standoff	4182MH0003900015012200D	1122	autofocus sub-frame for target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm
				4182MH0003900015012300D	1123	target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm
4182MH0003900015012400D	1124			target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4182MH0003900015012500D	1125			target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4182MH0003900015012600D	1126			target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4182MH0003900015012700D	1127			target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4182MH0003900015012800D	1128			target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4182MH0003900015012900D	1129			target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4182MH0003900015013000D	1130			target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4182MH0003900015013100D	1131			target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00024	Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff			4182MH0002400015013200D	1132	autofocus sub-frame for target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
				4182MH0002400015013300D	1133	target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4182MH0002400015013400D	1134	target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4182MH0002400015013500D	1135	target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4182MH0002400015013600D	1136	target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4182MH0002400015013700D	1137	target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4182MH0002400015013800D	1138	target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4182MH0002400015013900D	1139	target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4182MH0002400015014000D	1140	target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4182MH0002400015014100D	1141	target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00024	Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	4182MH0002400015014200D	1142	autofocus sub-frame for target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
				4182MH0002400015014300D	1143	target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
4182MH0002400015014400D	1144			target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4182MH0002400015014500D	1145			target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4182MH0002400015014600D	1146			target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4182MH0002400015014700D	1147			target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4182MH0002400015014800D	1148			target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4182MH0002400015014900D	1149			target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4182MH0002400015015000D	1150			target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4182MH0002400015015100D	1151			target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00050	Royal_Arches ~24 cm standoff			4182MH00019000015015200D	1152	autofocus sub-frame for target Royal_Arches - standoff near 24 cm
				4182MH00019000015015300D	1153	target Royal_Arches - standoff near 24 cm
mN00036	Royal_Arches ~4 cm standoff	4182MH0003600015015400D	1154	autofocus sub-frame for target Royal_Arches - standoff near 4 cm		
		4182MH0003600015015500D	1155	target Royal_Arches - standoff near 4 cm		
		4182MH0003600015015600D	1156	target Royal_Arches - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4182MH0003600015015700D	1157	target Royal_Arches - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4182MH0003600015015800D	1158	target Royal_Arches - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4182MH0003600015015900D	1159	target Royal_Arches - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4182MH0003600015016000D	1160	target Royal_Arches - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4182MH0003600015016100D	1161	target Royal_Arches - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4182MH0003600015016200D	1162	target Royal_Arches - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4182MH0003600015016300D	1163	target Royal_Arches - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00050	Boyden_Cave after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4182MH00019000015016400D	1164	autofocus sub-frame for target Boyden_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm		
		4182MH00019000015016500D	1165	target Boyden_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm		
mN00036	Boyden_Cave after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4182MH0003600015016600D	1166	autofocus sub-frame for target Boyden_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		4182MH0003600015016700D	1167	target Boyden_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		4182MH0003600015016800D	1168	target Boyden_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4182MH0003600015016900D	1169	target Boyden_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4182MH0003600015017000D	1170	target Boyden_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4182MH0003600015017100D	1171	target Boyden_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4182MH0003600015017200D	1172	target Boyden_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4182MH0003600015017300D	1173	target Boyden_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4182MH0003600015017400D	1174	target Boyden_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4182MH0003600015017500D	1175	target Boyden_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

Continued on Next Page...

mH00336	Boydén Cave after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4182MH000336001501176C00	1176	autofocus sub-frame for target Boydén_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4182MH000336001501177C00	1177	target Boydén_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4182MH000336001501178C00	1178	target Boydén_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4182MH000336001501179C00	1179	target Boydén_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4182MH000336001501180C00	1180	target Boydén_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4182MH000336001501181C00	1181	target Boydén_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4182MH000336001501182C00	1182	target Boydén_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4182MH000336001501183C00	1183	target Boydén_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4182MH000336001501184C00	1184	target Boydén_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4182MH000336001501185C00	1185	target Boydén_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mH00864	Boydén Cave after DRT ~1 cm standoff	4182MH000864001501186C00	1186	autofocus sub-frame for target Boydén_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4182MH000864001501187C00	1187	target Boydén_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4182MH000864001501188C00	1188	target Boydén_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4182MH000864001501189C00	1189	target Boydén_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4182MH000864001501190C00	1190	target Boydén_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4182MH000864001501191C00	1191	target Boydén_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4182MH000864001501192C00	1192	target Boydén_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4182MH000864001501193C00	1193	target Boydén_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4182MH000864001501194C00	1194	target Boydén_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4182MH000864001501195C00	1195	target Boydén_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 08_August_2024

Sol 4183 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	13-May-24
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	8
total focus merge products	16
total parent images + focus merge products	16

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4182 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00375	Focus Merges	4182MH003750001501196900	1196	target Boyden_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4182 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1188-1195 - best focus image product
		4182MH003750001501197500	1197	target Boyden_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4182 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1188-1195 - range map product
		4182MH003750001501198900	1198	target Boyden_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4182 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1178-1185 - best focus image product
		4182MH003750001501199500	1199	target Boyden_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4182 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1178-1185 - range map product
		4182MH003750001501200900	1200	target Boyden_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4182 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1168-1175 - best focus image product
		4182MH003750001501201500	1201	target Boyden_Cave - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4182 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1168-1175 - range map product
		4182MH003750001501202900	1202	target Royal_Arches - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4182 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1134-1163 - best focus image product
		4182MH003750001501203500	1203	target Royal_Arches - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4182 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1134-1163 - range map product
		4182MH003750001501204900	1204	target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4182 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1144-1151 - best focus image product
		4182MH003750001501205500	1205	target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4182 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1144-1151 - range map product
		4182MH003750001501206900	1206	target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4182 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1134-1141 - best focus image product
		4182MH003750001501207500	1207	target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4182 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1134-1141 - range map product
		4182MH003750001501208900	1208	target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4182 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1124-1131 - best focus image product
		4182MH003750001501209500	1209	target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4182 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1124-1131 - range map product
		4182MH003750001501210900	1210	target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4182 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1114-1121 - best focus image product
		4182MH003750001501211500	1211	target Quarry_Peak_Sol_4182 - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4182 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1114-1121 - range map product

updated: 09_July_2024

Sol 4184 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	14-May-24
camera positions	6
total parent images	45
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	45

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities

MAHLI imaged the targets Tenaya_Lake and Buck_Lake.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN000172	Tenaya_Lake ~20 cm standoff	4184MH000172000150121200	1212	autoFocus sub-frame for target Tenaya_Lake - standoff near 20 cm
		4184MH000172001501213000	1213	target Tenaya_Lake - standoff near 20 cm
mN000206	Tenaya_Lake stereo-1 ~55 mm standoff	4184MH000306000150121400	1214	autoFocus sub-frame for target Tenaya_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
		4184MH000306000150121500	1215	target Tenaya_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
		4184MH000306000150121600	1216	target Tenaya_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4184MH000306000150121700	1217	target Tenaya_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4184MH000306000150121800	1218	target Tenaya_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4184MH000306000150121900	1219	target Tenaya_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4184MH000306000150122000	1220	target Tenaya_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4184MH000306000150122100	1221	target Tenaya_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4184MH000306000150122200	1222	target Tenaya_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4184MH000306000150122300	1223	target Tenaya_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000206	Tenaya_Lake stereo-2 ~55 mm standoff	4184MH000306000150122400	1224	autoFocus sub-frame for target Tenaya_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm
		4184MH000306000150122500	1225	target Tenaya_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm
		4184MH000306000150122600	1226	target Tenaya_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4184MH000306000150122700	1227	target Tenaya_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4184MH000306000150122800	1228	target Tenaya_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4184MH000306000150122900	1229	target Tenaya_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4184MH000306000150123000	1230	target Tenaya_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4184MH000306000150123100	1231	target Tenaya_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4184MH000306000150123200	1232	target Tenaya_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4184MH000306000150123300	1233	target Tenaya_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000290	Buck_Lake ~25 cm standoff	4184MH000190000150123400	1234	autoFocus sub-frame for target Buck_Lake - standoff near 25 cm
		4184MH000190000150123500	1235	target Buck_Lake - standoff near 25 cm
mN000299	Buck_Lake stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4184MH000299000150123600	1236	autoFocus sub-frame for target Buck_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4184MH000299000150123700	1237	target Buck_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4184MH000299000150123800	1238	target Buck_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4184MH000299000150123900	1239	target Buck_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4184MH000299000150124000	1240	target Buck_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4184MH000299000150124100	1241	target Buck_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4184MH000299000150124200	1242	target Buck_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4184MH000299000150124300	1243	target Buck_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4184MH000299000150124400	1244	target Buck_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4184MH000299000150124500	1245	target Buck_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000299	Buck_Lake stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4184MH000299000150124600	1246	autoFocus sub-frame for target Buck_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4184MH000299000150124700	1247	target Buck_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4184MH000299000150124800	1248	target Buck_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4184MH000299000150124900	1249	target Buck_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4184MH000299000150125000	1250	target Buck_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4184MH000299000150125100	1251	target Buck_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4184MH000299000150125200	1252	target Buck_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4184MH000299000150125300	1253	target Buck_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4184MH000299000150125400	1254	target Buck_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4184MH000299000150125500	1255	target Buck_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 23_May_2024

Sol 4185 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	15-May-24
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	4
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	8

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4184 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00133	Focus Merges	4185MH0001530001501256R00	1256	target Buck_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4184 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1248-1255 - best focus image product
		4185MH0001530001501257S00	1257	target Buck_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4184 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1248-1255 - range map product
		4185MH0001530001501258R00	1258	target Buck_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4184 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1238-1245 - best focus image product
		4185MH0001530001501259S00	1259	target Buck_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4184 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1238-1245 - range map product
		4185MH0001530001501260R00	1260	target Tenaya_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4184 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1216-1223 - best focus image product
		4185MH0001530001501261S00	1261	target Tenaya_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4184 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1216-1223 - range map product
		4185MH0001530001501262R00	1262	target Tenaya_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4184 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1216-1223 - best focus image product
		4185MH0001530001501263S00	1263	target Tenaya_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4184 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1216-1223 - range map product

updated: 09_July_2024

Sol 4186 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	16-May-24
camera position	12
total parent images	63
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	63

Image ID: black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received

CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the target Parker_Lakes and the DRT-brushed target Tuolumne_Meadows.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00290	Parker_Lakes ~25 cm standoff	4186MH0019000150126400	1264	autofocus sub-frame for target Parker_Lakes - standoff near 25 cm
		4186MH0019000150126500	1265	target Parker_Lakes - standoff near 25 cm
mN00273	Parker_Lakes stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4186MH0017300150126600	1266	autofocus sub-frame for target Parker_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4186MH0017300150126700	1267	target Parker_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4186MH0017300150126800	1268	target Parker_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0017300150126900	1269	target Parker_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0017300150127000	1270	target Parker_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0017300150127100	1271	target Parker_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0017300150127200	1272	target Parker_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0017300150127300	1273	target Parker_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0017300150127400	1274	target Parker_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0017300150127500	1275	target Parker_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00273	Parker_Lakes stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4186MH0017300150127600	1276	autofocus sub-frame for target Parker_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4186MH0017300150127700	1277	target Parker_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4186MH0017300150127800	1278	target Parker_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0017300150127900	1279	target Parker_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0017300150128000	1280	target Parker_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0017300150128100	1281	target Parker_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0017300150128200	1282	target Parker_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0017300150128300	1283	target Parker_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0017300150128400	1284	target Parker_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0017300150128500	1285	target Parker_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00290	Tuolumne_Meadows before DRT ~25 cm standoff	4186MH0019000150128600	1286	autofocus sub-frame for target Tuolumne_Meadows - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4186MH0019000150128700	1287	target Tuolumne_Meadows - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00222	Tuolumne_Meadows before DRT ~5 cm standoff	4186MH0012200150128800	1288	autofocus sub-frame for target Tuolumne_Meadows - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm
		4186MH0012200150128900	1289	target Tuolumne_Meadows - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm
mN00290	Tuolumne_Meadows after DRT stereo-1 ~24 cm standoff	4186MH0019000150129000	1290	autofocus sub-frame for target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm
		4186MH0019000150129100	1291	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm
mN00290	Tuolumne_Meadows after DRT stereo-2 ~25 cm standoff	4186MH0019000150129200	1292	autofocus sub-frame for target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm
		4186MH0019000150129300	1293	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm
mN00290	Tuolumne_Meadows after DRT stereo-3 ~24 cm standoff	4186MH0019000150129400	1294	autofocus sub-frame for target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm
		4186MH0019000150129500	1295	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm
mN00336	Tuolumne_Meadows after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4186MH0033600150129600	1296	autofocus sub-frame for target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4186MH0033600150129700	1297	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4186MH0033600150129800	1298	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0033600150129900	1299	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0033600150130000	1300	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0033600150130100	1301	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0033600150130200	1302	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0033600150130300	1303	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0033600150130400	1304	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0033600150130500	1305	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00336	Tuolumne_Meadows after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4186MH0033600150130600	1306	autofocus sub-frame for target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4186MH0033600150130700	1307	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4186MH0033600150130800	1308	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0033600150130900	1309	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0033600150131000	1310	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0033600150131100	1311	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0033600150131200	1312	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0033600150131300	1313	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0033600150131400	1314	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0033600150131500	1315	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00864	Tuolumne_Meadows after DRT ~1 cm standoff	4186MH0086400150131600	1316	autofocus sub-frame for target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4186MH0086400150131700	1317	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4186MH0086400150131800	1318	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0086400150131900	1319	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0086400150132000	1320	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0086400150132100	1321	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0086400150132200	1322	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0086400150132300	1323	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0086400150132400	1324	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4186MH0086400150132500	1325	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 08_July_2024

Sol 4187 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	17-May-24
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	10

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4186 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	4187MH0002270001501326000	1326	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4186 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1318-1325 - best focus image product
		4187MH0002270001501327500	1327	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4186 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1318-1325 - range map product
		4187MH0002270001501328000	1328	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4186 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1308-1315 - best focus image product
		4187MH0002270001501329500	1329	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4186 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1308-1315 - range map product
		4187MH0002270001501330000	1330	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4186 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1298-1305 - best focus image product
		4187MH0002270001501331500	1331	target Tuolumne_Meadows - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4186 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1298-1305 - range map product
		4187MH0002270001501332000	1332	target Parker_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4186 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1278-1285 - best focus image product
		4187MH0002270001501333500	1333	target Parker_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4186 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1278-1285 - range map product
		4187MH0002270001501334000	1334	target Parker_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4186 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1268-1275 - best focus image product
		4187MH0002270001501335500	1335	target Parker_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4186 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1268-1275 - range map product

updated: 15_July_2024

Sol 4191 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	21-May-24	
		camera positions	4	Image ID:
		total parent images	33	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	3	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	6	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	39	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Pine_Creek and the focus stack images were merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002190	Pine_Creek after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4191MH00190001501336C00	1336	autoFocus sub-frame for target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		4191MH00190001501337C00	1337	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mN002168	Pine_Creek after DRT stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4191MH001680021501338C00	1338	autoFocus sub-frame for target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4191MH00168001501339C00	1339	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4191MH001680021501340C00	1340	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4191MH001680021501341C00	1341	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4191MH001680021501342C00	1342	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4191MH00168001501343C00	1343	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4191MH001680021501344C00	1344	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4191MH00168001501345C00	1345	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4191MH001680021501346C00	1346	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4191MH00168001501347C00	1347	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002168	Pine_Creek after DRT stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4191MH001680001501348C00	1348	autoFocus sub-frame for target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4191MH00168001501349C00	1349	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4191MH001680021501350C00	1350	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4191MH00168001501351C00	1351	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4191MH001680021501352C00	1352	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4191MH00168001501353C00	1353	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4191MH001680021501354C00	1354	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4191MH00168001501355C00	1355	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4191MH001680021501356C00	1356	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4191MH00168001501357C00	1357	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002743	Pine_Creek after DRT ~5 mm standoff	4191MH007430001501358C00	1358	autoFocus sub-frame for target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		4191MH00743001501359C00	1359	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		4191MH007430021501360C00	1360	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4191MH007430021501361C00	1361	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4191MH007430021501362C00	1362	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4191MH007430021501363C00	1363	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4191MH007430021501364C00	1364	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4191MH00743001501365C00	1365	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4191MH007430021501366C00	1366	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4191MH00743001501367C00	1367	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002193	Focus Merges	4191MH001930001501368R00	1368	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4191 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1360-1367 - best focus image product
		4191MH001930001501369S00	1369	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4191 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1360-1367 - range map product
		4191MH001930001501370R00	1370	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4191 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1350-1357 - best focus image product
		4191MH001930001501371S00	1371	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4191 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1350-1357 - range map product
		4191MH001930001501372R00	1372	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4191 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1340-1347 - best focus image product
		4191MH001930001501373S00	1373	target Pine_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4191 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1340-1347 - range map product

updated: 11_July_2024

Sol 4193 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	23-May-24
camera position	2
total parent images	35
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the target Lake_Catherine and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN00865	Lake_Catherine ~24 cm standoff	4193MH000865001501374000	1374	autoFocus sub-frame for target Lake_Catherine - standoff near 24 cm		
		4193MH000865001501375000	1375	target Lake_Catherine - standoff near 24 cm		
		4193MH000865001501376000	1376	target Lake_Catherine - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4193MH000865001501377000	1377	target Lake_Catherine - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4193MH000865001501378000	1378	target Lake_Catherine - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4193MH000865001501379000	1379	target Lake_Catherine - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4193MH000865001501380000	1380	target Lake_Catherine - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4193MH000865001501381000	1381	target Lake_Catherine - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4193MH000865001501382000	1382	target Lake_Catherine - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4193MH000865001501383000	1383	target Lake_Catherine - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4193MH000870001501394000	1384	autoFocus sub-frame for target Lake_Catherine - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm		
		4193MH000870001501385000	1385	target Lake_Catherine - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm		
		4193MH000870001501386000	1386	target Lake_Catherine - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4193MH000870001501387000	1387	target Lake_Catherine - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00877	Lake_Catherine Stereo 1 ~14 cm standoff	4193MH000870001501388000	1388	target Lake_Catherine - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4193MH000870001501389000	1389	target Lake_Catherine - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4193MH000870001501390000	1390	target Lake_Catherine - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4193MH000870001501391000	1391	target Lake_Catherine - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4193MH000870001501392000	1392	target Lake_Catherine - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4193MH000870001501393000	1393	target Lake_Catherine - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00877	Lake_Catherine Stereo 2 ~14 cm standoff	4193MH000870001501394000	1394	autoFocus sub-frame for target Lake_Catherine - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm
				4193MH000870001501395000	1395	target Lake_Catherine - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm
				4193MH000870001501396000	1396	target Lake_Catherine - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4193MH000870001501397000	1397	target Lake_Catherine - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4193MH000870001501398000	1398	target Lake_Catherine - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4193MH000870001501399000	1399	target Lake_Catherine - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4193MH000870001501400000	1400	target Lake_Catherine - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4193MH000870001501401000	1401	target Lake_Catherine - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
4193MH000870001501402000	1402			target Lake_Catherine - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4193MH000870001501403000	1403			target Lake_Catherine - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00189	Focus Merges			4193MH001930001501404000	1404	target Lake_Catherine - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4193 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1396-1403 - best focus image product
				4193MH001930001501405000	1405	target Lake_Catherine - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4193 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1396-1403 - range map product
				4193MH001930001501406000	1406	target Lake_Catherine - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4193 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1386-1393 - best focus image product
				4193MH001930001501407000	1407	target Lake_Catherine - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4193 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1386-1393 - range map product
		4193MH001930001501408000	1408	target Lake_Catherine - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4193 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1376-1383 - best focus image product		
		4193MH001930001501409000	1409	target Lake_Catherine - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4193 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1376-1383 - range map product		

Sol 4196 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	20-May-24	
		camera position	12	Image ID:
		total parent images:	120	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed:	0	CDPID:
		total focus merge products:	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products:	120	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the target Second_Lake and MAHLI imaged the targets Josephine_Lake and Timber_Knob, which includes a 5x1 mosaic from Josephine_Lake to Timber_Knob.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00359	Second_Lake ~24 cm standoff	4196MH00359001501410000	1410	autofocus sub-frame for target Second_Lake - standoff near 24 cm
		4196MH00359001501411000	1411	target Second_Lake - standoff near 24 cm
		4196MH00359001501412000	1412	target Second_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00359001501413000	1413	target Second_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00359001501414000	1414	target Second_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00359001501415000	1415	target Second_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00359001501416000	1416	target Second_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00359001501417000	1417	target Second_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00359001501418000	1418	target Second_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00359001501419000	1419	target Second_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00356	Second_Lake stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	4196MH00356001501420000	1420	autofocus sub-frame for target Second_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4196MH00356001501421000	1421	target Second_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4196MH00356001501422000	1422	target Second_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00356001501423000	1423	target Second_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00356001501424000	1424	target Second_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00356001501425000	1425	target Second_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00356001501426000	1426	target Second_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00356001501427000	1427	target Second_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00356001501428000	1428	target Second_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00356001501429000	1429	target Second_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00356	Second_Lake stereo-2 ~35 mm standoff	4196MH00356001501430000	1430	autofocus sub-frame for target Second_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		4196MH00356001501431000	1431	target Second_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		4196MH00356001501432000	1432	target Second_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00356001501433000	1433	target Second_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00356001501434000	1434	target Second_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00356001501435000	1435	target Second_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00356001501436000	1436	target Second_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00356001501437000	1437	target Second_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00356001501438000	1438	target Second_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00356001501439000	1439	target Second_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00865	Josephine_Lake ~24 cm standoff	4196MH00865001501440000	1440	autofocus sub-frame for target Josephine_Lake - standoff near 24 cm
		4196MH00865001501441000	1441	target Josephine_Lake - standoff near 24 cm
		4196MH00865001501442000	1442	target Josephine_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00865001501443000	1443	target Josephine_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00865001501444000	1444	target Josephine_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00865001501445000	1445	target Josephine_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00865001501446000	1446	target Josephine_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00865001501447000	1447	target Josephine_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00865001501448000	1448	target Josephine_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00865001501449000	1449	target Josephine_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Josephine_Lake stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	4196MH00182001501450000	1450	autofocus sub-frame for target Josephine_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4196MH00182001501451000	1451	target Josephine_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4196MH00182001501452000	1452	target Josephine_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00182001501453000	1453	target Josephine_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00182001501454000	1454	target Josephine_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00182001501455000	1455	target Josephine_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00182001501456000	1456	target Josephine_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00182001501457000	1457	target Josephine_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00182001501458000	1458	target Josephine_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00182001501459000	1459	target Josephine_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Josephine_Lake stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	4196MH00182001501460000	1460	autofocus sub-frame for target Josephine_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4196MH00182001501461000	1461	target Josephine_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4196MH00182001501462000	1462	target Josephine_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00182001501463000	1463	target Josephine_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00182001501464000	1464	target Josephine_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00182001501465000	1465	target Josephine_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00182001501466000	1466	target Josephine_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00182001501467000	1467	target Josephine_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00182001501468000	1468	target Josephine_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4196MH00182001501469000	1469	target Josephine_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

Continued on Next Page...

updated: 28_May_2024

Sol 4197 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	27 May 24
camera position	0
total parent images	0 <small>black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received</small>
focus merges performed	12 <small>CDPID:</small>
total focus merge products	24 <small>Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels</small>
total parent images + focus merge products	24

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4196 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m100458	Focus Merges	4197MH0004580001015130000	1530	target Timber_Knob - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4196 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1522-1529 - best focus image product
		4197MH0004580001015131500	1531	target Timber_Knob - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4196 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1522-1529 - range map product
		4197MH0004580001015132000	1532	mosaic from Josephine_Lake to Timber_Knob - mosaic position 5 of 5 - standoff near 85 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4196 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1512-1519 - best focus image product
		4197MH0004580001015133500	1533	mosaic from Josephine_Lake to Timber_Knob - mosaic position 5 of 5 - standoff near 85 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4196 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1512-1519 - range map product
		4197MH0004580001015134000	1534	mosaic from Josephine_Lake to Timber_Knob - mosaic position 4 of 5 - standoff near 85 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4196 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1502-1509 - best focus image product
		4197MH0004580001015135500	1535	mosaic from Josephine_Lake to Timber_Knob - mosaic position 4 of 5 - standoff near 85 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4196 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1502-1509 - range map product
		4197MH0004580001015136000	1536	mosaic from Josephine_Lake to Timber_Knob - mosaic position 3 of 5 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4196 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1492-1499 - best focus image product
		4197MH0004580001015137500	1537	mosaic from Josephine_Lake to Timber_Knob - mosaic position 3 of 5 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4196 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1492-1499 - range map product
		4197MH0004580001015138000	1538	mosaic from Josephine_Lake to Timber_Knob - mosaic position 2 of 5 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4196 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1482-1489 - best focus image product
		4197MH0004580001015139500	1539	mosaic from Josephine_Lake to Timber_Knob - mosaic position 2 of 5 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4196 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1482-1489 - range map product
		4197MH0004580001015140000	1540	mosaic from Josephine_Lake to Timber_Knob - mosaic position 1 of 5 - standoff near 95 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4196 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1472-1479 - best focus image product
		4197MH0004580001015141500	1541	mosaic from Josephine_Lake to Timber_Knob - mosaic position 1 of 5 - standoff near 95 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4196 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1472-1479 - range map product
		4197MH0004580001015142000	1542	target Josephine_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4196 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1462-1469 - best focus image product
		4197MH0004580001015143500	1543	target Josephine_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4196 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1462-1469 - range map product
		4197MH0004580001015144000	1544	target Josephine_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4196 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1452-1459 - best focus image product
		4197MH0004580001015145500	1545	target Josephine_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4196 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1452-1459 - range map product
		4197MH0004580001015146000	1546	target Josephine_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4196 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1442-1449 - best focus image product
		4197MH0004580001015147500	1547	target Josephine_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4196 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1442-1449 - range map product
		4197MH0004580001015148000	1548	target Second_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4196 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1432-1439 - best focus image product
		4197MH0004580001015149500	1549	target Second_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4196 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1432-1439 - range map product
		4197MH0004580001015150000	1550	target Second_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4196 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1422-1429 - best focus image product
		4197MH0004580001015151500	1551	target Second_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4196 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1422-1429 - range map product
		4197MH0004580001015152000	1552	target Second_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4196 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1412-1419 - best focus image product
		4197MH0004580001015153500	1553	target Second_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4196 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1412-1419 - range map product

updated: 25_July_2024

Sol 4199 - MAHLI Images

acquired(performed date(s))	20-May-24
camera position	65
total parent images	65
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	65

MAHLI image of the targets Garnet_Lake, Rixford_Pass and Reggae_Pole.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00290	Garnet_Lake ~24 cm standoff	4199MH00190001501554C0D	1554	autofocus sub-frame for target Garnet_Lake - standoff near 24 cm
		4199MH00190001501555C0D	1555	target Garnet_Lake - standoff near 24 cm
mN00878	Garnet_Lake stereo-1 ~9 cm standoff	4199MH00878001501556C0D	1556	autofocus sub-frame for target Garnet_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm
		4199MH00878001501557C0D	1557	target Garnet_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm
		4199MH00878001501558C0D	1558	target Garnet_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00878001501559C0D	1559	target Garnet_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00878001501560C0D	1560	target Garnet_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00878001501561C0D	1561	target Garnet_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00878001501562C0D	1562	target Garnet_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00878001501563C0D	1563	target Garnet_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00878001501564C0D	1564	target Garnet_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00878001501565C0D	1565	target Garnet_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00878	Garnet_Lake stereo-2 ~9 cm standoff	4199MH00878001501566C0D	1566	autofocus sub-frame for target Garnet_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm
		4199MH00878001501567C0D	1567	target Garnet_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm
		4199MH00878001501568C0D	1568	target Garnet_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00878001501569C0D	1569	target Garnet_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00878001501570C0D	1570	target Garnet_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00878001501571C0D	1571	target Garnet_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00878001501572C0D	1572	target Garnet_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00878001501573C0D	1573	target Garnet_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00878001501574C0D	1574	target Garnet_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00878001501575C0D	1575	target Garnet_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00290	Rixford_Pass ~25 cm standoff	4199MH00190001501576C0D	1576	autofocus sub-frame for target Rixford_Pass - standoff near 25 cm
mN00224	Rixford_Pass stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4199MH00224001501577C0D	1577	target Rixford_Pass - standoff near 25 cm
		4199MH00224001501578C0D	1578	autofocus sub-frame for target Rixford_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00224	Rixford_Pass stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4199MH00224001501579C0D	1579	target Rixford_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4199MH00224001501580C0D	1580	target Rixford_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00224001501581C0D	1581	target Rixford_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00224001501582C0D	1582	target Rixford_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00224001501583C0D	1583	target Rixford_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00224001501584C0D	1584	target Rixford_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00224001501585C0D	1585	target Rixford_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00224001501586C0D	1586	target Rixford_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00224001501587C0D	1587	target Rixford_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00224001501588C0D	1588	autofocus sub-frame for target Rixford_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00224	Rixford_Pass stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4199MH00224001501589C0D	1589	target Rixford_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4199MH00224001501590C0D	1590	target Rixford_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00224001501591C0D	1591	target Rixford_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00224001501592C0D	1592	target Rixford_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00224001501593C0D	1593	target Rixford_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00224001501594C0D	1594	target Rixford_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00224001501595C0D	1595	target Rixford_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00224001501596C0D	1596	target Rixford_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00224001501597C0D	1597	target Rixford_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mN00290	Reggae_Pole ~24 cm standoff	4199MH00190001501598C0D
mN00297	Reggae_Pole stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	4199MH00297001501600C0D	1600	autofocus sub-frame for target Reggae_Pole - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4199MH00297001501601C0D	1601	target Reggae_Pole - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
mN00297	Reggae_Pole stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	4199MH00297001501602C0D	1602	target Reggae_Pole - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00297001501603C0D	1603	target Reggae_Pole - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00297001501604C0D	1604	target Reggae_Pole - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00297001501605C0D	1605	target Reggae_Pole - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00297001501606C0D	1606	target Reggae_Pole - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00297001501607C0D	1607	target Reggae_Pole - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00297001501608C0D	1608	target Reggae_Pole - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00297001501609C0D	1609	target Reggae_Pole - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00297001501610C0D	1610	autofocus sub-frame for target Reggae_Pole - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4199MH00297001501611C0D	1611	target Reggae_Pole - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
mN00297	Reggae_Pole stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	4199MH00297001501612C0D	1612	target Reggae_Pole - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00297001501613C0D	1613	target Reggae_Pole - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00297001501614C0D	1614	target Reggae_Pole - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00297001501615C0D	1615	target Reggae_Pole - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00297001501616C0D	1616	target Reggae_Pole - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00297001501617C0D	1617	target Reggae_Pole - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00297001501618C0D	1618	target Reggae_Pole - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4199MH00297001501619C0D	1619	target Reggae_Pole - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 31_May_2024

Sol 4200 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	30-May-24
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	12
total parent images + focus merge products	12

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4199 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1000163	Focus Merges	4200MH001630001501620900	1620	target Reggae_Pole - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4199 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1612-1619 - best focus image product
		4200MH001630001501621500	1621	target Reggae_Pole - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4199 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1612-1619 - range map product
		4200MH001630001501622800	1622	target Reggae_Pole - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4199 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1602-1609 - best focus image product
		4200MH001630001501623500	1623	target Reggae_Pole - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4199 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1602-1609 - range map product
		4200MH001630001501624400	1624	target Rixford_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4199 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1590-1597 - best focus image product
		4200MH001630001501625500	1625	target Rixford_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4199 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1590-1597 - range map product
		4200MH001630001501626400	1626	target Rixford_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4199 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1580-1587 - best focus image product
		4200MH001630001501627500	1627	target Rixford_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4199 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1580-1587 - range map product
		4200MH001630001501628800	1628	target Garnet_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4199 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1568-1575 - best focus image product
		4200MH001630001501629500	1629	target Garnet_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4199 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1568-1575 - range map product
		4200MH001630001501630900	1630	target Garnet_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4199 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1558-1565 - best focus image product
		4200MH001630001501631500	1631	target Garnet_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4199 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1558-1565 - range map product

updated: 16_July_2024

Sol 4202 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	3-Jan-2012 to 4-Jul-2024
camera position	8
total parent images	85
focus merges performed	8
total focus merge products	18
total parent images + focus merge products	103

MAHLI imaged the targets Gray_Peak and Snow_Lakes. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mNI00359	Gray_Peak ~25 cm standoff	4202MH0003900015016320D	1632	autofocus sub-frame for target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm
		4202MH0003900015016330D	1633	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm
		4202MH0003900015016340D	1634	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH0003900015016350D	1635	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH0003900015016360D	1636	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH0003900015016370D	1637	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH0003900015016380D	1638	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH0003900015016390D	1639	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH0003900015016400D	1640	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH0003900015016410D	1641	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00182	Gray_Peak APXS spot 1 stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4202MH00018200015016420D	1642	autofocus sub-frame for target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4202MH00018200015016430D	1643	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4202MH00018200015016440D	1644	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00018200015016450D	1645	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00018200015016460D	1646	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00018200015016470D	1647	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00018200015016480D	1648	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00018200015016490D	1649	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00018200015016500D	1650	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00018200015016510D	1651	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00182	Gray_Peak APXS spot 1 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4202MH00018200015016520D	1652	autofocus sub-frame for target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4202MH00018200015016530D	1653	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4202MH00018200015016540D	1654	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00018200015016550D	1655	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00018200015016560D	1656	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00018200015016570D	1657	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00018200015016580D	1658	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00018200015016590D	1659	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00018200015016600D	1660	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00018200015016610D	1661	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00335	Gray_Peak APXS spot 1 ~2 cm standoff	4202MH00033500015016620D	1662	autofocus sub-frame for target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 2 cm
		4202MH00033500015016630D	1663	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 2 cm
		4202MH00033500015016640D	1664	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00033500015016650D	1665	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00033500015016660D	1666	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00033500015016670D	1667	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00033500015016680D	1668	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00033500015016690D	1669	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00033500015016700D	1670	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00033500015016710D	1671	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00182	Gray_Peak APXS spot 2 ~5 cm standoff	4202MH00018200015016720D	1672	autofocus sub-frame for target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4202MH00018200015016730D	1673	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4202MH00018200015016740D	1674	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00018200015016750D	1675	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00018200015016760D	1676	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00018200015016770D	1677	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00018200015016780D	1678	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00018200015016790D	1679	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00018200015016800D	1680	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00018200015016810D	1681	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00706	Snow_Lakes ~25 cm standoff	4202MH00070600015016820D	1682	autofocus sub-frame for target Snow_Lakes - standoff near 25 cm
		4202MH00070600015016830D	1683	target Snow_Lakes - standoff near 25 cm
		4202MH00070600015016840D	1684	target Snow_Lakes - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mNI00879	Snow_Lakes stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4202MH00087900015016850D	1685	autofocus sub-frame for target Snow_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4202MH00087900015016860D	1686	target Snow_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4202MH00087900015016870D	1687	target Snow_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		4202MH00087900015016880D	1688	target Snow_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00087900015016890D	1689	target Snow_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00087900015016900D	1690	target Snow_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00087900015016910D	1691	target Snow_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00087900015016920D	1692	target Snow_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00087900015016930D	1693	target Snow_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00087900015016940D	1694	target Snow_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4202MH00087900015016950D	1695	target Snow_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

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mH00879	Snow_Lakes stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4202MH00879001501696C00	1696	autofocus sub-frame for target Snow_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4202MH00879001501697C00	1697	target Snow_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4202MH00879001501698C00	1698	target Snow_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		4202MH00879001501699C00	1699	target Snow_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00879001501700C00	1700	target Snow_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00879001501701C00	1701	target Snow_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00879001501702C00	1702	target Snow_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00879001501703C00	1703	target Snow_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00879001501704C00	1704	target Snow_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00879001501705C00	1705	target Snow_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4202MH00879001501706C00	1706	target Snow_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mH00885	Snow_Lakes ~1 cm standoff	4202MH00885001501707C00	1707	autofocus sub-frame for target Snow_Lakes - standoff near 1 cm
		4202MH00885001501708C00	1708	target Snow_Lakes - standoff near 1 cm
		4202MH00885001501709C00	1709	target Snow_Lakes - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		4202MH00885001501710C00	1710	target Snow_Lakes - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00885001501711C00	1711	target Snow_Lakes - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00885001501712C00	1712	target Snow_Lakes - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00885001501713C00	1713	target Snow_Lakes - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00885001501714C00	1714	target Snow_Lakes - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00885001501715C00	1715	target Snow_Lakes - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4202MH00885001501716C00	1716	target Snow_Lakes - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4202MH00885001501717C00	1717	target Snow_Lakes - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mH00170	Focus Merges	4202MH0017000150171800	1718	target Snow_Lakes - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4202 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 1710-1717 - best focus image product
		4202MH0017000150171950	1719	target Snow_Lakes - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4202 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 1710-1717 - range map product
		4202MH0017000150172080	1720	target Snow_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4202 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 1699-1706 - best focus image product
		4202MH0017000150172150	1721	target Snow_Lakes - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4202 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 1699-1706 - range map product
		4202MH0017000150172280	1722	target Snow_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4202 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 1688-1695 - best focus image product
		4202MH0017000150172350	1723	target Snow_Lakes - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4202 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 1688-1695 - range map product
		4202MH0017000150172480	1724	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4202 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 1674-1681 - best focus image product
		4202MH0017000150172550	1725	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4202 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 1674-1681 - range map product
		4202MH0017000150172680	1726	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4202 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 1664-1671 - best focus image product
		4202MH0017000150172750	1727	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4202 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 1664-1671 - range map product
		4202MH0017000150172880	1728	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4202 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 1654-1661 - best focus image product
		4202MH0017000150172950	1729	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4202 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 1654-1661 - range map product
		4202MH0017000150173080	1730	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4202 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 1644-1651 - best focus image product
		4202MH0017000150173150	1731	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4202 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 1644-1651 - range map product
		4202MH0017000150173280	1732	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4202 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 1634-1641 - best focus image product
		4202MH0017000150173350	1733	target Gray_Peak - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4202 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 1634-1641 - range map product

updated: 06_June_2024

Sol 4206 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	5-Jun-24
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	11
total focus merge products:	22
total parent images + focus merge products:	22

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4205 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00449	Focus Merges	4206MH000490001501851900	1851	target Convict_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1843-1850 - best focus image product
		4206MH000490001501852500	1852	target Convict_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1843-1850 - range map product
		4206MH000490001501853900	1853	target Convict_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1832-1839 - best focus image product
		4206MH000490001501854500	1854	target Convict_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1832-1839 - range map product
		4206MH000490001501855900	1855	target Gem_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1818-1825 - best focus image product
		4206MH000490001501856500	1856	target Gem_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1818-1825 - range map product
		4206MH000490001501857900	1857	target Gem_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1808-1815 - best focus image product
		4206MH000490001501858500	1858	target Gem_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1808-1815 - range map product
		4206MH000490001501859900	1859	target Gem_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1798-1805 - best focus image product
		4206MH000490001501860500	1860	target Gem_Lakes - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1798-1805 - range map product
		4206MH000490001501861900	1861	target Starr_Minaret - mosaic position 6 of 6 - standoff between 15 cm and 22 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1786-1793 - best focus image product
		4206MH000490001501862500	1862	target Starr_Minaret - mosaic position 6 of 6 - standoff between 15 cm and 22 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1786-1793 - range map product
		4206MH000490001501863900	1863	target Starr_Minaret - mosaic position 5 of 6 - standoff between 15 cm and 22 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1776-1783 - best focus image product
		4206MH000490001501864500	1864	target Starr_Minaret - mosaic position 5 of 6 - standoff between 15 cm and 22 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1776-1783 - range map product
		4206MH000490001501865900	1865	target Starr_Minaret - mosaic position 4 of 6 - standoff between 15 cm and 22 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1766-1773 - best focus image product
		4206MH000490001501866500	1866	target Starr_Minaret - mosaic position 4 of 6 - standoff between 15 cm and 22 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1766-1773 - range map product
		4206MH000490001501867900	1867	target Starr_Minaret - mosaic position 3 of 6 - standoff between 15 cm and 22 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1756-1763 - best focus image product
		4206MH000490001501868500	1868	target Starr_Minaret - mosaic position 3 of 6 - standoff between 15 cm and 22 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1756-1763 - range map product
		4206MH000490001501869900	1869	target Starr_Minaret - mosaic position 2 of 6 - standoff between 15 cm and 22 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1746-1753 - best focus image product
		4206MH000490001501870500	1870	target Starr_Minaret - mosaic position 2 of 6 - standoff between 15 cm and 22 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1746-1753 - range map product
		4206MH000490001501871900	1871	target Starr_Minaret - mosaic position 1 of 6 - standoff between 15 cm and 22 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1736-1743 - best focus image product
		4206MH000490001501872500	1872	target Starr_Minaret - mosaic position 1 of 6 - standoff between 15 cm and 22 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1736-1743 - range map product

Sol 4207 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
		Camera position:	6		Image ID:		
		Total parent images:	53		Black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received		
		Focus merges performed:	0		CPDPD:		
		Total focus merge products:	0		Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in POS archive product labels		
		Total parent images + Focus merge products:	53				
summary of MAHLI activities: During the day, MAHLI imaged the target Convict_Lake. At night, MAHLI re-imaged the target Convict_Lake using different combinations of the LEDs, including ultraviolet to seek fluorescence.							
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)			
mN100706	Convict_Lake ~24 cm standoff	4207MH000706001501873000	1873	autofocus sub-frame for target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 24 cm			
		4207MH000706001501874000	1874	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 24 cm			
		4207MH000706001501875000	1875	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 24 cm - alternative auto-exposure			
mN100721	Convict_Lake APXS spot 2 stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	4207MH000721001501876000	1876	autofocus sub-frame for target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm			
		4207MH000721001501877000	1877	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm			
		4207MH000721001501878000	1878	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure			
		4207MH000721001501879000	1879	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4207MH000721001501880000	1880	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4207MH000721001501881000	1881	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4207MH000721001501882000	1882	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4207MH000721001501883000	1883	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4207MH000721001501884000	1884	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4207MH000721001501885000	1885	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4207MH000721001501886000	1886	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		mN100721	Convict_Lake APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	4207MH000721001501887000	1887	autofocus sub-frame for target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm	
				4207MH000721001501888000	1888	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm	
				4207MH000721001501889000	1889	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure	
				4207MH000721001501890000	1890	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
4207MH000721001501891000	1891			target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack			
4207MH000721001501892000	1892			target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack			
4207MH000721001501893000	1893			target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack			
4207MH000721001501894000	1894			target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack			
4207MH000721001501895000	1895			target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack			
4207MH000721001501896000	1896			target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack			
4207MH000721001501897000	1897			target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack			
mN100721	Convict_Lake APXS spot 1 ~45 mm standoff			4207MH000721001501898000	1898	autofocus sub-frame for target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm	
				4207MH000721001501899000	1899	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm	
				4207MH000721001501900000	1900	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - alternative auto-exposure	
				4207MH000721001501901000	1901	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4207MH000721001501902000	1902	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4207MH000721001501903000	1903	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4207MH000721001501904000	1904	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4207MH000721001501905000	1905	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4207MH000721001501906000	1906	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4207MH000721001501907000	1907	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4207MH000721001501908000	1908	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		mN100880	Convict_Lake APXS spot 2 night imaging ~5 cm standoff	4207MH000880001501909000	1909	autofocus sub-frame for target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - group 2 white LEDs on	
				4207MH000880001501910000	1910	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - group 1 white LEDs on	
				4207MH000880001501911000	1911	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - group 2 white LEDs on	
				4207MH000880001501912000	1912	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - group 2 white LEDs on - alternative auto-exposure	
4207MH000880001501913000	1913			target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - all white LEDs on			
4207MH000880001501914000	1914			target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - ultraviolet LEDs on with 30-second manual exposure			
4207MH000880001501915000	1915			target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - dark frame - no LEDs on - 30-second manual exposure			
4207MH000880001501916000	1916			target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - ultraviolet LEDs on with 60-second manual exposure			
4207MH000880001501917000	1917			target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - dark frame - no LEDs on - 60-second manual exposure			
4207MH000880001501918000	1918			target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - group 2 white LEDs on - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack			
4207MH000880001501919000	1919			target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - group 2 white LEDs on - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack			
4207MH000880001501920000	1920			target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - group 2 white LEDs on - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack			
4207MH000880001501921000	1921			target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - group 2 white LEDs on - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack			
4207MH000880001501922000	1922			target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - group 2 white LEDs on - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack			
4207MH000880001501923000	1923			target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - group 2 white LEDs on - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack			
4207MH000880001501924000	1924	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - group 2 white LEDs on - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack					
4207MH000880001501925000	1925	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - group 2 white LEDs on - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack					

updated: 10_June_2024

Sol 4208 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	0-Jun-24
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	4
total focus merge products:	8
total parent images + focus merge products:	8

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4207 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00133	Focus Merges	4208MH001530001501926R00	1926	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - group 2 white LEDs on - focus stack acquired sol 4207 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1918-1925 - best focus image product
		4208MH001530001501927S00	1927	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - group 2 white LEDs on - focus stack acquired sol 4207 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1918-1925 - range map product
		4208MH001530001501928R00	1928	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4207 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1901-1908 - best focus image product
		4208MH001530001501929S00	1929	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4207 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1901-1908 - range map product
		4208MH001530001501930R00	1930	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4207 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1890-1897 - best focus image product
		4208MH001530001501931S00	1931	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4207 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1890-1897 - range map product
		4208MH001530001501932R00	1932	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4207 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1879-1886 - best focus image product
		4208MH001530001501933S00	1933	target Convict_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4207 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1879-1886 - range map product

Sol 4209 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
		Camera position	72		Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received		
		total parent images	0		CPDPD:		
		focus merges performed	0		Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in POS archive product labels		
		total focus merge products	0				
		total parent images + focus merge products	72				
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Grass_Lake and the target Snow_Lakes.							
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)			
mNI00705	Grass_Lake after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4209MH0007060001501934C00	1934	autoFocus sub-frame for target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm			
		4209MH0007060011501935C00	1935	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm			
		4209MH0007060021501936C00	1936	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure			
mNI00879	Grass_Lake after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4209MH0008790001501937C00	1937	autoFocus sub-frame for target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm			
		4209MH0008790011501938C00	1938	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm			
		4209MH0008790021501939C00	1939	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure			
		4209MH0008790031501940C00	1940	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4209MH0008790041501941C00	1941	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4209MH0008790051501942C00	1942	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4209MH0008790061501943C00	1943	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4209MH0008790071501944C00	1944	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4209MH0008790081501945C00	1945	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4209MH0008790091501946C00	1946	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4209MH0008790101501947C00	1947	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		mNI00879	Grass_Lake after DRT stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4209MH0008790001501948C00	1948	autoFocus sub-frame for target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm	
				4209MH0008790011501949C00	1949	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm	
				4209MH0008790021501950C00	1950	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - alternative auto-exposure	
4209MH0008790031501951C00	1951			target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack			
4209MH0008790041501952C00	1952			target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack			
4209MH0008790051501953C00	1953			target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack			
4209MH0008790061501954C00	1954			target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack			
4209MH0008790071501955C00	1955			target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack			
4209MH0008790081501956C00	1956			target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack			
4209MH0008790091501957C00	1957			target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack			
4209MH0008790101501958C00	1958			target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack			
mNI00885	Grass_Lake after DRT ~1 cm standoff			4209MH000850001501959C00	1959	autoFocus sub-frame for target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm	
				4209MH000850011501960C00	1960	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm	
				4209MH000850021501961C00	1961	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure	
		4209MH000850031501962C00	1962	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4209MH000850041501963C00	1963	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4209MH000850051501964C00	1964	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4209MH000850061501965C00	1965	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4209MH000850071501966C00	1966	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4209MH000850081501967C00	1967	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4209MH000850091501968C00	1968	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4209MH000850101501969C00	1969	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		mNI00706	Snow_Lakes ~24 cm standoff	4209MH0007060001501970C00	1970	autoFocus sub-frame for target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 24 cm	
				4209MH0007060011501971C00	1971	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 24 cm	
				4209MH0007060021501972C00	1972	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 24 cm - alternative auto-exposure	
mNI00834	Snow_Lakes APXS spot 1 ~4 cm standoff	4209MH000840001501973C00	1973	autoFocus sub-frame for target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm			
		4209MH000840011501974C00	1974	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm			
		4209MH000840021501975C00	1975	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure			
		4209MH000840031501976C00	1976	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4209MH000840041501977C00	1977	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4209MH000840051501978C00	1978	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4209MH000840061501979C00	1979	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4209MH000840071501980C00	1980	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4209MH000840081501981C00	1981	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4209MH000840091501982C00	1982	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		4209MH000840101501983C00	1983	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		mNI00834	Snow_Lakes APXS spot 2 ~4 cm standoff	4209MH000840001501984C00	1984	autoFocus sub-frame for target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm	
				4209MH000840011501985C00	1985	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm	
				4209MH000840021501986C00	1986	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure	
4209MH000840031501987C00	1987			target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack			
4209MH000840041501988C00	1988			target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack			
4209MH000840051501989C00	1989			target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack			
4209MH000840061501990C00	1990			target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack			
4209MH000840071501991C00	1991			target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack			
4209MH000840081501992C00	1992			target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack			
4209MH000840091501993C00	1993			target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack			
4209MH000840101501994C00	1994			target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack			

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mN00814	Snow_Lakes APXS spot 3 ~4 cm standoff	4209MH00834001501995C00	1995	autofocus sub-frame for target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 4 cm
		4209MH00834001501996C00	1996	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 4 cm
		4209MH008340021501997C00	1997	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		4209MH008340031501998C00	1998	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4209MH008340031501999C00	1999	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4209MH008340031502000C00	2000	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4209MH008340031502001C00	2001	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4209MH008340031502002C00	2002	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4209MH008340031502003C00	2003	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4209MH008340031502004C00	2004	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4209MH008340031502005C00	2005	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 10_June_2024

Sol 4210 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	9 Jun 24	Image ID:	
camera position:	0	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received	
total parent images:	0	CDPID:	
focus merges performed:	6	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels	
total focus merge products:	13		
total parent images + focus merge products:	13		

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4209 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1000163	Focus Merges	4210MH001630001502006R00	2006	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4209 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1998-2005 - best focus image product
		4210MH001630001502007500	2007	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4209 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1998-2005 - range map product
		4210MH001630001502008R00	2008	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4209 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1987-1994 - best focus image product
		4210MH001630001502009500	2009	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4209 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1987-1994 - range map product
		4210MH001630001502010R00	2010	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4209 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1976-1983 - best focus image product
		4210MH001630001502011500	2011	target Snow_Lakes - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4209 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1976-1983 - range map product
		4210MH001630001502012R00	2012	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4209 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1962-1969 - best focus image product
		4210MH001630001502013500	2013	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4209 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1962-1969 - range map product
		4210MH001630001502014R00	2014	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4209 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1951-1958 - best focus image product
		4210MH001630001502015500	2015	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4209 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1951-1958 - range map product
		4210MH001630001502016R00	2016	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4209 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1940-1947 - best focus image product
		4210MH001630001502017500	2017	target Grass_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4209 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1940-1947 - range map product

updated: 31_July_2024

Sol 4212 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	01-Nov-2023
Camera position	4
total parent images	50
focus merges performed	4
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	54

MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Mammoth_Lakes after DRT and after a drill bit preload test. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALISE DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mNI00705	Mammoth_Lakes after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4212MH0007060001502018C00	2018	autoFocus sub-frame for intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		4212MH000706001502019C00	2019	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		4212MH0007060021502020C00	2020	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mNI00879	Mammoth_Lakes after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4212MH000879001502021C00	2021	autoFocus sub-frame for intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4212MH0008790021502022C00	2022	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4212MH000879002902023C00	2023	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		4212MH0008790031502024C00	2024	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4212MH000879003902025C00	2025	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4212MH0008790031502026C00	2026	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4212MH000879003902027C00	2027	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4212MH0008790031502028C00	2028	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4212MH000879003902029C00	2029	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4212MH0008790031502030C00	2030	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4212MH000879003902031C00	2031	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00879	Mammoth_Lakes after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4212MH0008790031502032C00	2032	autoFocus sub-frame for intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4212MH000879003902033C00	2033	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4212MH0008790031502034C00	2034	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		4212MH000879003902035C00	2035	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4212MH0008790031502036C00	2036	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4212MH000879003902037C00	2037	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4212MH0008790031502038C00	2038	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4212MH000879003902039C00	2039	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4212MH0008790031502040C00	2040	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4212MH000879003902041C00	2041	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4212MH0008790031502042C00	2042	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00822	Mammoth_Lakes after DRT APXS spot 2 ~1 cm standoff	4212MH000822001502043C00	2043	autoFocus sub-frame for intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		4212MH000822001902044C00	2044	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		4212MH000822002302045C00	2045	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		4212MH000822002702046C00	2046	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4212MH000822003102047C00	2047	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4212MH000822003502048C00	2048	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4212MH000822003902049C00	2049	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4212MH000822004302050C00	2050	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4212MH000822004702051C00	2051	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4212MH000822005102052C00	2052	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4212MH000822005502053C00	2053	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00879	Mammoth_Lakes after DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	4212MH0008790031502054C00	2054	autoFocus sub-frame for intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4212MH000879003902055C00	2055	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4212MH0008790031502056C00	2056	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		4212MH000879003902057C00	2057	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4212MH0008790031502058C00	2058	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4212MH000879003902059C00	2059	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4212MH0008790031502060C00	2060	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4212MH000879003902061C00	2061	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4212MH0008790031502062C00	2062	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4212MH000879003902063C00	2063	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4212MH0008790031502064C00	2064	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00881	Mammoth_Lakes after DRT after drill bit preload test ~35 cm standoff	4212MH000881001502065C00	2065	autoFocus sub-frame for intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after pre-load - after sol 4212 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 35 cm
		4212MH000881001902066C00	2066	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after pre-load - after sol 4212 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 35 cm
		4212MH000881002302067C00	2067	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after pre-load - after sol 4212 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 35 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mNI00153	Focus Merges	4212MH000153001502068M00	2068	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4212 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2037-2064 - best focus image product
		4212MH000153001902069S00	2069	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4212 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2057-2064 - range map product
		4212MH000153001502070M00	2070	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4212 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2046-2053 - best focus image product
		4212MH000153001902071S00	2071	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4212 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2046-2053 - range map product
		4212MH000153001502072M00	2072	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4212 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2035-2042 - best focus image product
		4212MH000153001902073S00	2073	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4212 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2035-2042 - range map product
		4212MH000153001502074M00	2074	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4212 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2024-2031 - best focus image product
		4212MH000153001902075S00	2075	intended Mammoth_Lakes drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4212 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2024-2031 - range map product

updated: 26_July_2024

Sol 4216 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	26-Jun-24			
		Camera position	2	Image ID:		
		total parent images	35	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received		
		focus merges performed	3	CDPID:		
		total focus merge products	6	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		
		total parent images + focus merge products	44			
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Mammoth_Lakes2 after a drill bit preload test. MAHLI also imaged the target Loch_Leven and the intended site for the Mammoth_Lakes2 sample discard pile. Focus stack images were merged as well.						
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN00465	Mammoth_Lakes2 after drill bit preload test ~35 cm standoff	4216MH000465001502076C00	2076	autofocus sub-frame for intended Mammoth_Lakes2 drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload - standoff near 35 cm		
		4216MH000465001502077C00	2077	intended Mammoth_Lakes2 drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload - standoff near 35 cm		
mN00882	Mammoth_Lakes2 after drill bit preload test ~5 cm standoff	4216MH000882001502076C00	2076	autofocus sub-frame for intended Mammoth_Lakes2 drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload - standoff near 5 cm		
		4216MH000882001502079C00	2079	intended Mammoth_Lakes2 drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload - standoff near 5 cm		
mN00190	Loch_Leven ~25 cm standoff	4216MH00190001502080C00	2080	autofocus sub-frame for target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm		
		4216MH00190001502081C00	2081	target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm		
mN00168	Loch_Leven APXS spot 2 stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4216MH00168001502082C00	2082	autofocus sub-frame for target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		4216MH00168001502083C00	2083	target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		4216MH00168001502084C00	2084	target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4216MH00168001502085C00	2085	target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4216MH00168001502086C00	2086	target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4216MH00168001502087C00	2087	target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4216MH00168001502088C00	2088	target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4216MH00168001502089C00	2089	target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4216MH00168001502090C00	2090	target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4216MH00168001502091C00	2091	target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00168	Loch_Leven APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4216MH00168001502092C00	2092	autofocus sub-frame for target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				4216MH00168001502093C00	2093	target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
4216MH00168001502094C00	2094			target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4216MH00168001502095C00	2095			target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4216MH00168001502096C00	2096			target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4216MH00168001502097C00	2097			target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4216MH00168001502098C00	2098			target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4216MH00168001502099C00	2099			target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4216MH00168001502100C00	2100			target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4216MH00168001502101C00	2101			target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00168	Loch_Leven APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff			4216MH00168001502102C00	2102	autofocus sub-frame for target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
				4216MH00168001502103C00	2103	target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4216MH00168001502104C00	2104	target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4216MH00168001502105C00	2105	target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4216MH00168001502106C00	2106	target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4216MH00168001502107C00	2107	target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4216MH00168001502108C00	2108	target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4216MH00168001502109C00	2109	target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4216MH00168001502110C00	2110	target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4216MH00168001502111C00	2111	target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00190	Intended Mammoth_Lakes2 Drill Sample Discard Site Before Discard ~24 cm standoff	4216MH00190001502112C00	2112	autofocus sub-frame for intended Mammoth_Lakes2 drill sample discard site - before drill attempt and before discard - standoff near 24 cm
				4216MH00190001502113C00	2113	intended Mammoth_Lakes2 drill sample discard site - before drill attempt and before discard - standoff near 24 cm
mN00289	Focus Merges	4216MH0019300150211400	2114	target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4216 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2104-2111 - best focus image product		
		4216MH0019300150211500	2115	target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4216 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2104-2111 - range map product		
		4216MH0019300150211600	2116	target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4216 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2094-2101 - best focus image product		
		4216MH0019300150211700	2117	target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4216 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2094-2101 - range map product		
		4216MH0019300150211800	2118	target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4216 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2084-2091 - best focus image product		
		4216MH0019300150211900	2119	target Loch_Leven - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4216 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2084-2091 - range map product		

updated: 29_july_2024

Sol 4234 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	6 Jul 24
camera position:	0
total parent images:	15
focus merges performed:	0
total focus merge products:	0
total parent images + focus merge products:	14

Image ID:	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
CDPID:	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the Mammoth_Lakes2 dr/ll hole and cuttings.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00187	Mammoth_Lakes2 drill hole drilled on Sol 4219 ~24 cm standoff	4234MH001970001502120C00	2120	autoFocus sub-frame for drill hole in rock named Mammoth_Lakes2 - drilled sol 4219 - standoff near 24 cm
		4234MH001970001502121K00	2121	drill hole in rock named Mammoth_Lakes2 - drilled sol 4219 - standoff near 24 cm
mN00774	Mammoth_Lakes2 drill hole drilled on Sol 4219 ~95 mm standoff	4234MH007740001502122C00	2122	autoFocus sub-frame for drill hole in rock named Mammoth_Lakes2 - drilled sol 4219 - sub-frame positioned to focus on surface outside hole - standoff near 95 mm
		4234MH007740001502123K00	2123	drill hole in rock named Mammoth_Lakes2 - drilled sol 4219 - focus based on preceding autofocus sub-frame - standoff near 95 mm
mN00152	Mammoth_Lakes2 drill cuttings ~25 mm standoff	4234MH001520001502124C00	2124	autoFocus sub-frame for Mammoth_Lakes2 drill cuttings - standoff near 35 mm
		4234MH001520001502125K00	2125	Mammoth_Lakes2 drill cuttings - standoff near 35 mm
		4234MH001520001502126C00	2126	Mammoth_Lakes2 drill cuttings - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4234MH001520001502127K00	2127	Mammoth_Lakes2 drill cuttings - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4234MH001520001502128C00	2128	Mammoth_Lakes2 drill cuttings - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4234MH001520001502129K00	2129	Mammoth_Lakes2 drill cuttings - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4234MH001520001502130C00	2130	Mammoth_Lakes2 drill cuttings - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4234MH001520001502131K00	2131	Mammoth_Lakes2 drill cuttings - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4234MH001520001502132C00	2132	Mammoth_Lakes2 drill cuttings - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4234MH001520001502133K00	2133	Mammoth_Lakes2 drill cuttings - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 16_August_2024

Sol 4235 - MAHLI Images

summary of MAHLI activities		Focus stack images from Sol 4234 were merged. MAHLI images that correspond to CDPIDs 3480 through 4911 (data from Sol 4056-4137) were deleted from the MAHLI OGA non-volatile memory storage. MAHLI imaged the Mammoth_Lakes2 drill cuttings.		
acquired/performed date(s):	5-Jul-24	Image ID:		
camera position:	4	total parent images:	2 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received	
total parent images:	2	focus merges performed:	1 CDPID:	
focus merges performed:	1	total focus merge products:	2 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels	
total focus merge products:	2	total parent images + focus merge products:	4	
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00258	Focus Merge	4235MH002580001502134K00	2134	Mammoth_Lakes2 drill cuttings - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4234 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2126-2133 - best focus image product
		4235MH002580001502135S00	2135	Mammoth_Lakes2 drill cuttings - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4234 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2126-2133 - range map product
mN00212	Mammoth_Lakes2 drill cuttings ~4 cm standoff	4235MH001120001502136C00	2136	autoFocus sub-frame for Mammoth_Lakes2 drill cuttings - standoff near 4 cm
		4235MH001120001502137C00	2137	Mammoth_Lakes2 drill cuttings - standoff near 4 cm

updated: 29_july_2024

Sol 4237 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	7 Jul 24
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	5
total focus merge products:	10
total parent images + focus merge products:	10

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4236 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00884	Focus Merges	4237MH000884000150220000	2200	Mammoth_Lake#2 drill hole wall - MAHLI pointing south - 30 degrees from normal and 9 cm standoff from plane defined by top of hole - night imaging - all white LEDs on - focus stack acquired sol 4236 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2187-2194 - best focus image product
		4237MH0008840001502201500	2201	Mammoth_Lake#2 drill hole wall - MAHLI pointing south - 30 degrees from normal and 9 cm standoff from plane defined by top of hole - night imaging - all white LEDs on - focus stack acquired sol 4236 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2187-2194 - range map product
		4237MH0008840001502202000	2202	target Lake_Ediza - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4236 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2174-2181 - best focus image product
		4237MH0008840001502203500	2203	target Lake_Ediza - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4236 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2174-2181 - range map product
		4237MH0008840001502204000	2204	target Lake_Ediza - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4236 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2164-2171 - best focus image product
		4237MH0008840001502205500	2205	target Lake_Ediza - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4236 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2164-2171 - range map product
		4237MH0008840001502206000	2206	target Glacier_Notch - stereo-2 - standoff near 30 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4236 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2152-2159 - best focus image product
		4237MH0008840001502207500	2207	target Glacier_Notch - stereo-2 - standoff near 30 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4236 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2152-2159 - range map product
		4237MH0008840001502208000	2208	target Glacier_Notch - stereo-1 - standoff near 31 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4236 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2141-2148 - best focus image product
		4237MH0008840001502209500	2209	target Glacier_Notch - stereo-1 - standoff near 31 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4236 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2141-2148 - range map product

Sol 4239 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	8 Jul 24
camera position:	75
total parent images:	75
focus merges performed:	0
total focus merge products:	0
total parent images + focus merge products:	75

MAHLI imaged the targets Lake_Dorothy and Pallasde_Glacier.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mNI00705	Lake_Dorothy ~25 cm standoff	4239MH00706001502210C00	2210	autofocus sub-frame for target Lake_Dorothy - standoff near 25 cm
		4239MH00706001502211C00	2211	target Lake_Dorothy - standoff near 25 cm
		4239MH00706001502212C00	2212	target Lake_Dorothy - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mNI00705	Lake_Dorothy stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4239MH00763001502213C00	2213	autofocus sub-frame for target Lake_Dorothy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4239MH00763001502214C00	2214	target Lake_Dorothy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4239MH00763001502215C00	2215	target Lake_Dorothy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		4239MH00763001502216C00	2216	target Lake_Dorothy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4239MH00763001502217C00	2217	target Lake_Dorothy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4239MH00763001502218C00	2218	target Lake_Dorothy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4239MH00763001502219C00	2219	target Lake_Dorothy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4239MH00763001502220C00	2220	target Lake_Dorothy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4239MH00763001502221C00	2221	target Lake_Dorothy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4239MH00763001502222C00	2222	target Lake_Dorothy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4239MH00763001502223C00	2223	target Lake_Dorothy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mNI00705	Lake_Dorothy stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4239MH00763001502224C00
4239MH00763001502225C00	2225			target Lake_Dorothy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
4239MH00763001502226C00	2226			target Lake_Dorothy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
4239MH00763001502227C00	2227			target Lake_Dorothy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
4239MH00763001502228C00	2228			target Lake_Dorothy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
4239MH00763001502229C00	2229			target Lake_Dorothy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
4239MH00763001502230C00	2230			target Lake_Dorothy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
4239MH00763001502231C00	2231			target Lake_Dorothy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
4239MH00763001502232C00	2232			target Lake_Dorothy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
4239MH00763001502233C00	2233			target Lake_Dorothy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4239MH00763001502234C00	2234			target Lake_Dorothy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00704	Lake_Dorothy ~1 cm standoff			4239MH00794001502235C00
		4239MH00794001502236C00	2236	target Lake_Dorothy - standoff near 1 cm
		4239MH00794001502237C00	2237	target Lake_Dorothy - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		4239MH00794001502238C00	2238	target Lake_Dorothy - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4239MH00794001502239C00	2239	target Lake_Dorothy - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4239MH00794001502240C00	2240	target Lake_Dorothy - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4239MH00794001502241C00	2241	target Lake_Dorothy - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4239MH00794001502242C00	2242	target Lake_Dorothy - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4239MH00794001502243C00	2243	target Lake_Dorothy - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4239MH00794001502244C00	2244	target Lake_Dorothy - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4239MH00794001502245C00	2245	target Lake_Dorothy - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mNI00705	Pallasde_Glacier ~25 cm standoff	4239MH00706001502246C00
4239MH00706001502247C00	2247			target Pallasde_Glacier - standoff near 25 cm
4239MH00706001502248C00	2248			target Pallasde_Glacier - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mNI00705	Pallasde_Glacier stereo-1 relief model position 1 ~5 cm standoff	4239MH00763001502249C00	2249	autofocus sub-frame for target Pallasde_Glacier - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4239MH00763001502250C00	2250	target Pallasde_Glacier - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4239MH00763001502251C00	2251	target Pallasde_Glacier - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		4239MH00763001502252C00	2252	target Pallasde_Glacier - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4239MH00763001502253C00	2253	target Pallasde_Glacier - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4239MH00763001502254C00	2254	target Pallasde_Glacier - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4239MH00763001502255C00	2255	target Pallasde_Glacier - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4239MH00763001502256C00	2256	target Pallasde_Glacier - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4239MH00763001502257C00	2257	target Pallasde_Glacier - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4239MH00763001502258C00	2258	target Pallasde_Glacier - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4239MH00763001502259C00	2259	target Pallasde_Glacier - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mNI00705	Pallasde_Glacier stereo-2 relief model position 2 ~5 cm standoff	4239MH00763001502260C00
4239MH00763001502261C00	2261			target Pallasde_Glacier - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm
4239MH00763001502262C00	2262			target Pallasde_Glacier - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
4239MH00763001502263C00	2263			target Pallasde_Glacier - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
4239MH00763001502264C00	2264			target Pallasde_Glacier - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
4239MH00763001502265C00	2265			target Pallasde_Glacier - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
4239MH00763001502266C00	2266			target Pallasde_Glacier - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
4239MH00763001502267C00	2267			target Pallasde_Glacier - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
4239MH00763001502268C00	2268			target Pallasde_Glacier - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
4239MH00763001502269C00	2269			target Pallasde_Glacier - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4239MH00763001502270C00	2270			target Pallasde_Glacier - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00705	Pallasde_Glacier relief model position 3 ~5 cm standoff			4239MH00705001502271C00
		4239MH00705001502272C00	2272	target Pallasde_Glacier - relief model position 3 - standoff near 5 cm
mNI00705	Pallasde_Glacier relief model position 4 ~5 cm standoff	4239MH00705001502273C00	2273	autofocus sub-frame for target Pallasde_Glacier - relief model position 4 - standoff near 5 cm
		4239MH00705001502274C00	2274	target Pallasde_Glacier - relief model position 4 - standoff near 5 cm
mNI00705	Pallasde_Glacier relief model position 5 ~5 cm standoff	4239MH00705001502275C00	2275	autofocus sub-frame for target Pallasde_Glacier - relief model position 5 - standoff near 5 cm
		4239MH00705001502276C00	2276	target Pallasde_Glacier - relief model position 5 - standoff near 5 cm

mN00794	Pallade_Glacier -1cm standoff	4239MH00794001502277C00	2277	autofocus sub-frame for target Pallade_Glacier - standoff near 1 cm
		4239MH00794001502278C00	2278	target Pallade_Glacier - standoff near 1 cm
		4239MH00794001502279C00	2279	target Pallade_Glacier - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		4239MH00794001502280C00	2280	target Pallade_Glacier - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in B-image relative focus stack
		4239MH00794001502281C00	2281	target Pallade_Glacier - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in B-image relative focus stack
		4239MH00794001502282C00	2282	target Pallade_Glacier - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in B-image relative focus stack
		4239MH00794001502283C00	2283	target Pallade_Glacier - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in B-image relative focus stack
		4239MH00794001502284C00	2284	target Pallade_Glacier - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in B-image relative focus stack
		4239MH00794001502285C00	2285	target Pallade_Glacier - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in B-image relative focus stack
		4239MH00794001502286C00	2286	target Pallade_Glacier - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in B-image relative focus stack
		4239MH00794001502287C00	2287	target Pallade_Glacier - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in B-image relative focus stack

updated: 12_July_2024

Sol 4240 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	20 Jun 24
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	6
total focus merge products:	12
total parent images + focus merge products:	12

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4239 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1000163	Focus Merges	4240MH00163000150228800	2288	target Pallasde_Glacier - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4239 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2280-2287 - best focus image product
		4240MH001630001502289500	2289	target Pallasde_Glacier - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4239 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2280-2287 - range map product
		4240MH00163000150229000	2290	target Pallasde_Glacier - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4239 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2263-2270 - best focus image product
		4240MH001630001502291500	2291	target Pallasde_Glacier - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4239 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2263-2270 - range map product
		4240MH001630001502292000	2292	target Pallasde_Glacier - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4239 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2252-2259 - best focus image product
		4240MH001630001502293500	2293	target Pallasde_Glacier - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4239 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2252-2259 - range map product
		4240MH001630001502294000	2294	target Lake_Dorothy - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4239 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2238-2245 - best focus image product
		4240MH001630001502295500	2295	target Lake_Dorothy - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4239 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2238-2245 - range map product
		4240MH001630001502296000	2296	target Lake_Dorothy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4239 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2227-2234 - best focus image product
		4240MH001630001502297500	2297	target Lake_Dorothy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4239 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2227-2234 - range map product
		4240MH001630001502298000	2298	target Lake_Dorothy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4239 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2216-2223 - best focus image product
		4240MH001630001502299500	2299	target Lake_Dorothy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4239 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2216-2223 - range map product

updated: 29_July_2024

Sol 4241 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	13 Jul 24
camera position:	2
total parent images:	35
focus merges performed:	3
total focus merge products:	6
total parent images + focus merge products:	39

MAHLI imaged the target Donohue_Pass and the focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00297	Donohue_Pass ~24 cm standoff	4241MH000390001502300C00	2300	autoFocus sub-frame for target Donohue_Pass - standoff near 24 cm
		4241MH000390001502301C00	2301	target Donohue_Pass - standoff near 24 cm
		4241MH000390001502302C00	2302	target Donohue_Pass - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4241MH000390001502303C00	2303	target Donohue_Pass - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4241MH000390001502304C00	2304	target Donohue_Pass - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4241MH000390001502305C00	2305	target Donohue_Pass - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4241MH000390001502306C00	2306	target Donohue_Pass - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4241MH000390001502307C00	2307	target Donohue_Pass - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4241MH000390001502308C00	2308	target Donohue_Pass - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4241MH000390001502309C00	2309	target Donohue_Pass - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00297	Donohue_Pass stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	4241MH0002970001502310C00	2310	autoFocus sub-frame for target Donohue_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4241MH0002970001502311C00	2311	target Donohue_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4241MH0002970001502312C00	2312	target Donohue_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4241MH0002970001502313C00	2313	target Donohue_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4241MH0002970001502314C00	2314	target Donohue_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4241MH0002970001502315C00	2315	target Donohue_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4241MH0002970001502316C00	2316	target Donohue_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4241MH0002970001502317C00	2317	target Donohue_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4241MH0002970001502318C00	2318	target Donohue_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4241MH0002970001502319C00	2319	target Donohue_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00297	Donohue_Pass stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	4241MH0002970001502320C00	2320	autoFocus sub-frame for target Donohue_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4241MH0002970001502321C00	2321	target Donohue_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4241MH0002970001502322C00	2322	target Donohue_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4241MH0002970001502323C00	2323	target Donohue_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4241MH0002970001502324C00	2324	target Donohue_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4241MH0002970001502325C00	2325	target Donohue_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4241MH0002970001502326C00	2326	target Donohue_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4241MH0002970001502327C00	2327	target Donohue_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4241MH0002970001502328C00	2328	target Donohue_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4241MH0002970001502329C00	2329	target Donohue_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00297	Focus Merges	4241MH0001930001502330R00	2330	target Donohue_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4241 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2322-2329 - best focus image product
		4241MH0001930001502331S00	2331	target Donohue_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4241 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2322-2329 - range map product
		4241MH0001930001502332R00	2332	target Donohue_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4241 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2312-2319 - best focus image product
		4241MH0001930001502333S00	2333	target Donohue_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4241 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2312-2319 - range map product
		4241MH0001930001502334R00	2334	target Donohue_Pass - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4241 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2302-2309 - best focus image product
		4241MH0001930001502335S00	2335	target Donohue_Pass - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4241 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2302-2309 - range map product

Sol 4243 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	13 Jul 24
camera position	0
total parent images	82
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	82

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

MAHLI imaged the target Cattle_Creek and the target Arrowhead_Spire, which included a 4x1 mosaic.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Cattle_Creek ~24 cm standoff	4243MH0001900011502336C0D	2336	autofocus sub-frame for target Cattle_Creek - standoff near 24 cm
		4243MH0001900011502337C0D	2337	target Cattle_Creek - standoff near 24 cm
mN00224	Cattle_Creek stereo-1 ~35 mm standoff	4243MH0002240011502338C0D	2338	autofocus sub-frame for target Cattle_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		4243MH0002240011502339C0D	2339	target Cattle_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		4243MH0002240011502340C0D	2340	target Cattle_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0002240011502341C0D	2341	target Cattle_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0002240011502342C0D	2342	target Cattle_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0002240011502343C0D	2343	target Cattle_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0002240011502344C0D	2344	target Cattle_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0002240011502345C0D	2345	target Cattle_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0002240011502346C0D	2346	target Cattle_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0002240011502347C0D	2347	target Cattle_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00224	Cattle_Creek stereo-2 ~35 mm standoff	4243MH0002240011502348C0D	2348	autofocus sub-frame for target Cattle_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		4243MH0002240011502349C0D	2349	target Cattle_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		4243MH0002240011502350C0D	2350	target Cattle_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0002240011502351C0D	2351	target Cattle_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0002240011502352C0D	2352	target Cattle_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0002240011502353C0D	2353	target Cattle_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0002240011502354C0D	2354	target Cattle_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0002240011502355C0D	2355	target Cattle_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0002240011502356C0D	2356	target Cattle_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0002240011502357C0D	2357	target Cattle_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00297	Arrowhead_Spire stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	4243MH0002970011502358C0D	2358	autofocus sub-frame for target Arrowhead_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4243MH0002970011502359C0D	2359	target Arrowhead_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4243MH0002970011502360C0D	2360	target Arrowhead_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0002970011502361C0D	2361	target Arrowhead_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0002970011502362C0D	2362	target Arrowhead_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0002970011502363C0D	2363	target Arrowhead_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0002970011502364C0D	2364	target Arrowhead_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0002970011502365C0D	2365	target Arrowhead_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0002970011502366C0D	2366	target Arrowhead_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0002970011502367C0D	2367	target Arrowhead_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00297	Arrowhead_Spire stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	4243MH0002970011502368C0D	2368	autofocus sub-frame for target Arrowhead_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4243MH0002970011502369C0D	2369	target Arrowhead_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4243MH0002970011502370C0D	2370	target Arrowhead_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0002970011502371C0D	2371	target Arrowhead_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0002970011502372C0D	2372	target Arrowhead_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0002970011502373C0D	2373	target Arrowhead_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0002970011502374C0D	2374	target Arrowhead_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0002970011502375C0D	2375	target Arrowhead_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0002970011502376C0D	2376	target Arrowhead_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0002970011502377C0D	2377	target Arrowhead_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00855	Arrowhead_Spire mosaic position 1 of 4 ~25 cm standoff	4243MH0008550011502378C0D	2378	autofocus sub-frame for target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm
		4243MH0008550011502379C0D	2379	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm
		4243MH0008550011502380C0D	2380	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0008550011502381C0D	2381	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0008550011502382C0D	2382	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0008550011502383C0D	2383	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0008550011502384C0D	2384	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0008550011502385C0D	2385	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0008550011502386C0D	2386	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0008550011502387C0D	2387	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00855	Arrowhead_Spire mosaic position 2 of 4 ~25 cm standoff	4243MH0008550011502388C0D	2388	autofocus sub-frame for target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm
		4243MH0008550011502389C0D	2389	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm
		4243MH0008550011502390C0D	2390	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0008550011502391C0D	2391	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0008550011502392C0D	2392	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0008550011502393C0D	2393	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0008550011502394C0D	2394	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0008550011502395C0D	2395	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0008550011502396C0D	2396	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH0008550011502397C0D	2397	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

Continued on Next Page...

mH00855	Arrowhead_Spire mosaic position 3 of 4 ~24 cm standoff	4243MH008550011502398C00	2398	autofocus sub-frame for target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 24 cm
		4243MH008550011502399C00	2399	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 24 cm
		4243MH008550011502400C00	2400	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH008550011502401C00	2401	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH008550011502402C00	2402	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH008550011502403C00	2403	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH008550011502404C00	2404	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH008550011502405C00	2405	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH008550011502406C00	2406	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4243MH008550011502407C00	2407	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mH00855	Arrowhead_Spire mosaic position 4 of 4 ~25 cm standoff	4243MH008550011502408C00	2408	autofocus sub-frame for target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm
		4243MH008550011502409C00	2409	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm
		4243MH008550011502410C00	2410	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH008550011502411C00	2411	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH008550011502412C00	2412	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH008550011502413C00	2413	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH008550011502414C00	2414	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH008550011502415C00	2415	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4243MH008550011502416C00	2416	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4243MH008550011502417C00	2417	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 15_july_2024

Sol 4244 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	06 Jul 24
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	8
total focus merge products:	16
total parent images + focus merge products:	16

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received

CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4243 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1000170	Focus Merges	4244MH00170001502418900	2418	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4243 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2410-2417 - best focus image product
		4244MH00170001502419500	2419	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4243 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2410-2417 - range map product
		4244MH00170001502420900	2420	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4243 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2400-2407 - best focus image product
		4244MH00170001502421500	2421	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4243 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2400-2407 - range map product
		4244MH00170001502422900	2422	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 23 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4243 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2390-2397 - best focus image product
		4244MH00170001502423500	2423	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4243 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2390-2397 - range map product
		4244MH00170001502424900	2424	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 23 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4243 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2380-2387 - best focus image product
		4244MH00170001502425500	2425	target Arrowhead_Spire - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4243 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2380-2387 - range map product
		4244MH00170001502426900	2426	target Arrowhead_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4243 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2370-2377 - best focus image product
		4244MH00170001502427500	2427	target Arrowhead_Spire - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4243 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2370-2377 - range map product
		4244MH00170001502428900	2428	target Arrowhead_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4243 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2360-2367 - best focus image product
		4244MH00170001502429500	2429	target Arrowhead_Spire - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4243 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2360-2367 - range map product
		4244MH00170001502430900	2430	target Cattle_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4243 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2350-2357 - best focus image product
		4244MH00170001502431500	2431	target Cattle_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4243 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2350-2357 - range map product
		4244MH00170001502432900	2432	target Cattle_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4243 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2340-2347 - best focus image product
		4244MH00170001502433500	2433	target Cattle_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4243 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2340-2347 - range map product

updated: 29_July_2024

Sol 4246 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):		26 Jul 24		
camera position:		4		
total parent images:		33		
focus merges performed:		3		
total focus merge products:		6		
total parent images + focus merge products:		39		
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the REMS UV sensor and the target Jack_Main_Canyon. The focus stack images were also merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALISE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00095	REMS UV sensor ~15 cm standoff	4246MH0000950015024340C0	2434	autoFocus sub-frame for REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation
		4246MH0000950015024350C0	2435	REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation
mN00059	Jack_Main_Canyon ~24 cm standoff	4246MH00039001502436C0	2436	autoFocus sub-frame for target Jack_Main_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm
		4246MH00039001502437C0	2437	target Jack_Main_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm
		4246MH00039001502438C0	2438	target Jack_Main_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4246MH00039001502439C0	2439	target Jack_Main_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4246MH00039001502440C0	2440	target Jack_Main_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4246MH00039001502441C0	2441	target Jack_Main_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4246MH00039001502442C0	2442	target Jack_Main_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4246MH00039001502443C0	2443	target Jack_Main_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4246MH00039001502444C0	2444	target Jack_Main_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4246MH00039001502445C0	2445	target Jack_Main_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00056	Jack_Main_Canyon stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	4246MH00036001502446C0	2446	autoFocus sub-frame for target Jack_Main_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4246MH00036001502447C0	2447	target Jack_Main_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4246MH00036001502448C0	2448	target Jack_Main_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4246MH00036001502449C0	2449	target Jack_Main_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4246MH00036001502450C0	2450	target Jack_Main_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4246MH00036001502451C0	2451	target Jack_Main_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4246MH00036001502452C0	2452	target Jack_Main_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4246MH00036001502453C0	2453	target Jack_Main_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4246MH00036001502454C0	2454	target Jack_Main_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4246MH00036001502455C0	2455	target Jack_Main_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00056	Jack_Main_Canyon stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	4246MH00036001502456C0	2456	autoFocus sub-frame for target Jack_Main_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4246MH00036001502457C0	2457	target Jack_Main_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4246MH00036001502458C0	2458	target Jack_Main_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4246MH00036001502459C0	2459	target Jack_Main_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4246MH00036001502460C0	2460	target Jack_Main_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4246MH00036001502461C0	2461	target Jack_Main_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4246MH00036001502462C0	2462	target Jack_Main_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4246MH00036001502463C0	2463	target Jack_Main_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4246MH00036001502464C0	2464	target Jack_Main_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4246MH00036001502465C0	2465	target Jack_Main_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00289	Focus Merges	4246MH00193001502466R0	2466	target Jack_Main_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4246 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2458-2465 - best focus image product
		4246MH00193001502467S0	2467	target Jack_Main_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4246 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2458-2465 - range map product
		4246MH00193001502468R0	2468	target Jack_Main_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4246 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2448-2455 - best focus image product
		4246MH00193001502469S0	2469	target Jack_Main_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4246 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2448-2455 - range map product
		4246MH00193001502470R0	2470	target Jack_Main_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4246 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2438-2445 - best focus image product
4246MH00193001502471S0	2471	target Jack_Main_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4246 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2438-2445 - range map product		

updated: 01_August_2024

Sol 4248 - MAHI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	28 Jul 24	
		camera position	64	Image ID:
		total parent images	64	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	4	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	8	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	72	
summary of MAHI activities				
MAHI imaged the sky, with the dust cover open and closed for flat fielding. MAHI also imaged the DRT-brushed target Amphitheater_Dome. The focus stack images were merged as well.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00712	sky flats - dust cover closed- MAHI looking at the sky opposite the sun at +45° azimuth, +35° elevation, away from the rover deck	4248MH00071200150247200	2472	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 9 - close focus position - focus as if for working distance 21 mm
		4248MH00071200150247300	2473	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 2412 - focus as if for working distance of 39 mm
		4248MH00071200150247400	2474	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 3078 - focus as if for working distance of 69 mm
		4248MH00071200150247500	2475	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 4062 - focus as if for working distance of 248 mm
		4248MH00071200150247600	2476	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 4488 - near infinity focus
mN00453	sky flats - MAHI looking at the sky opposite the sun at +45° azimuth, +35° elevation, away from the rover deck	4248MH00045300150247700	2477	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 15996 - close focus position - focus as if for working distance 21 mm
		4248MH00045300150247800	2478	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 14664 - focus as if for working distance of 39 mm
		4248MH00045300150247900	2479	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 13998 - focus as if for working distance of 69 mm
		4248MH00045300150248000	2480	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 13014 - focus as if for working distance of 267 mm
		4248MH00045300150248100	2481	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 12750 - focus as if for working distance of 633 mm
mN00453	sky flats - MAHI looking at the sky opposite the sun at +45° azimuth, +35° elevation, away from the rover deck	4248MH00045300150248200	2482	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 12552 - near infinity focus
		4248MH00045300150248300	2483	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 15996 - close focus position - focus as if for working distance 21 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol
		4248MH00045300150248400	2484	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 14664 - focus as if for working distance of 39 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol
		4248MH00045300150248500	2485	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 13998 - focus as if for working distance of 69 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol
		4248MH00045300150248600	2486	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 13014 - focus as if for working distance of 267 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol
mN00712	sky flats - dust cover closed- MAHI looking at the sky opposite the sun at +45° azimuth, +35° elevation, away from the rover deck	4248MH00071200150248700	2487	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 12750 - focus as if for working distance of 633 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol
		4248MH00071200150248800	2488	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 12552 - near infinity focus - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol
		4248MH00071200150248900	2489	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 0 - close focus position - focus as if for working distance 21 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol
		4248MH00071200150249000	2490	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 2412 - focus as if for working distance of 39 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol
		4248MH00071200150249100	2491	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 3078 - focus as if for working distance of 69 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol
mN00712	sky flats - dust cover closed- MAHI looking at the sky opposite the sun at +45° azimuth, +35° elevation, away from the rover deck	4248MH00071200150249200	2492	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 4062 - focus as if for working distance of 248 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol
		4248MH00071200150249300	2493	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 4488 - near infinity focus - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol
		4248MH00071200150249400	2494	autofocus sub-frame for target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 24 cm
		4248MH00071200150249500	2495	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 24 cm
		4248MH00071200150249600	2496	autofocus sub-frame for target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00168	Amphitheater_Dome after DRT APXS spot 1 stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4248MH00016800150249700	2497	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4248MH00016800150249800	2498	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00016800150249900	2499	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00016800150250000	2500	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00016800150250100	2501	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00016800150250200	2502	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00016800150250300	2503	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00016800150250400	2504	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00016800150250500	2505	autofocus sub-frame for target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4248MH00016800150250600	2506	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00168	Amphitheater_Dome after DRT APXS spot 1 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4248MH00016800150250700	2507	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4248MH00016800150250800	2508	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00016800150250900	2509	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00016800150251000	2510	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00016800150251100	2511	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00016800150251200	2512	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00016800150251300	2513	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00016800150251400	2514	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00016800150251500	2515	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00016800150251600	2516	autofocus sub-frame for target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 1 cm
mN00743	Amphitheater_Dome after DRT APXS spot 1 ~1 cm standoff	4248MH00074300150251700	2517	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 1 cm
		4248MH00074300150251800	2518	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00074300150251900	2519	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00074300150252000	2520	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00074300150252100	2521	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00074300150252200	2522	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00074300150252300	2523	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00074300150252400	2524	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00074300150252500	2525	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00016800150252600	2526	autofocus sub-frame for target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00168	Amphitheater_Dome after DRT APXS spot 2 ~5 cm standoff	4248MH00016800150252700	2527	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4248MH00016800150252800	2528	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00016800150252900	2529	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00016800150253000	2530	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00016800150253100	2531	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00016800150253200	2532	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00016800150253300	2533	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00016800150253400	2534	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4248MH00016800150253500	2535	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

Continued on Next Page...

mNH00133	Focus Merge	4248MH001530001502536R00	2536	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4248 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2528-2535 - best focus image product
		4248MH001530001502537500	2537	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4248 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2528-2535 - range map product
		4248MH001530001502538R00	2538	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4248 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2518-2525 - best focus image product
		4248MH001530001502539500	2539	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4248 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2518-2525 - range map product
		4248MH001530001502540R00	2540	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4248 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2508-2515 - best focus image product
		4248MH001530001502541500	2541	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4248 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2508-2515 - range map product
		4248MH001530001502542R00	2542	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4248 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2498-2505 - best focus image product
		4248MH001530001502543500	2543	target Amphitheater_Dome - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4248 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2498-2505 - range map product

updated: 01_August_2024

Sol 4250 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	23 Jul 24	
		camera position	12	Image ID:
		total parent images	85	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	0	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	85	
summary of MAHLI activities				
MAHLI imaged the target Saddlebag_Lake and the DRT-brushed target Eagle_Scout_Peak. At night, MAHLI imaged inside the ChemMin inlet for cleanliness.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Saddlebag_Lake ~23 cm standoff	4250MH00190001150254400D	2544	autofocus sub-frame for target Saddlebag_Lake - standoff near 23 cm
		4250MH00190001150254500D	2545	target Saddlebag_Lake - standoff near 23 cm
		4250MH00173001150254600D	2546	autofocus sub-frame for target Saddlebag_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm
		4250MH00173001150254700D	2547	target Saddlebag_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm
		4250MH00173001150254800D	2548	target Saddlebag_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00173	Saddlebag_Lake stereo-1 ~3 cm standoff	4250MH00173001150254900D	2549	target Saddlebag_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00173001150255000D	2550	target Saddlebag_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00173001150255100D	2551	target Saddlebag_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00173001150255200D	2552	target Saddlebag_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00173001150255300D	2553	target Saddlebag_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00173001150255400D	2554	target Saddlebag_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00173001150255500D	2555	target Saddlebag_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00173001150255600D	2556	autofocus sub-frame for target Saddlebag_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm
mN00173	Saddlebag_Lake stereo-2 ~3 cm standoff	4250MH00173001150255700D	2557	target Saddlebag_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm
		4250MH00173001150255800D	2558	target Saddlebag_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00173001150255900D	2559	target Saddlebag_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00173001150256000D	2560	target Saddlebag_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00173001150256100D	2561	target Saddlebag_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00173001150256200D	2562	target Saddlebag_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00173001150256300D	2563	target Saddlebag_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00173001150256400D	2564	target Saddlebag_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Eagle_Scout_Peak after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4250MH00190001150256600D	2566	autofocus sub-frame for target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		4250MH00190001150256700D	2567	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		4250MH00336001150256800D	2568	autofocus sub-frame for target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4250MH00336001150256900D	2569	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4250MH00336001150257000D	2570	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00336	Eagle_Scout_Peak after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4250MH00336001150257100D	2571	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00336001150257200D	2572	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00336001150257300D	2573	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00336001150257400D	2574	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00336001150257500D	2575	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00336001150257600D	2576	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00336001150257700D	2577	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00336001150257800D	2578	autofocus sub-frame for target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00336	Eagle_Scout_Peak after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4250MH00336001150257900D	2579	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4250MH00336001150258000D	2580	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00336001150258100D	2581	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00336001150258200D	2582	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00336001150258300D	2583	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00336001150258400D	2584	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00336001150258500D	2585	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00336001150258600D	2586	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00864	Eagle_Scout_Peak after DRT APXS spot 1 ~1 cm standoff	4250MH00864001150258800D	2588	autofocus sub-frame for target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		4250MH00864001150258900D	2589	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		4250MH00864001150259000D	2590	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00864001150259100D	2591	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00864001150259200D	2592	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00864001150259300D	2593	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00864001150259400D	2594	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00864001150259500D	2595	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00864001150259600D	2596	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00864001150259700D	2597	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00336001150259800D	2598	autofocus sub-frame for target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00336	Eagle_Scout_Peak after DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	4250MH00336001150259900D	2599	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4250MH00336001150260000D	2600	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00336001150260100D	2601	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00336001150260200D	2602	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00336001150260300D	2603	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00336001150260400D	2604	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00336001150260500D	2605	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4250MH00336001150260600D	2606	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00312	MAHLI 12.3 cm working distance above ChemMin inlet mesh; inlet cover open; position 1 of 3; otherwise same as above	4250MH00312001150260800D	2608	ChemMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
		4250MH00312001150260900D	2609	ChemMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at mesh at 124 mm working distance
mN00326	position 2 of 3; otherwise same as above	4250MH00336001150261000D	2610	ChemMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
mN00326	position 3 of 3; otherwise same as two above	4250MH00336001150261100D	2611	ChemMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
mN00326	~19 cm above open ChemMin inlet	4250MH00312001150261200D	2612	ChemMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at 19 cm working distance

updated: 22_July_2024

Sol 4251 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	23 Jul 24
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	12
total parent images + focus merge products	12

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4250 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1000163	Focus Merges	4251MH0001630001502613900	2613	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4250 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2600-2607 - best focus image product
		4251MH0001630001502614500	2614	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4250 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2600-2607 - range map product
		4251MH0001630001502615900	2615	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4250 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2590-2597 - best focus image product
		4251MH0001630001502616500	2616	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4250 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2590-2597 - range map product
		4251MH0001630001502617900	2617	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4250 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2580-2587 - best focus image product
		4251MH0001630001502618500	2618	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4250 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2580-2587 - range map product
		4251MH0001630001502619900	2619	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4250 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2570-2577 - best focus image product
		4251MH0001630001502620500	2620	target Eagle_Scout_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4250 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2570-2577 - range map product
		4251MH0001630001502621900	2621	target Saddlebag_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4250 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2558-2565 - best focus image product
		4251MH0001630001502622500	2622	target Saddlebag_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4250 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2558-2565 - range map product
		4251MH0001630001502623900	2623	target Saddlebag_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4250 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2548-2555 - best focus image product
		4251MH0001630001502624500	2624	target Saddlebag_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4250 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2548-2555 - range map product

updated: 14_January_2025

Sol 4253 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	26 Jul 24
camera position	2
total parent images	35
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the target Discovery_Pinnacle and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN00359	Discovery_Pinnacle *25 cm standoff	4253MH000390001502625000	2625	autofocus sub-frame for target Discovery_Pinnacle - standoff near 25 cm		
		4253MH000390001502626000	2626	target Discovery_Pinnacle - standoff near 25 cm		
		4253MH000390001502627000	2627	target Discovery_Pinnacle - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4253MH000390001502628000	2628	target Discovery_Pinnacle - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4253MH000390001502629000	2629	target Discovery_Pinnacle - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4253MH000390001502630000	2630	target Discovery_Pinnacle - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4253MH000390001502631000	2631	target Discovery_Pinnacle - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4253MH000390001502632000	2632	target Discovery_Pinnacle - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4253MH000390001502633000	2633	target Discovery_Pinnacle - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4253MH000390001502634000	2634	target Discovery_Pinnacle - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00224	Discovery_Pinnacle stereo-1 *55 mm standoff	4253MH0002240001502635000	2635	autofocus sub-frame for target Discovery_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
				4253MH0002240001502636000	2636	target Discovery_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
				4253MH0002240001502637000	2637	target Discovery_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4253MH0002240001502638000	2638	target Discovery_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
4253MH0002240001502639000	2639			target Discovery_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4253MH0002240001502640000	2640			target Discovery_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4253MH0002240001502641000	2641			target Discovery_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4253MH0002240001502642000	2642			target Discovery_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4253MH0002240001502643000	2643			target Discovery_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4253MH0002240001502644000	2644			target Discovery_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00224	Discovery_Pinnacle stereo-2 *6 cm standoff			4253MH0002240001502645000	2645	autofocus sub-frame for target Discovery_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm
				4253MH0002240001502646000	2646	target Discovery_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm
				4253MH0002240001502647000	2647	target Discovery_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4253MH0002240001502648000	2648	target Discovery_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4253MH0002240001502649000	2649	target Discovery_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4253MH0002240001502650000	2650	target Discovery_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4253MH00022400015026510000	2651	target Discovery_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4253MH00022400015026520000	2652	target Discovery_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4253MH00022400015026530000	2653	target Discovery_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4253MH00022400015026540000	2654	target Discovery_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00289	Focus Merges	4253MH0001930001502655000	2655	target Discovery_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4253 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2647-2654 - best focus image product
				4253MH0001930001502656000	2656	target Discovery_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4253 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2647-2654 - range map product
				4253MH0001930001502657000	2657	target Discovery_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4253 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2637-2644 - best focus image product
				4253MH0001930001502658000	2658	target Discovery_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4253 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2637-2644 - range map product
4253MH0001930001502659000	2659			target Discovery_Pinnacle - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4253 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2627-2634 - best focus image product		
4253MH0001930001502660000	2660			target Discovery_Pinnacle - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4253 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2627-2634 - range map product		

updated: 01_August_2024

Sol 4255 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	26 Jul 24
camera position	4
total parent images	33
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Russell_Pass and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002190	Russell_Pass after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4255MH0001900001502661C00	2661	autoFocus sub-frame for target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4255MH000190001502662C00	2662	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN002196	Russell_Pass after DRT stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4255MH0003360001502663C00	2663	autoFocus sub-frame for target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4255MH000336001502664C00	2664	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4255MH0003360021502665C00	2665	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4255MH0003360021502666C00	2666	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4255MH0003360021502667C00	2667	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4255MH0003360021502668C00	2668	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4255MH0003360021502669C00	2669	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4255MH0003360021502670C00	2670	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4255MH0003360021502671C00	2671	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4255MH0003360021502672C00	2672	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002196	Russell_Pass after DRT stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4255MH0003360001502673C00	2673	autoFocus sub-frame for target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4255MH000336001502674C00	2674	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4255MH0003360021502675C00	2675	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4255MH0003360021502676C00	2676	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4255MH0003360021502677C00	2677	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4255MH0003360021502678C00	2678	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4255MH0003360021502679C00	2679	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4255MH0003360021502680C00	2680	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4255MH0003360021502681C00	2681	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4255MH0003360021502682C00	2682	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002196	Russell_Pass after DRT ~5 mm standoff	4255MH0008480001502683C00	2683	autoFocus sub-frame for target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		4255MH000848001502684C00	2684	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		4255MH0008480021502685C00	2685	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4255MH0008480021502686C00	2686	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4255MH0008480021502687C00	2687	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4255MH0008480021502688C00	2688	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4255MH0008480021502689C00	2689	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4255MH0008480021502690C00	2690	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4255MH0008480021502691C00	2691	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4255MH0008480021502692C00	2692	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002193	Focus Merges	4255MH0001930001502693R00	2693	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4255 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2685-2692 - best focus image product
		4255MH0001930001502694R00	2694	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4255 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2685-2692 - range map product
		4255MH0001930001502695R00	2695	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4255 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2675-2682 - best focus image product
		4255MH0001930001502696R00	2696	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4255 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2675-2682 - range map product
		4255MH0001930001502697R00	2697	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4255 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2665-2672 - best focus image product
4255MH0001930001502698R00	2698	target Russell_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4255 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2665-2672 - range map product		

updated: 01_August_2024

Sol 4257 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	28 Jul 24	
		Camera position	43	Image ID:
		total parent images	4	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	4	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	8	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in POS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	50	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Kings_Canyon after DRT. The focus stack images were also merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Kings_Canyon after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4257MH0001900001502699Z00	2699	autofocus sub-frame for intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		4257MH000190001502700Z00	2700	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
mN00336	Kings_Canyon after DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	4257MH0003360001502701Z00	2701	autofocus sub-frame for intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4257MH000336001502702Z00	2702	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4257MH0003360021502703Z00	2703	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4257MH0003360021502704Z00	2704	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4257MH0003360021502705Z00	2705	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4257MH0003360021502706Z00	2706	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4257MH0003360021502707Z00	2707	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4257MH0003360021502708Z00	2708	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4257MH0003360021502709Z00	2709	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4257MH0003360021502710Z00	2710	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00336	Kings_Canyon after DRT APXS spot 2 ~5 cm standoff	4257MH000336001502711Z00	2711	autofocus sub-frame for intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4257MH000336001502712Z00	2712	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4257MH0003360021502713Z00	2713	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4257MH0003360021502714Z00	2714	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4257MH0003360021502715Z00	2715	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4257MH0003360021502716Z00	2716	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4257MH0003360021502717Z00	2717	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4257MH0003360021502718Z00	2718	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4257MH0003360021502719Z00	2719	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4257MH0003360021502720Z00	2720	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00864	Kings_Canyon after DRT APXS spot 1 ~1 cm standoff	4257MH000864001502721Z00	2721	autofocus sub-frame for intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		4257MH000864001502722Z00	2722	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		4257MH0008640021502723Z00	2723	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4257MH0008640021502724Z00	2724	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4257MH0008640021502725Z00	2725	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4257MH0008640021502726Z00	2726	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4257MH0008640021502727Z00	2727	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4257MH0008640021502728Z00	2728	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4257MH0008640021502729Z00	2729	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4257MH0008640021502730Z00	2730	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00336	Kings_Canyon after DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	4257MH0003360001502731Z00	2731	autofocus sub-frame for intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4257MH000336001502732Z00	2732	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4257MH0003360021502733Z00	2733	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4257MH0003360021502734Z00	2734	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4257MH0003360021502735Z00	2735	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4257MH0003360021502736Z00	2736	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4257MH0003360021502737Z00	2737	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4257MH0003360021502738Z00	2738	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4257MH0003360021502739Z00	2739	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4257MH0003360021502740Z00	2740	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00153	Focus Merges	4257MH000153000150274300	2741	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4257 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2731-2740 - best focus image product
		4257MH000153000150274250	2742	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4257 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2733-2740 - range map product
		4257MH000153000150274300	2743	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4257 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2731-2730 - best focus image product
		4257MH000153000150274450	2744	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4257 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2723-2730 - range map product
		4257MH000153000150274500	2745	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4257 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2713-2720 - best focus image product
		4257MH000153000150274650	2746	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4257 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2713-2720 - range map product
		4257MH000153000150274700	2747	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4257 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2703-2710 - best focus image product
		4257MH000153000150274850	2748	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4257 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2703-2710 - range map product

7 Definitions, conventions, and acronyms

7.1 Definitions and conventions

absolute focus stack

A MAHLI focus stack acquired using a commanded (manual) focus setting. The starting focus position (a stepper motor count), and the incremental change in focus position (a stepper motor count interval) between frames in the focus stack, are specified by instrument commanding.

best focus image product

A *focus merge product* created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. The *best focus image product* is a color JPEG that combines the in-focus (or closest to in-focus) elements of the up to 8 *parent images* into a single image. The onboard focus merge software also creates a *range map product*.

focus merge product

Using the methods described by Edgett *et al.* (2012), *focus merge products* are created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. Two products are created, a *best focus image product* and a *range map product*.

MAHLI toolframe +X distance

Same as *standoff distance*. See *standoff distance*.

parent and child images

Every MAHLI image has a *parent image*, the picture originally commanded to be acquired. Upon command, the parent image can spawn children (each a *child image*) onboard the instrument. Examples of children include *thumbnail images*, focus merge products, and any version of the image that is compressed differently than the parent (Edgett *et al.* 2012). While a parent can be an image that was compressed during image acquisition, our best practice since landing on Mars has been to acquire and store (onboard the instrument) most MAHLI images in uncompressed 8-bit form. An uncompressed 8-bit parent image can be commanded for compression some time after acquisition and storage, whereas a parent that was compressed at the time of acquisition cannot be further compressed onboard the instrument. When a parent is stored onboard in uncompressed form, it can be used to create multiple versions of the image, each time with a different compression scheme, for downlink to Earth. Thus, if the image received is over-compressed, we have the option to retrieve it again (as many times as necessary) in a less compressed form. Indeed, the majority of MAHLI images received from Mars have been losslessly compressed children of an uncompressed, 8-bit parent.

range

Used here in the context of describing a focus merge range map product, this term refers to the distance between the front lens element and in-focus elements of the imaged subject in a given MAHLI focus merge product. As each MAHLI focus stack is acquired at a fixed *working distance*, the range denotes the distance between the camera and the relief elements of the target (*i.e.*, subject), as indicated by grayscale pixel values (data number, DN) in the range map product.

range map product

A grayscale JPEG image *focus merge product* created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. The *range map product* accompanies a *best focus image product*. The grayscale pixel values (data number, DN) can be correlated with knowledge of instrument focus, *working distance*, *range*, and pixel scale.

RATIONALE_DESC

The term, RATIONALE_DESC, comes from the NASA PDS archivists. The RATIONALE_DESC for a given MAHLI image is a text description of the rationale or purpose behind the acquisition of a given MAHLI parent image or onboard focus merge product. Each parent image RATIONALE_DESC provides information that the MAHLI team desired to communicate to data users, such as the intended image target, intended working or standoff distance, intended purpose of the image (e.g., stereo, mosaic, autofocus sub-frame, range-finding), image position in a focus stack, as well as information regarding how the image supports observations made by other MSL science instruments, especially APXS and ChemCam. The RATIONALE_DESC for a focus merge product tells the user which images were merged (on what sol they were acquired and images of which CDPIDs were merged), as well as the focus merge product type (best focus or range map product).

relative focus stack

A MAHLI focus stack acquired using a starting focus position determined by a preceding instrument command. Usually, this is a focus setting based upon a focus position determined by a preceding autofocus command. The incremental change in focus position (a stepper motor count interval) between frames in the focus stack is specified by instrument commanding.

RP distance

RP refers to Rover Planners, the personnel who drive the Curiosity rover and operate its robotic arm. RP distance is equivalent to *standoff distance*. See definition of *standoff distance*.

sol

A Martian day; duration of ~1.027 Earth days.

Sol

A specific Martian sol during the MSL Curiosity mission. Because it landed during local afternoon, the sol that Curiosity arrived on Mars was designated Sol 0 and the first full sol after landing was Sol 1.

standoff distance

Also known as the MAHLI *toolframe distance* and *RP distance*, this is range between the subject photographed and the Y, Z plane defined by the two MAHLI contact sensor probe tips when they are not in contact with a surface. In the MAHLI toolframe, the X axis is equivalent to the instrument's optic (z) axis; the distance between the Y, Z plane and the subject is +X; the – X-axis goes from the Y, Z plane into the camera. *Standoff distance* and *RP distance* are equivalent to the +X MAHLI toolframe distance. MAHLI *standoff distance* is 1.9 cm less than *working distance*.

thumbnail images

Reduced-size versions of MAHLI *parent images* and *focus merge products*, approximately 1/8th size in terms of pixel dimensions. Under most circumstances, a *thumbnail image* is returned to Earth for every *parent image* acquired or *focus merge product* created, whether a full-size version of the *parent image* (or a *child image*) or *focus merge product* is returned or not.

working distance

A photography term that refers to the range between the front lens element of a camera and the subject imaged. MAHLI working distance is 1.9 cm greater than the toolframe (also known as standoff or RP) distance.

7.2 Acronyms

APXS

Alpha Particle X-ray Spectrometer (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CDPID or MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID

Each MAHLI parent image acquired or onboard focus merge product created and stored in the instrument's DEA flash memory is assigned a Camera Data Product ID (CDPID). This identifier, plus the time at which (or sol on which) the data were acquired, uniquely identify each image. The CDPID and sol are incorporated into the image ID. Data acquired by the camera but not stored in the DEA have less unique CDPIDs; these acquisitions have generally been rare and easy for the operations team to track (*i.e.*, 12 such images were obtained during Interplanetary Cruise, only one such image was obtained during the first 1000 sols of operations on Mars).

ChemCam

Chemistry Camera; Laser Induced Breakdown Spectrometer (LIBS) and Remote Microscopic Imager (RMI) (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CheMin

Chemistry and Mineralogy x-ray diffraction (XRD) and x-ray fluorescence (XRF) sample analysis investigation (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CHIMRA

Collection and Handling for Interior Martian Rock Analysis (sample handling and processing subsystem on Curiosity's robotic arm)

DEA

Digital Electronics Assembly, the MAHLI electronics housed inside Curiosity's rover body.

DN

data number (image pixel value)

DOF

image depth of field

DRT

Dust Removal Tool (wire brush tool on Curiosity's robotic arm)

EDR

Experiment Data Record

Hazcam(s)

Hazard cameras (engineering cameras aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

ID or image ID

Image identifier (NASA PDS image identifier for MAHLI images and focus merge products).

JPL-Caltech

Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology, Pasadena, California, USA

MAHLI

Mars Hand Lens Imager (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

MARDI

Mars Descent Imager (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

Mastcam-34 (also M-34 and M34)

34 mm focal length Mast Camera (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

Mastcam-100 (also M-100 and M100)

100 mm focal length Mast Camera (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

MSL

Mars Science Laboratory

MSSS

Malin Space Science Systems, San Diego, California, USA

NASA

National Aeronautics and Space Administration (USA space agency)

Navcam(s)

Navigation cameras (engineering cameras aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

PDS

Planetary Data System (NASA planetary science data archives)

QMS

Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer (part of the SAM instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

RDR

Reduced Data Record

REMS

Rover Environment and Monitoring Station (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

SAM

Sample Analysis at Mars (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

TLS

Tunable Laser Spectrometer (part of the SAM instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

USA

United States of America

UTC

Coordinated Universal Time

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